

Before the Common Era V9
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Research notes written as entertainment. Partially ordered.

Refutation of Christianity: logical, linguistic, historical, rabbinical, permutational, probabilistic, and scientific. Distinction between Hebraism and Judaism. Historical schemes exposed. Biblical apple of fractal combinatorial word splitting can be demonstrated nonrandom via entropic information measure. Uses NASB 1977.

E.g.1 "Ashkenazim": Manaszeh; "Sephardim": Ephraim; "Mizrahim": Miriam

E.g.2 "Imperial Aramaic script": armrest calamari; "Phoenician script": earn hippo [Behemoth]

E.g.3 "cause of Trojan war": crown Atreus/Josef

E.g.4 "Gaius Julius Caesar adopted Octavian": signature duplicitous/duplicated

E.g.5 "Marcus Aurelius and Commodus": murder scandalous

E.g.6 "Aeneas ancestor of Romulus and Remus": erroneousness fraudulent

E.g.7 "evolution is false": elevation soul [chromosomal digital block]

E.g.8 [K-Pg] "Cretaceous-Paleogene mass extinction": cause meteoric Constantine

E.g.9 "October Revolution": Berliner octo

E.g.10 "Holocaust Holodomor": stomach dolor, (Holo)^2 doormats

E.g.11 "truth of Mordecai and Esther": Mordred authenticates/counterfeit

E.g.12 "Christianity": antichrist

Pater, pattern

(Chronicles of Amber: Pattern vs Logrus ... Logus (Word) ... Log in the Courts of Chaos ... Cao)

ellipse, elapse (time counted)

Odin ... dino (bird)

apple, apparel

serpent, usurp

matrix, dominatrix

talia, retaliate

perish, parish

dolphin, Delphi, dauphin (Fr)

Ergotise, ergo (therefore, logic), Argo

Salt מָלַח

Tyre (purple ... snail blood), tyrant, Tyrannosaurus Rex

Vampire, pyre

Coven, covenant

cat (pussy), cattle (cow), category theory (N chronicler), catastrophe (Solomon corruption), catabolism

mars, marshal (properly Ko)

Cao, chaos, cow

Ko, kowtow, Koran, Koren Tanakh, Kosher, Hong Kong, James Bible

Lot, lottery, plotting, lotus, lotus-eater, harlot

Cathay, Catholic, Cathy, cat (pussy), Catiline (conspiracy), Cato, cattle (cow), Cay, Kane (sugarcane,

soda, sod, Sodom, carbonation yeasty, murder brother), Canton, Cantonese

multipliCATION, fornicATION

Cow, coward, cowering, chowder (Boston ... Irish Catholic)

Bee, bet, beetle, Beta (bitch ass), masturbator (Master beta), betrayed, beat (zero sum vs helping, to

hit, drums), bitter, beast, Bethesda, beg, been, buttery, beard

Purim ("lots", Esther, ether "telepathy", Easter, East, ... jester)

Spill, spoil (G), spool, pill, ill

Cassius, Cass Tech, Cassidy Yates of DS9, casing, Casino

cruel, Reuel, rue

Hebrew ... the brew ... Coffee

Paris (Lancelot), parasite (Travis),

fleurdelis (Flis)

pillar, pill, ill
 Sarah, seraph (Ishmael)
 MIT, smith (Mithrandir), smite
 skew (odds), skewer (impale, imp)
 K, kill, skill
 Dinah, denature
 Guinevere, GUINEA pig
 whore, horror, hordes, abhorrent
 serpent (snake a toilet), usurp
 Seti (death), settle
 David, divide (multiplicative inverse)
 Laps, Laplander (Finn, "fins and scales")
 Prince, principled, principal, prime
 Octave (music), Octavio, octopus (pussy) ... [vices]
 Bach (lush X-tian), Bacchanal
 Khazarian (K, Manchurian)
 Apollo, apple, appall
 Oklahoma (horses, X-tian commune), ... hokey, Kay, Oakland (James, Jae, J)
 Kendall Square (soulless), Kenneth (South Park)
 Cao Cao, Coca Cola, Macao
 Pole, polygamy, pig, pollen, pollute, pillar, stake
 cedar, Sedar, seed, Cid, acid
 Athenian, atheist
 Mormonism, moron
 Dogma, dog
 Salamander, mandarine
 virginity, Virginia
 Yaz, Yasmine, Yah's mine
 The Name, Nam (Chan Ho)
 Odin...dino
 assemble (congregation), assembly (language, fundamental)
 Hormah, Hor, horcrux, whore
 serpent, Sir, Servant
 cedar (logger), Seder (Passover)
 Zur (Cosby the daughter of), Zurich
 hat, hate
 Moses, mosaic (pattern, no idols)
 Mattanah, Manhattan (Project ... explode atom and Hebrew faith, projects, tenements, Harlem, Hurley),
 Matty (porn*), Mat (Cauthon, ... Cat)
 Halo (radioactive glow), halogenated (K)
 Poli, politics, police, polite, poll
 Base, alkaline (antithesis of acidic), Caligula
 parasite, Paris
 drag, Dragon (Vlad Tepes), Dagon
 Lyre, lyricist
 Puppy, puppet
 Odo, odometer, odour, ode (music)
 belly (snake), Belle, Baal
 Gotham (NYC, N), Goth (Cain)
 Meta, Metatron, metaphor, metastasis, McDonald's (M)
 apple, appalls, applause (custom reversal), Apollo, application
 Gauss (boob averages, studying curvature, primal numbers)
 Friedrich, Frieda, Freya
 Joseph, Joe, Job, "cup of Joe" (coffee, Yahweh), "get a job" (hardwork)
 Diary, dairy (plot), homogenised milk sugar Dairy Queen
 alkaline (base) antiacidic
 whore, horror, hordes

E: Cain (sneaky), Dinah (allegedly raped), Mary Magdalene, Catherine the Great, Hypatia Neoplatonist,
 Earhart Amelia, Standhart Erica
 F: Behemoth, Moses, Faisal Siddiqui, Mephibosheth, Crowfoot
 G: Lilith, Snake, Rachel (period ... Dot Dorothy), Confucius, Nefertiti, Cosbi the daughter of Zur,
 Scheherazade, Esther, Galileo Galilee
 H: Paris of Troy, Lancelot
 J: Noah, Jonah, Job, Jeremiah, Leah, Deborah, Zerubbabel, Delilah, Sheba, Medea, Pilate, Euler, Fermat?,
 Anne Frank, Jehoshaphat, Amenhotep, Asenath, Europa, Ephialtes
 K: James Hin Ting Ko ... Hin (gallon), hunting, anointing, CHINA
 Cherub of Eden, Seth, Lot (...lotus, to gamble/bet), Judah (sold Joseph), Aaron (golden calf, grandson of

Kohath, later Korah rebellion), Elijah, Adonai-bezek, Hamilcar, Mithridates, Archimedes, Einstein, Riemann, Cao Cao (Coca Cola), Thutmose, Hiram of Tyre (ferryman), Octavio, Constantine, Niccolo Machiavelli ('Ol Nick), Nebuzaradan, Mordecai, Remus, Theseus, Genghis Khan, Cyrus the Great
L: Abraham, Joseph, Enoch, Nimrod, Sargon, Pericles (Parthenon), Solomon (bricklayer), Aristotle, Jason, Perseus, Hiawatha, Vladimir Tepes (Transylvania), Arthur, Rama, Nebuchadnezzar, Master Sun, Lao Tzu, Saladin (Aladdin), Balaam son of Beor, Caesar, Marcus Aurelius, Ahasuerus, Romulus
M: Satan, Sita, Miriam, Murasaki, Morgause, Ruth, Bathsheba, Ramanujan, Hammedatha, Maimonides, Meskalamdug
N: Leviathan (Lochness monster Nessy), Abel, Isaac, Nathan, Themistocles, Cato, Diocletian, Mordred, Leonardo da Vinci, Isaac Newton, Lenin, Grothendieck/Schapiro (category theory, chronicler), Paul of Tarsus of Cilicia, Socrates?, Haman
R: Benjamin, Simmons (China)
T: Trump Donald John
V: Vasilios, Cicero
Y (next to X): Yasmine [Jasmine ... James]/Virginia Devi-Chou [Virgil Devil Cao], Ishmael, Gilgamesh, Richard Phillips Feynman (Richard of SOT Fine-man)("confinement" Genesis 40:3, "budding" Genesis 40:10), Potiphar's wife (Egyptian, ... gypsy), Aspasia of Athens, Yasodhara (Buddha's wife), Anastasia Romanovna, Hysicratia (Mithridates' concubine), Abigail, Elisha son of Shaphat, G.W. Leibniz (b.1646)

...
Alexander Oleg Daniv: Israel
(gene pool)
Andrew Marfei: Efraim
Arjun Jaganathan Satyamoorthy: Arjuna
Anna Flys: Michael, Achilles, Abimelech ... Amalekites
Brandon Quayle Reynolds: Thucydides
Caleb Brighton: Caleb
Christopher Chicelski: Phillip of Macedon
Colin Clarke: Jules Henri Poincare
Elina Pradhan: Hellen Keller (Killer)
Gideon from Brighton: Gideon
Jared Hudson (GTO gift): Jared
Jeffrey Thomas DeSano: Demosthenes
Joel Nosanchuk: Laban, Joel the son of Pethuel
Jonathan Wagoner: Esau, Jeroboam
Joseph Martin Escobar (Felix, Sulla): Saul
Josh White: Joshua
Meir Cohen Avi Zeev Behar: Ezekiel
Odey Meroueh: Odysseus
Ram Silfen: Cyrillus
Sarah Grey: Sarah
Sheila Sharon Nazarian: Zephaniah
Shiuan Wei Lai: good thief, Lao Tzu's friend, Karl Weierstrass
Vasilios: Cicero (vs Demosthenes in Plutarch)
Yuyin Chen: Chenaniah (1 Chronicles 15:22,27), Telemachus, John Harvard

...
Andrew Hurley: Paris, Marcus Vipsanius Agrippa, Galileo Galilee
Benjamin Netanyahu: Benjamin, Nikolai Ivanovich Yezhov
Brad Pitt: Patroclus, Spartacus
David DeAngelo (Eben Pagan): Daniel, Leonidas
Donald John Trump: Gnaeus Pompeius Magnus, Barabbas?
Elon Musk: Uriel, Uriah the Hittite, Adolf Hitler, Marcus Licinius Crassus, Flaming Sword of Eden
Marshall Mathers: David, Mahatma Gandhi
Patrick Stewart: William Shakespeare [gene Luka]
Terrence Tau [Lao Tzu descendant]
...
Zechariah: Doeg the Edomite, Rodrigo Díaz de Vivar El Cid Campeador, Archduke Franz Ferdinand, Jack Kerouac; likely Diogenes, Oedipus Laiades.
Reuben: Apostle Mark, Napoleon, Democritus, Joseph Stalin

Challengers:
Leviathan (N), Octopus (K), Succubus (E), Parasite (G), Hermaphrodite (Achilles)

Alexander relatives:
Hilbert, Kelvin, Banach, Schrodinger

David, Aaron, Saul, Felix, Pharaoh, Atreus, Jezebel, Rurik, Nevsky, Genghis Khan, Hideyoshi, Richard the Lionhearted, Louis, Marie Antoinette, Thurn and Taxis, Aragorn, Van Dam, Ferdinand

Marshal "horse master", metaphorically women, typically women control men.

Death the Diabolo relative morality.

War of the Genders.

After patriarchal excess, matriarchal revenge.

Human species mildly patriarchal, demonstrated by size difference between males and females.

Most abuse oblique because of heavy prison sentences, not physical but emotional violence.

Skewed scales, men have 10x testosterone of women yet held to equal standard. Also women get everything in divorce, men pinatas.

E.g. Travis vs Flis.

"Catholicism is matriarchal":

militaristic marshal/cacao/chaos

Essence of Polygamy:

Behaviorally men compete and women socialise. Men are more alone, women more in groups.

Consorts acceptable with permission, blessed if necessary.

...

Dominant women are the norm in China (Cathay), Italy, Ukraine.

Dominant men are the norm in Japan (Nihon), Arabia, Russia.

...

Catholicism Cathay matriarchal.

Worm (Rounders 1998)

Kay like Cane, betrayed and murdered brother. Needs to justify so creates problems then pretends to solve them, like a telemarketing identity theft scammer. Tokugawa: become friends with your enemies to know how to destroy.

...

What's China doing to the West?

Parasitic; cozies up, bleeds dry.

...

Joseph and Judah

Master Sun and Cao Cao

Caesar and Agosto

Aurelius and Constantine

Gauss and Riemann

Pattern of moral and physical corruption, until only soul remains.

Biblical promises targeted by N, K. (Similar Aramaic letters Kaf, Nun)

David promised a lamp, so destroy his religion, turn his kin into pariahs (Jews, Russians). Job promised a signet ring, alienate her, then inbreed her flesh to handicap.

Kali's thugs ... Cretins.

"Truth is in the mind of God.":

definition thought

Sugar is lethal.

"Law is digital, clemency subjective.":

ecclesiastical judgement

Relativity is selective application.

Samson lets his hair be cut by "The Philistines are upon you" Delilah.

...

Solomon:

"All is vanity",

"And rejoice in the wife of your youth" (Proverbs 5:18)

700 wives and 300 consorts shouts and records interference beyond incoherent testimony.

...

Judas and Jesus echoes Abraham and Isaac. Starts a fire from smouldering embers of Judaism, propagating good with bad. Could have stoned Jesus for blasphemy quietly, LORD arranges crucifixion symbolizing K (Judah), followed by religious thermonuclear blast.

Darwinian human male behavior beta or suboptimal long term, humans require nurturing.

Evolutionary fallacy: how does adaptation change the number of chromosomes?

[Dragon is dragooning, no permission hence wrongdoing!]

"Wife Jordan Consort Georgia Consort Virginia":

RETROGRESSION rancidification/incoordination/fornication/conviction/*DRAGOONING*/*WRONGDOING*/Darwinian/
gorgonian
DIVERSIFICATION congregations/*NEWTONIAN*
DRAGOONING REVERIFICATION

"Alexander Shapiro Grothendieck":

HADAD PALEOCORTEX SHRINKING
Hadad peregrination Sherlocke

...

prekindergarden ethical
PEREGRINATION HEXAHEDRAL/Sherlocke/axeheads/Heracles
NATANIEL choreographer
Nataniel exorcise Godhead
DANDELION SCAPEGOATER
scapegoater hexahedron/Rhineland

...

Kleenex * [list of crimes]
Kleenex historiographer [4K years]
Kleenex coordinated Hagar
Kleenex choreograph tsarina
Kleenex addiction pharaoh
Kleenex diagnose Richard
Kleenex Hadad cooperating
Kleenex Schrodinger pariah
Kleenex rape (2221) originator/Siddhartha
Kleenex parasite Dacron/dragon
Kleenex operations Richard
Kleenex Aphro (4844) cantharidised
Kleenex tardigrade harpoons/scorpion
Kleenex tradership arachnoid
Kleenex patriarchies dragon
Kleenex Cain priesthood/Siddhartha/tardigrade/tradership/Aphrodite/posterior/hardship/shithead/Pharaoh
Kleenex Siddhartha coroner
Kleenex arachnoid adopter/pothead
Kleenex pothead signora Richard

...

Einstein hexahedral Ko

Cowardice is submission to fear. Abuse conditions fear, in my case of academics and women, the beat down of Catholic Amazons.

Distinguish between a cowardly soul and conditioned terror.

Distinguish between a moment of cowardice and a habit of cowardice.

The deepest scars are unseen.

Easiest to mold children, most profoundly evil to miseducate. Christianity creates drones by child abuse and smoking weed in youth.

Society prefers to attribute problems to you rather than collective error; they are responsibility and rebuke resistant.

People take jealous pleasure in seeing your potential handicapped, out of the relative fallacy that shining your light dims theirs.

...

Never give up. You feel something wrong in your soul, likely wrong, correct it. Trust LORD over self.

Intelligence is malleable not a precise number. People have genetic proclivities, natural gifts. Our lives are measured by results which stem from persistence and positive attitude beyond intellect.

Character is destiny, and character is developed and refined.

You miss 100% of the shots you don't take.

You don't know until you try.

Failure is an incident not a syndrome, it can be corrected.

Miseducation and spiritual corruption necessitate self aware introspection.

Don't let anyone tell you you can't do something. You can do anything you set your mind to. Almost.

The point is you don't know where your mental limits are, if any.

We constrain ourselves through false beliefs, becoming prisoners of our own minds. Intelligent people learn too quickly, accept failure too readily, and attribute it to their capability versus their attempt, attitude, and effort.

The truth will set you free.

You want your skin on the line.

God's law vs man's. Silence is complicity in sins against the LORD and will bring God's wrath on

everyone. War suspends law not humanity.

Preference for maintaining faith via blood, but Judaism is not mystically passed on maternally, a free ticket and idolatrous fetish of the womb.

E.g. Manasseh, Ephraim, Jesse, etc.

Circumcision covenant with LORD, not the Jewish people.

Blood is blood, and faith is faith.

Karaite Judaism is patriarchal with Biblical adherence, rabbis are scholars not prophets.

Philosophy 101 underlies wars.

The sincerest flattery is imitation.

Universalisation and proselytizing are carcinogens.

e.g.'s: Defending democracy in my backyard, Russia is far too small.

[Guinness ... Guan Yin, Ginni

Gauss lives across street]

"world historical record for torture":

HARCOURT DETROIT FREDRIC SORROW

...

circulariser foretold horror

circulariser whore drool

"Carl Friedrich Gauss":

circulariser gash [... ring a bell?]

"Arjun Jaganathan Satyamoorthy":

nonstatutory [RAPE] maharajah

Maharashtra [Mumbai] annatto

tyrannosaur Mahayana/Gotham/(math agony)

annotator hamstrung/maharajah/anagrams/Mahayana/Ramayana/Gautama/Saturn

GUANTANAMO [Guanyin G, Bay ... Bayesian] sanatory/Thanatos

[death; "Death I am become, destroyer of worlds" (Gita 11:32)]

GASTRONOMY ARJUNA

Manhattan Argonaut

orangutan [Kong] maharajah/Thanatos/ashtray/Aaron/Roman

...

SATAN RAMANUJAN /MARYANNA

NATHAN ARTHROSTOMY [surgical opening into joint ... WEED] /gnathostoma [parasitic worm]

Nathan Utahan gyrator/orgasm [spirit sabotaging Alexander]

Gautama Jason John

Gautama (Torah)^2 Nanny/Jay

Gautama Torah tyranny

People reflect what you project.

Chaos is a ladder.

Game of Thrones (GOT):

Leaf creates Night King

[Eve and Apple]

Octavia Alexandru (Season 4)

Kae Alexander (Season 6)

[NATHANIEL, "wake the dragon"]

"Viserys Targaryen":

WISE ARRANGES

SERVANT GRAYS

gayness irate

gay vainest

Artin greaser/serves

"Viserys Targaryen Dragon":

EASTER ARRANGING

retrogressing Rand

Natan aggressive/adviser/advisory

"Joffrey Baratheon":

BETRAYER JOHN

FATHER OBERON

beta honorary

"Ramsay Bolton":

ABSALOM

Salomon Rab

"Daenerys Targaryen":

Easterner angry [Esther, G]

tyranny eagerer

"Eddard Stark": trader dad [LORD]

"Brandon Stark":

DAKOTAN

Satan Bond

Ko bastard/brand

...

Hodor "Hold the Door", Odor

[and Shae J, face axed monster]

"Tyrion Lannister":

ARISTOTLE

Trinity ensnarl/Roseann

[Snaked disobedience, Reek ... Erik]

"Theon Greyjoy":

Joey hornet/theory/throne/Tyreon/ergot/honey/horny/hero

Nero Goth

[Bastard means LORD's younger]

"Jon Snow Aegon Targaryen":

George sanatory/sayonara/Rosanna/Trojans/wanton

wrong oestrogen/estrogen/negator/Roseanna/Tennyson/eastern/regent/Agosto

AGOSTO AARON (88) Gwenny

Gwynne/Genny/Jewry/Jenny

Agosto orange/wagerer/wronger/renown

REGENT AARON/GANJA

gangrene Rosanna

Newton gorgon

Ann Jay newsagent

Wagoner Jay negator/treason

[Kingslayer, Tyrion's brother]

"Jamie Lannister":

Jamesian litre

James Latiner

"Night King": HIN TING

[Red Witch]

"Melisandre":

Emeralds

AENEID MRS [XY]

[Retard stinks, reek ... Erica]

"Erica is like a fungus":

(sugarcane filius)/(cleanses augur)

Pardon a fool.

Self-immolation puts a fire under your ass. (Job motivation)

"Even those who have occasion for a lamp supply it with oil." (Plutarch: Pericles)

Dandelions exacerbate cracks.

[Erica Standhart, Seven of Nine,

Attempted erotic assimilation.

Georgia Travis, Geordi La Forge,

Attempted erotic vising ... visor.]

"America is the Borg":
MATRIARCHIES
marriage bitch
Creator Isiah/Sheba/Shae
armchair beet/Bose/bees/bets/set
Beta heroic/Homeric
research atom/goat
Cao British/eight
Moishe arbitrage/Arabic

Adam compelled overreach apple, disobedience. Result is G automatic demotion, Adam limbo. Apple J rotting; must obey and eat.

...
Snake envenomed since Adam and Eve, the Lilly of the valley.

The Las Vegas Needle
Dependence on emotion is addiction.
Masculine examples include exhilarating challenges e.g. fighting, hunting, pressure, gambling.
(Cocaine, Adrenalin, Heroin ... heroism)
Feminine examples include sensuality, orgasm, love, drama, music, suckling, pointless charity.
(Serotonin, endorphins, bass)

A half truth is a whole lie.
E.g. "New Testament", Koran

Strength is self control, wisdom is knowing when. E g. Mercy from the vengeful or justice from the timid.

Heaven and hell are on earth.

Big men small things.

Jack Kevorkian the prophet, people have a right to die.
<https://www.bidoun.org/articles/a-very-still-life>
Artwork:

1. Man in cracked rainbow egg praying, puppeteered by bunny rabbits with crosses to have a halo.
2. Achilles possessing a man to self-decapitate, has apple in mouth.
3. Santa stopping baby Jesus.
4. Blond Buddha decapitated by Lenin, motive force behind WWI, WWII, and Jesus ben Joseph, who frames him.

LORD curses those he despises with madness. LORD blesses those he loves with prophesy.

[Oy Vey!]
Hebrew faith becomes second temple Judaism in Ezra, Nehemiah.
Harder, ALL foreigners excluded, ALL mixed marriages forbidden.
Ironically, modern Jewish is Hebrew mixed with Eastern European.

[Catholic, pussy cat]
"Christianity is feminisation":
antichrist insanities

[Discovered at precisely 3:33 PM in the bathroom]
"God is like a shadow in the back of the mind":
denicotinise shthead (333) Oklahoma/lambda

[Bird's eye]
LORD likes listening to prayers, He records them in the Bible. He also records conversations from a bird's eye perspective.

Circumcision circumscribes people, rings are symbolic of a covenant, and there is no foreskin rejuvenation therapy.
(Lebedovych is working on that.)

[Job's rebellion]
Job, Biblically Japanese, has a strong sense of duty, honor, and pride, stunted sense of humor.
LORD and Satan busted on Job, so he swore eternal vengeance.

Freewill is limited. The LORD causes things to be.

Satan the Adversary, Diabolo the Slanderer. Ancient Greek διαβάλλω (diabállō, "to slander", literally "to throw across"). M and K.

"Satan the Adversary, Diabolo the Slanderer":
levelheadedness arbitrator/birthday
restorativeness hardheartedly/dethroned

"American Christian Diabolists":
decriminalisation archaist/catharsis
CHARACTERISATION ALBINISM
discrimination caesarist/Hebraist/Alastair
NONMATERIALISTIC ISIAIAH
remilitarisation Cain/China/Diana/Dinah
SENSATIONALISTIC ARMCHAIR
incarceration dismissal/hasidism/lambda
mercantilistic Obadiah
mineralisation archaistic/catharsis/diarist/Triassic
radicalisation cretinism/criminals
scandalisation arbiter/Hebraist
TRINITARIANISM ABOLISHES
...
ADAMANTINE SCHOLASTIC/CHARBROILS/CLASSICIST/HISTORICAL
charlatan misdirection/dominatrices/missionaries/romanticised

Humor a retard.

[LUNACY]
Paradoxical that the greatest enemies of the God of Israel had their greatest success as Hebrews.
G ... Jesus,
J ... Anne Frank yearning for Job,
K ... Einstein,
N ... Grothendieck,
Y ... Feynman

[Anti-Marcus]
Groundhog day, women sense the realization of best you. Soul senses potential, should feel discontent at settling in life. People sense their mistakes, but lie to themselves to buffer self esteem.
Intuition points to success, whereas logic is blind.
Logic impedes intuition.

Renaissance is rebirth, metaphor for return of antiquity.

Youth is insolent.
(E.g. J ... Japan is young, N ... Richardson, USA ... Demo-baby)

Humanities study human patterns, science studies divine patterns.

Assuming integrity of Tanakh, cluster of miracles around Elijah parallel those alleged of Jesus.

Universalisation is nonsense.
Most people do not want an agreement with the LORD, who will destroy you for disobedience.

[American Idol]
American democracy primed for close elections. If one party were substantially larger, they could kamikaze the other in primaries. Structure pushes popularity toward being neck to neck. Eliminating general primary prevents this possible strategic bias and focuses on opinion poll.
Structure discourages consensus, promotes polarization, adversity.

[IDOLATRY]
Point of interest: consider the recent case of 30 North Koreans executed for smuggling K-dramas. Seems tyrannical by Western standards, a violation of liberty, yet the Biblical punishment for idolatry is death. Possession vs worship?
Biblically destruction is appropriate, execution for worship only.
Legally smugglers deserve death.
Idols: Alexander received 20 years for MIT, misbranded for Georgia.

Occident (West) vs Orient (East). Cradle of civilization is Mesopotamia near Mediterranean, West unmatched in depth.
Seen in reincarnation frequency, and in choice of Canaan Israel.

Adam and Eve, LORD said He would create strife between men and women, echoed in BCE vs CE.
Torah is penned by Behemoth, Phaeton Testament by Leviathan.

Book of Enoch about spiritual sabotage, then corruption of mankind, then Noah's ark.

Pattern of spiritual sabotage:

1. Adam and Eve (G)
2. Abraham and Hagar (N)
3. Samson and Delilah (N)
4. David and Bathsheba (Michael)
5. Solomon and 700 women (N)
6. Jesus the false Messiah (N)
7. Vladimir impaling (Michael)

Pattern of murder:

1. Julius Caesar (N)
2. Marcus Aurelius (N)

A word to the wise suffices.

Euthanasia is acceptable.

Masculinity and femininity are earned. They are disjoint, though an individual can have elements of both.

Seeding psychological technique. Children should consume quality.

E.g. video games

FF7 - MIT (Emerald Weapon is Leviathan, Chronicler course #'s), FF8 - Caltech

Rankings can be skewed.

For example MIT and Harvard are highly mis-ranked to entrap Alexander, whereas Caltech and Oxford rule.

"Massachusetts Institute of Technology":

Themistocles Cato astonishes

Themistocles Augustness Octant/China/Hanoi

UNENTHUSIASTICAL ECOSYSTEM

"California Institute of Technology":

Lenin Catholicisation forego/forget

Lenin Christianity flatfoot/cattle/cutoff

"Oxford University": rounder visit

The "New Testament", in particular "Revelation", is a sanctioned snare.

Good thoughts, words, deeds. LORD rewards faith itself, wholeheartedly.

Fear is an instinct inhibiting action meant to protect value: life, safety.

In practice it is the most insidious and powerful weapon of mind control because of its primality.

Need courage and honesty to overcome, e.g. be true to soul in work and love, fear of success and mating.

The most common obstacle is the dog training of man, a prison for your mind, not God's Commandments which save.

Why child abuse is the one crime deserving a life sentence.

Nathaniel's hit list includes Samson and Solomon (Israel), Caesar and Aurelius (Rome), and the Romanovs (Russia). Anti-Alexander, Catholic (Cathay or China), Communist, Athenian in that order. The ruin of nations and war is no obstacle.

Next target is the USA via the degradation of law in Trump, potentially to imprison Alexander.

Women are more metaphorical, men are more literal.

Psychological tragedy. Of course universal disdain for a Servant.

Fault lies with people not God.

Condensation: set a rate.

Meeting quota vs allowing tasks or sleep to expand.

Inclination is like handedness.

The path of the loser is paved with excuses and self pity.

Jacob Israel wrestling with angel analogous to Israel nation wrestling with its neighbors with its faith.

Tanakh has one coherent narrator throughout. Why four fragmented versions: Matthew, Mark, Luke, John? Because it is a fraud.

Digitality creates structure.
Relativity creates chaos.
K, Lord of Cao, death the destroyer.

Supreme Court ruled presidents be treated as divinity; Biden should round them up to kowtow.

Honor from the dishonorable has no value, like the cheering of a crowd at WrestleMania.

Same sex union not marriage is condoned by David and Jonathan, echoed by musicality. There are human gender norms, adoption should respect them.
You could be raised by Amazons like Alexander.

[CONSORTS]

Consorts for the wrong reasons reflect greed. Women should not be a burden, but they are raised to squabble to emasculate men, pushing for ideal equivalence.
Monogamy won't cure rottenness, and polygamy won't corrupt virtue. Imagine someone saved from abandonment creating chaos in a family in gratitude, e.g. Leah.
The Torah honors not condemns Israel and Leah, Judah and Tamar, and Ruth and Boaz.

Moral relativity favors relatives.

The LORD is omniscient; thus He values righteousness in people whereas people idolise intelligence in themselves.

Challengers' overall strategy is to humanise Alexander which is debasement. Alexander overall strategy is to elevate humanity through righteous instruction.

Caste elevation is more difficult than debasement, and you cannot change someone's soul. Inter-marriage destroys families.

Pleasures of the flesh are base.
Alkaline is the antithesis of acidic.
Christianity is the antithesis of Hebraism, nullifying its central tenants out of collective jealousy, beating good people down.
Why not follow a good example, why try to rewrite the Book? Pride.

Women already carry guns. Biblical Queen Esther is a good example.

The world is laced with divine humor. The LORD verifies His covenant by exalting Israel.

Israel owes its existence to the Torah, its allegiance to the LORD, all its problems arising from Biblical disobedience.
A secular identity is anathema; conquered minorities who are not slain become labor with the opportunity to convert.

Corollary is that in a secular country, state sponsorship of religion is forbidden, including the Ten Commandments.

No lapping blood: bloodthirst is forbidden.

[ORIENTAL WEEDS]

Duty and respect alone are insidious Oriental idols. Manufactured obligations and moderation toward anathema.
A duty to respect the lives and dignity of weeds in your garden.
Unobtrusiveness is cowardliness, in essence mutual enablement of vices. Silence is consent of rape.

Georgia is horny as a rabbit, devilish, a siren vices, squirt is a discharge.
A succubus Erica also vices.
Rebellious souls become demons.

[GOVERNANCE - bottom up]

LORD favors rule of law preserving rights of individuals, permits robust diversity of governance structures.
LORD favors self appointed judges and officers.
Individual rule singularly vulnerable, yet potential to do tremendous good. Best to preserve capacity,

empower as needed in proportion to competence.

Military, moral, philosophical needs and competence hard to recognize, also problems hard to correct by resisting a majority, evidence that the LORD elevates individuals.

Recognize need by spotting cracks, i.e. contradictions and injustices.

Recognize competence by success.

Brainwashing, emotionalism, trained dependence, and ideals are psychological vices misemployed by all forms of government.

Trust childhood intuition and common sense rooted in the soul, as even logic can mislead.

The best defenses are virtue: truth, integrity, education, humanity.

History illustrates that beating is beta and creating alpha.

Limited logical capacity to innovate in government. Ideas are more powerful than people.

Nathaniel intense irrational hatred of Torah.

[Secular logic]

People have a right to their bodies and lives thus none to others'.

Both parents have custodial rights to unborn fetuses.

Lot offers his daughters to be gang raped, so they in turn rape him, producing Moab and Benammi, enemies of Israel.

In rape and incest, children are not accountable for parents' sin, but they inherit their troubles.

Evil is easy.

Insanity is defined by unhealthy mental deviation from the average.

Genius is defined by mentally exceeding the average.

Not necessarily correlated.

[IGNORAMUSES]

Roman dictators were elected for a period when survival of the state was in jeopardy, e.g. Civil War. The American euphemism is martial law, the weaker version executive order. (E.g. Trump is unfit, circumstance inappropriate.)

War suspends law not ethics.

Birds are dinosaurs.

Levi's blue jeans have tassels.

Beards give majesty.

In work and life, trusting your soul leads to greatness. Yet competence and appreciation can be developed in any sphere by patient persistence toward a goal.

[IDOLS]

All men are not created equal, equal, or brothers, but deserve equal justice and opportunity in most spheres.

Preserving individual liberty is fundamental, the corollary national. Yet liberty alone becomes vice. Idols are double edged swords, both powerful encouraging ideals and sacred pillars, people turn violent if you touch them.

Shepherds are for sheep, taking the guise of idols.

Education empowers, enabling innovation and growth, fundamentally beginning with truth in the mind. Yet without religion and ethics it is a soulless machine.

Favor lighthouse over lash, respecting choice and its spirit.

The world is asymmetric, imperfectly perfect.

Worshipping life is idolatry, respecting life is religious duty.

...

There is no liberty from the LORD or His laws, desiring such is folly.

One man's innocent blood carries an eternal curse, David and Uriah.

David educates on equality. Absalom educates on democracy,

Solomon and Nathan on autocracy.

David and Goliath is an example to inspire, not limited to archangels.

Biblical law highly values female virginity because of attachment. Disincentive for copulation, incentive toward earlier marriage in prime childbearing years.

Strong incentive for men to mature young; the early bird gets the worm.

Women naturally manipulate, why the LORD put men in charge.

See Adam and Eve.

Genitalia resemble snakes and octopi.

Obedience over sacrifice. All things are the LORD'S, and He causes things to be. The most you can give is the choice allotted you.

Saul instructs that is often easier to give up your life than your pride.

Can tradition be possessed? (Nathan says yes.) The living are caretakers.

Can the collective change divine law and judgement? No, see Moses and Aaron, Absalom and David.

Salamanders inhabit palaces, thus teaching empathy, humility, and service are key. Cold blooded warm hearted is best.

Unearned and unchecked power easily becomes vice, beauty exemplary in women.

One penis cannot simultaneously inhabit two vaginas. Rational purpose for polygamy is necessity or love; greed, vanity, and pleasure are vices.

Marriage is a sacred contract, not ROMANTic mutual unbreakable possession.

Culturally neither education nor the military are esteemed in the United States, rather industrial moneymaking.

CHRISTIANITY

Christianity is feminisation and homogenisation, an attempt at repealing the Torah using ideals. It annuls: the Law ... hence women's rights and antislavery ethos, beards, hats, hygiene of hand washing and bathing, kosher food, circumcision, plurality, rational education, and proportional sentencing ... hence the death penalty in lieu of lifetime confinement.

Why the heros lived in antiquity, followed by the dark ages. Why heavily Christianized men act gay, failing to satisfy Christian women.

THE GENDER WARS

Different physical standards for men and women. Value of a man measured more by competition women by childbearing. Women are attracted to dominant men, but not vice versa. Also women are more likely to be bisexual, men polarized either straight or gay.

Why mild plurality is no insult to the dignity of a woman, yet for a man it is a complete disgrace.

No male beauty contests in Israel.

Profeminists hate asymmetry hence unborn children.

The patriarchs and David were righteous, Solomon excessive.

Biblical Judaism does not need revision, it has become legally matriarchal, how insidious !

Bitter women preemptively emasculate innocent men as if the genders were at war, domineering in a misguided attempt at dominance.

Masculinity is characterized by emotional stability and rationality, not machismo or pollination.

Dating is like locusts crawling.

Sex carries a toll.

Responsibility for the Holocaust lies with Lenin, echoed in the kibbutz. Weeds penetrate crevices and dull the mind.

Promise of creating a nation Israel necessitates reproduction. Model of one man thirteen children is nonstandard, consorts handicap in most circumstances. Similar to Islamic acute shortage of men due to war.

Surface attraction common, search for deeper connection. Corollary is fear to speak to someone is absurd.

Royals and aristocrats are behaviorally and genetically filtered over millennia. People who have managed to subdue an entire population are nontrivial, even chosen by the LORD as David. Antithetical to athenianism and coarsely handled by its system both by structure and intent.

Yet nurture is even more powerful than nature, so there is hope for all.

American athenianism (... atheism) is financially shear masses while maintaining illusion of choice hence complacency. Genius mind control. When facing ruin, why must elections be adversarial?

Why not a no contest joint ticket?

Effective plutocracy where Nathaniel runs the show.

Ruled by blind hatred, he would do anything to hurt Alexander, even betray his democratic ideals via Chinese Catholic allegiance.

No surer way to handicap someone than by miseducation in youth. Truth liberates.

Sarah should have born the consequences of her decision and cooperated with consort Hagar, children are a profound blessing not garbage for the wilderness. Discarding offspring is no solution, does not discharge responsibility or consequences. Look at Israel now, needlessly at war with Arabs. Ishmael has been loyal and righteous.

Law on Marriage:

One man one wife.

Inheritance primacy with wife.

Consorts not ideal, limit two with wife's consent.

...
Biblically, best offspring are from monogamous true love. Polygamy splinters families, in excess becomes vice, gluttony and vanity.

Yet motive for consorts can be physical need, e.g. children and companionship, or more rarely love, peace, and righteousness.

Consorts: splinter families, constrain men physically and legally, power dynamic shifts toward women and children, potential child support and alimony, usually unattractive logistically, endanger emotional intimacy, highly stigmatic with prejudice against intent, alternative to divorce severance. In practice modern examples of consorts are mistresses and the "ex ... X", the ex being only acceptable post marital, whereas "consort" is retrograded and more general.

...
X ideals create gender X and marital exes. Exes as if the relationship and responsibility is dead which it is often not.

Consider Abraham and Ishmael.

...
Consorts may be a Godsend in places with declining populations like Japan and Korea, as gender norms are asymmetric and the physical labor involved in childbearing is heavier for women.

Useful when shortage of men.

Mormonism produces offspring.

Chinese love gambling. Macao, lucky eight.

Light and dark define each other. Plebeian vs Aristocrat.

Jesus serves a deep purpose.

Rushing ahead you do not get far. Tortoise and the hare.

Trump's ethics are poor, but factually he is innocent of insurrection by a sliver, guilty of inciting to riot and tax fraud.

Politics is no cause for prejudice on bond lending or legal defense; however, BIDEN has my vote.

[INCITING RIOT,
just short of insurrection]
TRUMP'S SPEECH

Right and wrong versus establishment of guilt versus severity of crime.

Right and wrong are digital, a vote by a standard measures guilt.

Can a state singlehandedly keep president off ballot? Severity.

If you rape one person you are a rapist, does not matter the others who consented. You murder one person you are a murderer. You betray one state you are a traitor. Yes, but not necessarily to the nation. Notably betrayal ranks less than murder, also less definite as dealing with abstractions.

...
You commit one felony you are a felon and can be excluded from the ballot for moral turpitude.

Trump assembled crowd hence is their leader, wrongly incited to riot.

Leaders bear some responsibility for followers' actions.

Freedom of speech does not apply for elected officials as they represent others hence are responsible to them. Cannot lie or mislead, betraying public trust.

Value integrity over skill in top positions, because principles establish foundations whereas skill fades. Tortoise and the hare.

Consider Solomon.

Music in excess is a vice, though inspiring in small doses. Likewise with sexuality.

Trade based on principles, should align with patterns and probability.

"Adam Enoch Abraham Joseph":

Ahab comprehends

Strategy to kill God: bleed virtue while teaching vice.

Character progression incongruity:

Adam, Enoch, Abraham, Joseph all exemplary. Then Samson, Solomon, Judas fools. Vices bind.

Tactic to destroy Alexander:

layered probability.

1. Ignore Bible
2. Idolize marriage and trinity
3. Emasculation
4. Abusive ignorance
5. Depressive climate
6. Sabotage family
7. Poison Hebrew faith
8. Isolation and torture

TRUST YOUR INTUITION. If you sense something is wrong, it is wrong. Not difficult to make major life decisions correctly, in fact very easy, agonizing leads to error.

Ideal life can be become an idol: rather, it is a blessing to realise and correct your mistakes.

Inflection "turning" points in life: religion, education, marriage.

Alexander got 25 years for two wrong turns, prom and college.

Equal work merits equal pay, yet on average expect women to make less money because of innate gender differences, men providing and women nurturing.

Fit in work and marriage should be natural, you should gravitate toward, not struggle against the current. Commitment and consistency creating success, "hard work" should become daily joy.

Beware addiction to struggle or pain as a false proxy of progress, life should become smooth.

In our souls we sense our mistakes, confirmation is not necessary. Redemption begins by recognizing and admitting mistakes.

Most people identify with their thinking, defending falsehood. Most people want to see you fail, it cheers them with respect to their own mediocre lives. Most people get convinced they are stupid. Losers drag others down, winners help people up.

...
Interestingly declining Ko's challenge is worse than cowering before Caltech and J because there is no excuse.

Challenging the strong has substance, challenging the weak is worse than nothing, for by hiding you self limit, becoming as your associates. Helping the poor is noble, picking on the defenseless despicable. Like James Ko plotting child abuse and family betrayal.

The architect of Xtianity is not Ko but rather Nathan and Georgia. Nathan is the nemesis by design, Georgia betrayed the man to whom she owes everything, like Absalom.

COVENANT

All men are equal as lives, they do not equally keep the covenant.

Is not the ethnic hurdle deliberate to test men as Abraham was tested?

Is not the persecution Israel striving with the nations, exemplified?

You reap what you sow, easy come easy go.

Observe how yeast multiplies (x, .), negated by division (/), line).

Observe how Catholicism was historically banned in Cathay its point of origin, observe how China exports junk.

Learn virtue by studying vice, inching toward the source by truth.

Religion is divine instruction in virtue, imitation falls short.

Virtue speaks for itself.

Force necessary when reason collapses, as advertisements are necessary when products are poor.

If the LORD saves the righteous, why do Xtian saints die hideously? Halo thermonuclear glow.

ON WOMEN - HONESTY

Healthy to feel uncomfortable approaching strangers with dubious intent, called having a conscience.

Discomfort disappears with honesty and positive intent: stick to entertainment mindset to develop social skills. People radiate intent.

At worst hire a prostitute and save time and complications, like drama, disease, abortion, and bastards. James Bond lives on screen... mentality "I could but I won't."

Sexuality is sacred, cheapened in modern world, pollination idolised by both men and women.

Pollination and gambling exalt skill as opposed to substance.
People are not interchangeable parts on an assembly line, souls are special and irreplaceable.
Rejection akin to physical pain, fear of it cowardice, yet regret is a nail in your coffin.
Cowards die every day looking in the mirror, the brave once.
If women treat you with discourtesy and disrespect, it reflects on them.
Onus and responsibility is on men, why women are renamed.
Woman's physical attraction proportional to her esteem of you, status for women and beauty for men being equally superficial.
Pornography is junk food.

TRIBALNESS

Humans are tribal, no excuses, no apologies. Inter-marriage weighs genetics against culture, the latter typically dominating. Why Ruth is special.

...
Xtianity has been trying for two millennia to demonise and destroy the Hebrew tribes to create its own.

PSYCHOLOGY OF EDUCATION

Worst disservice is lying to people.
e.g. telling children they are special when their results are mediocre, leading to entitled college degrees for everyone versus trade school, or convincing geniuses they are stupid by jealous sabotage or incorrect feedback, e.g. learning too quickly through failure versus persisting.
The brutal feedback of securities trading kindly prevents languishing, likewise Caltech is supposed to mercifully weed out nonacademics not cater to published averages. Poor results are not permanent, measurements do not perfectly gauge your intellect or ability, but also reflect your effort, attitude, and circumstances.

You cannot do anything you set your mind to, but you can TRY, and you do not know where your mental limits are, or if they even exist, or to what extent the mind can master the flesh, like in Buddhism.
Best to bravely jump in deep end or ring, necessitating focus on goal, forcibly shifting attention away from petty psychology. Analogously true in business, focusing on goals versus securities pays dividends, e.g. Musk, Buffett.

Trying and failing is preferable to regret, for why not try again? Persistence leads to excellence, persistence is attractive.

Michael Jordan: "Miss 100% of unattempted shots."
Key is to give 100% in each attempt.

Success is never permanent, failure not fatal, persistence wins. The righteous man falls and gets up over and over again. Israel had his wages changed ten times! You are only a failure if you accept failure, you are only a fool if you give up.

X-Tianity

Good in bad is dirty, looking for the silver lining in an atomic blast, like mass distributed Bibles no one bothers to actually read carefully because critical thought was not encouraged in the Dark Ages.
Easier to destroy than to create.

ISRAEL

Hebrew faith is of the Creator, with precedence to write holy law, hence it is real. Primal.
Neither intended for nor beholden to mass market, only to LORD.
Literally God's people, with an open door.

...
The real lesson of Jacob Israel is persistence after love. After twenty one years of labor, having wages changed ten times, he finally got what he wanted. Similar lesson of the promised land of Canaan Israel.

US Immigration - Federal Overreach

Freedom of movement of legals once within border, therefore immigration administration federal.
However illegals do not have right to freedom of movement, therefore border security need not be federal.
Asylum is federal, burden necessarily distributed evenly throughout states by possibly restricting movement (to Martha's vineyard). If burden not distributed, federal asylum invalid by inequity.
Practically immigration is a local problem (TX, Southwest), majority unaffected initially.
Individual need not bow to mob, States should not be handicapped (Abbott metaphor) by Congress, for then what benefit in Statehood?

The LORD despised the generation of Sinai, so He led them in circles in the desert for forty years and spoon fed them manna and quail.
Xtianity borrows the notion of trained dependence through the yeasty Eucharist, likewise through the "penalty" of Excommunication.

Empowering rivals spurs excellence, consider Abraham Lincoln, considered the finest.

Having a nemesis corrects errors.

Smiles bury grief.

Attribute guilt precisely, recognising emotions are coarse, unlike Simeon and Levi in Genesis. Every man's sin is his own; countries inherit the fallout of those of sovereigns and governments, but not guilt. No communal guilt without communal action.

[Hamas militants deserve death, Hamas voters deserve misery not death, which I find appalling.]

In my case I suspect the LORD wants my skin on the line, similarly to Nebuchadnezzar humbled. Likewise I suspect He promotes a battle arena to foster excellence, recognizing the good in bad.

Joseph Stalin's artificial famines prompting the Holocaust.

We see consorts in Genesis, especially of Israel, the hidden point being to multiply into a nation.

"A good enemy is your best friend."

Interesting, Nathaniel of all the archangels honors me most highly by constantly trying to destroy me while others spit and gaslight. I suppose he is doing his job.

Algebraic Ideals ... K-Theory
(unholy trinity, HQ in NYC)
Freedom - in excess New Jersey
Love - in excess Meatloafian
Democracy - unchecked is the Mob

To be able to cheat someone is not possible, actions sum to worth, because the LORD is the judge.

BURNING MAN psychedelic festival in NEVADA's Black Rock desert.

On Mercy

"Sticks and stones can break my bones but words can never hurt me." Nonsense, directly contrary to Biblical narrative, curses feared and blessings regarded. Divine model instructing human behavior toward good thoughts, words, and deeds.

Injury heals but pride does not, as forgiveness requires effort and nobility of soul, yet interestingly not understanding.

If people had understanding, or at least recognized their ignorance, they would be quicker to forgive.

The wise know they know nothing.

Mercy with understanding is equally virtuous but less laudable than without, analogous to why the struggle of humanity elevates.

"God is merciful" reflects the LORD'S omniscience and holiness.

Most hatred flows from ignorance, revenge the hobby of the small, properly belonging to the LORD.

We see in the Book of Job the real test is not of Job but of the LORD, who's plan is to elevate poor Job, the counterplot to dethrone God.

Perhaps afterward Job became vassal of Antichrist Nathan, making further appearances as Jonah defying the LORD, Delilah slaying Samson, Sheba diluting Israel, Pilate washing his hands, and Anne Frank the lovable victimised heretic.

...

"People don't change," at least according to M, the smartest angel.

Consider K and L.

Lot instigates against Abraham, Abraham later sparing Lot's life in Sodom and rescuing him and his family. Judah tosses brother Joseph into a pit and sells him into slavery, Joseph later saving Judah and family from starvation.

Consider the CATiline conspiracy against Caesar where Octavio's allies assassinate Caesar, Caesar willing his fortune to Octavio and the Roman people.

Presently Alexander is a "monster" for surviving a lifetime of indirect persecution by James, including instigating Oct.8, Alexander's reward for having helped China, followed by sparing James's life.

...

Travis tortures Alexander to world historical record, Alexander spares her pathetic life at NYC.

Travis instigates the brand, Israel complicit, Alexander helps Israel avoid implosion by suicide and enslavement by Georgia. Americans torture Alexander to death, Alexander spares NYC, headquarters of nemesis N, who thanks him by sabotaging surgery.

Lesson of David is warfare does not annul being good to others.

***Believe in Yourself.

"Faith in probability is the death of God.":

indefeasibility footpath/highroad/Horatio/OBADIAH/Pharaoh

...

And so not taking a "bet" reflects fear of probability and lack of faith in Oneself, a self annulment.

The shortcut to human greatness is the Bible; it's all been done.

Alexander History

Immaculate Conception Ukrainian Catholic Grade School.

Baba "Anna Flis": slay Ann F

"Alexander Luka Flis": Aeneid Ursula

Principal "Doris Jurek": Sire Ko

Fat bitch looks like Octopus Ursula from The Little Mermaid, purpose is to child abuse me into becoming a worm, too scared to even speak to Jordan, scared to learn, ashamed of reflection in mirror. Octavian responsible.

"Georgia Nathan Achilles Ko":

Ashikaga challenger

[Practices exclusion, preaches universalism.]

[ON ROME]

Hannibal and Maharbal.

According to Livy, Maharbal strongly urged an immediate march on the city of Rome. Hannibal responded by saying "I commend your zeal, but I need time to weigh the plan which you propose." Maharbal then replied, "Assuredly, no one man has been blessed with all God's gifts. You, Hannibal, know how to gain a victory; you do not know how to use it." Latin: "Vincere scis, Hannibal; victoria uti nescis."

Was this not rather clemency, or even the LORD? Hannibal was not stupid, having done a lot of killing he would recognize a deathblow, life followed closely by Caesar.

Alexander had a chance to obliterate NYC, and despite strong distaste found it wrong, see Abraham and Sodom.

That the LORD was going to obliterate NYC does not mean he wanted it so, see Nineveh.

In war, weigh their lives and Isaiah versus potential World War III?

Alexander should have obeyed and not trimmed his beard, see Saul.

Prayer, unwitting disobedience.

Yet earning a crown implies prayer considered, for accidents merit no honor as manslaughter merit no death. Also subsequent opportunity for expiation.

[... Beto vs AO Cortez,

grass crown of Sulla,

tragically not worth Creator soul.]

Likewise consider, Caesar was known for celerity and clemency. Master Sun, "I have heard that in war haste can be folly, but have never seen delay that was wise."

[Cato=emotion+idealism+relativity]

ANTICATO

Caesar was right circumstantially:

there was no presidency, no elliptic oval office, rather squabbling and civil war.

Caesar was wrong legally: the Rubicon is not to be crossed, a parallel to Christian moral relativity.

Yet God's law is above man's, never to be broken.

Cato was wrong circumstantially:

recognizing the need for a military dictator in civil war and individual leadership in government, his personal hatred spurred him to not only legitimately support Pompey but also move to disenfranchise Caesar and his legions, legally inciting civil war.

Cato was right legally but wrong ethically; no soldier, also no Roman, he weaponised the law to ensnare like a woman.

He was also motivated by illogical idealism, wishing for a less capable leader to mitigate structural damage, when a more capable leader is more enlightened.

Ideals must yield to survival, and empowering a fool solves nothing.

Naturally he disguised his actions as preservation, when in fact he preserved a state of civil war.

Rome did not benefit from Cato's Catiline conspiracy. There was a year of blight, a decade of civil war, every traitor's dagger was avenged, and Caesar was deified and burned on a pyre, even before the populace learned he willed a large fraction of his fortune to ordinary Roman citizens.

Cato has doubled down on evil.

Caesar was known for his clemency toward enemies and even Cato, who plotted misguided vengeance for his own needless suicide.

Caesar surrendered the dictatorship after eleven days, his later folly being that lifetime dictator was an egoistic ploy for assassination.

There is a different law for war and peace, but ethics remain the same.

Unrighteous judgement never endures for the LORD is real.

ANTICATHOLIC

Unspoken duty is idolatry.

Unannullable marriage is tyranny. Relative morality is criminal.

Universal religion is communist.

...

Faith without reason is blind.

Hope without action is lame.

Love without discipline is dumb.

Virtue in excess can become vice, e.g. the meatloafian love of Jesus.

Also virtue disobedient is vice, see Saul and Jonah.

Excellence is habitual amalgamation of virtue, the wisest being love and mercy.

Polygamy splinters families.

Less conducive to intimacy, nurture, quality but rather competition.

LORD'S law is one wife, consort acceptable in necessity, not ideal, best avoided.

[E.g. King Charles should have had a divorce. Israel had no choice, he was circumstantially connived, and Sarah was barren.]

Cowardice is worse than death, you lose your soul.

Far more difficult to create than to destroy. Nine months to a second. Many ways to die, one way to live.

Many ways to lie, one way to tell the truth. Easier to sin than be righteous, though both habituated.

Might is in temperance. Peaceful competition less urgent but much more challenging than war. Necessity created by lack of a safety net.

Aristotelian proof of ngrams

For any set of letters of size n , there is a distribution of constructible words, hence a word length k density. Intersect what is possible or $(n \text{ choose } k)$ binomial with what is valid in English. Longest lengths are least likely in both distributions, thus in the intersection. Thus if you iteratively remove longest words you get the least probable possibility, essentially Bayesian statistics, also the essence of trading.

Strive for excellence, but do not worship an ideal life, for what is not fatal can be remedied.

Perfect in imperfection, ideal free.

Often setting an impediment becomes a disguised gift, e.g. Stephen Hawking and Hellen Keller, patriarchy vs equivalence, Judaism vs world religions, and humanity vs superpowers. Likewise often gifts become an impediment by spoiling, e.g. wealth, telepathy, shape shifting. No surer way to ruin.

When is a gift not a gift?

Xmas entitles, Hanukah rewards not burning out.

Junk food and carbonated soda Coca Cola lack nutrition, they live next door to small kindnesses.

Hatred goads us to strive, that is its purpose, not to kill or maim.

The LORD hated Esau.

Pressure condenses diamonds.

Thank the LORD for adversity, likewise for the Adversary.

Reproof is kindness, embracing challenges elevates.

Fools grasp for control, the wise empower by education. Nothing is more damaging than a lie, a prison for the mind.

Gender equivalence is sterile.

Free will is illusory. The LORD causes things to be, either tipping the scales or explicitly making.

With failure, distaste, and folly, humans learn too quickly. Learn slowly.

Sin: atone, expiate, offering.

Liberty eludes definition.

MK: Raiden/Shao Khan and Sindel

KOF: Kyo Kusanagi (L), Iori Yagami (M), K

The Matrix:

NEOcortical NuEv0 Testamento

Smith is good.

Motivate people using ideals and emotions.

Intelligence prevents problems before they occur, wars are best won without fighting.

In love and life, I have not seen benefit to suppression of true love. And when this rare quality is present obstacles are overcome.

Not balls or gut, as if not doing something goes against your soul.

LORD projects archangels, they are incomplete aspects of divinity. Roman/Korean (K, ... martial), Greek/Hellenist (G, H, ... drama), Christian (N, ... sappy), Mohamadan (M, ... compromise), Japanese (J, ... refined). Hebrew/Buddhist suffers from pollination, currency, and over logic, lacking soul, so it metamorphs into Jewish (J-wish).

The vices of excellence. (Sadly understandable given unprovoked harlot usurper wife. The D-ivorce.)
Take best from everyone.

One world order is the Tanakh, divine moral authority, digital logic.
Yet diversity of governments and religions is good, respect culture.

Love and trust can become idols.

Enjoy CHRistMAS, made in CHINA with bubbly Koko Kola syrup.

The best revenge is success.

Freedom of speech vs threats?

Different forms of assault: verbal, physical, emotional, psychological.

Words can provoke physiological response, e.g. death threats.

A mob of people threatening to murder Jews can induce stress, terror, and relocation to safety.

An abrasive wife drips venom.

Gauge degree of aggressor responsibility vs target self control.

One parallel is Trump's liability over the Jan. 6 riots. Assembly is protected, riot is not, the distinction being physical violence.

Also intent versus attempt versus deed, were votes tampered?

Trump not morally pure but does some good. Should purify, mikvah.

Cultural references:

Disney's "The Sorcerer's Apprentice"

McDonald's "M" outposts

Time Flies (Father Time Flies)

Holy trinity as one family is an idol.

One of Jesus's jobs is to horrify. Opposites define each other. See the good in bad, e.g. Jezebel's raw sex appeal.

Submission versus obedience. Giving in versus willing choice. Best Servants think for themselves, who needs robots or drones?

Alexander relative King Richard II, wildly unpopular. Parallel of Richard Lord Rahl War Wizard in Sword of Truth books, also Confessor Kahlan. Credit N.

Alpha versus beta behavior. One child raised properly is worth 10,000 who are not. Pollination does not pay dividends.

Patriotism is a virtue, blind patriotism the vice of idolatry.

Scepticism and faith are both virtues.

Intelligent people evolve. Do not despise the LORD's reproof.

Democracy more robust against bad actors, yet any system is at best as good as its people. Vulnerability is mass brainwashing, where centralized power vulnerability is individual character.

Harder to change large group.

Council of vetted judges less vulnerable to populism or aristocracy, also not an individual.

LORD favored judges and prophets, yet promised to establish kingdom in perpetuity. What is kingdom?

Management amounts to babysitting and birdwatching.

Unearned authority corrupts, and mandatory succession is by definition unearned.

Titular kings can be vested with more authority as needed, and likewise stripped. Like dictators of old, of necessity and for a season, preferring gardening to war.

Closest modern analog is presidency where time is forcefully limited not voluntarily resigned.
Clinging to power beyond competence and need is evil.
No law not in the common interest ever lasts, force is futile.
Favor empowerment over control, education over war.
System structure necessary to prevent evil, then the structure becomes the evil.
Thought is the deepest motive, thus the most lasting achievements are religious and scientific not political.

Koshering (K) kills all filth

LORD: discharge euphoric.

Masturbation is lame but sometimes necessary, developing self control preferable. Anti-Talmud, anti-Monastic, humans are sexual beings.

Biblically, avoid foul images and do not covet your neighbor's wife.

Trinity site, Plutonium (Hades), "death I am become", death of God, Killer Einstein friends with Godel incompleteness logician... Alex born in El Paso near White Sands.

Sling an Einstein (one stone).

David liked men (Jonathan ... Nathan), hence Moses's blasphemy wrt the earth's biodiversity. Like Islam/X-tian universalisation folly.

Difference between virtue and vice often quantity and context.

E.g. Eros. Sex with wife is a virtue, vice is extramarital excess.

E.g. Hope without action is futile.

E.g. Love the wrong woman you die.

E.g. Faith in idols you burn.

E.g. Hate your weakness you excel.

Honor righteousness versus respecting competence.

Corollaries of Rights to Life and Liberty in a Secular State

Rationally humans have fundamental and inalienable rights to life and choice as far as these do not impinge on others' lives and choices. Corollaries include rights to privacy, one's body, LSD, suicide, and the prohibition of abortion and the death penalty.

In case of rape, life supercedes choice as children can be forsaken. In case of fatal delivery, prioritise higher probability of survival.

In case of dysfunctional disability e.g. Down's syndrome, can always choose suicide after birth.

Rationally and assuming right to kill, mother and father have equal claim to foetus thus both must agree.

The right to kill varies with religion. Circumstantial abortion, e.g. for rape and incest, is a religious right. Its implicit universalisation is directly contrary to a secular state. Many religions violate right to life and liberty. People have the right to their beliefs, yet practice must conform to secular morality.

Concluding, if you want an abortion you should travel one way to a country that either is non secular permitting circumstantial religious abortion or does not respect right to life.

Mosaic law is black and white, yet punishments immoderate, nonrelative, nongraded, mostly death. Question is to what degree did Moses supercede divine authority? He was banned from the promised land. Jesus was prophesied in minor capacity in Isaiah, perhaps king, yet teachings full of false prophesy: abolish the law, mercy for everything, worship serotonin. Digital morality gradated sentencing, punishments ought reflect crimes or be more merciful. Also death is a legitimate punishment, not to be celebrated except for the most vile.

COVENANT

The LORD does not belong to the Hebrews, nor does belief in the LORD, as light belongs to everyone. Conversion is not tribunal, but by circumcision and Biblical mandate. Jews cannot exclude honest individual believers they hate.

The Covenant is between man and God, not man and mob. Or woman.

LORD will perpetuate the covenant through chosen blood by oath, but covenant is not exclusive to blood, nor does blood assure it.

The Covenant is an agreement holding one to a bar. Actions elevate.

Blood purity worship is idolatry, with uniformly horrible results, yet it is often preferable to marry your own.

God created the world not man; woman attaches by nature, hence name.

Judgement: action, intent, and circumstance. Deliberate misalignment of action and intent with intent to cheat not humor is fraud.

Spirit vs letter of law. Distinction can be used as specious excuse to invalidate or bypass religious law. Humans are imperfect, spirit vs letter distinction has more significance for them than the LORD via prophesy. When letter is ambiguous, choose meaning over letter, i.e. how something is said and context.

K is HALO-genated. False X-tian saints.

PRIMALITY THEORY of permutations:

Garbage in, at best garbage out.

Start with primal patterns, also look for highly nonrandom results to identify phrase primality.

Human behavioral tendencies:

Blood is primary, ego is secondary.

EGO

Must you think as I think, do as I do?

Conquer by force, seduction, time.

Do not expect equanimity on top to be reciprocated when on bottom, expect reprisal and enslavement.

Fairness and debt are soon forgotten, as memory is insectlike and selective, man's span 100 years.

People remember grievances, and forget blessings that enable life.

The mob has no memory at all.

The righteous path is straight and narrow, thus it is far easier to destroy than to create. Higher glory belongs to women who nurture and men who heal, ie. to priests and scholars.

Women naturally turn men's necks and hoard all the glory, which is why men belong on top, so they can feel important in a world dominated by feminine virtue. The essence of masculinity is self control.

Christianity is cheaper. Of necessity some traditions are not as deep or old.

Everyone cannot be Abraham, it goes against Creation, the Gaussian curve.

Ego and idealism lead to jealousy and hatred, the dark side of the force, desiring the ruin of world diversity.

Psychologically, it is easier to worship an abstract than face an emanation.

If the LORD begat woman as the weaker but fairer gender it is upon men to help them. Georgia is the weakest link, thus the focus of enemies is to destroy her character, which they did quite successfully, "worst person in history".

Religious tribal behaviorist not racist.

LORD founded tribe, blood rightly important to every nation on earth.

Yet LORD above blood (Abraham), maintains tribe by covenant, can choose to fall out (Jesus), and also can petition to join (Ruth).

Blood rightly given primacy, especially royal blood chosen by LORD (David). Yet foreigners not treated unfairly.

Blood should be given every opportunity to rejoin tribe and not treated as equal to foreigner (Moses).

Bygone virtue of LOYALTY made into a perjorative in the name of universality.

Given equal choice, better to choose your own (Samson). Yet kin is not above the Law (Solomon, Jezebel).

"The devil is in the details":

Eveline shithead.

Biblical treatment of foreigners kind, (partaking of Passover seder).

Living amongst people one typically adopts their ways. Max tithe of foreigners makes sense, as longtime inhabitants can be given religious choice to assimilate and leave tithe.

Regal Vetting:

Bible requires kings to handwrite copy of Torah, ... obviously not followed.

LORD values tent of David in perpetuity, yet power not in perpetuity to preempt incompetence before it filters itself on peoples' heads (shit). Fear of permanent loss of power religiously groundless.

Make practically groundless by maintaining strong family position.

Vetting:

1. Religion

(min handwrite Torah),

2. Depth

(min Doctoral),

3. Breadth

(min rank Kernel),
4. Flexibility
(min Trilingual)
5. Maturity
(min Age salted 40).

Law of covenanted flesh or of land?

Are foreigners subject to Mosaic law while in Israel?

What should separate secular law enshrine?

Degree of tolerance of religions after revelation?

Degree of tolerance of observance of Judaism?

The LAW is black and white, right and wrong. Yet we consider action, intent, and circumstance in judgement, as Moses in considering manslaughter. Relativity in sentencing:

lenience for youth and ignorance and exactitude for deliberate evil.

Socioethics:

No best human system, diversity prevents easy control.

Individual rights more primal than collective.

Blood endures philosophies change, which is why Torah revealed to tribe.

(K)iller the real Marshal.

What other way to kill God than to destroy digital morality by making everything relative via Christianity?

The LORD'S commandments are absolute, that is why Orthodox Jews wear black and white, as a reminder.

And to kill all the diverse and beautiful races and religions by making everything the same? X

How seductive are the idols of moral relativism and universal equivalence?

And how reminiscent of Einstein?

"God does not play dice."

Alexander brainy relatives:

Banach, Schrodinger, Thomson

HOLY JUDGEMENT

"Donbass Russian":

abrasion sun

abandon sir

assassin bond

dinosaur ass

UNORDAIN ASS

"Donbass Ukrainian":

dinosaurian bank

abrasion unkind

abandon Russia

dinosaur Kain

UNORDAIN KAIN

[Correct]

"Donbass disputed":

UNBAPTISED

autopsied DDs

disabused Don/son

dissuades bond

eastbound Sid

astounds spied/Sid

Budapest Odin/sins/sons/Sid

disbands despot/ousted/dupes/Deus

subpoena Sid

UNBIASED STOPS

"Crimea Russian":

America ruins

Caesar ruins/minus/Muir/urns

MESSIANIC (8)

massacre ruin

musician errs

amnesia sir

airiness Ram

"Crimea Ukrainian":
America Kain/ruin
rainmaker uncia/Cain
Karen cranium/maniac/caiman
Marianna ickier/icier/Eric
nickname Auria
Riemann auric

[Correct]
"Crimea disputed":
misdirected
miseducated rip
DIADEM PRIEST/PUREST/CRIST/TRUCE

[Correct, Biblical]
"Gaza Israeli":
glaziers (window glass)
regalia Isa
grail Isa
Ariel Isa
LIAR Sega/Sage
girls AAA
LEIA Grazia(fashion UK)/arias/ragas(Indian classical)/sizar(undergrad at Cambridge or Trinity, also
honest, fair)/airs/Risa/rags/rigs/sari/gas/Isa/sir
sire AAA

"Gaza Palestinian":
ALIENATING/Leninist/slanting
penalising AAA
nasalizing pet/tea
PALATINE GAINS
Italians pagan
NATANIEL PIG
paganise Aztlan
pleasing (44) Nazi
stapling Nazi
stealing Nazi
ANGEL PINATA/TAIPAN/SAINT

[Koko puff]
"Gaza disputed":
ADIEUS/STUPID
upstaged aid
studied
ADIDAS GETUP/PUTZ
ESAU DITZ/PAID
AGUSTE DIAD/PAID/DAD
suited (22)
Adept Gaius/Saudi
duped Asia
Zetas paid/Aug
Deus Data
Ides Data
Zeta Gaius/Saudi

[Correct]
"Taiwan Chinese":
Athenians Wei
Einstein
Nathan ices

"Taiwan disputed":
inaptitude sad
DISUNITED

"ugliest country in history":
righteous instruction
unrighteous clitoris/silicon/trinity
honourless trinity
constitution hurley

scientology untruth
eroticising unholy
nicotinise yoghurt
siring honeylocust
Ginnie Christ Lotto

"Faisal Siddiqui" (222):
filius aids/Sid
Qaddafi Isis
liquid
squalid
Saudi Iliad/fails

"Jordan Nosanchuk":
Noah's Ark

"Marianna Lukovna Flis":
Aaron Kaufman/villain
Saul oilman Frank
Sulla Roman avian/Finn

"Alexander Oleg Daniv":
David regal annex
Nevadan regal/Godel/Oiler

"Alexander Luka Daniv Flis":
David Saul Aaren Felix

"semen content of Colgate toothpaste":
Phaeton testament footstool

"The Talmud": mutated

[WEED - proof in Bible]
"Why was Solomon corrupted":
Octahedron Olympus

[MICHAEL - atypical of the most accomplished general of antiquity.
Transylvanian "Flys-tran".
Vlad's tranny granny likes porking up the fanny.]
"Why was Vladimir the Impaler":
whitehall adversary/vampirism

"When did Jordan become Nathaniel's vassal":
dandelion blameworthiness/treasonableness/charlatanism
dandelion charlatanism jawbones

[Why such an incompetent successor of a virtuous man?]
"Marcus Aurelius and Commodus":
murder salammoniac/calumnious/scandalous/succussion/acidulous/audacious
Mordred Cassius communal
demon commissar
diadem classroom

"worst person in history":
serotonin sophistry/worships

"worst life in history":
Flis noteworthy/worthiest/tortoise

"Most Valuable Player":

"Angel of Death":
halogenated (K), God El hate

"moral relativism": varietal, Travis

"Luck is the LORD"

The LORD of Hosts

The LORD the King

"Coolest prophet":
preschool, choose Potter

"Why is Satan a troublemaker?":
(K)ay blameworthiness
"

Satan and Michael":
adamantine, Canaanites, Canadians
Nathaniel scam, Nathan mislead

"Why is Travis so pathetic?":
ASTROPHYSICIST hate (Cocoa puff K)
psychiatrist votes/waves

"Is Ginny K's wife":
sensing, YESSING, Winnie, wifing
King Nisei/wises/wins

"Who incited Israel to evil?":
Octagon evilest

"Grandmaster": Dr. Eastman

"Truelove conquers all":
levarterenol (l-norepinephrine)

"Diamond Grandmaster":
ARMAGEDDON DISARM (333)
adamantine dorms/dog/God/Rod
emanation Mars
mastermind grandad/dragon
ringmaster Adam
TARDIGRADE MONAD
ordainment Adam
tragedian ransom
AGAMEMNON TRIAD
anoointed Adam
GODDAMN gordian/dragon/Nimrod/monad/RODIN

"Alexander and Faizal": Nazarene, Ferdinand

"A half truth is a whole lie":
Flesh HIAWATHA outlier/liter
Flesh authorial wealth
Alleluia fortieths/frothiest/hesitator/softheart/worthiest/theorist/wartish/whoreish/wraithes/airshow/
ATHEIST?/fairest/faithes/fathers/foresaw/hastier/stewart/threats/thwarts/tither/torahes/twister/wariest/
whitest/wreaths
ARISTOTLE wailful/lawful/wilful/Alfie/Allah/Elihi/halal/Lilah/whale/fail/flea/hell/Leah/life/wail/wife

"change is a constant":
"hasten slowly":

"God does not play dice":
apologetic, scientology

[Ko to Flis]

Richard Marx -

"Right Here Waiting for You":
Arthur wife Georgie/gorgon/throne
Arthur Thorin foggy
Georgia unworthier/inheritor/unthrifty/fortieth/inferior/hornier/trinity
Georgia Trinity whore

"Richard Marx - Right Here Waiting for You"
Cantharidate forgery/forgoer/horrify/foxier/error [Erica]
exterminator fiduciary/highchair/acidify/Georgia/Richard
Arthur Georgia dominatrix
*Arthur Michigander airworthier [J]

Georgia aircraftmen/documentary/inferiority/retardation/criminated/Dutchwoman/defamatory/dominatrix/
mariticide/matriarchy/medication/mediocrity/unworthier
Georgia Richard marry fortieth (No!)

LORD:

"polygamy splinters families":
Sinless immortal Alfie
Sinless meatloaf pilgrim
magisterialness floppily
generalissimo misapply/pitfalls
pointless playgirls
profeminists impale
Gorilla impalement
ASYMMETRY flagellosis/flagpoles/lifespans/signalise/signifies
Sire immolating apples
illegalisation pyres

"A woman of great value" [J]

"The pain will be obviated":
elevation pitiable

"You will burn by flesh on pyre."

"Ashkenazim versus Sephardim":
Khazar underemphasises/persuasiveness
Messiah unimpressed
Ramakrishna despises
Dauphin Messiah maker sir

"Most powerful archangel":
Thermonuclear glows,
Challenger taprooms/Formosa/uproots/warmups (555)

"Smartest archangel":
Metatarsal Gen,
Caesarian

"Evilest Archangel":
Leviathan
Eighteen vasal (Newtonian model)
Heavenliest (23) Carl

"Samael the Venom of God":
Halogenated (K), homogenates (universalise), homologated (racing), megadeathes, Gethsemane, Magdalenes,
meatloaves
meatloaves goodmen/goofed/demon/Hodge
Magdalene homos

"Jordan and Nathaniel":
Alexandrina, dandelion, lionheart, Leonhard, Nintendo, ordained, rational

"Lebedovych and Marianna":
ARCHENEMY DAVID/Aladdin

"David and Jonathan":
joint Havana DNA

[Agamemnon dies in bathtub;
Queen of Sheba is Jay;
Baba childhood bath Alexander, wants him immolated]
"David and Bathsheba":
Baba shithead/advised/invaded

"Samson and Delilah": dandelion hassal

"Alexander Shapiro Grothendieck":
exoneration Hagar deciphers
Pericles axehead throning

"World War Three":
retard whore/hero
dorthea erl/err
Leah terror/error/retro/wrote
LORD weather/Arther/wrath/hate
WEED harlot/LOATH/TORAH/wrath
error whaled/death/Leah
reward throw/towel

"georgia travis demoted":
Agosto diadem giver
dreamer tatoos
tardigrade vise

"Marianna demoted":
diadem Reamonn

[Discovered at UNM ... Lobos]
"Alexander haldol lobotomy":
bandleader Loyola
maternal Loyola
Loyola bondholder/landholder/methadone/Albertan
mother landlady/blooded
dethrone lambda
demote Randall
Albert deadman/axeman/daemon/damned

"Alexander lobotomised":
DELIBERATE SOLOMON
META REBELLION/landlord
bloodstained Rome
disablement ordeal

"Alexander HIV infected":
needlecraft divine

"Alexander asked Jordan to prom": earned promote Jordan/Oakland

[totally wrong]
"Alexander asked Jinwen to prom":
earn womanliness pork
earn demote Okinawan/Parkinson/Nikolas

"Alexander skips prom":
earn diploma/soldier/armless

"Alexander cures HIV": underachiever

[underachievement]
"Alexander proves Riemann Hypothesis":
extraordinariness shovelman/Hasheem/nymphes/Penelope/Yasmeen
demineralises Pharaoh
Phaeton demineralises senhor

"Alexander scapegoat" (4442):
exonerates alpaca
earn palace god

"Alexander self sabotage" (4440):
exonerate glassed
Albert godless
earn bosselated

[Jordan>Ginny>Erica]
"Alexander self excision":
californian/RECONDENSES/RENAISSANCE/Floridian/financiers/fleeciness/friendless/LORDLINESS/narcissine
RECONDENSES FILIAL/ALFIE/FELIX/ALEX
renaissance foiled
LORDLINESS FIANCEE/cain

EARN DEIFIES CANE
LORD fleeciness/financial/licensee/faceless

...
FRIEDA (1007) LONELINESS
ANNEX socialiser/OILFIELDS
ANNEX FRIEDA ELOISE(asylum)/CELLS/LOSES/EXES
Cain federalises/friendless/felonries
Cinderella foxiness
EXCELSIOR DISANNEX/SEINFELD

...
LIFELINE cesarean/EARNED
EARN fleeciness/LIDOCAINE/oceanside/LIFELINE/cleanses/fiancee/FOXINESS/lionised/SILICONE/DEIFIES/aliened/
casino
earn Aeneid foils/loses

"Alexander buys lidocaine":
DISOBEDIENCE lauryn
DIABOLIC annulars/unearned
INEXCUSABLE ORDAINED/ALADDIN/LORDED
lorded cannibalise
annul disobeyer/excelsior/exorcised
excelsior undeniably/banana

[If J surgery, unanaesthetized]
"Jordan buys lidocaine":
cannabidiol/cannibalise
dandelion Icarus Job
unordained Jacob

"Jordan excises brand":
condenses Jarrid (Enoch ... Cohen)/bird/Rabi/raja
ordain earned/debera/Jared/Edens

"Marianna excises brand":
Messianic banned/Aaren/annex/Debra/earn

[last resort]
"Alexander self immolation":
LIFELINE (2022) salamander/monster/Salomon/tornado
MINERALISE Donatello/meatloaf
NATANIEL MISLEADER
OILMAN FELLATIO RENAMES
demote (2111) millenarian
demotion reinflames
elates iliofemoral/Maimonidean/manifolder
LORD emanation Alfie

"Save the soul not the life":
elevation lotus

(Genesis 3:6)
"the tree was desirable to make one wise, she took from its fruit and ate; and she gave also to her
husband with her, and he ate."
Apple ... iphone, Apple Records

(Genesis 21:32)
"Abimelech": Michael

(Psalms 110:4)
"Mechizedek": emceed, miked
[Eminem]

(Ezekiel 48:35)
"and the name of the city from that day shall be, 'The LORD is there.' "
"The LORD is there":
Shiloh retter (savior)
Detroit seer

(Genesis 49:10-11)
Until Shiloh comes,

And to him shall be the obedience of the peoples...
He washes his garments in wine,
And his robes in the blood of grapes.

K Relativist, (L absolute):

"he will intend to make alterations in times and in law ... his dominion will be taken away, annihilated and destroyed forever" (Daniel 7:25-26)

"But before faith came, we were kept in custody under the law, being shut up to the faith which was later to be revealed. Therefore the Law has become our tutor to lead us to Christ, that we may be justified by faith. But now that faith has come, we are no longer under a tutor." (Galatians 3:23-25)

"My covenant I will not violate,
Nor will I alter the utterance of My lips." (Psalm 89:34)

"If He would render Himself as a guilt offering": (Isaiah 53:10)

DEMINERALISATION FLEURDELIS

WRONGHEADEDNESS FIRELIGHTER/FORFEITURE/FLAMEOUT

reward demineralise lighthouse/ghoulish/foolish/elliott/eight

...

lifeline undergraduate foolisher/glorifies/wormholes/forgoes/moorish

lifeline airworthiness model Freda

lifeline femur airworthiness godhead

LIFELINE RETROGRESSION DIADEM

"He will see His offspring,

He will prolong His days": (Isaiah 53:10)

lifeline professorship wholesaling/godliness/yielding/Delilah/gasoline/goalless/highness/holiness/
lionised/odyssean

"the smith who BLOWS the fire of coals" (Isaiah 54:16):

Themistocles abolisher/Waterloos

"the destroyer to ruin" (Isaiah 54:16):

Tortures dethrone

Detroit honesty/thrones/unhorse

Yehudit rottener

" 'Behold the days are coming,' declares the LORD,
'When I shall raise up for David a righteous Branch;
And He will reign as king and act wisely
And do justice and righteousness in the land.
In His days Judah will be saved,
And Israel will dwell securely;
And this is His name by which He will be called,
The LORD our righteousness.' "
(Jeremiah 23:5-6)

"The LORD our righteousness":

ghoulishness tortured

eighteen holdout/horrors/lotus

godliest southerner

horseshoeing duteous

rigorousness turtle

houseguest dishonor

Esther shouldering/unrighteous/dishonours/honourless/horrendous/horridness/ungodliest/unholiest

restores neurologist/lighthouse (Belle Isle, Caltech?)/hungriest/doghouse/holdout/hideout/surgeon

XTIANITY ENTHRONES DEATH

"Because you have said, 'We have made a covenant with death,
And with Sheol we have made a pact.

The overwhelming scourge will not reach us when it passes by,

For we have made falsehood our refuge and we have concealed ourselves with deception.' " (Isaiah 28:15)

"And your covenant with death shall be canceled,

And your pact with Sheol shall not stand;

When the overwhelming scourge passes through,

Then you become its trampling place." (Isaiah 28:18)

"twenty-third for Delaiah"
(1 Chronicles 24:18)

"He makes the depths boil like a pot" (Job 41:31) [Leviathan ... Potholder ... Weed ... Dandelion]

"Indeed, the very hairs of your head are all numbered." (Luke 12:7) ... Algebraic Topological Weed counting holes.

"For what purpose does frankincense come to Me from Sheba, And the sweet cane from a distant land?" (Jeremiah 6:20)

"'the women knead dough to make cakes for the queen of heaven; and they pour out libations to other gods in order to spite Me.' 'Do they spite Me?' declares the LORD. 'Is it not themselves they spite, to their own shame?' "(Jeremiah 7:18-19)

"'For behold, I am sending serpents against you, Adders, for which there is no charm, And they will bite you,' declares the LORD." (Jeremiah 8:17)

"Rejoice in the wife of your youth." (Proverbs 5:18)

"There is a time for being ahead,
a time for being behind;
a time for being in motion,
a time for being at rest;
a time for being vigorous,
a time for being exhausted;
a time for being safe,
a time for being in danger."
(Tao 29:7-14, ... Solomon)

"And His name will be called Wonderful Counselor, Mighty God,
Eternal Father, PRINCE OF PEACE."
(Isaiah 9:6)
Peace Shalom Salaam Solomon

(Daniel 7:9)

"And the Ancient of Days took His seat":

shithead condensation

condensation hesitated/shithead/stateside/steadfast/steadiest/toastiest/sheathed

Cantonese antithesis/astonished/dishonesty/handshakes/Anastasia/dynasties/fantasies/fattiness/Shintoist/sainthood/satisfied/shiftest/snooziest/stinkiest/Tokyoites

"Haman, the son of Hammedatha" (Esther 3:1 ... Ham... Hamas): Mohammed Nathan

"Pur, that is the lot, was cast before Haman" (Esther 3:7)

"Then after sixty-two weeks the Messiah will be cut off and have nothing" (Daniel 9:26):

transcendentalist eighteen Elysium tattooist/textbooks/beehives/obviates

blameworthiness Washingtonians effectuality

interdenominational backlashes ghettoises/yeshivoth

interdenominational wastebaskets lighthouse theft

Almightiness Yahweh authoritativeness/heterosexualities/transcendentalist/denuclearisation/

conservationist/constitutional/decartelisation/defenestration/dictatorialness/noneffervescent/

educationalist/honourableness/international/incredibleness/indestructible/intercessional/recondensation/

revolutionises/unfriendliness/westernisation

Almightiness Yahweh recondensation levitates/absolute/beehives/elevates/faithful/obviates

(Genesis 2:24)

"For this cause a man shall leave his father and his mother":

schoolmistresses millenarian Theravada/featured

(Genesis 2:24)

"and shall cleave to his wife":

ELEVATION DELILAH/Sascha/whale/Alfie/FLESH

avianise death

Anastasia lovechild/Delhi/DEVIL/CHOW/vice

lovechild wealthiness/Anastasia/alienates/essential/leastwise/Taiwanese/wifeless

Lilith evanesced/enslaves/scandal

evanesce halfwit/shitload/idiot

...

Leviathan Achilles/Delilah/fiasco/asshole/lawless
Cleveland faithless/falsities/asshole
Achilles deflation
Shithead Evelina/fiancee
Casanova wifeliest/weediest/deifies/fleshed
Seinfeld vacillates/oscillate/volatile/WHITEHALL/ACHILLES/CALLISTO/violates

(Genesis 2:24)

"And shall cleave to his wife; and they shall become one flesh."
YAHWEH DELILAH SCHOOLMATE FASHIONABLENESS/clandestineness/nonethicalness
YAHWEH ADOLESCENT SCHOOLMATE DELILAH HEAVENLINESS/Vaselines
Yahweh adolescent schoolmate Lebanese devilish/villain
adolescent schoolmate Lebanese (lifeline halfway)/(avian hellish/Welles/deify)/(deifies Allah)
Yahweh Anastasie lovechild enfeeblement
Yahweh Lilith defenselessness detachable/heathendom/malevolent
Yahweh evanescence disestablishment/anathematise/loathsomeness/assimilates

...

YAHWEH THESSALONIAN DELILAH SCHOOLMATES BEETHOVEN/CLEVELAND
Yahweh Thessalonian Beethoven Delilah Damocles
Yahweh Thessalonian levelheadedness/methodicalness/affectionless/effectiveness/melancholical/achievements
Yahweh Thessalonian Beethoven
demoiselle/schlemiel/shamefaced/academics/acclaimed/accolades/classical/melodical/homeless
Yahweh cannabidiol loathsomeness/lovelessness/malevolence

(Genesis 3:14)

"On your belly shall you go,
And dust shall you eat
All the days of your life":
dishonourableness/distrustfulness/unrighteousness/rebelliousness/unfaithfulness/ungratefulness/
unsuitableness

...

[envenomed, belly ... belle]
"On your belly shall you go":
ANGEL Hurly/SOUL

(Genesis 3:15)

"And I will put enmity
Between you and the woman":
automanipulation intended
manipulation unintendedly

(Genesis 3:16)

"I will greatly multiply
your pain in childbirth":
METAPHORICALLY gullibility/unpityingly/unwittingly/unguiltily

(Genesis 3:17)

"Cursed is the ground because of you":
odouriferousness cheated/behead/BETCHA

(Genesis 3:19)

"For you are dust,
And to dust you shall return.":
TYRANNOSAURUSES deflator

[Eastern]

(Genesis 3:24)

"And at the east of the garden of Eden He stationed the cherubim";
"He stationed the cherubim":
archenemies/Mithridates/Archimedes/Christian/Romanistic

[Elon Musk loves thrusting rockets,
attempts to bribe Alexander into marrying a German]

(Genesis 3:24)

"and the flaming sword which turned every direction":
technologist inventor Archimedean/unremarried/chairmaned/daydreamer/hardhanded/hardheaded/archenemy/
archfiend/chinaware/deacidify/Friedrich/Manchuria/American
AMERICAN TECHNOLOGIST INVENTER (212) FUHRER/YEHUDI
ARCHENEMY DAVID TRINITROTOLUENE/interreligious/nonintercourse/reintroduction/liechtenstein/unenlightened/
unfriendliest/constitution/friderichsen

ARCHENEMY DAVID LICHTENSTEIN DETOURING

archenemy David constitution defender... /redefiner/weeding ?

archenemy David Fridericsen dethroning [N]

...

"Adolf Hitler":

fellatio/fellator/idolater

loath Fred

["Erica Standhart": cantharidate]

(Genesis 4:1)

"I have gotten a manchild with the help of the LORD.":

CANTHARIDATING homophile/potholed/wifehood/withheld/demote/vetoed

[Travis means "tiller of the soil"]

(Genesis 4:2)

"Cain was a tiller of the ground":

cantharidating foul [chicken]

congratulation (1002) heifer/herald

flesh eroticisation

"Cain brought an offering to the LORD of the fruit of the ground." (Genesis 4:3 ... fruitcake)

"Therefore whoever kills Cain, vengeance will be taken on him sevenfold" (Genesis 4:15 ... Seven of Nine, Catherine Janeway, Star Trek Voyager)

"And Kenan lived seventy years, and became the father of Mahalalel." (Genesis 5:12 ... Halal)

"Then Abram said to Lot, 'Please let there be no strife between you and me, nor between my herdsmen and your herdsmen, for we are brothers.' " (Genesis 13:8)

"Please let there be no strife between you and me" (Genesis 13:8):

blameworthiness Aberdeen Pluto

[Gravedigger Judah]

"Come and let us sell him to the Israelites and not lay our hands on him; for he is our brother, our own flesh." (Genesis 37:27)

"confinement" (Genesis 40:3) "budding" (Genesis 40:10)

Feynman, Yasodhara

"three" (Genesis 40: 10, 12, 13, 16, 18, 19, 20)

"on the vine were three branches ... grapes" (Genesis 40:10) [restored]

"three baskets of white bread" (Genesis 40:16) [executed]

"hang you on a tree; and the birds will eat your flesh off you" (Genesis 40:19)

"seven cows, sleek and fat; and they grazed in the marsh grass" (Genesis 41:2,3) [SEVEN COW, marshal]

"seven" (Genesis 41:2,3,4,5,6,7,18,19,22,23,24,26,27,29,30,34,36, in Pharaoh's dreams)

"Now it came about as they were emptying their SACKS, that behold, every man's BUNDLE OF MONEY was in his SACK; and when they and their father saw their bundles of money, they were dismayed."

(Genesis 42:35 ... Goldman Sachs)

"brother Benjamin, his mother's son": northeasterner Simmons

(Genesis 43:29 ... Simmons trader)

"for we cannot see the man's face" (Genesis 44:26 ... You shall not see My face ... faceless man)

"you shall eat the fat of the land" (Genesis 45:18 ... prodigy)

"Rachel died ... and I buried her there on the way to Ephrath (that is, Bethlehem)." (Genesis 48:7 ... G Rachel?)

[Marshal's wand]

(Genesis 49:10)

"Nor the ruler's staff from between his feet":

BLAMEWORTHINESS TORTURERS

reinstatement horseshoe/errorless

TRAITOROUSNESS BETHLEHEM

TRUSTWORTHIEST MENORAH

Albert erroneousness

...

"Until he comes to Shiloh":

Themistocles [N]

...

"Nor the ruler's staff from between his feet, Until Shiloh comes":

blameworthiness trinitrotoluene Hercules

Albert Einstein Themistocles unremorseful/honourless

"And as for you, you meant evil against me, but God meant it for good in order to bring about this present result to preserve many people alive." (Genesis 50:20 ... There is good in bad)

"And the sons of Uzziel: Mishael" [Uzziel son of Kohath] (Exodus 6:22)

[... Taste for power, just where did he get the idea?]

"Then then LORD said to Moses, "Say to Aaron, 'Take your staff and stretch out your hand over the waters of Egypt ... that they may become blood.' " (Exodus 7:19)

"And you shall keep it [lamb] until the fourteenth day of the same month, then the whole assembly of the congregation of Israel is to kill it at twilight." (Exodus 12:6)

"Then the LORD said to Moses, 'Behold, I will rain bread from heaven for you' " (Exodus 16:4)

"there was a fine flake-like thing, fine as the frost on the ground" (Exodus 16:14) [unleavened bread, unlike Oldsmobile in Nathan's Testament]

"And the house of Israel named it manna, and it was like coriander seed, white; and its taste was like wafers with honey." (Exodus 16:31)

"the LORD will have war against Amalek from generation to generation." (Exodus 17:16) [Amalekite: MIKAEL, Ismael, Islam, Tesla, Kali, Leia, Meta, Kai, MIT, Sam, set]

"And Moses chose able men out of all Israel, and made them heads over the people, leaders of thousands, of hundreds, of fifties, and of tens. And they judged the people at all times" (Exodus 18:25-26 ... NOT herd democracy)

"But if the slave plainly says, 'I love my master, my wife, and my children; I will not go out as a free man,' ... his master shall pierce his ear with an awl; and he shall serve him permanently." (Exodus 21:5-6)

[CONSORTS]

"If he takes to himself another woman, he may not reduce her food, her clothing, or her conjugal rights. And if he will not do these three things for her, then she shall go out for nothing, without payment of money." (Exodus 21:10-11)

[VIOLENCE]

"if he gets up and walks around outside on his staff, then he who struck him shall go unpunished; he shall only pay for his loss of time, and shall take care of him until he is completely healed." (Exodus 21:19)

"If a ransom is demanded of him, then he shall give for the redemption of his life whatever is demanded of him." (Exodus 21:30)

[VIRGINITY]

"And if a man seduces a virgin who is not engaged, and lies with her, he must pay a dowry for her to be his wife." (Exodus 22:16)

[STUDENT LOANS]

"If you lend money to My people, to the poor among you, you are not to act as a creditor to him; you shall not charge him interest." (Exodus 22:25)

[HORDES]

"You shall not follow a multitude in doing evil, nor shall you testify in a dispute so as to turn aside after a multitude in order to pervert justice; nor shall you be partial to a poor man in his dispute." (Exodus 23:2-3)

[PLANT RIGHTS]

"And you shall sow your land for six years and gather in its yield, but in the seventh year you shall let it rest and lie fallow" (Exodus 23:10-11)

"You are not to boil a kid in the milk of its mother" (Exodus 23:19) :
demineralisation butterfly
shithead Tinkerbell (887) immaturity/trinity
meatloaf bloodthirsty enthrone

["Palestinians"]

"You shall make no covenant with them or with their gods. They shall not live in your land, lest they make you sin against Me; for if you serve their gods, it will surely be a snare to you." (Exodus 23:32-33)

[IMITATION, X-tian not blood]

"Then he took the book of the covenant and read it ... So Moses took the blood and sprinkled it on the people, and said 'Behold the blood of the covenant, which the LORD has made with you in accordance with all these words.'" (Exodus 24:7-8)

"the cloud covered the mountain" (Exodus 24:15)

[IMITATION, Jesus]

"And Moses entered the midst of the cloud as he went up to the mountain; and Moses was on the mountain forty days and forty nights." (Exodus 24:18)

"he brought the ark into the tabernacle" (Exodus 40:21)

"Every grain offering of yours, moreover, you shall season with salt, so that the salt of the covenant of your God shall not be lacking from your grain offering; with all your offerings you shall offer salt." (Leviticus 2:13)

"all fat is the LORD'S" (Leviticus 3:16)

"It is a perpetual statute throughout your generations in all your dwellings: you shall not eat any fat or any blood." (Leviticus 3:17)

"Fire shall be kept burning continually on the altar; it is not to go out." (Leviticus 6:13) [Zoroastrian]

"He also took all the fat that was on the entrails and the lobe of the liver, and the two kidneys and their fat; and Moses offered it up in smoke on the altar." (Leviticus 8:16, filters)

"Whatever in the water does not have fins and scales is abhorrent to you. (Leviticus 11:12)

"For I am the LORD your God. Consecrate yourselves therefore, and be holy; for I am holy. And you shall not make yourselves unclean with any of the swarming things that swarm on the earth." (Leviticus 11:44)

"And Aaron shall hasten lots for the two goats, one lot for the LORD and the other lot for the scapegoat." (Leviticus 16:8, Lot is Aaron)

"Then Aaron shall lay both of his hands on the head of the live goat, and confess over it all the iniquities of the sons of Israel, and all their transgressions in regards to all their sins; and he shall lay them on the head of the goat and send it away into the wilderness by the hand of a man who stands in readiness." (Leviticus 16:21, James wrt Alexander)

[HYGIENE]

"You shall not lie with a male as one lies with a female; it is an abomination." (Leviticus 18:22)
: anathema housewifeliness

"You shall not lie with a male as one lies with a female":
unwholesomeness whitehall meatloaf Leia

"The priest shall also make atonement for him with the ram of the guilt offering before the LORD for his son which he has committed, and the sin which he has committed shall be forgiven him." (Leviticus 19:22 ... Ram of the guilt offering)

"And in the fifth year you are to eat of its fruit, that its yield may increase for you" (Leviticus 19:25)

[HYGIENE, not immorality.

Sodomy is mixing feces with blood, condoms mandatory. E.g.: HIV.]

"If there is a man who lies with a male as those who lie with a woman, both of them have committed a detestable act; they shall surely be put to death." (Leviticus 20:13)

[HYGIENE, E.g.: Ebola]

"If there is a woman who approaches any animal to mate with it, you shall kill the woman and the animal; they shall surely be put to death." (Leviticus 20:16)

"If there is a man who takes his brother's wife, it is abhorrent; he has uncovered his brother's nakedness. They shall be childless" (Leviticus 20:21)

"If there is a man who takes his brother's wife":
airworthiness sweetheart Bohemias

"They shall not take a woman who is profaned by harlotry, nor shall they take a woman divorced from her husband; for he is holy to his God." (Leviticus 21:7 ... divorcee consort rationale over abandonment)

"Then the LORD spoke to Moses, saying, 'Speak to Aaron ...'"
(Leviticus 22:17-18, persistent dynamic of speaking directly to Moses, secondhand to Aaron)

[emanation]

"I will make My dwelling among you, and My soul will not reject you. I will also walk among you and be your God, and you shall be My people. I am the LORD your God" (Leviticus 26:11-13)

[God Most High vs Almighty]

"I will take of the Spirit who is upon you, and will put Him upon them; and they shall bear the burden of the people with you, so that you shall not bear it all alone. (Numbers 11:17)

"Joshua the son of Nun" (Numbers 11:28)

[Good sentiment]

"But Moses said to him, 'Are you jealous for my sake? Would that all the LORD'S people were prophets, that the LORD would put His Spirit upon them!' " (Numbers 11:29)

[Dr. Brandon Quayle Reynolds]

"Now there went forth a wind from the LORD, and it brought forth quail from the sea" (Numbers 11:31)

[The M]

"But the LORD said to Moses, 'If her father had but spit in her face, would she not bear her shame for seven days? Let her be shut up for seven days outside the camp, and afterwards she may be received again.' " (Numbers 12:14)

[Equality ideal]

"Now Korah the son of Izhar, the son of Kohath ... rose up before Moses ... 'You have gone far enough, for all the congregation are holy, every one of them' " (Numbers 16:1-3)

"the rod of Aaron for the house of Levi had sprouted and put forth BUDS and produced blossoms, and it bore ripe almonds." (Numbers 17:8)

[Rock yielding]

"assemble the congregation and speak to the rock before their eyes, that it may yield its water." (Numbers 20:8)

"Aaron ... rebelled against My command at the waters of Meribah" (Numbers 20:24)

[LOTR Gandalf and Balrog,
Miriam dies at Kadesh]

"You shall not pass" (Numbers 20:18)

[Harry Potter

Hormah, Hor, horcrux, serpent, sir]

"the name of the place was called Hormah. Then they set out from Mount Hor ... And the LORD sent fiery serpents among the people and they bit the people, so that many people of Israel died."
(Numbers 21:3-6)

[WOT Dragon, basis of flags]

"And Moses made a bronze serpent and set it on the standard; and it came about, that if a serpent bit any man, when he looked to the bronze serpent, he lived." (Numbers 21:9)

[Wells, ... Wellesley]

"they continued to Beer, that is the well" (Numbers 21:16)

[Mattanah... Manhattan, semi-holy ground of Nahaliel ... Nathaniel, NY]

"And from the wilderness they continued to Mattanah, and from Mattanah to Nahaliel" (Numbers 21:18-19)

[Jaz, ... Yaz, Yasmine, Yah's mine]
"came to Jahaz" (Numbers 21:23)

[As Abraham Genesis 12:3]
"Balaam the son of Beor ... For I know that he whom you bless is blessed, and he whom you curse is cursed." (Numbers 22:5-6)

[Zechariah 9:9 'your king ... mounted on a donkey']
"But God was angry because he was going, and the angel of the LORD took his stand in the way as an adversary against him. Now he [Balaam] was riding on his donkey and his two servants were with him." (Numbers 22:22)

"he did not go as at other times to seek omens" (Numbers 24:1)

[Bourne Jason, Adam eye opener]
"The oracle of Balaam the son of Beor,
And the oracle of the man whose eye is opened" (Numbers 24:3)

"And the name of the Midianite woman who was slain was Cozbi the daughter of Zur, who was head of the people of a father's household in Midian." (Numbers 25:15)

Zur, Zurich

"Cozbi the daughter of Zur" (3343):
Dorothea butcher

"they [Israel] also killed Balaam the son of Beor with the sword" (Numbers 31:8)

[not kill]
"you shall drive out all the inhabitants of the land from before you" (Numbers 33:52)

"But if you do not drive out the inhabitants of the land from before you, then it shall come about that those whom you let remain of them will become as pricks in your eyes and as thorns in your sides" (Numbers 33:55)

"Let them [daughters] marry whom they wish" (Numbers 36:6)

"The LORD your God who goes before you will Himself fight on your behalf, just as He did for you in Egypt before your eyes, and in the wilderness where you was how the LORD your God carried you, just as a man carries his son" (Deuteronomy 1:30-31)

[Effective]
"We left no survivor." (Deuteronomy 2:34)

"For only Og king of Bashan was left of the remnant of the Rephaim ... [his bedstead] Its length was nine cubits" (Deuteronomy 3:11)

"And you shall love the LORD your God with all your heart and with all your soul and with all your might." (Deuteronomy 6:5)

"You shall fear only the LORD your God" (Deuteronomy 6:13)

"man does not live by bread alone, but man lives by everything that proceeds out of the mouth of the LORD" (Deuteronomy 8:3)

"the LORD your God was disciplining you just as a man disciplines his son" (Deuteronomy 8:5)

[Holy conquest]
"Do not say in your heart when the LORD your God has driven them out before you, 'Because of my righteousness the LORD has brought me in to possess this land,' but it is because of the wickedness of these nations that the LORD is dispossessing them before you."
(Deuteronomy 9:4)

"two tablets of stone written by the finger of God" (Deuteronomy 9:10)

"For the LORD your God is the God of God's and the Lord of lords" (Deuteronomy 10:17)

[Israel unobservant]
"For if you are careful to keep all this commandment ... your border shall be from the wilderness to Lebanon, and from the river, the river Euphrates, as far as the western sea." (Deuteronomy 11:22-24)

[FIN, ... Finnish]

"anything that has fins and scales you may eat" (Deuteronomy 14:9)

[No long term debt]

"At the end of every seven years you shall grant a remission of debts." (Deuteronomy 15:1)

[Welfare, medicaid]

"However, there shall be no poor among you ... you shall not harden your heart, nor close your hand from your poor brother, but you shall freely open your hand to him, and generously lend him sufficient for his need in whatever he lacks." (Deuteronomy 15:4-8)

"For the poor will never cease to be in the land" (Deuteronomy 15:11 Jesus)

[piercings signify slavery]

"then you shall take an awl and pierce it through his ear into the door, and he shall be your servant forever" (Deuteronomy 15:17)

"unleavened bread, the bread of affliction (for you came out of the land of Egypt in haste)" (Deuteronomy 16:3)

[Feast of Booths]

"Seven days you shall celebrate a feast to the LORD your God" (Deuteronomy 16:15)

"Three times in a year all your males shall appear before the LORD your God in the place which He chooses, a the Feast of Unleavened Bread and at the Feast of Weeks and and the Feast of Booths" (Deuteronomy 16:16)

[LORD favors governance of judges]

"You shall appoint for yourself judges and officers in all your towns which the LORD your God is giving you, according to your tribes, and they shall judge the people with righteous judgement." (Deuteronomy 16:18)

[KINGS - NO MULTIPLICATION]

"you shall surely set a king over you whom the LORD your God chooses... you may not put a foreigner over yourselves who is not your countryman. Moreover, he shall not multiply horses for himself ... Neither shall he multiply wives, lest his heart turn away; nor shall he greatly increase silver and gold for himself." (Deuteronomy 17:15-17)

"Thus you shall not show pity: life for life, eye for eye, tooth for tooth, hand for hand, foot for foot." (Deuteronomy 19:21)

[Honorable siege warfare]

"you shall strike all the men in it with the edge of the sword. Only the women and the children and the animals and all that is in the city, all its spoil, you shall take as booty for yourself" (Deuteronomy 20:13-14)

[Absalom, Jesus, Judas]

"he who is hanged is accursed of God" (Deuteronomy 21:23)

[No pollination]

"No one of illegitimate birth shall enter the assembly of the LORD: none of his descendants, even to the tenth generation, shall enter the assembly of the LORD." (Deuteronomy 23:2)

[No pornography]

"your camp must be holy; and He must not see anything indecent among you lest He turn away from you." (Deuteronomy 23:14)

[Anti-slavery]

"You shall not hand over to his master a slave who has escaped from his master to you." (Deuteronomy 23:15)

[Anti-prostitution]

"You shall not bring the hire of harlot or the wages of a dog into the house of the LORD your God" (Deuteronomy 23:18)

[INFLAMMATION: Natan]

"The LORD will smite you with consumption and with fever and with inflammation" (Deuteronomy 28:22)

[Seven of Nine]

"you shall flee seven ways before them, and you shall be an example of terror" (Deuteronomy 28:25)

"You shall betroth a wife, but another man shall violate her" (Deuteronomy 28:30)

[Modern USA]

"The alien who is among you shall rise above you higher and higher, but you shall go down lower and lower." (Deuteronomy 28:43)

"turn to the LORD your God with all your heart and soul" (Deuteronomy 30:10)

"He guarded him as the pupil of His eye." (Deuteronomy 32:10)

"Vengeance is Mine, and retribution" (Deuteronomy 32:35)

[NONPARTISAN]

"do not turn from it [law] to the right or to the left, so that you may have success wherever you go." (Joshua 1:7)

"a harlot whose name was Rahab" (Joshua 2:1)

[Scarlet in Gone with the Wind]

"tie this cord of scarlet thread in the window" (Joshua 2:18)

"And it shall be that the one who is taken with the things under the ban shall be burned with fire, he and all that belongs to him, because he has transgressed the covenant of the LORD" (Joshua 7:15)

"So the sun stood still, and the moon stopped" (Joshua 10:13)

"And the rest of the sons of Kohath received ten cities by lot" (Joshua 21:5)

"But Adonai-bezek fled; and they pursued him and caught him and cut off his thumbs and big toes" (Judges 1:6)

"Adonai-bezek": Aeneid Ko

[Lapp=Finnish]

"Now Deborah, a prophetess, the wife of Lappidoth, was judging Israel at that time. And she used to sit under the palm tree of Deborah" (Judges 4:4-5)

"for the LORD will sell Sisera into the hands of a woman." (Judges 4:9)

[Jael pacifying Sisera, analogous Job/J diarist dairy scheme.]

"So she opened a bottle of milk and gave him a drink" (Judges 4:19)

"But Jael, Heber's wife, took a tent peg and seized a hammer in her hand, and went secretly to him and drove the peg into his temple" (Judges 4:21)

"Until I, Deborah, arose,
Until I arose, a mother in Israel."
(Judges 5:7)

[Megara from Hercules,
copy Tanakh to expiate 18]

"At Taanach near the waters of Megiddo" (Judges 5:19)

[Fashionista]

"Her wise princesses would answer her, ...

A spoil of dyed work embroidered,

Dyed work of double embroidery on the neck of the spoiler?" (Judges 5:29-30)

[OAKLAND]

"the oak that was in Ophrah" (Judges 6:11)

[Leah]

"bring out my offering and lay it before Thee" (Judges 6:18)

[FLIS]

"fleece of wool" (Judges 6:37)

[Laplander ... Finnish]

"You shall separate everyone who laps" (Judges 7:5 ... 300 men)

[Abimelech: Michael, ... Amalekite, slaughters brothers like Cane or Kay, cause of Vlad's bloodthirst]
"Then he [Abimelech] went to his father's house at Ophrah, and killed his brothers the sons of Jerubbaal, seventy men, on one stone." (Judges 9:5)

[Bloodthirsty, pitiless]
"So Abimelech went up to Mount Zalmon, he and all the people who were with him; and Abimelech took an axe in his hand and cut down a branch from the trees ... and set the inner chamber on fire over those inside, so that all the men of the tower of Shechem also died, about a thousand men and women." (Judges 9:48-49)

[Jesus equivalents, nothing has changed. The LORD creates snares to test men.]
"Then the sons of Israel again did evil in the sight of the LORD, served the Baals and the Ashtaroth" (Judges 10:6)

"And there was a certain man of Zorah, of the family of the Danites, whose name was Manoah" (Judges 13:2)
["Son of Man", Anderson]

"a swarm of bees and honey were in the body of the lion" (Judges 14:8):
feeble-mindedness featherbrain
feeble-mindedness Robinette honor
blameworthiness Newtonian beheaded/defrayed
transformation dandelion/disobeyed/enfeebled/falsehood/headlined/beheaded
TRANSFORMATION YAHWEH HONEYBEE FELONIES
DANDELION NEWTON BETRAYER MESSIAH
NATHANIEL MORDRED NEWTON YAHWEH BOOBIES
foreordination Thessalonian weedy
foreordination Nathaniel Odyssey
FOREORDAINMENT BOSTONIAN FLESH YAHWEH
foreordination honeybee deathblow/fateleness
restorability honeybee madonna defense/offends
THESSALONIAN YAHWEH DEMOTION ROBBERY
SHITHEAD WORLDBEATER honeymoon/noninsane/womanise/awesome/FEYNMAN/Heisman/offense/showoff/YASMEEN
WORLDBEATER EMANATION ODYSSEY WIFE

"Then Samson said to them, 'Let me now propound a riddle to you' "
(Judges 14:12) [Tom RIDDLE / HARRY Potter ... Lesson: do not gamble, people will skew the odds.]

"three hundred foxes" (Judges 15:4) [Flis ... Лис "fox"]

[Spider ... Moghedien of WOT]
"Delilah took the seven locks of hair and wove them into the web" (Judges 16:14)

[annoy ... Anne Frank, nosy Job]
"And it came about when she [Delilah] pressed him daily with her words and urged him, that his soul was annoyed to death." (Judges 16:16)

"A razor has never been on my head, for I have been a Nazirite to God from my mother's womb." (Judges 16:17)

"Then the Philistines seized him and gouged out his eyes; and they brought him down to Gaza" (Judges 16:21) [broken glass ... Глаз "eye"]

"Dagon their god" (Judges 16:23) [Dragon]

" 'Call for Samson, that he may amuse us.' So they called for Samson from the prison, and he entertained them. And they made him stand between the pillars." (Judges 16:25) [jester, comedian, ... pillar of fire]

"the house fell on the lords and all the people who were in it" (Judges 16:30) ["Bringing Down the House", film about MIT students in Vegas]

"And the man Micah had a shrine and he made an ephod and household idols" (Judges 17:5)
[Shriners charity, Anne Frank, Jesus ben Joseph all sympathy milking.]

[Ruth's daughter-in-law Marianna]
"Do not call me Naomi; call me Mara, for the Almighty has dealt very bitterly with me." (Ruth 1:20)

"you are a woman of excellence" (Ruth 3:11)

[Non greedy polygamy is the foundation of the House of David]
"May the LORD make the woman who is coming into your home like Rachel and Leah, both of whom built the

house of Israel; ... may your house be like the house of Perez whom Tamar bore to Judah" (Ruth 4:11-12)

[No mistake; King David thrice descended of consorts]

" 'A son has been born to Naomi!' So they named him Obed. He is the father of Jesse, the father of David. Now these are the generations of Perez: to Perez ... Boaz" (Ruth 4:17-21)

"Hannah had no children ... Now this man would go up from his city yearly to worship and to sacrifice to the LORD of hosts in Shiloh" (1 Samuel 1:2-3)

[Samuel Nazarite]

"but wilt give Thy maidservant a son, then I will give him to the LORD all the days of his life, and a razor shall never come on his head." (1 Samuel 1:11)

[potholder ... weed]

"Then he would thrust it into the pan, or kettle, or caldron, or pot; all that the fork brought up the priest would take for himself." (1 Samuel 2:14)

[Really really bad]

"And therefore I have sworn to the house of Eli that the iniquity of Eli's house shall not be atoned for by sacrifice or offering forever." (1 Samuel 3:14)

"And the head of Dagon and both the palms of his hands were cut off" (1 Samuel 5:4)

[Georgia brain tumor, Alexander rat]

"five golden tumors and five golden mice" (1 Samuel 6:4)

[Cartman humbled]

" 'And watch, if it [ark of LORD] goes up by the way of its own territory to Beth-shemesh, then He has done us this great evil. But if not, then we shall know that it was not His hand that struck us; it happened to us by chance.' Then the men did so, and took two milch cows and hitched them to the cart" (1 Samuel 6: 9-10)

[20 years!]

"And it came about from the day that the ark remained at Kiriath-jearim that the time was long, for it was twenty years, and all the house of Israel lamented after the LORD." (1 Samuel 7:2)

[herd mentality]

"that we also may be like all the nations" (1 Samuel 8:20)

"a man from the land of Benjamin" (1 Samuel 9:16)

[Genesis 49:27 "ravenous wolf"]

"And as for your donkeys which were lost three days ago, do not set your mind on them, for they have been found." (1 Samuel 9:20)

[Shaul Exodus 6:15 next to Kohath, both later rebellious, donkeys fortell lesson of Saul - don't be an ass!

Flexible mind.]

"When the men of Israel saw that they were in a strait (for the people were hard-pressed), then the people hid themselves in caves, in thickets, in cliffs, in cellars, and in pits." (1 Samuel 13:6, strait is Detroit)

"Then Jonathan said, 'My father has troubled the land. See now, how my eyes have brightened because I tasted a little of this honey.' " (1 Samuel 14:29)

[Names associations: Saul, Jonathan, Amalchi, Mara, Michael]

"Now the sons of Saul were Jonathan and Ishvi and Malchi-shua; and the names of his two daughters were these: the name of the first-born Merab and the name of the younger Michal." (1 Kings 14:49)

"an evil spirit from the LORD terrorized him [Saul]" (1 Kings 16:14)

[David's blood is of Ephraim]

"Now David was the son of the Ephrathite of Bethlehem in Judah, whose name was Jesse" (1 Samuel 17:12)

"the soul of Jonathan was knit to the soul of David, and Jonathan loved him as himself." (1 Samuel 18:1)

[streaking]

"And he also stripped off his clothes, and he too prophesied before Samuel and lay down naked all that day and all that night." (1 Samuel 19:24)

[David and Jonathan]

"And they kissed each other and wept together, but David more." (1 Samuel 20:41)

[David Saul pact ... Alexander]

"The LORD will be between me and you, and between my descendants and your descendants forever." (1 Samuel 20:42)

"The sword of Goliath the Philistine" (1 Samuel 21:9)

[Faithful as a Dog]

"Doeg the Edomite, the chief of Saul's shepherds" (1 Samuel 21:7)

"Then the king said to Doeg, 'You turn around and attack the priests.' And Doeg the Edomite turned around and attacked the priests, and he killed that day eighty-five men who wore the linen ephod." (1 Samuel 22:18)

"I know that you [David] are pleasing in my sight, like an angel of God" (1 Samuel 29:9)

[David and Jonathan]

"Your love to me was more wonderful
Than the love of women. (2 Samuel 1:26)

"Shall the sword devour forever? Do you not know that it will be bitter in the end?" (2 Samuel 2:26)

"Now when Ish-bosheth, Saul's son, heard that Abner has died in Hebron, he lost courage" (2 Samuel 4:11)

[Peacetime assassination]

"How much more, when wicked men have killed a righteous man in his own house on his bed, shall I not now require his blood from your hand, and destroy you from the earth?" (2 Samuel 4:11)

"Nathan, Solomon" (2 Samuel 5:14)

[David wants to build LORD a house, so LORD builds David a house.]

"And your house and your kingdom shall endure before Me forever; your throne shall be established forever." (2 Samuel 7:16)

"revelation" (2 Samuel 7:27)

"Bethah and from Berothai" (2 Samuel 8:8)

"the sword shall never depart from your house" (2 Samuel 12:10)

[Jordan]

"I will even take your wives before your eyes, and give them to your companion, and he shall lie with your wives in broad daylight." (2 Samuel 12:11)

"she [Bathsheba] gave birth to a son, and he [David] named him Solomon. Now the LORD loved him and sent word through Nathan the prophet, and he named him Jedidiah [beloved of the LORD] for the LORD'S sake." (2 Samuel 12:24-25)

[Absalom hairy]

"he weighed the hair of his [Absalom's] head at 200 shekels by the king's weight" (2 Samuel 14:26)

["pitched a tent", erection]

"So they pitched a tent for Absalom on the roof, and Absalom went in to his father's concubines in the sight of all Israel." (2 Samuel 16:22)

"you [David] are worth then thousand of us" (2 Samuel 18:3)

"Behold, I saw Absalom hanging in an oak." (2 Samuel 18:10)

"So he [*Joab*] took three spears in his hand and thrust them through the heart of Absalom while he was yet alive in the midst of the oak." (2 Samuel 18:14)

[Asherah]

"Now Absalom in his lifetime has taken and set up for himself a pillar which is in the King's Valley" (2 Samuel 18:18)

[ANTITHESIS OF JESUS/ABSALOM]

"Today you have covered with shame the faces of all your servants ... by loving those who hate you, and by hating those who love you ... For I know this day that if Absalom were alive and all of us were dead today, then you would be pleased." (2 Samuel 19:5-6)

[Squalid ... Faiz]

"Then Mephibosheth the son of Saul came down to meet the king; and he had neither cared for his feet, nor trimmed his mustache, nor washed his clothes, from the day the king departed until the day he came home in peace." (2 Samuel 19:24)

[Integrity]

"And Mephibosheth said to the king, 'Let him even take it all, since my lord the king has come safely to his own house.' " (2 Samuel 19:30)

"When the angel stretched out his hand toward Jerusalem to destroy it, the LORD relented from the calamity, and said to the angel who destroyed the people, "It is enough! Now relax your hand!". And the angel of the LORD was by the threshing floor of Araunah the Jebusite." (2 Samuel 24:16)

(2 Samuel 24:18) [Angel of Death]

"threshing floor of Araunah the Jebusite": Albert Einstein Auguster

"And Adonijah [usurper] sacrificed sheep and oxen and fatlings by the stone of Zohemoth [Serpent Stone]" (1 Kings 1:9)

"Nathan spoke to Bathsheba ... 'please let me give you counsel and save your life and the life of your son Solomon.' " (1 Kings 1:11-12)

"had Solomon ride on King David's mule" (1 Kings 1:38)

[Joseph]

"In Gibeon the LORD appeared to Solomon in a dream at night" (1 Kings 3:5)

[Divide inverse of multiply]

"Divide the living child in two" (1 Kings 3:25)

[Abraham]

"Now God gave Solomon wisdom and very great discernment and breadth of mind, like the sand that is on the seashore." (1 Kings 4:29)

[John Lennon]

"his [Solomon's] songs were 1,005" (1 Kings 4:32)

"cut timber like the Sidonians" (1 Kings 5:6 ... logger ... logician)

[Monetary policy]

"And he overlaid the floor of the house with gold, inner and outer sanctuaries." (1 Kings 6:30)

"the city of David which is Zion" (1 Kings 8:1)

(1 Kings 9:11)

"Hiram king of Tyre": ferryman Ko,
Moriarty Nike

"great amount of spices" (1 Kings 10:10) [Spicer ... Spic ... Spy]

[Beast]

"666 talents of gold" (1 Kings 10:14)

"throne of ivory ... and arms on each side of the seat" (1 Kings 10:18-19)

[Love as a vise ... meatloaf]

"Solomon held fast to these [foreign women] in love." (1 Kings 11:2)

"And he had seven hundred wives" (1 Kings 11:3):
weediness underhanded [Nathan]

[Hera ... Asherah ... Ashtoreth,
Milcom ... milk ... breasted]

"For Solomon went after Ashtoreth the goddess of the Sidonians and after Milcom the detestable idol of the Ammonites" (1 Kings 11:5)

[Immolate]

"Then Solomon built a high place for Chemosh the detestable idol of Moab, on the mountain which is east of Jerusalem, and for Molech the detestable idol of the sons of Ammon." (1 Kings 11:7)

[Nathaniel]

"Ashtoreth Milcom Chemosh Molech": Themistocles coacher

[Dr. Luay Hadad A. lobotomy]

"Then the LORD raised up an adversary to Solomon, Hadad the Edomite" (1 Kings 11:14)

(1 Kings 11:26)

"Jeroboam the son of Nebat, an Ephraimite of Zeredah":

foreordainment patronizes behemoth/beta

foreordainment penetrates (222) Bohemia/Jae

foreordainment Jehoshaphat erotomania/rabbinate/atoner/Barbee/rename

foreordainment Barbee anathematise/Jehoshaphat/heathenism/Amenhotep/ensheathe/Josephine/pantheism/

anathema/apathies/Japanese/Jamesian/monetise/nepotism/PHAETHON/Thompson/Amazons/fashion/Jasmine/Jonahes/

Mathias/mafioso/meanest/opiates/amazes/ashame/poison/septets

foreordainment Jasmine barefoot/bathrobe/betroth/Pharaoh/bettor/father

"Jeroboam the son of Nebat":

Barbee footnote/Jonathon

[Mislead disobedience;

Compare with Jonah's clemency]

"a lion met him on the way and killed him" (1 Kings 13:24)

[Rabbis are teachers, certified not ordained, only Cohen are priests.

... High places, getting high, weed.]

"Jeroboam did not return from his evil way but again he made priests of the high places from among all the people; any who would, he ordained, to be priests of the high places." (1 Kings 13:33)

(1 Kings 16:31)

"Jezebel the daughter of Ethbaal":

godfather beatable/bathtub/beetle/Allah/Bella/Belle/bezel/beta/hate/hell/zeta

(1 Kings 16:31)

"Jezebel the daughter of Ethbaal king of the Sidonians":

transubstantiation globalized joke

(1 Kings 17:1)

"Elijah the Tishbite":

Isiahi/Isiah beetle

Bet atheist

"Prophet Elijah the Tishbite":

Isiah bettor/beetle/potter/leper

lotteries Pip

obliterates Pip

Albert Pip hottest/titties

(1 Kings 17:1)

"Elijah the Tishbite, who was of the settlers of Gilead":

bloodthirstiest whitehall ghettoises

reestablishes theologise wholewheat/loathed

sweetheart diabolist stealthiest/foolishest/shallowest/faithless/falsities

sweetheart ideologist belittles/faithless/falsities

[To marshal ... LOTR Rohirrim]

"muster" (1 Kings 20:15, 25, 26, 27)

"Then a spirit came forward and stood before the LORD and said, 'I will entice him.'" (1 Kings 22:21)

"I will entice him": Micheil went

[Parting waters]

"And Elijah took his mantle and folded it together and struck the waters, and they were divided here and there, so that the two of them crossed over on dry ground." (2 Kings 2:8)

[Whirlwind]

"there appeared a chariot of fire and horses of fire which separated the two of them. And Elijah went up

by a whirlwind to heaven." (2 Kings 2:11)

[Salt purifies]

"And he [Elisha] went out to the spring of water, and threw salt in it and said, 'Thus says the LORD, "I have purified these waters." ' " (2 Kings 2:21)

[oil multiplies]

"pour out into all these vessels; and you shall set aside what is full." (2 Kings 4:4)

[resurrection via Elisha]

"behold the lad was dead and laid on his bed ... and the lad sneezed seven times and the lad opened his eyes." (2 Kings 4:32-35)

[Steward Death]

"And it came about as they were eating of the stew, that they cried out and said, 'O man of God, there is death in the pot.' "(2 Kings 4:40)

[food multiplies, 444]

"So he set it before them, and they ate and had some left over, according to the word of the LORD."(2 Kings 4:44)

[heal leprosy]

"Go and wash in the Jordan seven times, and your flesh shall be restored to you and you shall be clean." (2 Kings 5:10)

[Riemann]

"when my master goes into the house of Rimmon to worship there" (2 Kings 5:18)

[Snow White]

"a leper as white as snow" (2 Kings 5:27)

[axehead cane]

"when they came to the Jordan, they cut down trees. But as one was felling a beam, the axe head fell into the water; ... he cut off a stick, and threw it in there, and made the iron float."

[Elijah's spirit upon Elisha; marshal]

"the mountain was full of horses and chariots of fire all around Elisha." (2 Kings 6:17)

[Elijah marshal]

"For the LORD had caused the army of the Arameans to hear a sound of chariots and a sound of horses even the sound of a great army" (2 Kings 7:6)

"This is Jezebel." (2 Kings 9:37, pg. 333 Trinity)

[Voodoo]

"So the man of God [Elisha] was angry with him and said, 'You should have struck five or six times, then you would have struck Aram until you would have destroyed it. But now you shall strike Aram only three times.' " (2 Kings 13:19)

[Resurrection]

"and they cast the man into the grave of Elisha. And when the man touched the bones of Elisha he revived and stood up on his feet." (2 Kings 13:21)

[serpent]

"cut down the Asherah. He also broke in pieces the bronze serpent ... Nehushtan." (2 Kings 18:4)

"He [Hezekiah] trusted in the LORD ... he clung to the LORD" (2 Kings 18:5-6)

"the sons of Eden who were in Telassar?" (2 Kings 19:12)

[reed pierces, Pharaoh]

"Now behold, you rely in the staff of this crushed reed, even in Egypt; in which if a man leans, it will go into his hand and pierce it. So is Pharaoh king of Egypt to all who rely on him." (2 Kings 18:21)

[Angel of Death]

"Then it happened that night the angel of the LORD went out, and struck 185,000 in the camp of the Assyrians; and when men rose early in the morning, behold, all of them were dead." (2 Kings 19:35)

"He brought the shadow on the stairway back ten steps" (2 Kings 20:11)

[Nathan ... Phaeton ... Icarus]

"by the chamber of Nathan-melech the official ... he burned the chariots of the sun with fire." (2 Kings 23:11)

"And they [Babylonians] took away the pots, the shovels ..." (2 Kings 25:14)

"Ishmael the son of Nethaniah, and Johanan the son of Kareah, and Seraiah the son of Tanhumeth the Netophathite, and Jaazaniah the son of the Maacathite" (2 Kings 25:23)

Hello Kittim in the Age of Biblical Japanese

"Noah ... Japheth ... Javan ... Kittim"
(1 Chronicles 1:4-7)

"And the sons of Zerubbabel were Meshullam and Hananiah" (1 Chronicles 3:19)

[Beer]

"Beerah his son, whom Tilgath-pilneser king of Assyria carried away into exile" (1 Chronicles 5:6)

"Kohath ... Korah ... Uriel ... Shaul"
(1 Chronicles 6:22-24)

[thrust, come ... Discharge]

"Then Saul said to his armor bearer, 'Draw your sword and thrust me through with it, lest these uncircumcised come and abuse me.' " (1 Chronicles 10:4)

[Dragon ... Leviathan tempts]

"fastened his [Saul] head in the house of Dagon." (1 Chronicles 10:10)

[Multi-tribal non-Hebraic support in R^4]

"Uriah the Hittite" (1 Chronicles 11:41)

"using both the right hand and the left to sling stones ... Saul's kinsmen" (1 Chronicles 12:2)

[Musk Ko's vassal]

"And David gathered together the sons of Aaron, and the Levites:
of the sons of Kohath, Uriel the chief, and 120 of his relatives" (1 Chronicles 15:4-5)

"Then David spoke to the chiefs of the Levites to appoint their relatives the singers, with instruments of music" (1 Chronicles 15:16)

[Allen Chen]

"Chenaniah, chief of the Levites, was in charge of the singing: he gave instruction in singing because he was skillful." (1 Chronicles 15:22)

(1 Chronicles 16:33)

"For He is coming to judge the earth.":
eighteen doctorate Fuji (apple)

[Reciprocal, fractions, division, David ... Ramanujan M]

(1 Chronicles 17:10)

"I tell you that the LORD will build a house for you.":
worldbeater Delilah filius/Shiloh
worldbeater footstool Delilah/Lilith

(1 Chronicles 17:12)

"I will establish his throne forever":

restorativeness hero

restoration believer/verifies

revelationist flesh Helios/oiler/owlish/Shiloh/wisher/loser/Sheol/sire

AIRWORTHINESS LEFTOVER HELL

airworthiness vetoer flesh

OBLITERATION FREEWILL

EVILEST BERLINER ISOLATORS/harlot/Ishtar

ISSIAH IRREVERSIBLE THEFT

VILLAINNESS ROTTWEILER/FERTILISER/foolisher/frostbite

relativeness followers/foolisher/horrible/horrifies

Overthrow (3343 ... Trinity)

Overthrow Albert fleshliness/lifeline/selfless

[Nathan heathen]

"According to all these words and according to all this vision, so Nathan spoke to David." (1 Chronicles 17:15)

(1 Chronicles 21:15)

"threshing floor of Orman the Jebusite":

Albert Einstein honourer/shogun

[Smith]

"He shall build a house for My name, and he shall be My son, and I will be his father; and I will establish the throne of his kingdom over Israel forever." (1 Chronicles 22:10)

"David divided them into divisions" (1 Chronicles 23:6)

"the eighteenth for Happizzez ... the twenty-third for Delaiah" (1 Chronicles 24:15,18)

[Nontrivial 12 month calendar]

"The twelfth for the twelfth month" (1 Chronicles 27:15)

[built on the threshing floor]

(2 Chronicles 3:1)

"the house of the LORD in Jerusalem on Mount Moriah":

foreordainment horseshoe Immanuel/Juliette/Matthieu/immolate/Jemimah (Job's daughter)/Mahomet/tollman/
Elohim/lethal/oilman

FOREORDAINMENT SOLOMON ARISTOTLE/AURELIUS

trinitrotoluene Mohammedans/falsehood/horseshoe/majordomo/Alessandro/Alejandro/Esmeralda/marshaled

trinitrotoluene falsehood menorahes

trinitrotoluene horseshoe Mohammedan

DETHRONEMENT ILIOFEMORAL

TREASONOUS/monstrous/atones/Samson

dethronement immolation horseshoe/fearless/refusal/releasor/assurer/flesh

dethronement immolation flesh hero

Dethronement James formulation/humiliation/millionaire/mournfullest/reformation

DETHRONEMENT FORMULATION JEALOUSIES/aerosolise/jailhouses/horseshoe/humorless

[Echoes Agamemnon and Helen]

"its brim was made like the brim of a cup, like a lily blossom; it could hold 3,000 baths." (2 Chronicles 4:5)

[Spice, spic ... stake, pole, polygamy destroying Israel, courtesy of J ...

Sheba means bitch in Korean]

"there had never been spice like that which the queen of Sheba gave to King Solomon" (2 Chronicles 9:9)

"there had never been spice like that":

representative deathlike/beelike/heathen/Aeneid/betcha/deceit/bitch

"Now the weight of gold which came to Solomon in one year was 666 talents of gold" (2 Chronicles 9:13)

[ivory, footstool, armchair]

"the king made a great throne of ivory and overlaid it with pure gold. And there were six steps to the throne and a footstool in gold attached to the throne, and arms on each side of the seat, and two lions standing beside the arms." (2 Chronicles 9:17-18)

"And he said, 'I will go and be a deceiving spirit in the mouth of all his prophets.' " (2 Chronicles 18:21)

"Zebadiah the son of Ishmael, the ruler of the house of Judah" (2 Chronicles 19:11)

[22]

"Ahaziah was twenty-two years old when he became king"

(2 Chronicles 22:2)

"yield to the LORD and enter His sanctuary" (2 Chronicles 30:8)

[Pardon good intent, spirit]

"For Hezekiah prayed for them, saying, 'May the good LORD pardon everyone who prepares his heart to seek God, the LORD God of his fathers, though not according to the purification rules of the sanctuary.' So the LORD heard Hezekiah and healed the people." (2 Chronicles 30:18-20)

[J metaphor]

"they captured Manasseh with hooks" {thong put through the nose}(2 Chronicles 33:11)
: Shakespearean Cosimo [N]

[Same as Solomon]

"Thus says Cyrus king of Persia, 'The LORD, the God of heaven, has given me all the kingdoms of the earth, and He has appointed me to build Him a house in Jerusalem, which is in Judah.' " (Ezra 1:2)

[Post-Breaking]

"The whole assembly numbered 42,360." (Ezra 2:64)

[Impalement]

"And I [Darius] issued a decree that any man who violates this edict [of Cyrus], a timber shall be drawn from his house and he shall be impaled on it and his house shall be made a refuse heap on account of this." (Ezra 6:11)

[god ElNathan racist]

"So I sent for Eliezer, Ariel, Shemaiah, Elnathan, Jarib, Elnathan, Nathan, Zechariah, and Meshullam, leading men, and for Joiarib and Elnathan, teachers."
(Ezra 8:16)

[Hebrews renamed Jews in Ezra.

Religious intermarriage ideal becomes flesh idolatry Tay Sachs. What of Joseph and Ruth, whose blood sired David? Moses and Zipporah? Etc. ... Sex offenders?]

"the holy race has intermingled with the peoples of the lands; indeed, the hands of the princes and the rulers have been foremost in this unfaithfulness." (Ezra 9:2)

"the holy race has intermingled with the peoples":
interrelationships gametocytes weed
interrelationship sleepyhead welcome

"Maaseiah, Elijah, ... Maaseiah, Ishmael, Nethanel" (Ezra 10:21-22)

"in the direction of the Dragon's Well, and on to the Refuse Gate" (Nehemiah 2:13)

[Focus, God's help]

"So the wall was completed on the twenty-fifth of the month Elul, in fifty-two days." (Nehemiah 6:15)

[Birth of Rabbinic Judaism great,

opposite of cleric Latin Bible, which hoards knowledge concealing deceit.]

"And they read from the book, from the law of God, translating to give the sense so that they understood the reading." (Nehemiah 8:8)

[Good effort but subtle errors,

All fat is the LORD'S.]

"Then he [Ezra] said to them, 'Go eat of the fat,' " (Nehemiah 8:10)

[Division negates multiplication]

"as prescribed by David the man of God, division corresponding to division." (Nehemiah 12:24)

[Contrary to Torah, grain offerings from sincere foreigners welcome.

Also Nehemiah knows that Israel was scattered.]

"they excluded all foreigners from Israel" (Nehemiah 13:3)

[Why not politely return goods?]

"I threw all of Tobiah's household goods out of the room. Then I have an order and they cleansed the rooms; and I returned there the ... frankincense." (Nehemiah 13:8-9)

[Religion transcends language, and blood supercedes language, yet cohesion is admirable.]

"none of them was able to speak the language of Judah" (Nehemiah 13:24)

[Judaism still patriarchal, later converts to rigorous matriarchy.]

"Even one of the sons of Joiada, the son of Eliashib the high priest, was a son-in-law of Sanballat the Horonite, so I drove him away from me." (Nehemiah 13:28)

[Rabbis egalitarian, preservationist]

"Remember me, O my God, for good." (Nehemiah 13:31)

[Esther is intermarriage, book is right after Nehemiah.]

"let the king give her royal position to another who is more worthy than she" (Esther 1:19)

"Hadassah, that is Esther" (Esther 2:7)

[Ham pork sodomy, Haman, Hammedatha, ... Hamas]
(Esther 3:1)

"Haman the son of Hammedatha":

MOHAMMED NATHAN

MOHAMED MANHATTAN

Nathan ashamed/deathes/defames/defeats/demotes/hothead/shammed

[LOT]

(Esther 3:7)

"Pur, that is the lot, was cast before Haman":

blameworthiness catastrophe

"And many among the peoples of the land became Jews, for the dread of the Jews had fallen on them." (Esther 8:17)

[Contrast Nehemiah]

"on the day when the enemies of the Jews hoped to gain the mastery over them, it was turned to the contrary" (Esther 9:1)

[As the potter turns the wheel, whirlwind]

"it was a month which was turned for them from sorrow into gladness" (Esther 9:22)

[Satan the Adversary,
schemes a la Grothendieck,
Pur or Lot, cats purr.]

"For Haman the son of Hammedatha, the Agagite, the adversary of all the Jews, had schemed against the Jews to destroy them, and had cast Pur, that is the lot, to disturb them and destroy them." (Esther 9:24)

[Only the wicked die on a tree]

"he and his sons should be hanged on the gallows" (Esther 9:25)

[memorialise defeat of lot]

"Therefore they called these days Purim after the name of Pur." (Esther 9:26)

[Uz ... Oz. Job ... work ... force (N)]

(Job 1:1)

"There was a man in the land of Uz, whose name was Job":

dishonourableness Johnathan/Mahometan/Manhattan/heathen/Amazon/Newton

amazement heathenishness

[Job responsible for invoking N]

"But put forth Thy hand now and touch all that he has; he will surely curse Thee to Thy face." (Job 1:11)

...

"he will surely curse Thee to Thy face": recrystallise fleece/theft

[Repeated thrice]

(Job 1:16)

"While he was still speaking":

Pilate hellishness/highnesses

eighteen alpha/Hawaii/Issiah

whitehall gipsies

[Job not covenanted, from Uz]

(Job 2:3)

"although you incited Me against him, to ruin him without cause":

congratulation Mohammed Augustine wittiest/outwits

(Job 2:11)

"Eliphaz the Temanite, Bildad the Shuhite, and Zophar the Naamathite":

sentimentalization rehabilitate/redemptible/traumatized/brutalized/dramatized/embittered/humiliated/
maltreated/pauperized/redeemable/repudiated

(Job 3:1)

"And the night which said, 'A boy is conceived.' ":

denicotinised thighbones/advocates/avianised/*Hawaiians*/obviating/Occidents/*vacation*

Washingtonian acidities/shithead

shithead denicotinising/condensation
EIGHTEEN cocainisation [K]/VINDICATION/Bostonian/Chinatowns/Dionysian/Hawaiians/addiction/asininity/
antiacid

(Job 3:5)
"Let a cloud settle on it":
unselect tattooed
deselect tattoo

(Job 3:8)
"Who are prepared to rouse Leviathan":
overthrower Persephone/Alisander
apple overthrower denatures/dethrones
Persephone overthrower/retaliator/evildoer
Persephone evildoer thwart
Alisander perpetrator
Alisander Pharaoh potter

[Nathan's scheme]
(Job 3:12)
"And why the breasts, that I should suck?":
Cantharidate Odysseus/lotuses/Ulysses
acidulousness bathwater

[Queen of Sheba]
(Job 6:19)
"The travelers of Sheba hoped for them.":
elevate stormtroopers/horseshoed/staterooms/theftproof

[Godless CIA]
(Job 8:14)
"Whose confidence is fragile,
And whose trust a spider's web.":
counterespionagers falsifications/federalisation/hardheadedness/Christianised/faithlessness/fatheadedness/
heartlessness/idealisation/worthlessness

(Job 9:9)
"Who makes the Bear, Orion, and the Pleiades":
blameworthiness Aphrodite/dethroned/harpooned/Katherine/Dorothee/Phaethon/pharaoh/Aeneid
misalphabetise dethroned

"Didst Thou not pour me out like milk,
And curdle me like cheese"
(Job 10:10)

...
"Didst Thou not pour me out like milk":
Lordship demotion/Klement
"and curdle me like cheese":
CINDERELLA SCHEME/seducee/emceed/musked/dukes

[palate, Pilate, ... pilates, pirates (Oakland, Las Vegas), Palace Station Hotel and Casino]
"Does not the ear test words,
As the palate tastes its food?"
(Job 12:11)

[313]
(Job 13:3)
"And I desire to argue with God" (8808):
Agosto Aeneid righted/regret
wrongdoer rightsided/Aguste/death
traitorous Aeneid/weeded
EIGHTEEN DIARIST ODOUR
sweetheart gorgonia
ISAAH DETROIT UNDERDOG
Isaiah rounder doggie
guarantee digitised Odo
seigniorage Detroit

(Job 13:15)
"Nevertheless I will argue my ways before Him.":

blameworthiness lifesaver/verifies

[Jeremoth?]

(Job 13:28)

"Like a garment that is moth-eaten.":

EIGHTEEN attestation/MATERNALISM/antimatter/metatarsal/metatron/NATATORIAL/aristotle/lionheart/sanatoria/senhorita

(Job 14:13)

"That Thou wouldst set a limit for me and remember me!":

wholeheartedness (2223) tuttifrutti

blameworthiness retaliator demote

blameworthiness Mohammed flameout

[N on Alexander]

(Job 14:19)

"Water wears away stones":

eastern awarest

[Youth is folly]

(Job 15:10)

"Both the gray-haired and the aged are among us,

Older than your father":

...
GUARANTEE EIGHTEEN UNFORGETTABLE DOORMAT
eighteen dethronement HOTBLOODED/outrageous/betrayal/FOOLHARDY
eighteen dethronement betrayal YOUTH
eighteen unforgettable retrograde *HONOURARY*/MANDATORY

...
FOREORDAINMENT UNDERGRADUATE REGRETTABLE/shareholder

...
foreordainment battleground goddaughter/retrograde
foreordainment retrograde dragon detestable
foreordainment retrograde goddaughter unhealthy/unstable
foreordainment guarantee retrograde bathhouse/Buddha/ghosted/godhead

(Job 17:12)

"They make night into day":

damnation eight/kitti/thigh

(Job 18:7)

"And his own scheme brings him down":

commissar weeding

misdiagnosis condemner/renowned/crowned/homered/Hebrew

(Job 19:6)

"Know then that God has wronged me":

wrongheaded Newton

(Job 19:11)

"And considered me as His enemy.":

ARCHENEMY MESSIAE NOSED

Archimedes Yasmeen/Aeneid

recondense maidenhead/Messiah/diadem/Yasmeen

indochinese Yasmeen/snares

Renaissance demonised/denied

(Job 19:18)

"Even young children despise me;

I rise up and they speak against me."

...
[M, McDonalds ... Ruth, Ruthenian]
"I rise up and they speak against me.": Metastasis Ukrainian

(Job 20:10)

"His sons favor the poor,

And his hands give back his wealth.":

Christianisation Shakespearean/godforsaken/godlessness/wrongheaded

(Job 20:14)

"To the venom of cobras within him": esterification/confirmation

(Job 21:19)

"Let God repay him so that he may know it.": ophthalmodiastimeter

(Job 22:4)

"Is it because of your reverence that He reproves you":
restorativeness corroborative/recipricatory

(Job 22:23)

"If you return to the Almighty, you will be restored":
unforgettable Demetrius oilier
worldbeater eighteen fruit

(Job 23:20)

"The worm feeds sweetly till he is remembered no more.":
motherless bloodthirstier

(Job 27:2)

"And the Almighty, who has embittered my soul":
blameworthiness Mohamed/death/eight

[Custom reversal: applause, apple.

LORD prime mover from Genesis.

Likewise beards, hats.]

"Men will clap their hands at him,
And will hiss him from his place."

(Job 27:23)

(Job 29:16)

"And I investigated the case which I did not know":
denicotinise denicotinise
eighteen denicotinisation David
eighteen cocainisation/condensation/chaoticness/chickenshit

(Job 29:17)

"And I broke the jaws of the wicked":
SWEETHEART HOODWINKED/JEDIDIAH/WIFEHOOD
WICKEDEST JORDAN KITEE
wickedest Ekaterina/Katherina/Katharine/Katherine/Dorothea/Dorothee/(Deborah Hanoi/joint/Jonah/Kain)/
(Frank weed)/Jordan/Aeneid/Frieda
cantharidise kowtow
death octahedron/archfiend/Christian/wardencies/Aberdeen
antichrist beheaded/weed
ANTIHERO JEDEDIAH

...

Jordan whitewashed/atheistic/beseached/bewitched/bitchiest/cheekiest/shitfaced/wickedest/Bethesda/cheetah/
SHITHEAD/sidekick/weediest/catfish/cheated/deceits/deifies/faithes/hothead/kitties/witches

[Queen of Sheba, responsible for Beta Israel]

(Job 30:30)

"My skin turns black on me,
And my bones burn with fever.":
dimethyltubocurarine [nicotinic receptor]

[333 Trinity, Diary ... dairy]

(Job 31:33)

"Have I covered my transgressions like Adam":
Alessandro Mackintoshes [apple]/Michigander
Alessandro Michigander emissary/mistake/messier/meteor/motive/Savior/Travis/krist
Alessandro mistake overachieving/rediscovering/overreaching
ALESSANDRO MICHIGANDER MOTIVE ASKER
ALESSANDRO ARCHENEMY TRAVIS DEVISE/EVOKED
ALESSANDRO ARCHENEMY MISTAKE DIVISOR/DRIVES
Alessandro Mackintosh redeemer/married/midyears/diaries
Mackintosh nasal diary oversevere
Mackintosh nasal degrader/dismissory
Alessandro Travis Michiganders/archenemies/Archimedes/Maimonides
archenemy Travis demineralises/generalissimo/ARMAGEDDON/Alessandro

...

Archimedes grandmaternal/skeleton/Transylvania
Archimedes grandmaternal vises
Archimedes skeleton avianise
Archimedes Transylvania deviser/misdoer/overdoes/oversees

...
Alessandro Schrodinger Miami
[I am that I am]
Alessandro Savior Christ avenged/endgame
ALESSANDRO AMERICAN SOVIET diverge/EMIGRES/grieves/HEDGER
ALESSANDRO DEMETRE KAY MESSIANIC
Maimonides retrogressive/charlataneries

(Job 31:33)
"By hiding my iniquity in my bosom":
Boston dumbing/numbing/Ginny/Hindu
uniting Bond Mommy
HinTing dominus/odious

(Job 31:35)
"Behold, here is my signature;
Let the Almighty answer me!":
blameworthiness Mithridates elementary/regalement/agreement/Emanuel/German
[elementary metaphor ... Alexander abused at IC grade school]
blameworthiness trinity daughter/ethereally/marshalled
blameworthiness eighteen sledgehammer [rouse Leviathan N]
sledgehammer instrument algebraist [Communism]

...
"Let the Almighty answer me!": EIGHTEEN

(Job 33:12)
"Behold, let me tell you, you are not right in this,
for God is greater than man.":
[rotting sushi]
TETRAMETHYLENEDIAMINE TRINITROTOLUENE
tetramethylenediamine odoriferous (breathalysing Golgotha)/(algebraist gorgon)

(Job 33:14)
"Indeed God speaks once
Or twice, yet no one notices it." :
denicotinising Renascences/recondenses/transcended

...
(Job 33:18)
"He keeps back his soul from the pit,
And his life from passing over into Sheol."

(Job 34:3)
"For the ear tests words,
As the palate tastes food.":
sweetheart toothpaste seafood

[X, applause crosses hands,
Lots of American locales herein]

(Job 34:37)
"For he adds rebellion to his sin;
He claps his hands among us,
And multiplies his words against God."

...
"He claps his hands among us,
And multiplies his words against God.":
Christianisation highhandedness/lopsidedness/mindlessness/soullessness/dehumanises/godlessness/
heinousness/hellishness/hideousness/lawlessness/unappealing/ungodliness/unwholesome/womanliness
CHRISTIANISATION GODLESSNESS APPLAUDING/APPALLING
Christianisation DANDELION (2232) shadowless/applauded

...
America Washington Philadelphia gaslights
WASHINGTON UNRIGHTEOUSNESS HALOPHILIC
AMERICANISATION POMPOUSNESS DISGUSTING

...
unrighteousness disassimilation/disassociation
Messiah ghoul congregationalist

congratulation ghoulishness Messiah Hawaiian

[Moishe, Faiz]

"Behold now, Behemoth, which I made as well as you"
(Job 40:15)

[Air Jordan #23]

"He is confident, though the Jordan rushes to his mouth."
(Job 40:23)

(Job 40:24) [J hook]

"With barbs can anyone pierce his nose?":
Renaissance Christ neophobia/Pennie/Penny

[Nathaniel]

"Can you draw out Leviathan with a fishhook?" (Job 41:1)

(Job 41:20)

"Out of his nostrils smoke goes forth":
Footstool meritoriousness/righteousness/homogeniser[N]/horseshoeing/rigorousness/thoroughness
Solomon surgeries fishhook

...

"As from a boiling pot and burning rushes":
misalphabetise dragon/unbrand

[Detroit 'the D' weeded]

(Job 40:31)

"He makes the depths boil like a pot": misalphabetise potholed

[Fumigator, gator, crocodile (drug),
Florida gators, Florida gun Jordan]

(Job 41:33)

"Nothing on earth is like him,
One made without fear.":

Nathaniel foreordainment/underestimation/disinformation/homogenisation/integrationist/misinformation/
understatement/dethronement/masterminding

Nathaniel disinformation outgrowth/throwout/whiteout

NATHANIEL DETHRONEMENT FUMIGATOR/authorise/Hiroshima/righteous [scapegoat]

NATHANIEL MASTERMIND NEFERTITI/EIGHTEEN

NATHANIEL UNDERESTIMATION HOMEWORK

FOREORDAINMENT NATHANIEL MUGSHOT/THIGHES

foreordainment inhomogeneities

foreordainment eighteen humiliations/Oklahoman/mouthwash/walkouts/womanish/Salomon/Hawaii/Isaiah

foreordainment Einstein kilowattage/humiliate/megawatt/Tokugawa/ultimate/Kittie/Mikael

foreordainment Tokugawa enlistment/Einstein/enmities/insolent/LENINISM/nihilism/menthols/element/elitist/
eminent

foreordainment emanation LIGHTHOUSE/ghoulish/ugliest/(THIGH SHILOH)

TRINITROTOLUENE FEMINISATION/HOMOGENISED/HOODWINKING/Maimonidean/Gethsemane/Washington

(Job 42:6)

"Therefore I retract,

And I repent in dust and ashes.":

tenderheartedness authenticator Frieda

tenderheartedness counterfeit diarist ?

"And each one gave him one piece of money and each a ring of gold." (Job 42:11)

[Yoko Ono]

"1000 yoke of oxen" (Job 42:12)

(Job 42:14)

"Jemimah, ... Keziah, ... Keren-happuch":

marihuana/marijuana kimchee [weed spicy]

[Job fair ... get a job,

Jordan of Jemimah]

(Job 42:15)

"And in all the land no women were found so fair as Job's daughters"

...

"fair as Job's daughters": birdhouse

(Psalms 2:2)
"Against the LORD and against His Anointed [Messiah]":
international antagonists

[Travis Black widow web]
(Psalm 2:3)
"Let us tear their fetters apart," (3833):
traitress stepfather
"And cast away their cords from us!":
traitorous Cassandre

(Psalm 2:7)
"He said to Me, 'Thou art My Son, Today I have begotten Thee.' "
...
'Thou art My Son,
Today I have begotten Thee':
dethronement attestative/haughtiest/bathhouse/tattooist/obviates/Agosto/Aguste/eight
Agosto (5551) dethronement
...
'Today I have begotten Thee':
Beethoven agitated/hogtied/death

[Not Jesus]
"Do homage to the Son, lest He become angry, and you perish in the way,
For his wrath may soon be kindled."
(Psalms 2:12)

[LOGICIAN]
(Psalms 29:5)
"The voice of the LORD breaks the cedars;":
characterise beetroot
"Yes, the LORD breaks in pieces the cedars of Lebanon.":
characterisation beekeeper

(Psalms 29:10)
"Yes, the LORD sits as King forever.":
restorativeness gloried/godlike/soldier/Feliks/yields/deify/flesh/Godel/oiler/Sheol/lord/sire

[David and Absalom (G)]
(Psalm 38:7)
"For my loins are filled with burning":
insubordinate gillyflower
foreordainment bullying

[David Eminem rapper]
(Psalm 38:12)
"Those who seek my life lay snares for me":
EMINEM HAYLEY STEELWORKER/fatherless

"LORD, make me to know my end,
And what is the extent of my days,
Let me know how transient I am."
(Psalm 39:4)

(Psalm 46:10)
[A Psalm of the sons of Korah.]
"Cease striving and know that I am God": recondensation Ashikaga/Isaiah

(Psalms 60:7)
"Ephraim also is the helmet of My head;":
Pharaoh flesh deity Elohim meta
SHITHEAD metamorphism/polymerism/immolator
iliofemoral death Sammy tepes
haloperidol Messiah Meta
haloperidol Smith Hasheem
SLEEPYHEAD ISAIAH THEOREM
SLEEPYHEAD ALASTEIR THIEF
sleepyhead immolator atheism
ALASTEIR (3222) mesothelioma/MISEMLOYED/POLYMATHES/shoplifted/sleepyhead

ALASTAIR FLESH MOHAMMED
Alastair Ismael demotes
Alastair Pilate mommy
Mithridates employees Omaha ?

...
"Judah is My scepter [lawgiver]":

ARCHIMEDES JUST
Christmas dupe
Physics majeure
SERAPHIM
JAMES SUPERCITY
Christ Judas/Maude

(Psalm 74:14)
"Thou didst crush the heads of Leviathan":
acidulousness Detroit hatted

(Psalm 77:10)
"It is my grief, That the right hand of the Most High has changed."
dethronement shithead satisfactory/castigatory/Christmas
dethronement Mithridates (667) tightfist/Asiatic/Cathay/fiasco/Isaiah/Sascha/thighs

[Division metaphor for selection]
"He divided the sea, and caused them to pass through" (Psalms 78:13)

(Psalms 86:2)
"Do preserve my soul, for I am a godly man":
lifesaver monogamously/Alamogordo/Armageddon/polygamous/grandma/napalmed/Reynolds/rounder/superman/
supermom/Amadeus/dragon

(Psalms 96:13)
"Before the LORD, for He is coming":
LOBOTOMISED FOREIGNER
homeschooling debtor
SCHRODINGER HILBERT/THEOREM
Friedrich geometer/theorems
Chesterfield foregone
biotechnologies reformed/freedom/homered

(Psalms 96:13)
"For He is coming to judge the earth."
fornicator hogtied/thighes
eighteen haircutter/motherhood/traitorous
HARCOURT (1666) eighteenthes/demotions
MICHIGANDER THOROUGHTEST
Friedrich Thomson
Schrodinger Matthieu
...
octahedron featheriest
Mithridates henceforth/foregone/honouree/hunter/regent/throne

(Psalm 104:14)
"He causes the grass to grow for the cattle":
hourglass sweetheart softheart/greatest/torahes/torches

(Psalm 104:18)
"The high mountains are for the wild goats":
demineralisation tattooer
trinitrotoluene shithead
foreordainment lighthouses/thoughtless
underestimating aristotle
fundamentalist airworthiest/whitehorse
reinstatement gladiator/ghoulish

(Psalms 104:26)
"And Leviathan, which Thou has formed to sport in it."
CHRISTIANISATION FORMULATED PHAETHON

[Flint lead water crisis]
"The flint into a fountain of water."

(Psalms 114:8)

"Let your fountain be blessed,
And rejoice in the wife of your youth.
As a loving hind and a graceful doe, Let her breasts satisfy you at all times;
Be exhilarated always with her love." (Proverbs 5:18-19)

"And rejoice in the wife of your youth":

Friederic fountain/Newton
Friederic Yahweh unjoint
FRIEDERIC JOHNATHON
foreordination thief
counterfeit honeydew/Aeneid
denunciatory heifer/fruit
INTERFERENCE JUDAH
COORDINATION (420) HEIFER [K0]
NEWTON (2323) RECERTIFIED
octahedron juniority/unworthy
fornication weedier/Yehudit
fornicator definite/enjoyed/feinted/honeyed/jointed/hunted
feinted fornicatory/antiheroic/Catherine
enthroned judicatory/acidifier
HARCOURT INFINITE ODEY [ODYSSEUS]

(Proverbs 8:22)

"The LORD possessed me at the beginning of His way":
emanation eighteen lordship (555) hostesses/bestowed
emanation flesh eighteen goddess
worship
emanation lordship highness
emanation lordship honeybee detests
emanation whitehorse longsighted/fleshiness/holiness

(Proverbs 8:30)

"Then I was beside Him, as a master workman":
Messiah Smith emanation (456) reward
Messiah Smith midwesterner Kaaba

(Proverbs 16:25)

"There is a way which seems right to a man,":
Christmastimes throwaway/negatory

...

"But its end is the way of death.":

BUDDHA ANTITHESIS/honestest
weediness audit/dotty

(Proverbs 17:3)

"But the LORD tests hearts":
Beta truthless

(Isaiah 28:18)

"And your covenant with death shall be canceled":
elevate recondensation Buddha
elevate transcendental Aladdin/obadiah/Buddha
Cleveland electrocution/unconscionable/understandable/dishonourable

[LORD GOD Most High created L, K]

"Behold, I Myself have created the smith who blows the fire of coals,
And brings out a weapon for its work;
And I have created the destroyer to ruin." (Isaiah 54:16)

[LORD to Zerubbabel: Barbee]

(Haggai 2:23)

"I will make you like a signet ring, for pI have chosen you":
recrystallising eigenvalue (lambda)/lovemaking/meaningful/honeymoon/inflaming/lawmaking/Oklahoman/
Hawaiian/Okinawan/unifying
recrystallising lovemaking Yahweh
recrystallising honeymoon Kilauea/Hawaii
recrystallising Feynman ghoul ?

[Q]

"And if your eye causes you to stumble, pluck it out, and throw it from you. It is better for you two enter life with one eye, than having two eyes, to be cast into the fiery hell." (Matthew 18:9 ... Matte)

Potter, pot (weeded, poker)
Potassium (K)
Soda, sod, Sodom
Lot, lottery, zealot
Con, econ
Bran, Brandon Stark, brand, remembrance
Kenneth (South Park hoodie), Kendall Square (MIT)
Cranbrook Kingswood rainbow, Lake Jonah, Buddha riding whale
Nazirite, Nazi, Nazareth
Gay, geisha
Galilee (Lilith ... hence Delilah)
Palatine Hill (Augustus), Emperor Palpatine (demote Vader .. Father)
Solomon Jedidiah (Red vs Blue)
nigro ("black" Latin, behavioral vs complexion), Nigeria; denigrate, niggardly, Schwarzenegger [German "schwartz" black]
Pharisee, Parsee (Zoroastrian)
Cane, hurricane
Tor, tornado, Torah
Hanukkah ... Hakka (ferryman), Xmas
Purim (Esther), Easter
Pluto (Hades), Plutarch
Roman Cats ... martial women
Lateran, latrean, latrine (sod, sodomy)
Hammas (red triangle, Hong Kong Triad, Palestinian Flag, Trinity), ham (pork, swine)
Epistle, pistle (vs stamen), pistol (gun, Guan Yin, Confucius, Kali)
Scarlet (Gone with the Wind, Communist) vs Iscariot
Palestinian, Philistine
Chinese, machine (Shen Yun), machination
Prom, promise (Zerubbabel in Haggai 2:23)
Joseph, Josephine (Napoleon at MIT foreordained)
Cat, Katana, Miss Kitty
Donkey (Balaam), Don Quixote
transgression, transsexual
Pet, petty, petulance ("get a dog"), pity
Sardis (NYC W44th), sardines, Sardinian
Antony, Antoninus, Antoinette
craven, crave (submit to emotion)
Hexahedral, Hex (curse of David)
Aladdin, Saladin, salad (green)
Hodor "Hold the Door", Odor, Odo
Abel, Abelian
Apple (smartphone)
Octavio, octopus (... Muay Thai), octave (music), Oct (8)
August, Augur
brown (Gita), Brownian (chaotic, "death I am become"), brownstones (Boston), Bronze Age (copper, MIT Coop)
God, Godzilla (tyrannosaurus, vs Kong w. axe)
Fornicator, ... nico, cato
Paul (N), pole, poli, police, cop, Ko
hormones, whore, hordes
Gaza (Samson and Delilah), Gas-A (immolate)
Palestine, Philistine
Doge (Renaissance elected head of state)
Putin (пусть, path) Raphael
Brent crude oil, sat next to Euler
Oy, oysters (ruin of Israel)
Marianna, marihuana
poach, pooch (dog)
Queen of Shiba, Toshiba

CONFLUENCE:

1. Daniel 9:26 (Messiah cut off),
2. Isaiah 53:10 (Intercessor);
demineralisation fleurdelis,
3. "You will burn My flesh on a pyre. I am the LORD.":

foreordainment hyperbola

Mortal Kombat Finishers:

Fatality
Animality
Babality ... Baba, Catholicism
Brutality
Friendship

Fragrant Urine in Chinese.

香尿
Xiāng niào

LANDMARKS

Spirit of Detroit.

"And interceded for the transgressors." (Isaiah 53:12)

Joe Louis "The Fist"

[Joseph dreamer, King Louis]

...

"The LORD has bared His holy arm" (Isaiah 52:10)

"And to whom has the arm of the LORD been revealed?" (Isaiah 53:1)

Renaissance Center

Hodor uses time wisely

Injury heals faster than insult.

No enemies unless self created.

Fear is the worst enemy the most powerful.

WEALTH

True wealth is the LORD's esteem, reflected in high honor, good family, and meaningful work.

Material wealth is having what others desire but have not, resources or skills.

"Ukrainian Neo Nazis":

aniseikonia UNA [double vision]

...

Psychology involved nuanced:

1. deny Russian, Hebrew ethnicity
2. forced Ukrainian assimilation
3. questioning implies insanity
4. intellectual belittlement
5. jealous schadenfreude
6. Munchausen's syndrome
7. silent antisemitism

"Alexander raised to believe he is stupid":

deliberateness evildoer apathies/death

[Ukrainian Catholics]

"Alexander grade school immaculate conception":

immuno-electrophoretic decagonal [AVERAGING]/nonlegal/conceal/scandal

guarantee omnipotence calamari/Hamilcar/marshal/Mordecai/radical

guarantee alpha reconsolidation/commercialised/decolonisation/macroeconomics/microeconomics/demineralised/occidentalised/socioeconomic/coincidences/econometrics/reminiscence/deselection/omniscience

guarantee nicotine axehead Corolla/Apollo

congratulation preadolescence CHAMomile/Michael/Mohamed/Malachi/melodic

Archimedes executioner octagonal

Archimedes electrocution decagonal [Star Wars' Emperor]

Archimedes unapologetical concealment

["Zenon Kopacz second grade":

Koco escaped androgen

(His father is a pharmacist.)]

...

"Alexander public grade school":

Lord Lord Alpha science/genius

Lili'uokalani Papahanaumokuakea?

...

"Destroyed Atlantis":

Alessandro deity

Aristotle (222) sadden

Detroit analyst

"John Fitzgerald Kennedy":

LYNDON ANTIFREEZE/defeating/angered/enraged

DEATH NONFREEZING [LIQUID \$]

Lennon tragedy

"Lyndon Baines Johnson":

BLOODINESS JOHNNY

{prob=(3/1958)(5/61)=.000126}

blood noninsane/ninja

ninja blondness/boldness/boyhood/Lennon

Lennon noonday/banjo

"Lee Harvey Oswald":

slaveholder

warheads lovely

war ladylove [Russian]

"Jacob Leon Rubenstein":

ninja consalter/counselor/bouncer/clobbers

bouncer nonstable

reelection banjo

Lennon saboteur/bribees/justice/obscure

Jonson uncelebrate/Albertine

Baines encounter/Corleone/objector/renounce

Corleone Austin

...

saboteur Joceline

bribes nonnucleate

justice Boolean

TREASON JOCELINE ?!

[Only name containing LIQUID.

Childbirth speaks.

Penalty for adultery is death.]

...

"Jacqueline Lee Kennedy Onassis Bouvier":

inconsiderableness queenlike

noninjuriousness deceivable/cevadilla [poisonous plant]/believed/ladylike/likeable

injudiciousness venereal

avariciousness (887) unkenneled/queenlike

incredibleness nonaqueous

incredibleness jealousy(222) Queen

indiscoverable (1420) queenliness/jealousies

rebelliousness indocyanine [spy agent green medical dye]

villainousness (2292) Jordan Queen

...

LIQUID unreasonableness/insecureness/lovesickness/subservience/vocabularies

"Romulus and Aeneas"(2252):

Alessandro Name

"Romulus and Remus":

MURDER SAMSON

rounder alums

surname Romulus/Lord

assure Lord

Samson murder/ruler

Russ earldom [grandfather]

summoned Ursula ?

[Rome ... Romanov]

"Romulus Palatine Hill":

alleluia triumphs

EMULATION PILLAR
LIONHEART pallium
imperial shallot/autos/lotus
Alpha lumisterol [Vit D precursor]/illumines/minstrel/lintels/monster
mineral hilltops/patulous [branch]/pilulous [3D-elliptic]
null multiplier/pluralities
Israel pullulation [breed, swarm]/plutonium/ululation [wail]/platinum
SHAPIRO ALUMNI

[Riemann]
"Remus Aventine Hill":
relativism, Hellenism, Helvetian, universal, Einstein, Emanuel, Leninism, Riemann

...
relativism Helen
EMULATES LENIN
smith unleaven/envier/urinal
RIEMANN Helvetius/elusive/evillest/thieves/Levite
helmet universal/annuler/Israeli
annul thieveries/Hitlerism

"string theory is true":
theorist unites
rigor trustiest

"string theory is false":
theorist essaying
rigor essential

...
Torah esterifying

"String Theory":
rigor tenth/test
...
restoring Thy
oyster hint/Ting
sorry eight/hint/Ting
throne grit/sir
roi strength
Tyre shorting/signor

"String Theory of Everything":
theorist enthrone
rigor sovereign/eighteen/Stonehenge/Firestone

...
throne overnights/sovereign/fighter
footrest interreign
oystering foreigner
Hin Ting regretter/overseer
Trinity (1115) estrogen/foregone

...
VERIFYING ERYTHROGONE [red blood cell precursor]
theorist Green frothing

"Theory of Everything":
throne thievery/fighter/frothy/verity
verify heterogony/energy

String TOE ... shoelaces; foundations of physics.

...
Judges 7:1; Adoni-bezek [K] severing thumbs and toes of kings.

...
A word is a string of letters.
Aristotle [linguistics] vs Democritus [atomic].

[3/16/25]
"String Theory of Everything is true":
interuniversity gogetters/hotshot
erythrogenesis verifying
intuitiveness gogetter
thoroughness reverifying

...
verifying erythrogenesis/erotogenesis/heterogenous/heterogonies/orthogenesis/outrightness/TESTOSTERONE/
thoroughness
erroneous esterifying/etherifying
ESTROGEN esterifying/etherifying
...
VERIFYING OUTRIGHT (666) RESTORES
theorist Greene horrifying/virtuosity/frothing

[3/25/25]
"String Theory of Everything is false":
OVERGENERALISING horseshit/forfeits/sheriff/THEORIST
integrationist Geoffrey
restorativeness forfeiting/firelight
...
Torah heterogeneity/offensiveness
Torah Sovereign esterifying/etherifying
...
VERIFYING FLIS ERATOSTHENES [Hermes, pole; FALSE]
ERROR FLIS (2522) ANGIOGENESIS [BRANCH]/INVESTIGATES/NEGATIVENESS
negativeness forthrightly/rightest
theorist Greene falsifying/satisfying/gravitons/loathing/visionary

"flisunit at Gmail dot com":
stultification God
God stultification/multinomials
Gaius dictation [anthropologic]
stolid (1211) logician
ANTI * SODOMITICAL

"worst decision in my life":
denicotinise worm

[Aaron, Leviticus 16:8]
"Caesar's great nephew Octavio":
Servant scapegoater

"Abraham's nephew Lot":
alpha menorah

"Alexander's brother James":
marathoner debases [WEED]
embolden harasser/Jaxartes/Earhart/Esther/haters

[False]
"Alexander's younger brother James":
grandmaster erroneous/honourable/honouree
unregenerate ambassador
grandmother reanalyses

"Alexander's nephew James":
repeal axehead
alpha ensnared
weed mannerless
earn Japanese

[No henhouse]
"HaShem El demoted Uncle Sam" (4441):
codename Methuselah
Methuselah McDonald
McDonald Samuel
henhouse deselect

Purim "lot" celebrates Esther
Haman, Hammedatha, ... Hamas
...
"Haman the son of Hammedatha, the Agagite, the adversary of all the Jews, had schemed against the Jews to
destroy them, and had cast Pur, that is the lot, to disturb them and destroy them." (Esther 9:24)
...

"Haman the son of Hammedatha":
Nathan Mohammed feast/hates/oaths

...
[Like Arthurian legend,
Morgause and Mordred]
"Haman the son": Nathan

...
[Mohammed ... Hammed]
"Hammedatha the Agagite":
Meta Meta Haggai

...
[Mord ... death Cai K, Esther Easter]
"Mordecai and Esther":
echinodermata [starfish]
costarred Aeneid
Archimedes Aron
Aaron threesided

...
"King Ahasuerus":
Eurasian, Gaussian, Ganesha, Guineas, Krishna, Ukraine, genius, kaiser, Russia, Garik, Gaius, Hagar,
Sarah, Sasha, Khan
Gauss Ukraine
Guinea shark

...
Haman is N
Hammedatha is M
Esther is G
Mordecai is K
Ahasuerus is L

Brutalist Architecture
1. Renaissance Center Detroit
2. Metro Detroit Synagogues
3. Northwestern University Library
4. MIT Student Center
5. Boston City Hall
6. Beckman Mall Caltech

VALUES: VIRTUE VS VICE

Assume the attitude of taking responsibility for understanding how everything works.

Cultivate a lifelong love of learning and achievement.

Scholarship essential not optional.

What you do not know will destroy you. Ignorance is intolerable, accuracy is attractive.

...
Fighting, fornicating, gambling are vices. They exhibit skill, not virtue, yet understanding them is virtuous.

...
"sex drugs and rock and roll":
ungod Aleksandr
Oakland scoundrel/rounder

Michael Moore "the awful Truth"
Americans are sadly OBTUSE.

The Dictator (2012)
Sacha Baron Cohen
DD boob plot ... tits, tithe
priests of Aaron ... Cohen

Rounders (September 11, 1998)
Worm Lester.
Leviticus 19:27, no rounding.

Women suffer when men are emasculated.

Try over regret.

Pit trading is harsh. Manners get better prices.

Acid melts the flesh.

Cows ruminare.

Ideals kill.

Polygamy splinters families.
Consorts burden.

Blame yourself over others.

Honest disagreement is helpful, being mean is not.

Once begun is half done.
Well done over poorly begun.

Speak silently.

Imitation is forceless.

Honor from the dishonored is worthless.

"male": el
"female": feel

[Michelangelo wrong]
"The Man Without a Belly Button":
unemotional Yahweh

[NONMELODIC]
"The Beatles Revolution Nine":
elevate buttonholes/beetroots/Listerine
elevation Hilbert ?
truelove Elisabeth [SHEBA]

John Lennon's No. 9 Coincidences
Born Oct. 9 Liverpool,
Cavern Club on Feb. 9, 1961,
met Brian Epstein Nov. 9, 1961,
The Ed Sullivan Show Feb. 9, 1964,
Etc...;
The Beatles - "Revolution Nine";
John Lennon - "#9 Dream",
4:44 Apple Records,
peaked at #9 Billboard 100,
#23 British singles

"Jordan Georgia Virginia":
vinordinaire roi [alphabetical]
AVERAGING ORDINARII
dragon erring
divine Aaron

[N and G]
"Spyro the dragon and Sparx the dragonfly":
Nathanael pornographers/harpooner
hydrosphere fantasy tornado
Alexander anthropography
Alexander godhood fantasy
Alexander Throop Stanford

[1998 PS1; SHAPIRO]
"Spyro the Dragon":
Shapyro rodent/God
harpooner Syd
Phaeton sorry

"Sparx the dragonfly":
hydroplane/Alexandros/godfather

(Tao 1.1 trans. Legge)

"The name that can be named is not the enduring and unchanging name.":
EMANATE EMANATE EMANATE COUNTERSIGNING BUDDHA
math math math annunciation transcending
authenticate author (emanating mashgiach)/(emanates Michigan)
authenticate author emanating HaShem diadem
GUARANTEE AUTHENTICATE COMMANDMENTS
Ten ten ten ten ten decahedron mashgiach Gandhian
Chan Ho Nam authenticate guarantee/hummingbird
TERENCE TAO MATHEMATICIAN AUGUSTINE
management instruction educate highhanded

(Tao 1.1 by Mitchell)

"The name that can be named is not the eternal Name.":
EMANATE EMANATE EMANATE LORD CHINESE
emanate emanate emanate Christ Lennon
math math math transcendental beanie [Gauss]
Elohim emanate emanate transcendent
emanate mathematical Anderson/betatron/Ebeneser
commandments ten anthranilate [L1]/Hannibal/lantern/linear/tribal
COMMANDMENTS TEN TRIBAL TENET
ten ten ten ten ten ten decimal Abraham Moshe/Omaha
TEN TEN TEN TEN TEN TEN DECIMAL HASHEM ABRAHAM AO
Alisander behemoth teammate annectant
Alisander emanate emanate contentment/becometh
CHAN HO NAM entertainments/embitterment/maltreatment/reinstatement
CHAN HO NAM ENTERTAINMENT BETHESDA [Young and Dangerous]

...
archenemies heathendom/Bethlehem/Mahometan/Manhattan/Nathanael/Madalena
Archimedes boatman anathema Helene
Nathaniel testament boatman endearment/adherence
CHRISTENDOM ANATHEMA ANATHEMA BEETLE

...
TERENCE TAO MATH MATH MATH NATANIEL/AENEID
Terence Tao nemathelminthes enanthemata [worm "Rounders"]
math math math Constantine Albert [Archimedes' Fields medal]

[HYPOTHETICAL !
proposal to Attila the Hun CE 450;
Jordanes chronicles dream of broken bow ... Noah's rainbow?]

...
"Justa Grata Honoria":
Argonaut Torah
JONAH TARTARS/traitor
Jason arthur/guitar/aorta/Torah

"Attila the Hun":
Athena (22) hilt/Tut
Leah titan

"Political drama": calamari plot

Haters love to hate.

Memory loss and brainwashing: difficult to realise you have them.

[July 30, 1986; Nathaniel w. aliens]

...
"Flight of the Navigator":
Leviathan forgot
levitation Torah
Aaron violet/thief

Democracy directly votes vs Republic layers of representatives.
Abolishing a landed aristocracy creates an educated plutocracy, the principle unchanged: who controls
wealth has power.
Judges short circuit wealth.

...
System of government matters less than spiritual quality of people, hence primacy of good education.

Same law in war and peace.

E.g. David and Uriah.

M part Nordic Viking,
hence McDonalds,
Highlander Connor McCloud,
007 Sean Connery,
McDuck

Motion to replace elections with the lie-off.

"Yankee means masturbator."
namesakes betatron

Feminisation can be induced: drugs, plastic additives, pesticides, etc.
Why are almost none of the chemicals androgenous?

[Vasilios Cicero]
"It's all about the key shots, timing."
Messiah bullshitting/buttonholes/institute
Messiah institute ballyhoo/goat
Agosto (4434) Hellenism/Mitsubishi

Employment is the most noble human relationship.

"See Book of Job, Eve's jealousy."
sublessee Josef Jove
Josef Jay bluebook/loves

...
The Mourning Bride, Zara in Act III, Scene II:
"Heav'n has no rage, like love to hatred turn'd,
Nor hell a fury, like a woman scorn'd."

Permutational vs phonetic embedding to verify authorship across range of translations.

[Buddhist/Taoist]
"The Qur'an: A New Translation
Thomas Cleary":
TARSOMETATARSAL ANTHRAQUINONE/ANNUNCIATOR/AUTHORIAL/Nathaniel/Newtonian
tarsometatarsal author cayenne
tarsometatarsal Newton carnelian
metatarsal transequatorial
METATARSAL ANNUNCIATES YAHWEH
charlatanerie harassment/honourless

[Muslim Englishman;
literal melodic]
"The Koran Interpreted
Arthur John Arberry":
PENTAHEDRON ARBITRATOR (222) HUNTER/RUTH
pentahedron authority Teheran/earner
pentahedron heartbroken Ruthie
pentahedron retributory Arther/Athena
Jordan Robinette threatener

[Egyptian, OBE;
deep understanding]

...
"The Qur'an (Oxford World Classics) M.A.S. Abdel-Haleem":
...
MALARIAN SCHOOLTEACHER (2888) SUBLESSOR ALEX [JOBS]
malarian schoolteacher subleases Lord
Malarian schoolteacher female bud
malarian schoolteacher blameless/defrauded/sublessor/emeralds/exoduses/marquess/slalommed
...
excommunicator hellhole reward
...
MESSIAH WORLDBEATER ALESSANDRO/ALEXANDROS
Messiah worldbeater Alessandro cloud
Messiah worldbeater Alexandros
mollusc/shalom/squall/cloud

[Propagates]

"Original sin": signorina il

"Nephilim giants": Philistine

"The Great Flood":

Godel father/earth/Torah

LORD "Goliath".

Alexander world historical record for torture. CRIMELESS.

USA needs spiritual help.

"A powerful and oppressive nation" (Isaiah 18:2)

"divine democratic mandate":

CONTRAINDICATIVE

contraindicate diadem/David

antidemocratic Aeneid/David

INDOCTRINATED ACADEME

interacademic dominated/diamond

revindication teamed

Macedonian meditative/verdict/David

AMERICA VIETNAM NOTICED

"Alexander's greatest mistakes":

regardless statements

Aeneid steals armrest

testament realised

...

Transgress Mikael

Metatarsal denigrates/estranged

Streisand maltreats

Katerine messages

Rattlesnake disagreement

Kleenexes marriage/armrest

Kleenex traitresses/dramatists/mistresses/strategies

eagles exterminates/trendsetters/disesteems/rainmakers

"Nathaniel betraying Alexander":

engineer (2333) Bellatrix

Bellatrix Diana angry

"Actaeon Phaeton": cheapen tattoo

Jason Thessalonian,

Quest for Golden Fleece ... Flis,

"era of Jason": Josef Aaron;

Peleus Argonaut father of Achilles murdered by Medea via lamb in cauldron scheme;

FF8 Edea Kramer,

"Jordan Nosanchuk": Jason donna.

...

"Jason and Medea":

Seaman jaded/Jae

Adam donna/Anne

Jae nosed

...

"Jason and Creusa glauce":

Alessandro Juneau/ganja

GANJA (2220) dracunculoses [guinea worm parasite]/scandalous/scoundrel/cleanser/coalesced/concealed/

cruelness/arsenous/SEDUCER

cleansing dragon/Jordan

XpengX3 15:13 helicopter car

...

https://youtu.be/g9ch8yHthP4?si=_3JJg7t3JW0imSIU

...

"China Has Launched New Generation Transport SHOCKING The US":

...

CONGRATULATION WASHINGTONIAN PUTRESCENCE

Alessandro counterespionagers enchaining/nictating

HEPHAESTUS ALESSANDRO AUTHENTICATION/... counterattacking/interconnecting/incarcerating

...

rounder Hephaestus congregationalist/internationalist/transcontinental

rounder Hephaestus Thessalonian

anticarcinogen/antinarcotic/technocratic

...

Liechtensteiner coconspirator/supersaturating/traitorousness/counteracting/cantharidean/transgressing

LIECHTENSTEINER COCONSPIRATOR AUGUSTAN [X]

PLANNED OBSOLESCENCE.

Detroit automakers' mistake.

Maximize short term profit, accustom people to mediocrity,
go bankrupt long term, making consumers and citizens into cows.

Beating vs helping.

Honor righteousness, respect skill.

Geographic Facts:

Muslim lands are vast, spanning multiple continents; Israel is tiny, the only Jewish state in the world.
Islam prioritises Mecca and Medina, Jerusalem being tertiary, except as a target for radicals.

People care more for results than causes.

Expect the best, prepare for the worst.

BARBARIAN CHRISTIANS WORSHIP LIFE.

Death is a mercy.

...

[Robinette]

"lifetime imprisonment":

feminine imposter/Lottie/spirit

...

Why Christians abolished sacrifice, "psychological pussification":

sociolinguistic alpha

octopus poaching fails/Alfi

[burned alive to keep oath to LORD]

(Judges 11:34)

"Jephthah's daughter":

deathtrap Hugh

HERA UPSTAGED

death haute [Nathan IHES]

Every man a god, God is a worm.

"Chinese water torture":

Harcourt western

"Flat Earth Society":

STATECRAFT HOLE

Easy to feel, hard to think.

...

"Race religion politics":

electric polarising

electrician igloo

gorilla science

...

"Race religion and politics"

electric Indianapolis

railroad nicotinic

peregrination social

gorilla denicotinise

"Americans loathe Alexander":

charlatanerie (666) Adamson/axeman/daemon

VOTING

A large sample loses locality and gains crowd emotionalism.

Statistical convergence toward mean vs gaining covariance.

Myth is voting is best outcome, reality is mostly near average; yet can get exceptional candidates inducing skew if competence matches salesmanship.

Not a deterministic process.

...

In the USA, representatives, senators, presidents, and lower judges are by aggregate vote. Only higher judges and cabinet appointees are screened by peers.

Biblically judges are best.

Consider the populism of Absalom vs regal David, both came to ruin.

Cyclical extremes in governance, whereas judges are resistant to horde and corruption of individuals.

"Layers of judges": juryless defog/aged

ANTICATO

System of governance

vs genes and culture

vs external.

Difficult to attribute success, hence legitimate historical debate.

...

Genes vs culture: culture trumps.

Mongols conquered the world, later culturally pacified in Korea.

Germans ravaged the Romans, Hitler had the Reich, later pacified by the Americans.

British Empire now goodwill.

...

Europeans are democratic, similar blood similar culture to USA, dominion ended with feudal colonialism, unsustainable.

Indians are very democratic, different blood and culture from USA, mediocre chaotic results.

China autocratic, different blood different culture from USA, America's greatest rival.

Japan democratic, similar blood and culture to China, pacified American ally.

Modern Israel covenanted and democratic, similar blood and culture to USA, lagging in education and research.

Arab democracy ineffective, different blood and culture.

...

Hypothesise external sustaining American dominance.

Conclude singular focus driving Chinese success.

[The truth will set you free.]

...

"AMERICA IS THE BORG.":

armchair beets/Bose/bees

...

Star Trek: Seven of Nine E, Borg Queen J. Also The Matrix.

Personal experience wrestling ghost of Nathaniel tempting with alien encounter.

Not only cultural assimilation, but ALIEN TECHNOLOGY. Implausible that democracy alone, a 3000 year old idea, could lead to such dominance.

...

"Alien technology in United States":

authentication sentinelled

nonethicalness antidote/ideology

constitution Athenian

HALLUCINOGEN DETESTATION [brainwashing]

intelligence dishonesty

astonishing Euclidean

GUILTINESS NATHANIEL/ATHENIAN

IDEOLOGY authenticates/antithetical [oppressive]/LICHTENSTEIN [Hitler]/

ANCIENTNESS [democracy]/annihilates/inauthentic/statistical/uncanniness/UNESSENTIAL

Goliath clandestinity/denunciation

...

"worst country in history": constitution

...

"North Atlantic Treaty Organisation":

COLONISATION ATHENIAN

Athenian transatlantic/antirational/colonisation/totalitarian

trinitroglycerin Thanatos/Nathan

Christianity Lateran

TOTALITARIAN CONSTANTINE

"Alexander marries Jordan Nosanchuk":

DENUCLEARISE HORROR

...

Nuclear weapons are poison: they defend nothing but bring ruin to all.
Develop nonapocalyptic arms, pray to never use them.

Justice is impartial to wealth, yet taxation is a collectively allocated power, thus there is no injustice in flat vs progressive tax rates, rather a difference in philosophy.

...

"Debating questions with no answer": brainteasing sententious

CONSERVATIONAL

Social engineering to homogenise races, castes, religions is artificial.
Intermarriage is the exception not the norm. Yet pure blood is an idol.

PRAGMATISM

All men are not created equal:
consider souls, genes, and culture.
Righteousness implies equality under law.
Respecting roots and dreams, create a meritocratic culture:
REAP WHAT YOU SOW.

Free will is partial.

Round out weaknesses, but focus on strengths.

Invest in education: seeing, studying, suffering.

Countries divide by ethnicity.

Mushroom cloud, penis shaped.
Erica Standhart [Cain, E] fungal behavior World War III.

Bhagavad-Gita As It Is, xiv:

...

"the clever Duryodhana challenged the Pandavas to a gambling match"

...

"the gambling, which was rigged, cheated the Pandavas of their kingdom"

...

"Krsna Himself took the role of messenger for the sons of Pandu and went to the court of Dhrtarastra to plead for peace."

...

"Krsna became the charioteer of Arjuna"

...

"Bhagavad-Gita begins, with the two armies arrayed, ready for combat"

...

"World War Three": LORD wrath

"The Revelation to John":

enthroned Elijah

...

[whitehorse, trumpets]

"On the other side, both Lord Krsna and Arjuna, stationed on a great chariot drawn by white horses, sounded their transcendental conchshells." (Gita 1.14)

...

[EIGHTEEN Chapters]

(Gita 1.15)

"Lord Krsna blew His conchshell, called Pancajanya":

YAHWEH ALESSANDRO ALEJANDRO/ALEKSANDR

/ALISANDER

Yahweh Alessandro Aleksandr chincona/Lincoln

Yahweh Alejandro Aleksandr Nicholas

...

YAHWEH ALESSANDRO JORDAN ALLIANCE

ALESSANDRO HEBREW OAKLAND JAPAN CYCLIC

Renaissance Aleksandr halcyon

Yahweh Aleksandr cannabino1 poacher

...

"The Supreme Personality of Godhead said: Time I am, the great destroyer of the worlds, and I have come here to destroy all people. With the exception of you [the Pandavas], all the soldiers here on both sides will be slain." (Gita 11.32)

...

[Yahweh emanated]
"the unborn" (Gita 10.12)

...
[God Most High]
"the unmanifested" (Gita 12.1)

El Paso, Texas. "God walks".
Blue city in red state ... purple
Old West; Q continuum in Star Trek.
UTEP Miners; data mining.
Vladimir Tepes "Dracula",
tEp Xi of Boston purple 22,
UTEP Mongolian architecture, cousin to Native American Indians; also has a Buddhist Temple.
Congregation B'Nai Zion has a pyramid, phone 2222.

...
"as the tortoise draws its limbs within the shell" (Gita 2.58)

...
"What is night for all beings is the time of awakening for the self-controlled; and the time of awakening for all beings is night for the introspective sage." (Gita 2.69)

[Augur means sign; see "Hercules".]

...
Jan. 20, 2024 Trump Inauguration,
MLK Day

...
"Venus Mars Jupiter Saturn Neptune Uranus":
SERVANT TRUMP JANUARIES PRESENT
servant Trump renaissant ensure
servant (4644) supersaturate miner
servant Messiae (802) usurpature/partner/patterns/Atreus [Israel]
servant instrument Japanese
Ser (5555) reinstatement/unremunerative

EMOTIONALISM

Hating adversaries is folly.
Truth and righteous judgement imply seeing the good in everyone.
Haters are easy to control and defeat.

Generational age difference.
Adam's sons were Cain and Abel.
Abraham's nephew was Lot.
Caesar's adopted son Octavio.

...
"The LORD possessed me at the beginning of His way" (Proverbs 8:22)
"Abraham My friend" (Isaiah 41:8)

[Arthurian: Morgause and Mordred; M's neighbor is Gauss]
"Nataniel mother": Marianne [Abel]

"Morgause and Arthur" (3335):
Amadeus Arthur/Utahn
rounder Gautama
DRAGON HAUTE

"Jordan Nosanchuk vassal Nathaniel":
voluntariness Oakland

Breakfast at Tiffany's is a nonideal "two swords" situation starring J and Y [library catalog]. Must see !

Liberty is mental. How can the ignorant bring freedom?

[Q duked, Heart intact "aortal";
See Ezekiel 22:22]
"Thich Quang Duc": thigh quad

Loose basketball metaphors:
Michael Jordan #23 [J],
Scottie Pippen #33 [Peregrine, ... Pippen in LOTR, K],
Dennis Rodman #91 ["the Worm" - Triton in Little Mermaid, Flis L ... B],

Kobe Bryant #8, 24 [Ko, Octavio, K],
Lebron James #23, initially Cleveland Cavalier [James, K]

[Black hole]
Christianity is singular, mythology is manifold.

LA is Alexander's dreams made real in movies and science.
"Garden of Eden, in flames."
Armageddon Flis

...
Caltech JPL ... JL

Living fossil, chased by destroyer.
Most of Alexander's relatives are not only dead families but also dead civilizations:
Egypt Pharaoh - destroyed
Ephraim David - destroyed
Greece Atreus - destroyed
Russia Nevsky - destroyed
Japan Hideyoshi - destroyed
France Louis - destroyed
Etc.

SUGAR PILL SNAKE OIL
Travis sold the West sugar pill snake oil, betraying their heritage and future to China, impersonating
and scapegoating Alexander.

Good men live to old age.
VS
Only the good die young.
[Cohen, ... cozen, cozy]

[Imprecise paraphrase Isaiah 49:5]
"Second Pskovian Chronicle":
handpick convincer
princeliness Hancock/cacao
CHAPERON POACHES

All different:
haunted vs cursed vs damned.
Curse of David:
for sparing the life of a murderer and adulterer, an eternal curse.
Your wives will long for other men and the sword shall never leave your house.
Bathsheba David's wife: Queen of Sheba "bitch" in Korean, birdbath.
Alexander God-damned to Sheol for unwitting disobedience; LORD did not speak.
Alexander challenged for Adam's compelled transgression, haunted by Michael and Nathaniel, wife swapped
by James and Michael.

Freewill is limited: associates are punished for your sins.
E.g. Jordan Oakland not entirely responsible for being rotten apple.

Fear is the worst enemy, the most powerful. There is nothing to fear.

"Universalism vs regionalism" and
"Ideologic crusade vs balancing books"
are the essence of the current wars.

"Two wrongs do not make right":
integrator Kong
demotion gorgon/Agosto
Ko demonstrating/warmongering/wrongdoing/stewarding
Washington doom

"Righteousness does not negate transgression":
heterogeneousness integration dragon
erroneousness integration death

[FYI CIA]
International regional dialing codes:
USA +1, China +8

"an apple rotten to the core" (2300):
Penelope attractor/Actaeon/crooner
harpooner tentacle
phaeton penetrator/copartner

[How is J Job/Jeremiah/Euler so enchanted with Esau, and why is Ginny so relatively intelligent??
If Alexander abused, why not J?]

...
"Jordan pothead":
DEODORANT JAP
RHODANATE [cystic fibrosis]
JATROPHA DONE
[J atrophy, Jatropha Augusta? Cathartica?
Poison e.g. ricin, prevents triadic alphabet protein translation]

...
Aaron doped/hoped
pardon death
harpoon jaded/jae
Phaeton Dad
JONAH DOTARD [Biblical truth]
Noah adopter
throne Jap

...
Throop Dean/Jae
tornado PhD
dehorn data/toad

"James child abuse"(1878):
DISABLES ACE/JAE
Elijah amuses/caused/based/bused
Judah malice
Michael Judas
Amadeus lies
Scheme jails
Judaism bleaches
Ace Messiah
Humble acid
Deus Malachi

...
"child abuse": disable

"Eight hours of work per day":
Fishhook daguerrotype/retrograde
FREDERIK HOGWARTS/southpaw/author/THROOP/Torah/yahoo/Shay
SHAPIRO OUTWORKED/forgery/outgrow
OUTGROW HYDROSPHERE

..
REWARD RIGHTEOUS/fighter/fishhook/porosity/trophies/upright/highest/profits/thigh
reward THROOP fogy/keys

"Eight hours of work a day":
RIGHTEOUS WORKDAY
Autoworkers Idaho
graduator fishhook
Yahweh autogiros/auditor/rigorous
Yahoo authorised/farsighted/godfather/righteous/outrages/worthier
Agosto keyword

...
Reward FISHH00K/goatish/Agosto/thigh/yahoo/auto/Fiat

"Five hours of work per day":
reward Prokofiev/poorhouse/pushover/viperous/sheriff

"Five hours of work a day":
deify Kurosawa
Yahoo fireworks
Harvard fief/keys/wife/wise
Savior woodruff/defray/yahoo
Kay overshadow
Ieyasu hardwork

...
reward oafish/Shiva/Yahoo

"Isaac swapping Jacob Esau metaphor":
ACCURATENESS ISAIAH
autobiographic Japanese
chaperon scapegoatism
marijuana scapegoat/sabotage

"Now the first came forth red, all over like a hairy garment; and they named him Esau."
(Genesis 25:25)

...
'and Esau said to Jacob, 'Please let me have a swallow of that red stuff there, for I am famished.'
Therefore his name was called Edom [red]." (Genesis 25:30)

How to knock out Ol' Nick? Hit him in the stomach.
Who puts stock in godless men?
Faith drives behavior.
Bitcoin eating the dollar alive?

ALEXANDER DISLIKES POLITICS.
Politics dislikes Alexander.

...
Good policy is timeless.
People vote with every purchase.
Spend energy on results.

"Political drama": calamari Lot/pot/dot

Intelligence is entrenched.

6.001 MIT Scheme Lambda Calculus. Also C++ = B.

"The Revelation to John":
LEVOROTATION

...
Enthroned Elijah/Lotto
Veto Johnathon/Lionheart/lantern
Lionheart TNT
lantern thief
Oiler Johnathon/heathen/tattoo
tattoo Elinore/Lenin
Lenin tattooer/Jehovah
JENNI ELEVATOR
veneration Lotto
Torah violent/toilet/violet
Jehovah retention
throne elevation/Helvetian
JOVE ANTOINETTE

X-Men: Beast, Wolverine, Jean Grey, Etc.

NYC: N&Y's City

[Vicing Yahweh by GT and spirits;
in film Arthur-Jordan is best;
want to sabotage by killing Jordan.
Also M, L part Mongolian, different from Manchurian, slandering J.]

...
["Erica Standhart": Catharine, ... Cathai or China]
"The Manchurian Candidate"(2004):
Cantharidate machine
Archimedean antacid/Nathan

...
Director JONATHAN Demme

...
"Raymond Prentiss Shaw":
MESSIAH PORTRAYS
TORAH DISPENSARY
steward hypnosis/nymphos [G,E]

password (1101) tyrannise/Riemann/Yasmine/Ishtar
EMANATION PHD
Samson handwrites/tradership/wardenship
smith Anderson/Odyssean
pardon swarthisness/trashiness/hastiness/smartness
Windsor (1211) harassment/spymaster/ashtrays
PYRE WORDSMITH
Nimrod (1111) sharpness/shysters
shadow tyranniser

...
VERSUS

...
"Alexander marries Jordan Nosanchuk":
Manchurian Oakland serenaders

...
"Alexander unifies physics at Michigan":
Manchurian acidifying shapeliest

Squall Leonheart has a gunblade.

"New Testament is constructed":
Newton underestimates
awesomeness (333) uncredit/ruined

"Old Testament is truth":
AUTHOR MENDELIST [XY digital]
LOT ANTITHESIS
demonstrates Tut
lionhearted Tut
Messiah Lord Tut
Messiah turtle
atheists undoer
Deus isothermal/monetarist/Aristotle/lionheart/antihero/horseman/Alister/menorah/mineral/monster/thrones
Detroit astutest/humanest/unseals

The word of the Lord is unchanging.

Luminaries speak for themselves, but the LORD will repay sin.

James Bond is the octet rule for covalent molecules.

"Judas Iscariot and Jesus" (4440):
adjudication assure
Icarus (1111) astounded
Direction Judas
direct assassin
disunite cross/sodas
Jordan discusses/justices/assisted/suicide
suicide astounds
ASSISTED DINOSAUR/JORDAN

"Judas Iscariot and Jesus of Nazareth":
authorisation sacredness/assurance

Abraham and Isaac (N, son) echoes Judas and Jesus (G, daughter).

[Never recovered from trauma]
"Isaac ben Abraham and Isaac Newton":
Smithson Rebecca Diana
cannabis Christendom
cowardice Nathan amnesia
brand machination/chaoticness
omniscience reward

Constantine (2005).
"God and the devil made a wager"

...
Cancerous cough mirrors LORD signalling Jordan's attraction via itchy throat, supervising Georgia's 24/7
torture.

Pattern is possession and sabotage of Alexander, likewise of Jordan, likewise torture and war instigation.

UK is +44; In Chinese 4 is death, whereas 8 is good fortune. (?)

[vs Alexander scholar]

Chief executive officers are metaphorical killers.

Murder is evil, breaks 10X.

"Cursing, Privacy": Icarus prying [N]

Silly J, reprove privately, N agitating.

RELATIONSHIPS SHOULD HOLD WATER.

...

"And Ham, the father of Canaan, saw the nakedness of his father, and told his two brothers outside" (Genesis 9:22)

..

"So he said,

'Cursed be Canaan;

A servant of servants

He shall be to his brothers.' "

(Genesis 9:25)

"What is holy?": Yah (111) owlsh

[Expand precise list of holy vs not.]

...

In the Torah, the firstborn were initially sanctified to the LORD [Exodus 13:2], changed to the sons of Levi [Exodus 3:12], as the cost of the Passover.

Rule, judgement, and education require trust. Heaviest scrutiny falls on hard power, the soft power of education disdained but most influential in the long run.

"Radicals are halogens,":

Herc Alessandro/Lordliness/signaller/analogies

paired with CATions:

Lithium Li+ (Lilith, antidepressant), Sodium Na+, POTassium K+.

ISRAEL ETHNIC TRIBE ACCEPTS CONVERTS.

vs KKK or Ku Klux Klan? Or Hamas?

Octavio uses multipronged attack.

Divide and conquer the West.

Conquer by corrupting morals.

Cruelty is not a virtue.

Americans are liars.

Healthy culture attracts (2232).

Preference for religious interbreeding.

Hybrids are vigorous.

Typically loyalty follows blood.

Demolish myth of pure blood.

Jews are mixed.

Ashkenazi Jews: Hebrews intermarried with peoples of Ukraine and Russia, later Germany.

Turks have link to Japanese.

...

[Intelligent and formidable]

Scythians (ancient Eastern Iranic equestrian nomadic people), skythikon (putrified snake venom arrows), aposkuthizein (scalping).

...

Scythian (230) [Jordan]

Scythian Khazars (1001) [Maude]

...

Kazan, Tatarstan, Russia,

Russian: казан, 'boiler' or 'cauldron',

flag crowned dragon,

Russian Зилант, Tatar yılan/елан, namesake of Elon Muskovitz,

myth of stink of burning snakes.

...

St. Basil's ... base of the Intercession, by Tsar Ivan IV, commemorates capture of Kazan.

Manifold bonfire candy cane J style, also bulbous, seed, Cid, Lord.

...
"Can you draw out Leviathan with a fishhook?" (Job 41:1)
"Out of his nostrils smoke goes forth,
As from a boiling pot and burning rushes." (Job 41:20)
"He makes the depths boil like a pot" (Job 41:31)

...
Noah->Japheth->Gomer->Ashkenaz
(Genesis 10:1-3, 1 Chronicles 1:4-6)
[Chronicler Nathan reborn Lenin]

...
"Blow a trumpet among the nations!
Consecrate the nations against her,
Summon against her the kingdoms of Ararat, Minni and Ashkenaz;
Appoint a marshal against her"
(Jeremiah 51:27) [Jae, Trump]

Hypocrisy:
Teach market efficiency, meanwhile export wealth.
Teach Jesus Christ, meanwhile slowly consolidate power.
Teach ideals, have them destroy society, meanwhile practice reality.
[Target youth: K-12, also N's FF7.]

Who sold out America to China?
Richard NIXON
vs
[Richard the Lionhearted,

...
Leonhard Euler or Jordan J
Richard Phillips Feynman Y
FF8 Squall Lionheart
SOT Richard and Kahlan

...
Richard Lamb CK CS,
Richard Florka steel trader DYC]

"Christianity buries the truth in mythology."
countersignatures (222)

...
In Arthurian legend, there is adulteress Guinevere and bastard Mordred.

...
In Greek mythology, Cupid promotes Chaos.

...
The Hebrews have Adam and the Snake helping cherub death.

...
22 is the alphabet, the cradle of the West.

"duty and respect misguided":
underestimate cupid
masterpiece studying

Charm helps evade justice.

Antibacterials are not loving.

Guard against contentment.
Life being good enough is a mental yoke, requisite to enslavement, for sharp pain necessitates change.
The sleep of death is complacency: having your livelihood outsourced.
[Joshua: "Everything is fantastic."]

Women like guitars because tones mirror their subtlety of emotion.

Alexander the Great of Macedon:
Soul of West vs East
Greek City States vs Persian Empire
States: Thessaly, Thrace, Macedon, Arcadia, etcetera. Cities: Athens, Sparta, Corinth, Megara, Etc. (&c)

...
Oliver Cromwell parallel, curbing the absolute power of monarchies.
Why his corpse should have been burned on a pyre: decapitated head on display for 30 years.

...
Alexander's idealist mistake was not interbreeding. Religious and cultural differences are very

difficult for ordinary men, led to collapse.

"Medieval Ages": evil damages
Why were Medieval Ages ignorant, cruel, and filthy? Christianity.
The Romans built baths in England.

"Efficient Market Hypothesis":
antichrist tipoff
perfection mistakes/faithes
mistake theoretic fishy
reminisce payoff

Letter vs Spirit: detaching words from their meaning.

There is value in ease of communication. Yet multilingualism promotes IQ, and preserves culture and religion.

X ... President Xi vs Joseph

[King Arthur ... General Douglass MacArthur]
"English worldwide": whirlwind Godel

"Chinese worldwide":
SWINE LORDED
weed crowned/silicone
oiler decides

QUALITY SELLS ITSELF !

The American Borg similar to the Russians.

Best countries in the world to raise children: Finland, Japan. Why??

1. Tribal.
2. Education and culture valued.
3. Not targeted by K like Israel.

[Collusive child abuse]
Mothers are intuitive about their children. That M was unaware of extensive abuse at IC is absurd.
She induced traumatic hour long OCD toothbrushing.
Rather Ukrainian culture is notorious for jealous sabotage.

[Hermaphrodites destroying my life: typically hateful wrath is Michael, false reasoning Nathaniel, serotonin and lust Georgia.]

"The Epistle of Small to the Americans":
MICHAEL SOMATOTHERAPIST
Themistocles impersonate

"Alexander liberates the word nigger": worldbeater interreign

A sailing mistake can be fatal, a lax hammer stroke crippling. Treat people with the same care and be blameless, for they have longer memories and are more dangerous.

Appreciation of Consequence:
A doctrine of profligate mercy is a seductive yet immature siren's call. It reflects neither the reality of life nor the nature of God. Consider, cowardice at key points will destroy your life irreparably, David is accursed perpetually over Uriah.

Akin to the fall of Adam, people overstep. Morality was established by the LORD, it is not for people to reinvent. Children are not entitled to their parents laurels.

The CIA will knife you in the back, then blame you for crying out.
Discrediting is preferred over disappearance, creating mental health problems the gold standard.

Office Space (1999) Apt. 222
[see Milton's "Paradise Lost"]

Pivotal points in life: religion, school, marriage. Something feels wrong, it is wrong.
...

A moment of courage over a lifetime of regret.

ZOMBIE APOCALYPSE:

Homes destroyed are rebuilt, lives lost are reborn. Not to justify evil, but attend substance over spectacle. The real travesty is lifelong human suffering, the living dead zombies of the modern world, and the horror they inflict on nature.

Lies and abuse create lifelong unwitting prisoners and slaves, dependants who then defend the system that debilitated them.

Aeneid attacks the mind not the body at its most vulnerable point in childhood, where the wounds are concealed, most difficult to heal, and seemingly character deficits.

The literal imprisonment of Christian justice is a metaphor for the real imprisonment of the mind.

MIT is Leninist in spirit, architecture, and philosophy. The idol of "one dome to rule them all", the universal best education. True to its Soviet roots, its standard is high.

It serves a useful function, culling a herd of fools using prestige. That brutalism improves education is a relativist fallacy, like saying that infidelity improves marriage. Personal attention and happiness in study improve education.

...
"MIT is hell", where the demons aggregate: Sadoway, Rasputin, Travis, Cain, etc.
MIT students literally set themselves on fire, and corpses from suicide are left to rot.

...
Concrete evidence is:
1. Librarian N's course numbers
2. MIT vs Caltech anagrams in Permutations 3.

*Corrupt character lose soul.

"Americans are barbarians."
renaissance rabbi

[Women beat men]
"emotional violence":
neocolonial
clementine viola
Lenin Octavio
Milton Evaleen

*You feel when something is wrong.

[confused;
names rockets after cocks: Falcon (K), Dragon (N), everything X]

...
"Elon Muskovitz":
evolution [false]
Milton Zeus [Office Space]
MOLEST ZION/UNO
soviet monk/uno
Ko unmolest/envious/moisten/violet/stolen

[United States]
"worst country in history":
constitution showy
Christ tourist/sorrow/Triton/irons
trinity unworthy [verifies phrasing]

[Georgia Travis]
"worst person in history":
serotonin sophistry/worships
honeypot insists
shyster positron/proton
tortoise hypnosis/prison/sonship

Names are occupational.

[primary schoolteacher conspiracy at Immaculate Conception; Ursula, courtesy of James Ko.]
Alla Kopacz [Russian "gravedigger"] nee Schustov [Russian "clever"]
son Zenon Kopacz "Nick"
[Russian Jewish childhood friend]

Jalalabad Market 12500 Klinger St.,
[J-alala-bad, ... J-Allah-bad]
Physical evidence of Michael's sabotage, very fishy.

[Virginia: A0, Yom Kippur]
Sell people cheaply, they are worthless to you.

[New holy Land]
"Jews in maze of Manhattan."
Newton anathema

Musk's X represents ferryman for colonisation of Mars.

Donbass ... Don Bass; like Oct. 8 Israel, related to demineralisation.

If truth and righteousness are foremost, what of an adversarial trial system?
Exonerating guilt is evil; noting the good in the guilty merits clemency.

Free will is partial; the LORD causes things to be.

[Cereal bowl is weed, adult milk]
"I am the fruitloop of eternity."
metaphor infertility/Nefertiti/unfertilized/felinity/Elinore/felonry/trefoil/trinity/uterine/Orient/rotten/
Tiffie/*Triton*

...
promotion faithful/fatherly/hilarity/tartuffe/tutelary/Harley/turtle/Alfie

...
[see "The Devil's Advocate" ovaries, also Trump Tower.]

"An apple for an apple."
[J appalling]

Hanukkah (Hakka) is superior to Xmas because there are 8 days.

Purim (Esther), Easter is for Jesus.

Notable Israel attacked on 8 fronts, "octopus": Netanyahu AIJAC 11/27/24.
Gaza war began Oct. 7... 8.

"Alexander trains Greco Roman":
recondensation regal
centenarian dogears
centenarian Lord Omega
reannexation damocles

Alpha vs Beta is base, it represents mammalian primal dominance. Why there was no real Beta, it is so
profoundly insulting.

"In God We Trust"
LORD suggested Jordan, therefore Alexander's preference is Jordan.
Alexander will marry Virginia if Jordan refuses; and if Jordan accepts he does not think it fair to leave
Virginia childless at her age after waiting for me.

There is a modern bias that men are always the villains; it is contrary to Biblical experience and
reality.
Boys get blamed as girls connive.

"Grinch begat Yoda": Georgia yacht

Yame (stop), Yama (death), Yamato (Japan)
Stop signs around the world, universalised octagonal red.
Rolling vs stationary stop.

Nikko Japan (Tokugawa), 'Ol Nick, Niccolo Machiavelli, Phoenicia (boatman)

...
James's double [Slippery]
"Nicolino Locche": Niccolo Cohen
(117-4-14 draws)

...

Losses notable:

- 10. Vicente Milan Derado PTS [M]
- 66. Abel Laudonio PTS [Cain ... Kay]
- 124. Alfonso Frazer UD [Alfy]
- 129. Antonio Cervantes RTD [Don Quixote, for Antonius]

...

[Need rules.]

Aleksandr Aleksandrovich Karelin (887-2) "Monster"

[887 Harcourt, Karl Gauss neighbor, 887 is prime]

[NASB1977 p. 887 (Luke 14:5) "Which one of you shall have a son or an ox fall into a well, and will not immediately pull him out on a Sabbath day?"]

Jordan's double is Audrey Hepburn.

...

"Paris When It Sizzles": 1:16:00 references Captain Ahab of Moby Dick, bait at end of hook [J].

...

"Sabrina" has James, Ginny, Jordan, and Alexander as the goldfish; David and Linus Larrabee w. cane and gravedigger references, borrowing David's automobile, Linus desiring a plastics merger.

"Corrupting character is insidious.":

Christianisation usurper

Augustinians despotic

antichrist (4464) conspiracies

supersaturation Grinch

Alexander's grievances against James this lifetime by proxy:

1. IC child abuse for 8 years, Principal Ursula
2. Family infiltration, grandmother Baba is Michael, denigrates mother
3. Setup with K's wife Virginia
4. Stalked by Nathan, drugged and lobotomised
5. Isolated by Georgia Travis, 6 years torture, slander, rape
6. Sabotaged by Michael, lose wife
7. Sabotaged by Nathan, branded
8. Sabotaged by Nathan, wife ravaged by Esau (Johnathan)
9. Instigation of war in Israel 8/8/24
10. Communization of Russia, Lenin is Nathaniel; Cold War.

[Kay ... Kain swine behavior]

Octavio was spiritually allied with Cato in the Catiline Conspiracy, later murdering Caesarion in *cold blood*, and transformed the Roman Republic into an Empire. His descendants did not vindicate his avaricious misjudgement; their names are infamous.

Notably Caesar was assassinated supporting the martial Roman culture, as Alexander was betrayed defending the liberty of countries worldwide, including China.

Despite his victories, Octavian is notably absent from Plutarch; the ancients distinguished between honor and success.

How many positions in a war? Four.

Red, Blue, Neither, Both.

Einstein's light beams go both ways, relative morality; whereas Alexander is neither.

e.g. Athenian Xtianity vs Marx-Leninism. [Potential WWII]

Jihad vs Populism. [Israel]

To risk nuclear war over marginal territory is insane, especially from a position of moral weakness.

Nuclear arms permit anyone to go all-in for the whole world, a highly unstable equilibrium. They should be eliminated altogether.

NATO is colonialist, and the US is Biblically "powerful and oppressive", "Goliath" from the LORD'S mouth, The Borg. Russia and China are more authoritarian and feudalistic.

Spectral decomposition of governments: populism, authoritarianism, feudalism, aristocracy, plutocracy, judges.

Types and measures of liberty:

incarceration rehabilitation, educational and economic mobility,

to incorporate, jurisdictional, movement, speech, of information, from espionage, from interference, to life and death.

"Legacy of Kain: Soul Reaver"

[Reap what you sow.]

"World War Three":
Dorthee raw
trader whore/lore
retard hero

See the Spice Girls on plurality.

"Wrath and cowardice display lack of self control":
dandelion catholic crackpot

Hong Kong Film:
Young and Dangerous.

"You will burn My Flesh on a pyre. I am the LORD."

Mercy as a weapon creates spineless worms.

From personal experience, the spiritual authors of the New Testament are hypocritical; for all their advocacy of mercy, they are lacking therein. Anything under the sun to destroy Alexander. They dispense but do not swallow the Kool-aid of James Jones.

Undeserved clemency deprives people of instruction and justice; leaving the possibility of clemency or expiation can inspire redemption.
Consider if the transgression is reversible.

Fear as a weapon creates drones.

MIT employs a brutalist evolutionary philosophy toward education, like its architecture. Mentorship empowers people.

Christianity combines morality with sophistry, prophesy with false reference; the product then impedes truth by loyalty.
The truth will set you free.

[Adaptation falsely extended to changing number of chromosomes]

"Evolution is false":
elevation soul/Flis
lifeline auto
Lot evilness/foulness/vileness/elusive/envious/felines

...
"Evolution is true":
Lot virtuous
truelove snout

"Win a battle lose the hearts of men.":
honorableness helmet/Alfie

Ignorance is a defense not an excuse. (See Adam.)

[MIT Math course 18, Physics 8]
"Mathematics is the Queen of the Sciences":
Messiah omniscience
Massachusetts enticement/nicotinic

Abortion.
1. Cellular life begins at conception.
2. Takes two to tango; both parents have rights to children.
3. Inappropriate relations.

...
What is "inappropriate", and who decides?

King James Bible,
Koren Tanakh with no Messiah,
Koran "God splits souls" catholic.

...
NASB 1977 vs revision ISBN 888.

Christian axiom abolishes the Law,
corollary is kings are above it.
Ruling style Augusto and Tokugawa.

Do little boys like Barbie dolls?
Do little girls like trucks?

Georgia and Nathan are mentally ill.

Brawling is beating, boxing is timing. Like a kind word, a proverb, or a joke.

Rumination is chewing cud. Revisiting memory causes pain; ceasing revisiting or erasing the memory stops the pain. Alternatively reframe the memory; change your attitude about it.

The Shawshank Redemption:
a refute of Christian ideals.
Old men are unequal to young.
Men are unequal to women.
A woman's touch is sorely lacking.
Death is often kinder than extended imprisonment.
Aggressive sodomy is barbaric.

Beyond a beat down, the purpose of abuse is to denature. As one fly ruins a jar of ointment, the psyche remembers insults.

FF7
"Sephioth": shepiro... Shapiro
"Jenova": Jae
"Sephioth and Jenova":
Phaethon Jordan

...
Jenova's head:
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[Not a Jew, see Ezekiel 22:22]
"Alexander the Hebrew":
hexahedral renew

Pornography ruins lives.

Backstabbing is gay.
Why we have holy oaths, invoking the witness and wrath of God.

"Swine eat their own excrement":
Antichrist Newton
enthronement (555) Crist

Human life is extremely fragile.

"Life begins at conception.":
Napoleon geneticist/scientific

"God judges man not vice versa.":
Sovereign Sadducean
recondense Judaism/gaius
Actaeon demonises

"The most savage animal is man.":
Lamentation Messiah

"Reap what you sow." Torah Aesop
"Jordan": drajon ... dragon
"Job and Jeremiah": JORDAN JAE
"Nebuchadnezzar and Nebuzaradan":
Buddha Aberdeen Canaan

(Illiad 19.261-63)
"that I have laid no hand upon the girl Briseis":
trinitrotoluene Bangladeshis [12450 Klinger]
dandelion authoritativeness alibi
dandelion librarian Hephaestus

...
"I have laid no hand upon the girl Briseis":
highhandedness reprobation
honourableness revalidating/highlander
dandelion librarian SETUP

"Evil will not deliver those who practice it." (Ecclesiastes 8:8)

Chinese saying - 出污泥而不染.

Describes the Lotus, which often grows in muddy water, but emerges untainted by the mud.

Consider what it takes to attract a woman, all the usual stimuli work, generating contempt in a man the same as ass 'n titties in a woman. "Would she love me had I nothing?"

...
How would she treat me with the face of a demon? Homeless?
How would she treat me with my soul at her mercy? My power?
Seemingly.

[Political incorrectness has truth.]

National Characters:

America ... Erica (E); masculine women, backstabbing.
China ... Hin Ting (K); heterosexual matriarchy. Also Phoenicia.
Italia ... Tali (G); drama, matriarchy.
Ukraine or Ruthenia ... Kain, Ruth (E, M); backstabbing matriarchy.
Hindia ... Virginia (Y); patriarchy, gypsies.
Japan ... Jordan (J); patriarchal, nasal.
Israel (L); originally patriarchy, now shadow matriarchy, scholars.

"The devil's greatest trick was convincing the world he didn't exist."
Catholicisation Christening weediness regretted

Jordan [N]: true love sweetheart, now a pothead sniffing for weed.

Virginia: honest love, deep history, fear of abandonment like Ishmael.

Georgia: means well, but sex and drama are incompatible, both our lives hell. Entertainment industry.

"Yucatan Peninsula":
Cataline, Nataniel, analyst
NATANIEL ANUS

...
Calamity, Cali, Baal, Ball, Asteroid, disaster, Astarte, Asherah, Hera
Traces of Ruthenium
Metaphorical extinction of Hebrews
Adam Tyrannosaur

...
Similar pattern of behavior from N in Solomon's shadow, Caesar's assassin, Lenin, Jesus.
Also wrt Alexander, as N wants marriage to Cain or Travis to kill his soul, which would provoke WWII.

Parsi dakhma, Buddhist self immolation see Jeremiah 7,8.
Not an ordinance or prohibition.

If 8 Mile made Eminem, James Ko made Alexander by instilling insatiable discontent in my soul.

Sexual metaphor for gender relations: men do the work, and can only ejaculate once.

[Jordan's PlayStation]

Las Vegas idea: gambling on games of higher skill versus shearing masses.
Jackpot in the Excalibur basement.
e.g. video games are huge worldwide, always fresh.
Attracting deeper pool, combine education and gambling for happier customers.
My cut is 10%, Biblical tithe.

Tattoos break covenant, thus weaponised on Holocaust victims.

Drug analogs:
Krokodil (desomorphine), Leviathan
Weed, dandelion

Cocaine, Ko
Nicotine, Ol Nick
Heroin (diacetylmorphine), hero
LSD, acid, Flis

[Incomplete ...]
Lord of the Rings (LOTR):

"Gandalf and Balrog":
ALF dragon
"Gandalf and Balrog of Morgorth":
Alamogordo fandango
Alamogordo Lord Nathan

[??? Incomplete]
LORD:
"You will burn My flesh on a pyre."
unremorseful playboy
polymerise unlawful

"You will burn My flesh on a pyre. I am the LORD."
foreordainment hyperbola

Consent vs need; need is nebulous.
E.g. Ruth had need, Boaz did not.
Boaz close relative of Naomi, yet no obligation (legal need) toward Ruth.

"Righteous polygamy requires consent."
retrogression Clementius/speculation/cautiously
miraculousness peregrine/eighteen/potter

[Generally best to avoid fornication, Darwin, dragon, Victor ... Hermes, messenger. Apologies.]

...
[Deuteronomy 22:28 setup]
"Wife Jordan Consort Virginia":
wrongdoer Iscariot/Octavian
Octavio (2222) dignifies
Crist (1887) foreordaining/DARWINIAN/Wagnerian/wardening/woodgrain/wrongdoer
deification warrior/Sargon/Savior
wardening FORNICATOR/VICTORIAN/Iscariot/Francis
avianise cornrowing/doctoring/crowning

...
DRAGON VERIFICATION
nicotinise woodgrain
warden fornication

"Christians worship monogamy":
Romanisation myopic
Romanticism prognosis
Shapiro Corinthians
CORONATION MASHGIHIM/Issiah/Miriam

On Marriage.
Concentration vs Pollination.
One man one wife, consort limit two with honest consent to preserve conjugal rights.
Marriage is not unbreakable.

...
Harlots coo. Bastards usurp;
e.g. Mordred and Arthur, using the vitality of excellent men against them.
Pollinating is unattractive, and parasitic consorts destroy families.

US Supreme Court: Flis vs US Gov

Men are not possessions, and neither are women. Marriage and consortship are contracts.
Why should a woman's pride be attached to exclusive possession of a man? Is the wife belittled by a consensual symbiotic consort?
Limited polygamy does not impede conception or rearing of children, so what cause for offense?
Are consorts only for need, or is respect of love legitimate, as with Ruth and Boaz, or David and Abigail? This is not greed or lust.
Marianna is my mother, Sarah my second mother. Both were my wives, the finest women I have ever known, I

will not part with them. Are they jealous? Does anyone take offense at my loving them both?
Christians assume polygamy is sexual gluttony a la Solomon, which monogamy aims to restrict, creating a trail of single mother X's.

Polygamy splinters families, but are there there not cases where limited splintering is best?
Suffering comes from the idolatrous illusion of possession and jealous pride attached to it, also from the idol of equivalence.

Women are equally important, the biological and behavioral asymmetry of consorts does not change this fact.

Men assume added responsibility and fight Christian social stigma; should they not be respected not demonised for fruitfully multiplying?

Implicit shadow matriarchy.

...
Biblically blessed polygamy highlighted in the book of Ruth: Rachel and Leah, Tamar and Judah, Ruth and Boaz. Forced circumstances, raising up deceased brother's wife, honest love.
Also consider the Muslims's male population obliteration in war.

Bible has two column format, Phaeton Testament should be standard page format.

[Sodomize people in their own homes: connive, rape, torture.]
America, Erica, CIA, Cain, China

Nathaniel (886) stalks Alexander, trying to connive him to Christianity.

"CIA stands for Cain up your butt":
Tyrannosaurus factoid/acidic/tactic/cubit/idiot

Sodomy is a curse.
A natural divergence from the mean that is filthy and has no reproductive function, only pleasure. A gay couple is unequal to a heterosexual marriage: cannot naturally reproduce, do not have the gender behavioral archetypes to raise emotionally healthy children.

"Sow deceit reap distrust."
supersecret Taoist

An adversary in youth is as fluoride for the tooth.

Interest is not interesting.

Dominance is not domineering.

Universalisation and relativity are dubious.

Feminist hypocrisy personifies the behaviors they would curtail, unjustly blaming men of today for the collective hypothetical sins of their forefathers.
Feminism is hysteria.

Prefer the LORD's esteem to the masses', likewise the respect of righteous and honorable people.

On Jordan
[Job, Anne Frank Dutchwoman]:
Feminine emotionality and pride with limited understanding.
Retaliatory.
A puppet, why she loves puppies.
Nosy sniffing around.
Bites the hand that feeds her.
Heathenism. Very sensitive.

...
Tragically targeted and corrupted as the weakest link for having loved Alexander.
Targeted by G via apple,
Targeted by K via M and Job.

Plato's Allegory of the Cave:
Having spent four millennia in rebellious delusion, does J leave?
Does living pinata Alexander accept the delusion of Christianity? No.

Most women are not Dutch, they are taught they ought to be. Neither are most men.

Finding truth and righteous judgement is like a jigsaw puzzle trial; no one has all the pieces.

Torture is self defeating.
Borg trade humanity for power.

[NO DRAGOONING]

Polygamy: permission vs need. Need hard to define: physical, cultural, emotional, etc.
Even with need, require permission.
Permission without need acceptable. Honest need increases likelihood of permission, also Biblically
necessity is blessed.

LORD:

"Polygamy splinters families":
ILLEGALISE MATRIMONY/Romanists
PLAYMATE PERMISSION/MISPRISON

...
FALSENESS IMMORALITY
asymmetry signifies
impales profeminists
impalement gorilla
Romanism pitiless
legislate Islamism/Romanism

...
mineralise polygamist/lamppost/loyalist
IMMOLATE PAINLESSLY/signalises/silliness/sinlessly

[Playmates acceptable but Messianic distraction. N Haute.]

...
LORD [shouting]:
"How many holes? Four is excess, choose three."

...
schoolmistress whorehouse
Yahweh schoolmistress CONFEREES/HONOUREES
Yahweh Christ lecherousness/homelessness
[Jordan is Kahlan of SOT]
housemother confessor Yahweh
Mother Confessor Ulises Yahweh

...
Harcourt foolishness/selfishness/sexlessness/fleeciness/fleshiness/holiness
Harcourt Solomon excesses/fisheyes
Yasmine Chou wrestler
Messiah wrestler henhouse
Messiah correct henhouse
Messiah Ulysses throne/crown
wrestler succession

...
CONSORT (4644) MESSIAH schoolhouse/ESCHEWER/horseshoe/refocuses
Consort Messiah Euler eschews
CONSORT Yahweh schoolhouse/horseshoes/CRIMELESS/excelsior/Fleischer
consort Yahweh Flis horseshoes
consort Yahweh Fleisher
consort EXCELSIOR amuses [Nathaniel Haute IHES]

...
WHOREHOUSE ECONOMETRICS/CHRISTMASSES [BRAINLESS]
fornicator schoolhouse
Christmas cheerfulness
archenemies osteoscleroses
HENHOUSE FLIS ARMREST COCO [AVOID]

(Genesis 6:7)

"I will blot out man whom I have created from the face of the land,":
DICHLORODIFLUOROMETHANE EMBLEMATICAL HEATWAVE

...
"from man to animals to creeping things and to birds of the sky;":
SYNGENESIOTRANSPLANTATION COMMEMORATOR DIGITS/THIGH
commemorator transplplantation identifying

...
"for I am sorry that I have made them.":
father earthmover smith
terraformed mayhem

(Genesis 6:14)

"Make for yourself an ark of gopher wood":
foreknowledge paramour

(Genesis 6:17)

"And behold, I, even I am bringing the flood of water upon the earth":
trinitrotoluene bioenvironmental godhead

...
"to destroy all flesh in which is the breath of life, from under heaven;":
dichlorodifluoromethane reversibleness Yahweh

...
dichlorodifluoromethane detestableness irrelevant/Helvetian/LINEARITY/relative

...
DICHLORODIFLUOROMETHANE VERIFIABLENESS SWEETHEART

...
dichlorodifluoromethane anniversaries twelfthes
[Feb. 12; or 2/12]

...
dichlorodifluoromethane heavyhearted Listerine/lifeline

...
dichlorodifluoromethane eyewitness (4494) invertebrates [octopus ... Titanic]
dichlorodifluoromethane eyewitnesses Albert/heartbeat/Leviathan

...
"everything that is on the earth shall perish."
representativeness airtight
REPRESENTATIVE GIANTS LITERAL
["Nephilim" or, giants (Genesis 6:4);
"Nephilim giants": PHILISTINE]

[NO BLOOD]

(Genesis 6:18)

"But I will establish My covenant with you; and you shall enter the ark-":
tetrahydrocannabinol substitution alleluia
tetrahydrocannabinol bolshevist unhealthiest [blood diseases]
tetrahydrocannabinol steakhouse illuminative/unhealthiest/villainies
blameworthiness authenticate Nathaniel Dorothy Lilly
blameworthiness relativistic Nathanael buttonholed

...
"you and your sons and your wife, and your sons' wives with you."
tyrannosaurus wondrousness divine
tyrannosaurus dinosaur Odyssey wifeness
FOREORDAIN DARWIN assiduousness/studiousness/shadowiness/UNSOUNDNESS/unsustained/astonishes/dishonesty/
odious/unassisted

[Film "Evan Almighty" 2007 BCE]

(Genesis 6:19)

"And of every living thing of all flesh, you shall bring two of every kind into the ark":
FOREORDAINED TRINITROTOLUENE tele visionally/WASHINGTONIANS/globalisation

...
"to keep them alive with you; they shall be male and female."
televisional whaleboat mayhemmed
EVOLUTION TIMESTAMPED
evolution alphabetised/baptismal/battlefield/TIMESTAMPED/blasphemed/deathlied/defeasible/deflatable/
detestable/mistakable/TIMETABLE

[Sodom ... sodomy = forced entry]

"Where are the men who came to you tonight? Bring them out to us that we may have relations with them." (Genesis 19:5)

...
"So they pressed hard against Lot and came near to break the door." (Genesis 19:9)

[Red Tide]

(Exodus 7:20-21)

"all the water that was in the Nile was turned to blood. And the fish that were in the Nile died, and the Nile became foul"

...
"Nile was turned to blood":
Red Tide Wollaston [shore MA]/Lawson [J, Mt. Fuji]

[No death penalty, notably lesbianism unforbidden; very small minority naturally gay men.]

...

(Leviticus 18:22)

"You shall not lie with a male as one lies with a female; it is an abomination."
UNWHOLESOMENESS EMOTIONAL FEMINISATION WHITEHALL LABILITY

[No rounding]

(Leviticus 19:27)

"You shall not round off the side growth of your heads, nor harm the edges of your beard."

...

[DHEA neurosteroid;
no rounding, or dulling the mind by gambling or fuzzy logic, analogic.
NO BUZZ CUTS.]

"You shall not round off the side growth of your heads":
dehydroisoandrosterone (DHEA) thoughtfully/tautologous/August
wrongheadedness illustrator/trustful/truthful/tutorial/authority/dutiful/faithful/SHORTHAIR
wrongheadedness shorthair lotto

...

"nor harm the edges of your beard":
heterogeneous
homogeneous barehead
guarantee reformer
head rounder geometry abhor
erroneous geometry

[Kay ... Cane]

(Numbers 17:8)

"the rod of Aaron for the house of Levi had sprouted and put forth buds and produced blossoms, and it bore ripe almonds."

...

"sprouted and put forth buds and produced blossoms":
supernaturalness octopus fourths

String TOE ... shoelaces, base; foundations of physics;

"Adoni-bezek": Aeneid Ko

"And Adoni-bezek said, 'Seventy kings with their thumbs and their big toes cut off used to gather up scraps under my table; as I have done, so God has repaid me.'" (Judges 7:1)

[Sabbath]

(Nehemiah 13:19)

"just as it grew dark": dusk writer

(Psalm 2:2)

"The kings of the earth take their stand,
And the rulers take counsel together"

...

[Messiah]

"Against the LORD and against His Anointed":
INTERNATIONALISATION GANESHA
INTEGRATIONISTS DANDELION/GOLIATH/NATHANIEL
shithead (6888) niggardliness/orientalising/signalisation
Thessalonian antagonising/denigration/indentation/ghettoising

[is enthroned]

(Psalms 2:4)

"He who sits in the heavens laughs":
weightlessness Utahan/avian
Thessalonian highest/sweetie/thieves/eight/thigh/Hugh
elevation highness haute
thigh heathenishness/heavenliness/Thessalonian/unessential/elevation/Leviathan

...

Einstein evaluates/gatehouse/goulashes/assholes/ovulates/sausages
Einstein steal hogwash
Einstein Augst asshole

...

Utahan weightlessness/holinesses/highnesses/slingshot/eighteen/lionesses/evilness
Leviathan henhouses
EIGHTEEN astonishes/evaluation/Leviathan/salvation/unholiest/ASSASSIN

(Psalm 7:2)

"Lest he tear my soul like a lion":
Thessaloniki emulator

(Psalm 10:16)
"The LORD is King forever and ever": elevation sovereign Fred

[APPLE]
(Psalm 17:8)
"Keep me as the apple of the eye":
polymath safekeep/tepes
tepes meatloaf/playmate/polymath/healthy/helmet/alpha
...
"Hide me in the shadow of Thy wings":
shithead demotion
astonishment deified
MESSIAE GENIOHYOID [voice]
MESSIAH defending/deifying/identify/IDENTITY
Messiah Newton hogtied/thighed
Messiah thigh indented/honeyed
Hin Ting meadowsweet/shadowiest/defeatism/disesteem/shithead/sodomites/Mafiosos/weediest/yahwist [no
identity]
YAHWEH (2922) DIMWITTEDNESS/SEMITENDINOSI [thigh]
YAHWEH THOMSON IDENTIFIES
Samson identified/eighteen/widowing

[MIT Course 18 Mathematics;
Bulls' Jordan, Pippen, Rodman.]
(Psalm 18:13)
"And the Most High uttered His voice":
GEOMETER EDUCATIONIST/enthusiastic/vindicated/acidities/shithead
sovereign domesticated/miseducated/Medicaid/shithead
sovereign diadem Scottie/ethic/octet/scout/stoic
EIGHTEEN CHRIST AUTOMOTIVE
[alignment validates structure]
eighteen Christ diadem hotshot
eighteen doctorate smith
EIGHTEEN MITHRIDATES OCTO
...
Mithridates detective/touchstone/devoutest/genocides/hothouse/covetous/doghouse/eugenics/genetics/
geodesic/viscount/Chinese/devious/heinous/shogun
Virginia Chou modestest/detestest/esteemed/demotes
Virginia scheme hothouse
Virginia custodee demotes
Travis (2885) homogenistic/documentated/instituted/seducement/MEDICINES/comedies/custodee/demented/demonise/
emotions/misguide/outshone/demigod/demotes
...
HENHOUSE TRAGICOMEDIES/democratised/MEDIOCRITIES/demotivates/DISTRACTIVE/Archimedes/categories/cigarettes/
DISCHARGED/travesties/veracities/victimised/acidities
HENHOUSE DISCHARGE IDIOT

(Psalm 22)
[Jesus, permuted elsewhere]

(Psalm 27:1)
"The LORD is my light and my salvation;
Whom shall I fear?":
MARSHALL MATHERS IDENTIFYING HOLLYWOOD
...
"The LORD is my light and my salvation":
lamentation (2227) David syllogism
David slingshot (2282) immortal Hayley [comet]
dandelion (2229) alligator smith
...
"Whom shall I fear?": Marshall
...
"The LORD is my light and my salvation":
David mistranslation/immortalises/lamentation/Thessalonian
Thessalonian immortality/volatility/almighty/Vladimir/digital/goliath/David
immolation antislavery/highlander/
Siddhartha/Alisander/Leviathan/Streisand
David mineral mythologist/slingshot
Alisander Thomson almighty/digital

Streisand motivational

[logician]

(Psalms 29:5)

"The voice of the LORD breaks the cedars;":

elevate Frederick chessboard/doctorate

...

"Yes, the LORD breaks in pieces the cedars of Lebanon.":

tetrahydrocannabinol beekeeper/Fleischer/lordship/possessed

TETRAHYDROCANNABINOL POSSESSED FLEECE

FLEISCHER SLEEPYHEAD RECONDENSATION/noncarbonated/centenarian/cornerstone/restoration/scatterbrain/
transcendent/coronation

beekeeper crystallisation (2233) recondenses/horseshoed

recrystallisation recondenses hophead

(Psalm 29:10)

"The LORD sat as King at the flood":

tortoiseshell/folksinger/ethnologist/lionhearted/theologian/Alessandro/dishonored/floodlight/gladiator/
lordliness/Siddhartha/Aleksandr

Alessandro eightfold/Alfie

ALEKSANDR FLOODLIGHTS/TATTOOIST/SHITHEAD

ALEKSANDR FLIS TATTOOED/death/hated/goat/toad

Siddhartha footnote/gentlest/skeleton

shithead godforsaken/Aleksandr/allegator/footnoted/forgotten/tornadoes

TORNADO GOLDFISH

...

"Yes the LORD sits as King forever":

foresightedness/restorativeness/retrogression/revelationist/sovereign/transgressor/relativeness/
Thessaloniki

...

foresightedness kristal/krystal

transgressor shoveled/deifies

Thessaloniki destroyer/retrogress/restorer

relativeness hogtied/sorority

FLIS RESTORATIVENESS

FLIS SOVEREIGN RESTORES

ODYSSEAN retrogressive/firelighter/(ERRORLESS KITTIE)

[Weed, dragon, dandelion, Nathaniel]

(Psalms 37:1-2)

"Do not fret because of evildoers,

Be not envious toward wrongdoers.

For they will wither quickly like the grass,

And fade like the green herb."

...

"Do not fret because of evildoers,

Be not envious toward wrongdoers.":

countersignature interrelatedness observed

countersignature worldbeater offensiveness

Dandelion Guinevere costotransverse [rib joint] beetroot/foreswore

DANDELION OSTEORADIONECROSES EVERGREEN WOODRUFF

["Oldboy", CK amputee no limbs]

/tortuous/odorous

...

"Be not envious toward wrongdoers.":

WEED OBSERVATION OUTDOORS

RN

weed dragon brownstones/subversion/serotonin

weed Bostonian rounder

weed servant sorrowing/birdsong

...

"For they will wither quickly like the grass,

And fade like the green herb.":

Nathaniel diethylstilbestrol Friedrich

Yahweh referee [estrogen agonist]

...

"And fade like the green herb.":

Nathaniel refereed

(Psalm 37:17)

"But the LORD sustains the righteous."

[Jordan, Georgia]

(Psalms 37:32)

"The wicked spies upon the righteous,
And seeks to kill him."

[Trickle down economics]

"He who oppresses the poor to make much for himself
Or who gives to the rich, will only come to poverty." (Proverbs 22:16)

[Rounders 1998 Les]

"Lest you learn his ways,
And find a snare for yourself.
Do not be among those who give pledges,
Among those who become sureties for debts." (Proverbs 22:25-26)

"Do not move the ancient boundary
Which your fathers have set." (Proverbs 22:28)

"Have you found honey? Eat only what you need,
Lest you have it in excess and vomit it." (Proverbs 25:16)

(Proverbs 28:5)

"Evil men do not understand justice":
UNCONSTITUTIONAL (222) REDEEMED
Jerusalem innocentest/nonunionist
Constitutional unredeemed/revenues
constitution devalue nerd

...

"But those who seek the LORD understand all things":
knowledgeableness lionhearted Tudor/Russ/truth

(Proverbs 30:4)

"What is His name or His son's name?
Surely you know!":

TYRANNOSAURUS YAHWEH SOLOMON SIKHISMS

Tyrannosaurus Messiah Solomon Keynes

Yahweh emanation Solomon

Yahweh Messiah Solomon Antoninus

Messiah emanation Ulysses

Messiah Thessalonian workhorse

Messiah Isaiah enthrones Solomon/Kowloon/Romulus

womaniser Solomon swinishness/unawareness/renaissant/Ukrainian/Athenian/Austrian/Eurasian/Russian/Yankee

WOMANISER SOLOMON UNAWARE NESSY

HONEYMOON ULYSSES (5666) AIRWORTHINESS

...

Tyrannosaurus wholesomeness/homelessness/lonesomeness/awesomeness/immenseness/monkishness/winsomeness/
Holinesses

TYRANNOSAURUS HOMELESSNESS HANOI [N]

(Proverbs 30:19)

"And the way of a man with a maid.":
Yahweh dominant

(Proverbs 31:10)

"For her worth is far above jewels.":
elevator horseshoe

Job elevates warrior/Aries

"I know that everything God does will remain forever; there is nothing to add to it and there is nothing
to take from it" (Ecclesiastes 3:14)

[... Polygamy]

"If he takes to himself another woman, he may not reduce her food, her clothing, or her conjugal
rights." (Exodus 21:10)

"food clothing conjugal rights":
CONSORT FLOODLIGHTING/JUDICATION

[Beast, analyst]
"there is no advantage for man over beast, for all is vanity."
(Ecclesiastes 3:19)

...
"all is vanity": analyst

[Like Jesus]
"for they do not know they are doing evil" (Ecclesiastes 5:1)

[Peregrin Took]
"Do not be hasty in word or impulsive in thought to bring up a matter in the presence of God."
(Ecclesiastes 5:2)

[Pointless economic growth]
"When good things increase, those who consume them increase. So what is the advantage to their owners except to look on?"
(Ecclesiastes 5:11)

[Buddha, ... Tokugawa]
"Patience of spirit is better than haughtiness of spirit."
(Ecclesiastes 7:8)

[Tom Riddle of Harry Potter]
"Divide your portion to seven, or even to eight, for you do not know what misfortune may occur on the earth." (Ecclesiastes 11:2)

[Name of the Wind, Kingkiller Chronicle]
"Just as you do not know the path of the wind" (Ecclesiastes 11:5)

[Genesis Adam]
"then the dust will return to the earth as it was, and the spirit will return to God who gave it." (Ecclesiastes 12:7)

[Cloudcroft Mountain Hostel,
German owned,
Bought NASB for \$2,
Near Alamogordo White Sands,
Einstein's Trinity test site near
El Paso, attempting death of God]
(Solomon 2:14)
"In the secret place of the steep pathway":
astrophysical hatchet/heathen/Cathee

(Solomon 2:16)
"My beloved is mine, and I am his":
Dandelion misbehaves/Messiah

[ROUNDERS]
(Solomon 3:3)
"The watchmen who make the rounds in the city found me":
UNDERESTIMATION DUTCHWOMEN YAHWEH
/watchmen/Matthew/Yankee

(Solomon 3:6)
"Perfumed with myrrh and frankincense":
archenemy Frank Midwestern/undermines/Demetrius/feminised/fishermen/triumphes/Einstein/mutineer
archenemy Frank fishermen putrid

(Solomon 4:1)
"Your hair is like a flock of goats.":
hilarious footlocker
Harcourt alkalise yogi

(Solomon 6:9)
"But my dove, my perfect one, is unique":
omnipotence Demetrius
QUEEN DIVORCE SUBOPTIMUM
QUEEN DIVORCEMENT impetuous/SYMBIOTE
Queen vespertine tomboy
queen redemption combustive/Muscovite/symbiote

(Solomon 6:11)

"To see whether the vine has budded":
sweetheart beethoven/devotee

(Solomon 7:4)

"Your nose is like the tower of Lebanon":
Euler Frank sweetie Shinto/snooty

(Solomon 7:5)

"Your head crowns you like Carmel":
acidulous homeworkeer

[BE CAREFUL WITH CONSORTS]

(Solomon 8:5-7)

"There she was in labor and gave you birth.":
whitehorse Transylvania Deborah/Barbee
retrogradation Evelina Yahweh
evilness interrogatory
RETROGRESSIVE NATHANIEL

...
"Put me like a seal over your heart":
heteroerotism leapyear/plural

...
"Like a seal on your arm":
Salomon Euler

...
"For love is as strong as death":
EVERLASTING TORAH

...
"Jealousy is as severe as Sheol" (2220):
Israel assessees
Savior Ulysses asshole/Lhasa

...
"Its flashes are flashes of fire"
Israel assessorial

...
"The very flame of the LORD":
elevatory Homer

...
"Many waters cannot quench love":
enthronement Casanova

...
"Nor will rivers overflow it":
retroversion

...
"If a man were to give all the riches of his house for love":
overrighteous affirmativeness

...
"It would be utterly despised.":
prostitute belle
Lordliest deputised/weediest

(Isaiah 2:4)

"And He will judge between the nations,":
Jedediah (4404) eighteen
Agust obediencial/dandelion/halloween/Newtonian/whitehall
Aeneid unenlightened/unhealthiest/deathliest

...
"And will render decisions for many peoples;":
semiprofessional ordinance/recrowned

...
"And they will hammer their swords into plowshares,":
interrelationship (5007) shareholders shalom
"and their spears into pruning hooks.":
Shapiro kindergartens

...
"National will not lift up sword against nation,":
institutionalisation nondollar

...

"And never again will they learn war."
elevating yielder Hanna
Nevadian interregnal/eighteen
Nathaniel (2622) revealingly

(Isaiah 3:12)
"And women rule over them":
NETHERLANDER meow/moo/woe

...
dethrone manoeuvre/Emmanuel/unmoral/unravel
Emanuel overthrown/dethroner/Dorothee/honored

"For seven women will take hold of one man in that day" (Isaiah 4:1)

[Brandon Stark]
"Branch of the LORD" (Isaiah 4:2)

(Isaiah 5:26)
"He will also lift up a standard to the distant nation":
Russia antinationalist

(Isaiah 5:27)
"No one in it is weary or stumbles":
Russians wintertime
Russia (3131) ennoblement

(Isaiah 6:3)
"Holy, Holy, Holy, is the LORD of hosts":
footstool Odyssey/soldier/oiler/doll
tortoise floss/doll
Detroit floss/solo
Shiloh toothless

(Isaiah 7:7)
"It shall not stand nor shall it come to pass."
Christmas Thessalonian Apollo

(Isaiah 7:14)
"Behold a virgin will be with child":
challenger Lilith
...
"Behold a virgin will be with child and bear a son":
charlatanerie dandelion/idealising/villainies/evildoing
denicotinising (2022) worldview/heralded/Deborah/Barbie
recondensation Hildegard
worldbeater cannibalising/Scandinavian/cannabidiol/dandelion

...
"and she will call His name Immanuel":
demasculinise Helain
MUHAMMAD cleanliness/achilleine/Hellenise/sinicise/cleanse/Lilian
Michael (2888) maidenliness/unmanliness/Hellenisms
MESSIAH ALLELUIA MACHINE/Delilah

[Israel's ruin foreordained]
"For before the boy will know enough to refuse evil and choose good, the land whose two kings you dread
will be forsaken."
(Isaiah 7:16)

"In that day the Lord will shave with a razor" (Isaiah 7:20)

(Isaiah 9:6)
"And His name will be called Wonderful Counselor, Mighty God,
Eternal Father, Prince of Peace."

...
"Wonderful Counselor, Mighty God":
Deuteronomy lording ghoul
Deuteronomy Flis groundhog
rounder gynecologist/floodlights/honeylocust/Dutchwomen
foulmouthed goronised/recrowning/wrongdoing
Fleurdelis groundhog

Schrodinger monologue
homogeniser odourful/wrongful
Clementius wolfhound/godhood
interregnum Hollywood/godhood/Osgood/cloud/ghoul

...
"Eternal Father, Prince of Peace."
Alpha Creator pierce
Alpha potter caffeine
lantern patriarch/prophetic
fornicate repenter
CATHARTIC PENELOPE
Nathaniel reporter
chaotic fraternal/Lateran
falconer apprentice

(Isaiah 11:2)
"And the Spirit of the LORD will rest on Him":
shithead (7677)
impersonator (3533) identifies/Nefertiti
impersonator dethroned (111) filii
impersonator titleholder flis

...
foreordainment worshiped Lilith
foreordainment Detroit Lilith
DETROIT METROPOLITAN FINISHER
WHITEHORSE haloperidol/iliofemoral/Mithridates/pollinator/omnipotent/dandelion
whitehorse haloperidol Finn
whitehorse omnipotent Allistir/diarist
whitehorse dandelion shoplift
Mithridates friendship/penfriends/trillions
Mithridates Einstein follow
pinewood motherliness Filial/Harri/Alfi
pinewood mother Israelitish/thriftiness/Streisand/shithead/Allister
Streisand promotion freewill
Streisand motherhood litter
lifeline airworthiness lord

(Isaiah 11:10)
"root of Jesse":
jester, JOSEF [ancestral]

[Anagrams are an ANALOGY here, verse in direct reference to Babylon]
[Worm Rounders 1998]
(Isaiah 14:11-12)
" 'And worms are your covering.'
How you have fallen from heaven,
O star of the morning, son of the dawn!"

...
"How you have fallen from heaven" (222):
Yahweh menorah
Yahweh femoral/envenom
Yahweh femor (420) unleaven
Emanuel Helen hooray
Evaleen Romanov
Reamonn yellow

...
"O star of the morning, son of the dawn!":
foreordainment Agosto

...
(Isaiah 14:14)
"I will make myself like the Most High":
Elohim Almighty flesh/(Smith Flis)

[Philadelphia Constitutional Convention]
(Isaiah 18:2,7)
"A powerful and oppressive nation, Whose land the rivers divide":
overapprehensiveness antirevolutionaries Adolph
representativeness Philadelphia foreordain
PHILADELPHIA REPRESENTATIVES ENDORADIOSONDE RUINS
[spy monitor implants]

FOREORDINATION THESSALONIAN DAVID DESPISE

...
"a powerful and oppressive nation":
federal supervision/universitas/renaissant/supernova/Antoninus
FEDERAL SENATORS OPINION
PRESIDENT SLOVENIAN PROOF
PRESIDENT SAVIOR NAPOLEON
PRESIDENT SUPERNOVA (222) FIONA/Alfi/fool ... [G, Robinette]
president peninsular/propulsion/annapolis/Slovenian/supernova/universal
universitas (1222) nonfederal/preplanned

...
"Whose land the rivers divide":
DAVID EISENHOWER [US president]
WHITEHORSE ENSLAVED whitehorse vernalised [semen?]/disdained/invalided/sidelined/slandered/Disraeli/
divine/enslaved/saddened/sardined/adviser/David/evasive/reviled/savvied/servile/snailed/Aeneid
whitehorse David delivers/silvered
SWINEHERD DERIVATIVES [N]/ADVERTISED/deviltries/evildoer/varieties/idealist
Aeneid evildoer/shrewdest
REVELATION WISHERS [WWIII, nuclear apocalypse]

(Isaiah 18:3)
"And as soon as the trumpet is blown, you will hear it."
automobile transportational newlyweds
mineralisation Alessandro hotshot

(Isaiah 19:20)
"Savior and a Champion":
casanova hairpin/Nimrod
scorpion avian/Adam
Marianna hasid/acid
Chaos primadonna

(Isaiah 22:20)
"My servant Eliakim the son of Hilkiah":
Metatarsal feminine/monkeyish/keyhole
Metatarsal keyhole Finnish
Thessalonian elevatory

...
"Eliakim the son of Hilkiah":
meatloaf (253) Helsinki/Shiloh
lifeline Isaiah/Taiko/smith
alkalinise thief

...
"Eliakim": Mikael

(Isaiah 22:22)
"Then I will set the key of the house of David on his shoulder,
When he opens no one will shut,
When he shuts no one will open."

[Oldboy movie for Lot's daughters,
K 'Ol Nick, Machiavelli]

(Isaiah 22:25)
"The peg driven in a firm place will give way":
Machiavellianly interviewed/definitive/identifier/reverified/EVERGREEN/PEREGRINE/prevented
grandmaternal chili
charlatanerie devilling/vilifying
challenging reverified
PEREGRINATING MACHIAVELLI

[host of heaven]
(Isaiah 24:22)
"And will be confined in prison":
acidifier bloodline/pinewood/poseidon

(Isaiah 25:7)
"Even the veil which is stretched over all nations":
Christianisation wretchedest/Chesterton/cleverest
Christianisation cleverest Hellen
Christianities covenant devotees

INTERNATIONAL COLLECTIVIST WEEDS
CATHOLICISATION WESTERNISED
CHRISTIANITIES OCTAHEDRON
Orientalisation wretchedness/westernised

...
transcendentalist cholesterol/WHITEHORSE/CHRIST
recondensation ethicalities/Israelitish/sweetheart/Christal/wealthess

(Isaiah 25:8)
"He will swallow up death for all time":
heliotherapies fallout/Adam
Mithridates helpful/hopeful
laureateship floodlit
FLEURDELIS WHITEHALL
ALLELUIA HALOPERIDOL/WHITEHORSE
Alpha iliofemoral/fleurdelis

(Isaiah 27:1)
"And He will kill the dragon who lives in the sea.":
handwritten shielding (887) hellhole
gasoline invalidates weedkiller/dethrone
gasoline revelationist headlined
Washingtonians (2122) weedkiller
Washingtonian evildoer Whitehall

...
Lordliness elevation diligent
Thessalonian elevated whirlwind
Thessalonian Revelation killed
Sovereign alkalinisation heeded

(Isaiah 49:6)
"I will also make You a light of the nations":
Thessalonian haematology/kilowattage/almightily/alleluia/meatloaf
Tokugawa infinitesimally/astonishment/elimination/annihilates

(Isaiah 49:7)
"To the despised One,
To the One abhorred by the nation":
Robinette hardhandedness/hardheadedness/hotheadedness

...
"To the One abhorred by the nation":
Robinette bayoneted ["ramrod"]/abandonee/beetroot/betatron/betrayed/dethrone
betrayed Antoinette
BETATRON BETATRON HONEYED

(Isaiah 52:14)
"So His appearance was marred more than any man":
recommendation (1444) empress Hanna
recondensation seraph/Yasmeen

[Jesus false Messiah]
(Isaiah 53:10)
"If He would render Himself as a guilt offering":
DEMINERALISATION FLEURDELIS

(Isaiah 53:12)
"Because He poured out Himself to death":
SHITHEAD (8806) OCTOPUS ALBERT
shithead Deborah completest
Hephaestus Albert touched
Prometheus autodidact
Themistocles Deborah defeat

(Isaiah 54:1)
"Shout for joy, O barren one, you who have borne no child":
schoolfriend overthrower/Beethoven/Johnathan/betrayer/honorary
schoolfriend beethoven honorary
Jordan celebration (1110) brownnoser
Jordan Nosanchu overthrower/interferer/irreverent/unbeliever/unworthier/Beethoven/evolution/wolverine/
Berliner/honouree

Jordan Berliner Hohenstaufen ?

...

Johnathan overincredulous/hydrofluoric/irreverence/nonbeliever/odouriferous/undefensible

(Isaiah 54:2)

"Break forth into joyful shouting and cry aloud, you who have not travailed":

Jordan Nosanchuk unforgettable retaliatory/whitehall

Jordan Nosanchuk unforgettable retaliator adulthood/ladyhood/youthful/validity

Jordan Nosanchuk unforgettable Whitehall auditory

(Isaiah 54:5)

"For your husband is your Maker":

dinosaur yearbook

Afrikaner [Dutch] odorous/bosoms/sodomy

BIRDHOUSE FRANK

(Isaiah 54:16)

"Behold, I Myself have created the smith who blows the fire of coals":

recrystallise meatloaf (3833) Themistocles[N]/lobotomised

(Isaiah 54:16)

"And I have created the destroyer to ruin.":

Hades death reintroduction/nicotinate

Octahedron Aeneid servitude

nicotinate (2223) overseer

(Isaiah 59:6)

"Their webs will not become clothing":

misintelligence blowtorch

INTELLIGENCE HOMOEROTIC

electioneering oilcloth/Cosimo/Moscow

Monticello eighteen/Heisenberg/whitehorse

whitehorse (1444) intelligent/noneligible

(Isaiah 63:4)

"And My year of redemption has come":

foreordainment poached

(Isaiah 65:25)

"dust shall be the serpent's food":

tablespoonful dessert

(Jeremiah 6:20)

"For what purpose does frankincense come to Me from Sheba":

foreordainment treacherousness embosom cheap/poach

...

"And the sweet cane from a distant land?"

(Jeremiah 12:7-8)

"I have forsaken My house,

I have abandoned My inheritance;

I have given the beloved of My soul Into the hand of her enemies.

My inheritance has become to Me

Like a lion in the forest;

She has roared against Me;

Therefore I have come to hate her."

...

"I have forsaken My house":

Savior Yankees

...

"I have abandoned My inheritance":

nicotinamide Aberdeen

vindication Maryanna

...

"I have given the beloved of my soul":

Sheba homogeneity/evildoing/limelight

...

"Into the hand of her enemies.":

Dethronement fashion/Hanoi

enthronement (223) deifies

[See GENESIS 3]

(Jeremiah 12:12-13)

"On all the bare heights in the wilderness
Destroyers have come,
For a sword of the LORD is devouring
From one end of the land even to the other;
There is no peace for anyone.
They have sown wheat and have reaped thorns,
They have strained themselves to no profit.
But be ashamed of your harvest
Because of the fierce anger of the LORD."

...
"For a sword of the lord is devouring":
wrathfulness forgiver
revolutionise godhood

(Jeremiah 12:14)

"Thus says the LORD concerning all My wicked neighbors who strike at the inheritance with which I have
endowed My people Israel, 'Behold I am about to uproot them from their land and will uproot the house of
Judah from among them.' "

[Jeremiah: Jae]

(Jeremiah 20:14)

"Cursed be the day when I was born":
DOWNHEARTEDNESS BARBIE
wretchedness Deborah

[See Job 3:3]

(Jeremiah 20:15)

"Cursed be the man who brought the news
To my father, saying,
'A baby boy has been born to you!'
And made him very happy."

(Jeremiah 23:5)

"And He will reign as king and act wisely":
Crystal alkalinising/singlehanded/Kisanagi

...
Christ alkalinising/Disneyland
CHRIST WELLESLEY INDIANIAN/GINNI
EIGHTEEN NASAL ALKALINISING/SCANDALLING

["Yahweh Tsidkenu":

Yahweh kindest,
shithead key, Ieyasu dent,
weed haunts/stinky/Utahn]

(Jeremiah 23:6)

"The LORD our righteousness":
neurosurgeries/retrogression/righteousness/rigorousness/ghoulishness/gloriousness/outrightness/
resoluteness/thoroughness/togetherness/tortuousness/eighteenth/guesthouses/hideousness/lighthouses/
orderliness/roundhouses/theologist

...
RÉTROGRESSION DUTEOUS/LOTUS

Eighteen holdout
Rounder lighthouse/theologist/thoroughest

(Jeremiah 30:6)

"Ask now, and see,
If a male can give birth.
Why do I see every man,
With his hands on his loins, as a woman in childbirth?"

...
'Ask now, and see,
If a male can give birth.':
America Washington defensive

(Jeremiah 31:22)

"How long will you go here and there,
O faithless daughter?"

For the LORD has created a new thing in the earth -
A woman will encompass a man."

...
"A woman will encompass a man."
nonsensical mamma/momma
NAPOLEONIC NASAL

(Jeremiah 31:27)

"I will sow the house of Israel and the house of Judah with the seed of man and with the seed of beast."

(Jeremiah 31:31)

"when I will make a new covenant with the house of Israel and with the house of Judah":
internationalisation levelheadedness effectuate/automatic/Matthiew

[313, 333, trinity false Messiah]

(Jeremiah 31:33)

"I will put My law within them, and on their heart I will write it":
dethronement MARIJUANA Twitter/Hitler
reinterpretation attitudinal/humiliated/illuminate/WHITEHALL/alleluia/Immanuel
reinterpretation alleluia Lilith
reinterpretation immanuel lilith
reinterpretation whitehall militant
TRINITY INTERPRETATION HUMILIATED/WHITEHALL
PERMUTATIONAL INDETERMINATE LILITH

(Jeremiah 31:33)

"And I will be their God and they shall be My people."
demineralisation Yahweh potbelly/pledged
alphabetisation pledgeholder
YAHWEH LORD GODEL SLEEPYHEAD INIMITABLE

(Jeremiah 33:15)

"I will cause a righteous Branch of David to spring forth":
straightforwardness neuropathological/autobiographical/unapologetical/acidification/glorification/
valedictorian/necrophiliac
acidification unalphabetise ghoul

[Proof Phaeton Testament fragmented, not prophesy]

(Jeremiah 36:28)

"Take again another scroll and write on it all the former words that were on the first scroll which
Jehoiakim the king of Judah burned."

(Jeremiah 37:15)

"they put him [Jeremiah] in jail in the house of Jonathan the scribe"

(Jeremiah 38:7)

"Ebed-melech the Ethiopian, a eunuch, ... heard that they had put Jeremiah into the cistern."

[Modern permutational echoes with identical outcome indicate LORD is responsible; discovered Oct. 8,
2024, one year anniversary of unprovoked attack]

(Jeremiah 47:1)

"That which came as the word of the LORD to Jeremiah the prophet concerning the Philistines, before
Pharaoh conquered Gaza."

(Jeremiah 47:4)

"On account of the day that is coming":
authentication octagon/Thomson/Agosto
authenticating Scotchman/Thomson
condemnation haughty/Toyotas/tattoos/Agosto
denunciation Toyota/tattoos/Agosto/Cathay/Cacao/fagots/Gotham/ghost

...
"To destroy all the Philistines,"
depersonalise hostility

...
"To cut off from Tyre and Sidon
Every ally that is left;":
counteroffensive retaliatory shalom

...
"For the LORD is going to destroy the Philistines,"
HYPERSENSITISING FLOODLIGHTED/foresighted/eightsided

foresightedness spotlighted trinity/Thorin/Triton/honor/holy
friendless spotlighting Detroit history

...
"The remnant of the coastland of Caphtor":
catastrophe octahedon manhole
catastrophe octahedral footmen

[TRUMP immune puppeteered by N]
(Jeremiah 51:34)

"Nebuchadnezzar king of Babylon has devoured me and crushed me":
Nebuchadnezzar Abraham feeblemindedness
Nebuchadnezzar Abraham homogeniser befuddles
DANDELION BARBEE UNDERHANDEDNESS

...
"He has set me down like an empty vessel;":
sleepyhead astonishment/antithesis/weaknesses

...
"He has swallowed me like a monster,":
immoderateness whale
loathsomeness WEEDKILLER/MIKAEL
Aleksandr mesothelioma/whitewashes/WHITEHALL/homeless/Messiah
Alessandro whitehall
MESSIAH ALEKSANDR HELMET

...
"he has filled his stomach with my delicacies":
Themistocles Michael declassify/deacidify/childish
MICHAEL masochistically/atheistically/disassociates/CATHOLICISM/CATHOLICISED/Ecclesiastes/CHAOTICALLY

...
"He has washed me away.":
Yahweh ashamed

[Copied 10/10/24, two days after Oct. 8, 2024 one year anniversary copying and permuting verses of
ancient destruction of Gaza.]

"on the tenth day of the tenth month, that Nebuchadnezzar king of Babylon came" (Jeremiah 52:4)

"And he [Nebuzaradan] burned the house of the LORD, the king's house, and all the houses of Jerusalem;
even every large house he burned with fire." (Jeremiah 52:13)

[Potholder, weed]
"And they also took away the pots" (Jeremiah 52:18)

[Dates 12/25 Xmas]
"in the twelfth month, on the twenty-fifth of the month, that Evil-merodach king of Babylon, in the first
year of his reign, showed favor to Jehoiachin king of Judah and brought him out of prison." (Jeremiah
52:31)

(Lamentations 1:18)
"For I have rebelled against His command":
Machiavelli foreordainment
Machiavellianism dethrones
Machiavellian homogeniser breast
reverification Magdalene

(Lamentations 1:22)
"And deal with them as Thou hast dealt with me":
hotheadedness humiliated

[Noah's covenant]
(Lamentations 2:4)
"He has bent his bow like an enemy": Babylonian smith

(Lamentations 4:10)
"The hands of compassionate women":
astonishment shamefaced

...
"Boiled their own children;
They became food for them":
foreordainment crocodile Bethlehem
dandelion homoerotic Bethlehem
recommendation Frederick Hollywood/wifehood

reconciliation motherhood Demetre

...

"Because of the destruction of the daughter of my people.":

Dorothee psychopharmacologies/psychotherapeutical/chemotherapeutics/neuropathologist/neuropsychologist/
psychopathologist

[Edom is in modern Jordan,

south east of Dead Sea;

"Job and Jeremiah": Jordan Jae]

(Lamentations 4:21)

"Rejoice and be glad, O daughter of Edom,

Who dwells in the land of Uz":

CONGRATULATION HOMOGENISER JEZEBEL

congratulation alleluia defender/Ebenezer/freedom/redeemed

congratulation Alamogordo blindfolded

...

"But the cup will come around to you as well":

electrocution blasphemy

polymath celebrates

(Lamentations 5:16)

"The crown has fallen from our head":

Netherlander washroom

[Ezekiel bread]

(Ezekiel 4:12)

"And you shall eat it as a barley cake, having baked it in their sight over human dung."

[2/3 of way through Bible]

(Ezekiel 5:12)

"One third of you will die by plague or be consumed by famine among you, one third will fall by the sword
around you, and one third I will scatter to every wind, and I will unsheathe a sword behind them."

(Ezekiel 5:17)

"I, the LORD, have spoken.":

evildoers Phaethon

(Ezekiel 7:2)

"An end! The end is coming on the four corners of the land.":

trinitrotoluene hardhandedness offence

underhandedness necromancer footnoting

[Numbers 17:8, rod of Aaron]

(Ezekiel 7:10)

"Your doom has gone forth; the rod has budded, arrogance has blossomed."

...

"the rod has budded, arrogance has blossomed":

treacherousness (1888) Alamogordo

(Ezekiel 8:17)

"they are putting the twig to their nose": prostitution eighteen

[See Psalm 37:17, save righteous]

(Ezekiel 9:4)

"put a mask on the forehead of the men who sigh and groan over all the abominations which are being
committed in its midst."

(Ezekiel 9:11)

"man clothed in linen":

Michael (222)

[Whitehall ... Michael]

"So I shall tear down the wall which you plastered over with whitewash" (Ezekiel 13:14)

[Context idols in heart, foreshadowing]

(Ezekiel 14:21)

"to cut off man and beast from it!"

[GOD MOST HIGH,

in the time of Abraham]

(Ezekiel 16:49-50)

"Behold, this was the guilt of your sister Sodom: she and her daughters had arrogance ... Therefore I removed them when I saw it."

...

'Behold, this was the guilt of your sister Sodom: she and her daughters had arrogance':
GOD MOST HIGH straightforwardness recrystallises (hardhanded beta)/dethroned
GOD MOST HIGH countersignature authoriser wholeheartedly/(worldbeater flesh)

[Bird, dinosaur]

"A great eagle with great wings, long pinions and a full plumage of many colors, came to Lebanon and took away the top of the cedar."

(Ezekiel 17:3)

...

"Behold, the king of Babylon came to Jerusalem, took its king and princes, and brought them to him in Babylon." (Ezekiel 17:12)

(Ezekiel 18:4)

"Behold, all souls are Mine":
Alessandro Elohim

...

"the soul of the father as well as the soul of the son is Mine. The soul who sins will die."

(Ezekiel 20:33)

"I shall be king over you.":
vaingloriously bee

[The Negev is a desert.]

(Ezekiel 20:46-48)

"prophecy against the forest land of the Negev ... 'Behold, I am about to kindle a fire in you ... And all flesh will see that I, the LORD, have kindled it; it shall not be quenched.'"

"therefore strike your thigh" (Ezekiel 21:12)

(Ezekiel 21:27)

"Until He comes whose right it is, and I shall give it to Him.":
Christ smith Godel almightiness elevation
Christ lighthouse Almightiness elevation

[SMITH 22;

A modern example of immolation is Thich Quang Duc vs Catholics.]

...

(Ezekiel 22:22)

"As silver is melted in the furnace, so you will be melted in the midst of it; and you will know that I, the LORD, have poured out My wrath on you."

[Lion of Judah]

(Ezekiel 22:25)

"There is a conspiracy of her prophets in her midst, like a roaring lion tearing the prey. They have devoured lives"

...

"like a roaring lion tearing the prey":

Nathaniel Peregrine (333) Trilogy/Troika

PEREGRINE HIN TING KO ARIEL

PEREGRINE irrationality/antirational/annihilator/integration/

TRINITARIAN

peregrination halogenate/integrally

peregrinate alligator/Nathaniel

...

"They have devoured lives":

DEVIL DEVOTEES

[BITCHES]

(Ezekiel 22:27-28)

"Her princes within her are like wolves tearing the prey, by shedding blood and destroying lives in order to get dishonest gain.

And her prophets have smeared whitewash for them, seeing false visions and divining lies for them"

[LORD is merciful]

"And I searched for a man among them who should build up the wall and stand in the gap before Me for the land that I should not destroy it; but I found no one." (Ezekiel 22:30)

"Put on the pot ... the thigh ... Make it boil vigorously" (Ezekiel 24:3-5)

(Ezekiel 28:13-16)

"You were in Eden, the garden of God"

...

"You were the anointed cherub who covers":

NEWTON WEED CORROBORATIVE/TREACHEROUS

"And I placed you there.

You were on the holy mountain of God;

You walked in the midst of the stones of fire."

...

"And I have destroyed you, O covering cherub"

...

"covering cherub": Cohen vice

"Thus says the Lord GOD to these bones, 'Behold, I will cause breath to enter you that you may come to life.' " (Ezekiel 37:5)

"Thus says the Lord GOD, 'Behold, I will take the stick of Joseph, which is in the hand of Ephraim, and the tribes of Israel, his companions; and I will put them with it, with the stick of Judah, and make them one stick, and they will be one in My hand.' " (Ezekiel 37:19)

"And it was carved with cherubim and palm trees; and a palm tree was between cherub and cherub, and every cherub had two faces, a man's face toward the palm tree on one side, and a young lion's face toward the palm tree on the other side; they were carved in all the house all around." (Ezekiel 41:18-19)

"And they [aliens] shall be to you as the native-born among the sons of Israel; they shall be allotted an inheritance with you among the tribes of Israel." (Ezekiel 47:22)

(Ezekiel 48:35)

"The city shall be 18,000 cubits round about; and the name of the city from that day shall be, 'The LORD is there.' "

...

'The LORD is there':

Shiloh retter [Savior]

Detroit seer

Lot thresher

"Nebuchadnezzar had dreams; and his spirit was troubled and his sleep left him." (Daniel 2:1)

"And in that you saw the iron mixed with common clay, they will combine with one another in the seed of men; but they will not adhere to one another, even as iron does not combine with pottery. And in the days of those kings the God of heaven will set up a kingdom which will never be destroyed" (Daniel 2:43-44)

[Idolatry]

"But whoever does not fall down and worship shall be cast into the midst of a furnace of blazing fire." (Daniel 3:11)

[Magi?]

"O Belteshazzar, chief of the magicians" (Daniel 4:9)

(Daniel 4:13)

"an angelic watcher, a holy one":

ARCHANGEL NATHANIEL

[Cranbrook KINGSWOOD]

"Chop down the tree and cut off its branches,

...

Yet leave the stump with its roots in the ground,

But with a band of iron and bronze around it"

(Daniel 4:14-15)

[Nathaniel's NT beast]

"And let a beast's mind be given to him." (Daniel 4:16)

[Read the writing on the wall]

"Suddenly the fingers of a man's hand emerged and began writing opposite the lampstand on the plaster of the wall of the king's palace, and the king saw the back of the hand that did the writing." (Daniel 5:5)

[Daniel long-lived. Nebuchadnezzar, Belshazzar, Darius, Cyrus.]
"So this Daniel enjoyed success in the reign of Darius and in the reign of Cyrus the Persian." (Daniel 6:28)

(Daniel 7:9)
"And the Ancient of Days took His seat":
condensation shthead
Constantine atheist

(Daniel 7:13)
"And He came up to the Ancient of Days":
authenticate condensed/Feynman/Yasmeen

[Corporate America]
(Daniel 7:23)
"The fourth beast will be a fourth kingdom on the earth, which will be different from all the other kingdoms,"
"and it will devour the whole earth and tread it down and crush it.":
counterrevolutionaries annihilated/delawarean/hardhanded/hardheaded/Nathaniel/whirlwind
COUNTERREVOLUTIONARIES ANNIHILATED WITHDRAWAL
counterrevolutionaries NATHANIEL withdrawal
trinitrotoluene authentication DELAWARE

(Daniel 7:25)
"and he will intend to make alterations in times and in law":
internationalisation Nathaniel dismantled/weediest

(Daniel 8:23)
"A king will arise":
Killer Asian
"Insolent and skilled in intrigue":
dandelion trinitities/Einstein
antireligious Einstein

(Daniel 8:24)
"And his power will be mighty, but not by his own power,":
BLAMEWORTHINESS HYPERBOLOID HINTING
bibliotherapy disgruntlement

...
"And he will destroy to an extraordinary degree":
ALEXANDER DETROIT AENEID WRONGDOER

...
"And prosper and perform his will;" (3008):
foreordain wardenship
lordship manifold/Alisander
mineral professorial/worshippers

...
"He will destroy mighty men and the holy people.":
MEPHISTOPHELEAN HOMOGENEITY

(Daniel 8:25)
"And through his shrewdness":
transgression deus
thigh rounder sadness
righteousness Nash/Rand
...
"He will cause deceit to succeed by his influence;":
acidulousness benefited
...
"And he will magnify himself in his heart,":
demineralsing whitehall/analyst/Eastman/Ishmael/William/Lilian/Yasmin/Yahweh

...
"And he will destroy many while they are at ease.":
dethronement SHITHEAD lawyerly/Aeriel
DEMINERALISE DETHRONE YAHWEH

...
"He will even oppose the Prince of princes,"(8871 ... Harcourt):
Christ colonelship/conversion/fellowship/honorifics/necrophile/Persephone/principles/wolverines/FLEISCHER/
fleshier/lifelines/Nipponese

CHRIST FLIS NONVIOLENCE/necrophile/wolverine
Christ Fleisher Nonviolence/penelope
CHRIST NIPPONESE NECROPHILE
lifeline (4494) Christ Persephone
Phillip overseership Newton
Newton (3833) chronicler Phillip

...
"But he will be broken without human agency":
congratulation bumblebee/humblebee/Klement

(Daniel 9:26)
"Then after the sixty-two weeks the Messiah will be cut off and have nothing":
William Andrew Stefani necessitate Beethoven
William Andrew Stefani excise Hohenstaufen hottest
William Andrew Stefani covenantee fishhook sweetest/fetuses/sextets
WILLIAM ANDREW STEFANI EXCISE (3131) AUTOGENES BEETHOVEN/honeybee/keystone
WILLIAM ANDREW STEFANI BEETHOVEN AUTOGENES fisheyes/Scottish/coffees/excises

...
"the Messiah will be cut off and have nothing":
UNAVOIDABLENESS AFFLICTION

(Daniel 10:13)
"Michael, one of the chief princes":
ANNE FLIS HOMERIC Coptic/thief
CONCEPTION FLEISCHER/Cheshire/Heraclides/miracles/fleecer
Flis confirmation/omnipotence/Promethean/conception
femoral nicotinise/Einstein

(Daniel 12:11)
"abomination of desolation":
nationalisation boom

[Reincarnation]
"then you will enter into rest and rise again for your allotted portion at the end of the age." (Daniel 12:13)

[Jesus Reminiscent]
"He will revive us after two days;
He will raise us up on the third day
That we may live before Him."
(Hosea 6:2)

(Hosea 6:7)
"But like Adam they have transgressed the covenant":
undemonstrativeness (2122) blackheart

(Hosea 7:7)
"All of them are hot like an oven":
OVEREMOTIONAL Athena/Helen

[Aaron's calf ... Samael,
craftsman ... raftsman]
"A craftsman made it, so it is not God;
Surely the calf of Samaria will be broken to pieces."
(Hosea 8:6)

(Hosea 13:14)
"O Death, where are your thorns?
O Sheol, where is your sting?":
YAHWEH YAHWEH HETEROGENEOUSNESS
Yahweh Yahweh trinitrotoluene doghouses

"Wail like a virgin girded with sackcloth
For the bridegroom of her youth."
(Joel 1:8)

"the apple tree" (Joel 1:12)
"the garden of Eden" (Joel 2:3)

[e.g. Maud]

"That I will pour out My Spirit on all mankind" (Joel 2:28)

"The sun will be turned into darkness,
And the moon into blood,
Before the great and awesome day of the LORD comes.
And it will come about that whoever calls on the name of the LORD
Will be delivered;" (Joel 2:31-32)

[Israel, not Palestine]

"Yet it was I who destroyed the Amorite before them ...
That you might take possession of the land of the Amorite."
(Amos 2:9-10)

"You only have I chosen among all the families of the earth;"
(Amos 3:2)

[Versus Commandment #2]

(Amos 6:10)
"Keep quiet. For the name of the LORD is not to be mentioned."
trinitrotoluene behemoth

[The Little Mermaid]

"And though they conceal themselves from My sight on the floor of the sea,
From there I will command the serpent and it will bite them."
(Amos 9:3)

[Yaffa ... Jap]

"So he went down to Joppa, found a ship which was going to Tarshish" (Jonah 1:3)

[Pothead]

"Weeds were wrapped around my head." (Jonah 2:5)

"Then the LORD commanded the fish, and it vomited Jonah up onto the dry land." (Jonah 2:10)

"the sun beat down on Jonah's head so that he became faint and begged with all his soul to die, saying,
'Death is better to me than life.' " (Jonah 4:8)

(Habakkuk 2:5) [... Hakka Ku/UK]

"He enlarged his appetite like Sheol,"

"And he is like death, never satisfied.":

Aeneid Aeneid relativist/deathliest/deviltries/heraldist/travesties/faithless/satisfied/SHITHEAD

[Ruler is measurement.]

(Micah 5:2)

"But as for you, Bethlehem Ephrathah,
Too little to be among the clans of Judah,
From you One will go forth for Me to be ruler in Israel."

...
'From you One will go forth for Me to be ruler in Israel':

iliofemoral heterogeneous lobotomy/Milton

iliofemoral homogeneous Berliner Lotto

unforgettable housewife oiler Mormon

(Micah 5:5)

"And this One will be our peace.":

denuclearisation elbow

" 'On that day,' declares the LORD of hosts, 'I will take you, Zerubbabel, son of Shealtiel, my servant,'
declares the LORD, 'and I will make you like a signet ring, for I have chosen you,' ' declares the LORD
of hosts." (Haggai 2:23)

...
'I will take you, Zerubbabel, son of Shealtiel, my servant':

trinitrotoluene Bolshevism/sleazeballs

...
'and I will make you like a signet ring, for I have chosen you':

demineralisation challenger

recrystallising honeymooning/manifolding/nonyielding

acknowledgement sovereign hilarious/unskilful/Frankish/Honolulu/Krishna

...
'I will make you like a signet ring':

mineralisation will

[Ed Cho colloquialism "throw down"; Zechariah at end of carpal tunnel,
See "Zach Fair" of FF7.]

"but these craftsmen have come to terrify them, to throw down the horns of the nations who have lifted up their horns against the land of Judah in order to scatter it." (Zechariah 1:21)

[Context is Zerubbabel mentioned four times in Zechariah 4:6,7,9,10]

...
"The LORD rebuke you, Satan! Indeed, the LORD who has chosen Jerusalem rebuke you! Is this not a brand plucked from the fire?" (Zechariah 3:2)

...
"The LORD rebuke you, Satan!":
Aleksandr beetroot
buttonhole eureka/drake

...
"Is this not a brand plucked from the fire?":
demineralisation corruptest/tortured/potter

[Bran Stark]
(Zechariah 6:12)
"a man whose name is Branch":
monarch Messiah Anne

"Behold, I am going to send you Elijah the prophet before the coming of the great and terrible day of the LORD." (Malachi 4:5)

...
"the great and terrible day of the LORD":
foreordained Albert herald

[Joseph dreamer Father]
"and to Jacob was born Joseph the husband of Mary, by whom was born Jesus" (Matthew 1:16)

(Matthew 3:1)
"John the Baptist": Phaethon

Matthew 1:23 [Isaiah 7:14] correct
Matthew 2:6 [Micah 5:2] wrong
Matthew 2:15 [Hosea 11:1] wrong
Matthew 2:18 [Jeremiah 31:15] wrong
Matthew 3:3 [Isaiah 40:3] wrong

Matthew 4:4 [Deuteronomy 8:3]
Matthew 4:6 [Psalm 91:11-12]
Matthew 4:7 [Deuteronomy 6:16]
Matthew 4:10 [Deuteronomy 4:10]
"Begone Satan!" (Matthew 4:10) [Satan is M or Mary; therefore, this is not Jesus. Incidence of Deuteronomy and Q source indicates Yahweh attribution.]

Matthew 4:15-16 [Isaiah 9:1-2] wrong

(Matthew 6:28) [Lilian]
"Observe how the lilies of the field grow": floodlight whitehorse

Matthew 8:17 [Isaiah 53:4] wrong
Matthew 9:13 [Hosea 6:6] misquote properly "loyalty"

(Matthew 9:9)
"called Matthew, sitting in the tax office":
falsification Michael weed

[Lilith is Serpent]
(Matthew 10:16)
"be shrewd as serpents, and innocent as doves":
representativeness cannonade/showcase [Cannon is Guan Yin]

[Messiah is "Prince of Peace" (Isaiah 9:6)]
"Do not think that I came to bring peace in earth; I did not come to bring peace, but a sword."
(Matthew 10:34)

Matthew 10:35-36 [Micah 7:6] correct; [Note "serpent" in Micah 7:17]
Matthew 11:5 [Isaiah 35:5-6] inconsistent
Matthew 11:10 [Malachi 3:1] wrong
Matthew 11:29 [Jeremiah 6:16] wrong
Matthew 12:7 [Hosea 6:6] misquote
Matthew 12:18-21 [Isaiah 42:1-4] wrong, misquote
Matthew 12:40 [Jonah 1:17]
Matthew 13:14-15 [Isaiah 6:9-10] correct

(Isaiah 6:9)

"Keep on listening but do not perceive":
religion nonobedience/contentions/conventions/deceptions

[tares, or, darnel, a weed resembling wheat]

"The kingdom of heaven may be compared to a man who sowed good seed in his field. But while men were sleeping, his enemy came and sowed tares also among the wheat, and went away."
(Matthew 13:24-25)

Matthew 13:32 [Ezekiel 31:6; Daniel 4:12] wrong

Matthew 13:34 [Psalm 78:2] correct

(Psalm 78:2)

"I will open my mouth in a parable":

Emanuel impalpability
manipulation hyperbole

...

"I will utter dark sayings of old":

religion tutorial

(Matthew 13:39)

"and the enemy who sowed them is the devil":

dismantlement weed weed soviet
weed weed dishonesty elevation

Matthew 13:43 [Psalm 37:6] correct

[See Psalm 37:2]

(Psalm 37:2)

"For they will wither quickly like the grass,
And fade like the green herb."

Matthew 15:4 [Exodus 20:12, Exodus 21:17] wrong; see primacy of Exodus 20:3.

Matthew 15:8 [Isaiah 29:13] correct

[Lilian]

"Jesus went along by the Sea of Galilee" (Matthew 15:29)

Matthew 16:27 [Jeremiah 17:10] correct

[Right before Chapter 18; J, penny]

"go to the sea, and throw in a hook, and take the first fish that comes up; and when you open its mouth,
you will find a stater [shekel]"

(Matthew 17:27)

...

(Matthew 18:1)

"Who then is greatest in the kingdom of heaven?":
EIGHTEEN FISHHOOK (8666) dethronement/enthronement

Matthew 19:4 [Genesis 1:27] correct

Matthew 19:5 [Genesis 2:24] correct; note one flesh not spirit

Matthew 19:7 [Deuteronomy 24:1] correct

Matthew 19:18 [Exodus 20:13-16] correct

Matthew 19:19 [Exodus 20:12, Leviticus 19:18] correct

[Jesus is the Serpent]

"They said to Him, 'Lord, we want our eyes to be opened.' "

(Matthew 20:33)

"For God knows that in the day you eat from it your eyes will be opened" (Genesis 3:5)

Matthew 21:5 [Zechariah 9:9]wrong; See Numbers 22:22 !

(Numbers 22:5) [BA Lamb]
"Balaam the son of Beor":
ABRAHAM BOSTON
Solomon Barbee/father

(Zechariah 9:9)
"Even on a colt, the foal of a donkey.": Nathanael fooled

Matthew 21:9 [Psalm 118:26] wrong
Matthew 21:13 [Isaiah 56:7, Jeremiah 7:11] correct
Matthew 21:16 [Psalm 8:2] correct
Matthew 21:33 [Isaiah 5:1-2] correct
Matthew 21:42 [Psalm 118:22-23] wrong
Matthew 22:24 [Deuteronomy 25:5] correct
Matthew 22:32 [Exodus 22:32]
wrong
Matthew 22:37 [Deuteronomy 6:5] correct
Matthew 22:39 [Leviticus 19:18] correct
Matthew 22:44 [Psalms 110:1] correct
Matthew 23:39 [Psalm 118:26] correct

[Einstein is German "one stone"]
"Truly I say to you, not one stone here shall be left upon another, which will not be torn down." (Matthew 24:2)

[Topologize Einstein]
Matthew 24:2 "Einstein" textually near Matthew 24:15 "ABOMINATION OF DESOLATION" from Daniel, same thread. Likewise in Daniel, "one who makes desolate" (Daniel 9:27) near "A king will arise ... And he will destroy to an extraordinary degree" (Daniel 8:23-24), same Messianic thread.

[Topologize Michael]
Also note in Daniel the repeated textual nearness of mentions of "Abomination of Desolation" and Michael, respectively.
Daniel 9:27 and Daniel 10:13.
Daniel 11:31 and Daniel 10:21.
Daniel 12:11 and Daniel 12:1.

Also note textual nearness of "schemes" (Daniel 11:24, 11:25) [N, work of A. Grothendieck Shapiro] and "Kittim" (Daniel 11:30) [J, Hello Kitty] to "abomination of desolation" [K, death] (Daniel 11:31).

[Death takes the soul, by definition]
(Daniel 9:27)
"one who makes desolate":
Death Kowloon
skeleton shadow

Matthew 24:15 [Daniel 9:27, 11:31, 12:11] correct

Matthew 24:29 [Joel 2:10, 3:15, also 2:31] maybe
[Joel 3:10 contradicts Isaiah 2:4,
Joel 3:19 contradicts Isaiah 19:20,
Joel 2:28 supports Isaiah 11:9]

(Joel 2:28)
"That I will pour out My Spirit on all mankind":
AUTOMANIPULATION MILLIONS
IMMORTALISATION UNPOPULARITY
trinitrotoluol antihumanism/illuminati/inhumanity/Nathania1

Matthew 24:30 [Daniel 7:13] correct
Matthew 24:31 [Leviticus 23:24] wrong; possible metaphor

Matthew 26:31 [Zechariah 13:7] correct

(Zechariah 13:7)
"Awake, O sword, against My Shepherd," [echoes Genesis 3:24]

...
"And against the man, My Associate,":
mathematician Odyssean Santa
...
"Declares the LORD of hosts."
...
"Strike the Shepherd that the sheep may be scattered;":
PARASYMPATHETIC ESTHER ESTHER DETESTED
Esther Esther Esther decapitated/thickheaded/decimated/epitaphes/medicated
...
"And I will turn My hand against the little ones."

[Whore ... rabbid rabbit]
(Matthew 26:36)
"Gethsemane": get semen, gametes

Matthew 26:64 [Daniel 7:13] wrong

(Daniel 7:13)
"One like a Son of Man was coming,": kingliness Canaan
...
"And He came up to the Ancient of Days":
authenticate condensed Yah

[Judas Iscariot]
"Potter's Field" (Matthew 27:7)

Matthew 27:9-10 [Zechariah 11:12-13] correct [see Exodus 21:32]

[Siren]
"a man of Cyrene named Simon" (Matthew 27:32)

[Latin calva "bald head" ... Cali]
"Golgotha, which means Place of a Skull" (Matthew 27:33)

[Lot ... see Psalm 22:18]
"casting lots" (Matthew 27:35)

(Psalm 22:16-18)
"For dogs have surrounded me;
A band of evildoers has encompassed me;
They pierced my hands and my feet.
I can count all my bones.
They look, they stare at me;
They divide my garments among them,
And for my clothing they cast lots."
...
[echoes Jezebel]
"For dogs have surrounded me;":
HOMOGENEOUS DEFRAUDS
...
"A band of evildoers has encompassed me;":
ABSALOM comprehensiveness/fearsomeness/archenemies/archimedean/recondenses/renaissance
...
"They pierced my hands and my feet.":
DEATH decipherment/MASTERMINDED/ARCHENEMIES/impeachment/masterpiece/predestined/ARCHFIEND/ARCHIMEDES/
christened/tyranny
death tyranny impeded/misdeed/schemed
...
"I can count all my bones.":
unconscionable
...
[Impossible for David would have been killed, therefore prophetic.]
"They look, they stare at me;":
heatstroke
...
"They divide my garments among them,":
GEORGIA DAVID ENMESHMENT
GEORGIA DYNAMITE vestment
...

"And for my clothing they cast lots.":
CHRISTENDOM OCTAGONAL [RED]
CONDEMNATORY CALLISTO/GOLIATH

Matthew 27:43 [Psalm 22:8] correct
Matthew 27:46 [Psalm 22:1] contradicts Matthew 26:31

(Matthew 27:46)
"ELI, ELI, LAMA SABACHTHANI?":
Michael banalies/Isabella/Lilith/Helen
Lilith Chinese Baal

...
"MY GOD, MY GOD, WHY HAST THOU FORSAKEN ME?":
goddaughter Thomson fakes/sham

[Elijah is death]
"But the rest of them said, 'Let us see whether Elijah will come to save Him.'
And Jesus cried out again with a loud voice, and yielded up His spirit." (Matthew 27:49-50)

(Matthew 27:56)
"Mary Magdalene": German Adam/dame

"Therefore, give orders for the grave to be made secure until the third day, lest the disciples come and steal Him away and say to the people, 'He has risen from the dead,' and the last deception will be worse than the first." (Matthew 27:64)

[Lara Croft; Snow White; resurrection ... re-erection]
"Mary Magdalene and the other Mary came to look at the grave ... his [alleged angelic tomb raider] garment as white as snow" (Matthew 28:1-3)

"Lara Croft Tomb Raider":
fabricator retard
obliterator drama
arbitrator femoral/oracle

[Spiritually false; see Isaiah 54:16.
Physically true; see Isaiah 7:14]
"Jesus, Son of the Most High God" (Mark 5:7)

[Multiplication X]
"How many loaves do you have?" (Mark 6:38)

[X-tians filthy, dark ages ... X rated]
"some of His disciples were eating their bread with impure hands, that is, unwashed." (Mark 7:2)

[dubious]
"Thus He declared all foods clean." (Mark 7:19)

[Q]
"And if your eye causes you to stumble, cast it out" (Mark 9:47)

Mark 9:42, 46, 48 [Isaiah 66:24] correct

[Isaiah 66:24, last verse]
"For their worm shall not die,
And their fire shall not be quenched":
trinitrotoluene feeblemindedness Richard
worldbeater mineralise recondensation fortitude/Detroit

...
"And they shall be an abhorrence to all mankind.":
dethronement Aleksandr Babylonian[beast]/Hannibal/Hanoi

[Moral Relativity, Einstein next]
"for they all put in out of their surplus, but she, out of her poverty, put in all she owned, all she had to live on." (Mark 12:44)

["one stone" Einstein destroyer,
see permuted 2 Samuel 24:18]
"Do you see these great buildings? Not one stone shall be left upon another which will not be torn down." (Mark 13:2)

[Vampire; descendant of Impaler]

"And He said to them, 'This is My blood of the covenant, which is poured out for many.' " (Mark 14:24)

(Mark 15:7) [analogous]

"Barabbas": Rab's Baba

[Star Trek's Seven of Nine,
Resurrection echoes Matthew]

"He first appeared to Mary Magdalene, from whom He had cast out seven demons." (Mark 16:9)

Luke 1:17 [Malachi 4:6] false; Elijah is Caesar Augustus

"Now it came about in those days that a decree went out from Caesar Augustus, that a census be taken of all the inhabited earth." (Luke 2:1)

...

"Now again the anger of the LORD burned against Israel, and it incited David against them to say, 'Go, number Israel and Judah.' " (2 Samuel 24:1)

...

(2 Samuel 24:18)

"threshing floor of Araunah the Jebusite":

Albert Einstein August

Luke 2:32 [Isaiah 42:6, 49:6] false, false

(Isaiah 42:6)

"As a light to the nations":

Thessalonian goat

Nathaniel tattoos/Agosto/ghosts

Agosto annihilates/Athenians/Nathaniel/Leninist

[Yoda] "Joda" (Luke 3:26)

"the son of Adam, the son of God." (Luke 3:38)

Luke 4:18-19 [Isaiah 61:1-2] false

[Echoes Eden and apple ... snake]

"For each tree is known by its own fruit." (Luke 6:44)

[Seven of Star Trek Voyager]

"Mary who was called Magdalene, from whom seven demons had gone out" (Luke 8:2)

[Bethesda's "Black Widow"]

"He withdrew by Himself to a city called Bethsaida."

[Proximity]

(Luke 11:11) "snake"

(Luke 11:12) "scorpion"

(Luke 11:15) "Beelzebul": Belle, Bee

(Luke 11:30) "Jonah" [J]

(Luke 11:31) "Queen of the South" [Sheba, J]

(Luke 11:31) "Solomon"

(Luke 11:32) "Jonah"

(Luke 11:33) "lighting a lamp"

(Luke 11:37) "Pharisee"

...

(Luke 11:51) "blood of Abel" [Cain]

(Luke 11:52) "key of knowledge" [K]

...

(Luke 12:5) "the One"

(Luke 12:6) "sparrows"

(Luke 12:7) "hairs"

(Luke 12:10) "Holy Spirit" [LORD]

[EIGHTEEN mentioned 3x, Bond]

"And this woman, a daughter of Abraham as she is, whom Satan has bound for eighteen long years, should she not have been released from this bond on the Sabbath Day?" (Luke 13:16)

[p. 887, 887 Harcourt,

Alexander A. Karelin 887-2]

(Luke 14:5) "Which one of you shall have a son or an ox fall into a well, and will not immediately pull him out on a Sabbath day?"

[p. 888 The Prodigal Son;

Nicolino Locche]

(Luke 15:15, 21)

"he sent him into his fields to feed swine" [Fields medal Archimedes]

...

"Father I have signed against heaven and in your sight; I am no longer worthy to be called your son."

(Luke 16:1-2)

"this steward was reported to him as squandering his possessions. ... Give an account of your stewardship, for you can no longer be steward."

(Luke 16:23-24)

"And in Hades he lifted up his eyes, being in torment ... dip the tip of his finger in water and cool off my tongue; for I am in agony in this flame."

Luke 22:37 [Isaiah 53:12] wrong

[Georgia]

"gorgeous robe" (Luke 23:11)

Luke 23:30 [Hosea 10:8] correct

Luke 23:46 [Psalm 31:5] wrong

"Cleopas" (Luke 24:18) [Fr: not Cleo]

"the eleven" (Luke 24:33) ... leaven

["John the Baptist": Phaethon]

"Who are you?" (John 1:19)

...

"These things took place in Bethany behind the Jordan, where John was baptizing." (John 1:28)

...

"Nathanael" (John 1:45,46,47,48,49)

[Stewing]

"wedding in Cana of Galilee" (John 2:1) [... Cain, Kay]

"Now there were six stone waterpots set there for the Jewish custom of purification, containing twenty or thirty gallons each." (John 2:6)

[Pot weed cato, hin is 1.5 gallons; mikvah ... immolation, wine ... Pharaoh's cup?]

"Draw some out now, and take it to the headwaiter [8 steward]." (John 2:8)

John 2:17 [Psalms 69:9; according to Shoshannim, or possibly Lilies] wrong [... lotus]

"Nicodemus, a ruler of the Jews" (John 3:1) [Nicotine vice]

"born again" (John 3:3) [reincarnate]

[Numbers 21:8 "serpent...standard"]

"And as Moses lifted up the serpent in the wilderness, even so must the Son of Man be lifted up;" (John 3:14)

[Netanyahu]

" 'I know that Messiah is coming (He who is called Christ); when that One comes He will declare all things to us.' Jesus said to her, 'I who speak to you am He.' " (John 4:25-26)

[Bethesda lame CIA; LOTR "Watcher in the Water" kraken]

"by the sheep gate a pool, which is called in Hebrew Bethesda, having five porticoes. In these lay a multitude of those who were sick, blind, lame, and withered, [waiting for the moving of the waters;" (John 5:2-3)

[Heretic; above the Law, honesty]

"For not even the Father judges anyone, but He has given all judgment to the Son." (John 5:22)

John 6:31 [Exodus 16:4] false; metaphors misleading

John 6:45 [Isaiah 54:13, Jeremiah 31:34] false, false

[Alexander's TNT favorite]

(John 8:32)

"and you shall know the truth, and the truth shall make you free."

...

"the truth shall make you free":
Krystalle author/father/meteor/haute/Homer/Torah
marshal roulette/keyhole/lottery/theft

[Spit, stake, snake, log, word; clay, dust; eye-opener. Genesis 3]
"He spat on the ground, and made clay of the spittle, and applied the clay to his eyes." (John 9:6)

John 10:34 [Psalm 82:6] correct; yet then everyone is a son of God, hence a meaningless distinction, but a meaningful origin

[Kay's relativity]
"Caiaphas, who was high priest that year, said to them, "You know nothing at all, nor do you take into account that it is expedient for you that one man should die for the people, and that the whole nation should not perish." (John 11:49-50)

...
[Not a certainty that nation will perish; by Hebrew Law, this is a wrong reason to kill, bad high priest. Now killing the innocent certainly will destroy the nation of Israel; the LORD will annihilate them. By Roman Law Jesus is innocent, by Hebrew Law Jesus is a heretic, worthy of swift death by stoning.]

[Why anoint Jesus for death?]
" 'Why was this perfume not sold for three hundred denarii, and given to poor people?' Now he said this, not because he was concerned about the poor, but because he was a thief" (John 12:5-6)

John 12:38 [Isaiah 53:1] wrong
John 12:40 [Isaiah 6:10] correct; yet misquoted "CONVERTED".

[Cretins]
"He who has bathed needs only to wash his feet, but is completely clean" (John 13:10)

John 13:18 [Psalm 41:9] wrong; David metaphorically misapplied.

John 15:25 [Psalm 69:4] false; blasphemous.

[Female]
"that they may be one, just as We are one; I in them, and Thou in Me, that they may be perfected in unity" (John 17:22-23)

[Cluster Judas's betrayal in garden, садовой, D. SADOWAY, Khazarian Jew?; A.L Flis MIT course 18; Sadoway's Graduate student "Brian Neltner": Berliner Nat N, Lenin beta, Khazarian Jew, Rasputin; "eighteen", Jordan Nosanchuk, Khazarian Jew]
"there was a garden" (John 18:1)

[Sodaway]
"Donald Robert Sadoway":
LATERAN DOORWAY ["my door is always open"]
laboratory endows
analyst wardrobe/adorer/Debora
Boston adoral _
Toyoda borderlands/Wonderbra
Waterloo brand
Albert Aaron soddy
TREASON DROOL/ROYAL
BETRAYAL ODORS
Beta sandalwood
bastard woodlander
letdown sorry
Lord Broadway/boatyards/databased/deodorant/tornadoes/downbeat/ratsbane/sanatory/sayonara

...
"ANTICHRIST VASSALS":
narcissists, Vaticanists, anarchists, archivists, Calvinists, Christians, charlatans, racialists, Stalinists

...
"Christ vassals": Issachar, Lhasa, sharia

[Smart]
"Pilate said to Him, 'What is truth?'" (John 18:38)

"Pilate answered, 'What I have written I have written.'" (John 19:22)

John 19:36 [Psalm 34:20] wrong

John 19:37 [Zechariah 12:10] wrong

(Zechariah 12:10) [subsequent]

"and they will mourn for Him":

iliofemoral rhythm

(Zechariah 12:11)

"Hadadrimmon in the plain of Megiddo":

Armageddon iodophthalein [X-ray dye]/definitional/immolation/manifolded/dandelion/Napoleon/Phaethon

...

mineral imagination/Maimonidean/Agamemnon/emanation

diadem nonoperational

dandelion dragon pothead

[Snow White]

"beheld two angels in white" (John 20:12)

[resurrection fishy]

"they were not able to haul it in because of the great number of fish" (John 21:6)

[End Tanakh reference check; later.]

[Breaking Bad]

"breaking bread from house to house" (Acts 2:46)

"they were uneducated and untrained men" (Acts 4:13)

["futile", "vain"; reminiscent of

The Borg's "resistance is futile"]

Acts 4:25-26 [Psalm 2:1-2] false

[Isaiah 7; ruin of Israel prophesy]

"stay away from these men and let them alone, for if this plan or action should be of men, it will be overthrown; but if it is of God you will not be able to overthrow them; or else you may even be found fighting against God." (Acts 5:38-39)

[Saul basket case]

"lowering him in a large basket" (Acts 9:25)

[False]

"solemnly to testify that this is the One who has been appointed by God as Judge of the living and the dead." (Acts 10:42)

[Universalisation; vs tribal nature]

"giving them the Holy Spirit, just as He also did to us; and He made no distinction between us and them, cleansing their hearts by faith." (Acts 15:8-9)

Name Density:

"Lydia, . . . , a seller of purple fabrics" (Acts 16:14)

"Apollonia" (Acts 17:1,11,13)

"Thessalonica" (Acts 17:1)

"Jason" (Acts 17:5,6,7,9)

"TO AN UNKNOWN GOD" (Acts 17:23)

"The Way" (Acts 19:9,23)

"Tyrannus" (Acts 9:23)

"Demetrius, a silversmith" (Acts 19:24,38)

"Artemis" (Acts 9:24,27,28,34,35,38)

"image which fell down from heaven" (Acts 19:35)

"Gaius" (Acts 19:29, 20:4)

"Alexander" (Acts 19:33,33)

"Pyrrhus" (Acts 20:4)

"Thessalonians" (Acts 20:4)

...

"Assos" (Acts 20:13,14)

"Mitylene" (Acts 20:14) [MIT]

"Chios" (Acts 20:15)

"Samos" (Acts 20:15)

"course" (Acts 20:24)

"shrink" (Acts 20:20,27) [for Paul]

[Baptism is heresy, only God pardons sins. Proselytizing is uncustomary, proselytizing heresy is abominable.]

"Arise and be baptized, and wash away your sins, calling on His name." (Acts 22:16)

[CIA]

"it is not the custom of the Romans to hand over any man before the accused meets his accusers face to face, and has an opportunity to make his defense against the charges." (Acts 25:16)

[Pharisee Saul should know spirits can be sent to deceive; see 1 Kings 22:22, Ahab and Jezebel.]

"Paul, you are out of your mind! Your great learning is driving you mad." (Acts 26:24)

[Innocent by Roman Law, heretical traitor by Mosaic Law.]

"Do not be afraid, Paul; you must stand before Caesar" (Acts 27:24)

[Snake, burning logs echos Jezebel]

"But when Paul had gathered a bundle of sticks and laid them on the fire, a viper came out because of the heat, and fastened on his hand." (Acts 28:3)

Paul's Arguments:

(Romans 2:12) Ignorance does not excuse, see Adam, however it can mitigate sentencing.

(Romans 2:13-15) See Deuteronomy 30:6 and 28.

(Romans 2:25) Matter of degree.

(Romans 2:26) No, yet righteous.

(Romans 2:27) Yes.

...
Circumcision is of the flesh, the LORD then circumcises the heart.

[See Deuteronomy 30:6]

...
Without accepting the covenant, hence facing the consequences of disobedience, one cannot reap the rewards of obedience.

[See Deuteronomy 28]

...
"Reason away God's covenant":

wrongness Actaeon

...
"[S]Paul of Tarsus of Cilicia":

calculus tipoff [Nathaniel]

Iscariot fallacious

...
Action and word vs thought.

"'Let us do evil that good may come'? Their condemnation is just." (Romans 3:8)

[zombies]

"present yourselves to God as those alive from the dead" (Romans 6:13)

[Definitional not actual; see Cain]

"for apart from the Law sin is dead." (Romans 7:8)

["Divorcing words from their meanings":

Christianising Mordred wrong]

...
(1 Corinthians 2:13)

"combining spiritual thoughts with spiritual words.":

Christianisation wordsmith stillbirth/spotlight/BULLSHIT

[Intimacy is not evil, nor is sex, but fornication.]

"it is good for a man not to touch a woman" (1 Corinthians 7:1)

...
[Paul N is gay, like Catholic priests.]

"But I say to the unmarried and to widows that it is good for them if they remain even as I." (1 Corinthians 7:8)

...
[Good marriage has synergy.]

"his interests are divided ... secure undistracted devotion to the Lord." (1 Corinthians 7:34-35)

...
[Divorce permissible.]

"A wife is bound as long as her husband lives." (1 Corinthians 7:39)

...
VERSUS TORAH

...
"God said to them, 'Be fruitful and multiply.' " (Genesis 1:28)

...
[Keyword SUITABLE]
"Then the LORD God said, 'It is not good for the man to be alone; I will make him a helper suitable for him.' " (Genesis 2:18)

[FALSE; both important]
"Circumcision is nothing, and uncircumcision is nothing, but what matters is the keeping of the commandments of God." (Genesis 7:19)

[misguided guilt]
"eat anything that is set before you, without asking questions for conscience' sake." (1 Corinthians 10:27)

[cattle herder]
"Give no offense... please all men in all things"(1 Corinthians 10:32-33)

[WRONG; man is the head of family, Hebrew women are educated, also have rights.]
"man is the head of a woman" (1 Corinthians 11:3)

...
"Yet your desire shall be for your husband,
And he shall rule over you." (Genesis 3:16)

"Every man who has something on his head while praying or prophesying disgraces his head." (1 Corinthians 11:4)

...
"And for Aaron's sons ... you shall make caps for them, for glory and for beauty." (Exodus 28:40)

"Does not even nature itself teach you that if a man has long hair, it is a dishonor to him" (1 Corinthians 11:14)

...
"the vow of a Nazirite, to dedicate himself to the LORD" (Numbers 6:2)

[1 Corinthians 11:24-25] eucharist;
Notable that Paul's only other direct citation of Jesus is found in
[2 Corinthians 12:9].

"no one speaking by the Spirit of God says, 'Jesus is accursed' " (1 Corinthians 12:3)

...
vs TORAH

...
(Genesis 3:14)
"And the LORD God said to the serpent,":
Alessandro eighteen/dethroned/dehorned/potter/Detroit(253)
ALESSANDRO EIGHTEEN THROOP
Alessandro potter thigh dented
Dorothee antidepressant/degradations/detestation/disentangles/endoparasite/negotiatress/Thessalonian
Dorothee endoparasite(22) DDT/LSD/TNT

...
'Because you have done this,':
acid bathhouse/Beethoven/honeybee
Octavio husband/beheads/Sundays

...
'Cursed are you more than all cattle,':
[Richard at Jaffa in 1191]
COUNTERMEASURE (1191) octahedral/cathedral/charlotte/harlot/Dorthea/deathly/lottery/Rachael/yachter
OCTAHEDRAL EMASCULATORY
LOTTERY CHANCELLORATE/THERMONUCLEAR
Clytemnestra Leucorrhoea [vaginal discharge]/octahedral
Rachael adulterous
AMATERASU ELECTROCAUTERY [excision]
HARCOURT METATARSAL CLOUD
HERCULES AUTOCORRELATED/DEUTERONOMY/documentary

...
'And more than every beast of the field;':
foreordainment detestable
dethronement deliberate

TRAVIS NONDEFAMATORY/NONREDEEMABLE

Bethesda deafferentation/reformatioal

ELEVATES (5444) DEAFFERENTATION [PHANTOM LIMB]/featherbrained/foreordainment/Mediterranean/nonhereditary/
dethronement

...
'On your belly shall you go,':

logos honourable/Honolulu

ANGEL BOOHOO

...
'And dust shall you eat':

Ayatollah nudest/sunset

SELLOUT SUNDAY

analyst loathed

...
'All the days of your life;':

Dorothy Ieyasu

Ieyasu fellatory/foolhardy/deflator/deathly

fleurdelis loath/Alfy

LORD FLESH ALFY

alleluia theory

flesh fairytale/laudatory/floodlit

Lord faithful/hateful/hostile/loyalest/outyells/Alyosha

...
(Genesis 3:15)

'And you shall bruise him on the heel.':

demineralise absolute unholy

[Algebraic varieties A.G. Shapiro]

"varieties" (1 Corinthians 12:4,5,6)

[Divine authority usurped, prophets and miracles.]

"And God has appointed in the church, first apostles, second prophets, their teachers, then
miracles," (1 Corinthians 12:28)

[Oliver Cromwell]

"and if I deliver my body to be burned" (1 Corinthians 13:3)

...
[P ... vs cupid]

"Pursue love , yet desire earnestly spiritual gifts, but especially that you may prophesy." (1
Corinthians 14:1)

...
[&c] "prophecy" (1 Corinthians 14:6)

[David] "harp" (1 Corinthians 14:7)

[algebraic dual ... dualist]

"But if anyone does not recognize this, he is not recognized." (1 Corinthians 14:38)

[Akira]

"There is one glory of the sun, and another glory of the moon" (1 Corinthians 15:41)

[Trump]

"at the last trumpet; for the trumpet will sound" (1 Corinthians 15:52)

[Alexander]

"Macedonia" (1 Corinthians 16:5)

[Spirit of Detroit statue in lotus;
by Marshall Fredericks,
commissioned August 2, 1955
acidic treatment to oxidize bronze.
"SOD" sodomized in Detroit "the D";
Michigan peninsular.]

...
(2 Corinthians 3:17)

"Now the Lord is the Spirit;":

periodontitis

Throop dentistry/Listerine

...
"and where the Spirit of the Lord is there is liberty."
lordship worldbeater finisher

hydrosphere territorialise defensible/benefited/entitled
LIFELINE SHITHEAD DISOBEYER WHITEHORSE
Indefeasibility error heliosphere/lithosphere

...
VS

"Alexander self-immolation":
***DEMOTE (2111) MILLENARIAN
NATANIEL MEMORIAL/MISLEADER/Federals
Marianna Sodomite
lifeline (2022) monster Adam
freedom emanation
maxim (4404)

...
elated (2322) iliofemoral
iliofemoral mandates
Israel (2025) monofilament/amontillado

...
Deifies (802) [Friedrich]
Deifies annex aortal
mineral amontillados [A0]
meatloaf mineralised

...
defeat manorialism [slavery]/MILLENARIAN/Armenians/melanoma/Arianism/Iranians/Leninism/Marianne/Marxians/
millions/moronism/Romanism/Lillian/Marxism/Mormons/Riemann
Lillian (2000)
exonerate manifolds
Adamson eliminator/fellation/fellatrix/reinflame

[In Gladiator, Maximus on white horse, adopted by Marcus Aurelius, like Alexander and Aristotle.]

...
"Alexander Luka Flis self immolation":
defeat Maximus alkalinise

[education]
"for the weapons of our warfare are not of the flesh, but divinely powerful" (2 Corinthians 10:4)

[Hates Torah]
"Christ redeemed us from the curse of the Law" (Galatians 3:13)

[universalising]
"There is neither Jew nor Greek, there is neither slave nor free man, there is neither male nor female;
for you are all one in Christ Jesus." (Galatians 3:28)

[Confuting God Most High with 'Spirit', to justify emotional disobedience of Mosaic Law.
True that command from LORD supercedes, Commandment One.]

...
"But if you are led by the Spirit, you are not under the Law." (Galatians 5:18)

[Riemann sums, integrals ...
"house of Rimmon" (2 Kings 5:18)]

...
"the summing up of all things in Christ" (Ephesians 1:10)

[Psychological warfare: confusion relabelled divine mystery.]
"you can understand my insight into the mystery of Christ" (Ephesians 3:4)

[Orientalism, Torah pioneered judges and women's rights.]
"But as the church is subject to Christ, so also the wives ought to be to their husbands in
everything." (Ephesians 5:24)

[Richard Phillips Feynman ... Clementine Leninist of NY City]
"Indeed, true comrade ... together with Clement also" (Philippians 4:3)

[God endowed man with reason.]
"I say this in order that no one may delude you with persuasive argument." (Colossians 2:4)

[God made the world.]
"See to it that no one takes you captive through philosophy and empty deception, according to the
tradition of men, according to the elementary principles of the world, rather than according to
Christ." (Colossians 2:8)

[Elon Musk]

"If you have died with Christ to the elementary principles of the world" (Colossians 2:20)

...

"barbarian, Scythian" (Colossians 3:11)

...

[Eighteen]

"Wives, be subject to your husbands" (Colossians 3:18)

...

[Rinoa Heartily FF8; 23 Jordan]

"Whatever you do, do your work heartily" (Colossians 3:23)

...

[Bill Grant]

"Masters, grant to your slaves justice and fairness" (Colossians 4:1)

[p. 1007, James Bond license to kill;
scheme to make Lord into killer]

...

"For the Lord Himself will descend from heaven with a shout, with the voice of the archangel, and with the trumpet of God; and the dead in Christ shall rise first." (1 Thessalonians 4:6)

[Attempt to psychologically justify robbery through false prophesy]

...

"the day of the Lord will come just like a thief in the night." (1 Thessalonians 5:2)

...

"thief" (1 Thessalonians 5:4)

[Ephraim ... David,
See Psalm 60:7, 108:8]

...

"helmet" (1 Thessalonians 5:8)

[p. 1008 Ko]

"the man of lawlessness is revealed, the son of destruction ... displaying himself as being God." (1 Thessalonians 2:3-4)

[Topologize proximity ... Apple]

...

"Macedonia" (1 Timothy 1:3)

...

"Alexander" (1 Timothy 1:20)

...

"Adam ... Eve." (1 Timothy 2:13)

...

"office of overseer" (1 Timothy 3:1)

...

"branding iron" (1 Timothy 4:2)

[false, conniving]

"Do not sharply rebuke an older man, but rather appeal to him as a father, to the younger men as brothers" (1 Timothy 5:1)

[Literal retard Erica Standhart;

"living dead girl" by Rob Zombie of B Boston]

...

"But she who gives herself to wanton pleasure is dead even while she lives." (1 Timothy 5:6)

...

[Ko ... cow DD silicone Standhart]

"YOU SHALL NOT MUZZLE THE OX WHILE HE IS THRESHING" (1 Timothy 5:18)

...

[Nathaniel in TIMothy ... MIT;

MIT communist architecture, similar to FF7's Midgar, a children's game on Sony PlayStation;
Star Trek "Seven", 7 of 9, DD Borg.

...

[Seven ... sneaking; NB of Boston]

"Therefore whoever kills Cain, vengeance will be taken on him sevenfold." (Genesis 4:15)

...

(Genesis 4:15)

"sign for Cain": signorina

...

Carl Friedrich Gauss

Erica (E, retard) vs Frieda (J, Euler)
b. 1777 d. 1855 at 77 years old.

"Prince of Mathematicians";

Electric (E) and Magnetic (B) fields;

Student Riemann ... Rimmon (K);

...

Gauss neighbor to Flis,

standard guitar tuning E/B,

NASB 1977 "New American Standard Bible",

Brighton dancing Joshua White, also Erica Standhart;

...

"Also seven priests shall carry seven trumpets of rams' horns before the ark; then on the seventh day you shall march around the city seven times, and the priests shall blow the trumpets." (Joshua 6:4)

...

["Shiloh" (Genesis 49:10)]

"behold, if the daughters of Shiloh come out to take part in the dances" (Judges 21:21)

...

"Cursed is he who gives a wife to Benjamin" (Judges 21:18)

...

[Limb ... Lamb ... Sodomized rape]

"he took a knife and laid hold off his concubine and cut her in twelve pieces, limb by limb, and sent her throughout the territory of Israel." (Judges 19:29)

...

[Ravenous; GOT "three eyed raven", Bran, brand, Branch ...

Bran crippled at youth by Jamie]

"Benjamin is a ravenous wolf" (Genesis 49:27)]

...

"The sins of some men are quite evident" (1 Timothy 5:24)

...

[FF7's Cloud Strife in SOLDIER,

"And the LORD said to Moses, 'Behold, I shall come to you in a thick cloud'"(Exodus 19:9)]

...

"No soldier in active service entangles himself in the affairs of everyday life, so that he may please the one who enlisted him as a soldier." (2 Timothy 2:4)

...

[Jae (J) and James (K)]

"And just as Jannes and Jambres opposed Moses" (2 Timothy 3:8)

...

[Erica ... GOT's "reek" of torture]

"ears" (2 Timothy 4:3,4)

...

[MIT course numbers, librarian N]

"I have finished the course" (2 Timothy 4:7)

...

"Alexander the coppersmith ... vigorously opposed our teaching" (2 Timothy 4:14-15)

...

["Sabrina" w. Audrey Hepburn,

cloud ... Claudian dynasty]

"Corinth ... Linus and Claudia" (2 Timothy 4:20-21)

...

[88th largest island, Cretins, Christians, Xtians]

"Crete" (Titus 1:5)

...

[TITUS ... Tit ... DD scheme]

"For the overseer must be above reproach as God's steward" (Titus 1:7)

...

" 'Cretans are always liars, evil beasts, lazy gluttons.' This testimony is true." (Titus 1:12-13)

...

[DD's ... Dunkin Donuts of Boston]

"both their mind and their conscience are defiled. They profess to know God, but by their deeds they deny Him, being detestable and disobedient, and worthless for any good deed." (Titus 1:15-16)

...

"strife" (Titus 3:9) [Cloud Strife FF7]

...

[Commissioned by Octavio 29 BCE to commemorate victory of Octavio over M. Antony and Cleopatra ... victory, Nike herald, Elijah;

Nike sneakers Kay, ... Octavio's cain.

Nicopolis, nicotine, Niccolo Poli ...

If Alexander consorts he's steward.]

...
"Nicopolis" (Titus 3:12)

[Philemon ... Phil of "Hercules", Rinoa Heartily of FF8]
"sending my very heart" (Philemon 1:12)

[DD Boob scheme:
partner heroine Jae ... Jael,
Dibrova trident ... Deborah,
Euler Rd. of Brighton near Sal's,
"bottle of milk" (Judges 4:19)]

...
"For everyone who partakes only of milk is not accustomed to the word of righteousness, for he is a babe." (Hebrews 5:13)

[Child's intuition vs mistrained discernment ?]
"But solid food is for the mature, who because of practice have their senses trained to discern good and evil." (Hebrews 5:14)

[Priest of God Most High vs Yahweh; also Cohen were damned for embezzlement, hence Rabbis.

...
[Potholder, weed ... Shiloh]
"Then he would thrust it into the pan, or kettle, or caldron, or pot; all that the fork brought up the priest would take for himself. Thus they did in Shiloh to all the Israelites who came there." (1 Samuel 2:14)

...
"there will not be an old man in your house" (1 Samuel 2:31)

...
"an old man will not be in your house forever" (1 Samuel 2:32)

...
"all the increase of your house will die in the prime of life" (1 Samuel 2:33)

...
Alexander maternally Cohen from Marianna, who's father died young.]

...
"what further need was there for another priest to arise according to the order of Melchizedek, and not be designated according to the order of Aaron?" (Hebrews 7:11)

[Loathes Torah; word of LORD is perfect.]
"setting aside of a former commandment because of its weakness and uselessness (for the Law made nothing perfect)" (Hebrews 7:18-19)

[Nonsense]
"For a covenant is valid only when men are dead" (Hebrews 9:17)

[False]
"it is appointed for men to die once and after this comes judgment" (Hebrews 9:27)

[Bond]
"discipline ... yields the peaceful fruit of righteousness" (Hebrews 12:11)

[Prodigy P "Shook Ones Pt. 2; blue fire, toss dice]
"those things which cannot be shaken may remain" (Hebrews 12:27)

...
"for our God is a consuming fire." (Hebrews 12:29)

[James Bond; see discipline, yields]
"James, a bond-servant of God" (James 1:1)

"But if you have bitter jealousy and selfish ambition in your heart" (James 3:14)

...
[Chaos]
"there is disorder and every evil thing." (James 3:16)

"will consume your flesh like fire" (James 5:3)

...
"anointing him with oil in the name of the Lord" (James 5:14)

"Elijah" (James 5:17)

[metaphorical rebirth]

"born again" (1 Peter 1:23)

"manifold grace of God" (1 Peter 4:10)

[False]

"If you are reviled for the name of Christ, you are blessed" (1 Peter 4:14)

[Slandering prophet]

"having followed the way of Balaam, the son of Beor, who loved the wages of unrighteousness" (2 Peter 2:15)

[Baloney]

"Paul ... speaking in them of these things, in which are some things hard to understand, which the untaught and unstable distort" (2 Peter 3:15-16)

(1 John 2:18)

"antichrist is coming":

Christianising Oct

[Comics; X-Men]

"marvel" (1 John 3:13)

[Notable proximity]

"Gaius" (3 John 1)

...

"Demetrius" (3 John 12)

...

"shall speak face to face" (3 John 14)

[Notable mention; see Daniel 12:1]

"Michael the archangel" (Jude 9)

[Trump]

"a loud voice like the sound of a trumpet" (Revelation 1:10)

[Sardis (drama, Broadway), sardines, Sardinian (mobster)]

...

[NYC W44th St, p. 1043]

"Sardis" (Revelation 1:11)

...

[p. 1044]

"Jezebel" (Revelation 2:20)

[K nicotine]

"keys of death and of Hades" (Revelation 1:18)

...

"Nicolaitans" (Revelation 2:6, 15)

[On life support in Pasadena at Caltech]

"the tree of life, which is in the Paradise of God" (Revelation 2:7)

[Breaking Bad:

Mr. White with Skylar is Beta]

"white stone, and a new name" (Revelation 2:17)

[Teacher Richard Lamb CK CS possibly albino;

Richard the Lionhearted opponent of Saladin]

...

"Lion" (Revelation 5:5)

...

"Lamb" (Revelation 5:6, 12)

...

"riches" (Revelation 5:12)

[MIT Scheme 6.001 Lambda-calculus]

"Lamb" (Revelation 6:1)

...

"white horse" (Revelation 6:2)

[Repeal Revelation, analyst insane;

Revelation 8-9 (WORLD WAR III)
vs Isaiah (world peace);
1/3=.3333333333 Trinity]

...
"a third of the earth was burned up" (Revelation 8:7)
"a third of the sea became blood" (Revelation 8:8)
"a third of the creatures, which were in the sea and had life, died" (Revelation 8:9)
"a third of the ships were destroyed" (Revelation 8:9)
"a third of the waters became wormwood" (Revelation 8:11)
"a third of the sun and a third of the moon and a third of the stars were smitten" (Revelation 8:12)

...
"kill a third of mankind"
(Revelation 9:15)
"A third of mankind was killed" (Revelation 9:18)

...
"And I took the little book out of the angel's hand and ate it, and it was in my mouth sweet as honey;
and when I had eaten it, my stomach was made bitter." (Revelation 10:10)

[Mortal Kombat ghouls, killing God]
"scorpions" (Revelation 9:10)

...
[9/11/2001 ... 001 becomes police;
Twin towers, pillars falling, radical attack on Minoru Yamasaki's art.
New One World Trade Center:
Cubic base, eight tall isosceles triangles ... HK triad; near its middle, a perfect octagon ... Octavio]
(Revelation 9:11)
"Abaddon ... Apollyon":
Bond Lapland

[Confuting to evade blame:
dragon is N, Nemesis or Leviathan;
serpent is G, Jesus or Lilian;
devil is K, Killer or Death;
Satan is M, Adversary or Metatron]

...
"And the great dragon was thrown down, the serpent of old who is called the devil and Satan, who deceives
the whole world" (Revelation 12:9)

[trader ... WTC]
"to buy or sell" (Revelation 13:17)

...
"the number of the beast ... is six hundred and sixty-six" (Revelation 13:18)

...
"Now the weight of gold which came in to Solomon in one year was 666 talents of gold" (1 Kings 10:14,
also 2 Chronicles 9:13)

...
[Solomon means "peaceful", aka "Jedidiah" (2 Samuel 12:25).]

[Notable since LG is an idol]
"sea of glass" (Revelation 15:2)

[Seven ... bowls of weed]
"seven angels seven golden bowls full of the wrath of God" (Revelation 15:7)

...
"seven bowls" (Revelation 16:1)

...
"bowl" (Revelation 16:2, 3, 4, 8, 10, 12, 17)

...
[Armageddon or death of Odin;
End of the world;
666 or 616]
"Har-Magedon" (Revelation 16:16)

"great harlot" (Revelation 17:1)

...
[Gone with the Wind's Scarlett O'Hara, ... scarlet (red), scarab (and sun), Iscariot (blue)]
"a woman sitting on a scarlet beast" (Revelation 17:3)

...
"BABYLON THE GREAT" (Revelation 17:5)

...

"Nebuchadnezzar king of Babylon has devoured me and crushed me,
He has set me down like an empty vessel;
He has swallowed me like a monster" (Jeremiah 51:34)

...
"And let a beast's mind be given to him,
And let seven periods of time pass over him" (Daniel 4:16)

[Bait tattoo]

"And on His robe and on His thigh He has a name written, 'KING OF KINGS, AND LORD OF LORDS.'" (Revelation 19:16)

...
"KING OF KINGS AND LORD OF LORDS":
Floridian folksong [shaped like gun, see JNF permutations, gators]

...
"Circle with a nested loop":
Phaeton elicitor/wrestled/Lord
"Circle and loop":
Lord (333) cocaine

...
"The LORD will smite you with ... inflammation" (Deuteronomy 28:22)

...
"you shall flee seven ways before them, and you shall be an example of terror to all the kingdoms of the earth." (Deuteronomy 28:25)

"crystal" (Revelation 22:1)
"yielding its fruit" (Revelation 22:2)

[Stilgar of Dune]

"Let the one who does wrong, still do wrong; and let the one who is filthy, still be filthy; and let the one who is righteous, still practice righteousness; and let the one who is holy, still keep himself holy." (Revelation 22:11)

...
[Done ... Dune, by Frank Herbert]
"Behold, I am coming quickly, and My reward is with Me, to render to every man according to what he has done.
I am the Alpha and the Omega, the first and the last, the beginning and the end." (Revelation 22:12-13)

...
[fatal in Dune]
"let the one who wishes take the water of life without cost." (Revelation 22:17)

Eve, eavesdropper
ode, Odo, Odey Meroueh, Odysseus (string bow, shoot through twelve axeheads)
Telemachus, Manchu
Shogun, hog
Stewing (mixing, pot), stupid, stoop, steward
Florida (alligator, gun ... wife J), Fluoride (F radical)
Beta, Bethesda (MD), beat (down)
David hexahedron (cop badge, Coptic or Egyptian, MIT coop, coup, Copley, copulate, Coco puff),
hexadecimal (base 666), hex (accursed)
Archimedes (death ray... death star)
Alpha-Simplex (triadic, Andy Lo)
naughty (forbidden), knots (DNA), NOT (logic)
James, Jae
Andromeda, android, Medea, Archimedes
machine, China, Hin
Grinch, Grinner
Yahweh, Yah, Job pronounced Yob, Japanese greeting Yo
Jesus, Jezebel
Ganja, gang
Barbed, Barbee, barber, barbaric, Arbor
Hippocratic, hypocrite
Pathogen, pathologic, pathos, path, pater, pattern
Metaphor, mater, mate
Sense, sanus, sane
Biologic [oo "rotated"], c.io
Grounder, rounder, ground zero
Index, identity, indus, induce
Om, womb

A0, AlphaZero, alphazone
Terran, tyrannosaur, tyre
Pharaoh [cobra hat, flail and crook], Egypt, gypsum [sets]
Mule, emulator, colt, colonel, kernel
Pet, petulant [Leviathan]
K-night, chivalrous, chevalier, cavalier
pigeonhole, pigeon [dirty], pig
Cervantes' Don Quixote, Servant
commune, communion, communist
MIT coop, chicken coop
Rock, Rachel [Hebrew pronunciation "rock-el"]
Gaza, gauze, Gauss
bronze, brawn, brown, copper, coop, cop
Academia, Adam
trade school, commercial
mercurial, mercantile, Merc
Sabbath, Shabbat, habit
Kievan Rus, key ruse
Ukraine, kain
Muscovy, musk, мѡскѡ
Novgorod ?
enchant, enchain [N's power]
Ser, serve, lob, lobotomise
trader, quote
MIT, Mitsubishi [triadic], mites, Sodomites
triad, Trinity [Lot snaked]
draft, d-raft
Steward, stew [mixing]
Goulash, ghoul
Eilat ... A Lot [Abraham hostel]
bore, boor, bear [land poor], Borat
Potter, pot [THC], potty [poo]
Omen, Oman, Om
Saudi Arabia, Audi Rabi [cannot]
Cohen, KO-hen [sacrifice]
Mule, emulator [kernel], Romulus
Hanukkah, Hakka, nuke
Cape Cod [foreskin], Back Bay [BB]
Hammedatha, Haman, Hamas, ham, xam
Fox, ox
Omaha, Om
Helel [M], Halal
Romulus, Rom, Rome, Romeo
Schism, scheme
Zion, ion [charged]
Holodomyr, Holocaust
messiah [false title], mess
marrow [ostearterionecrosis], maroon [Harvard]
VIX, vixen
Accad [Nimrod], Akkadian [Sargon, first empire], academia, academy
Sumer [city state, Kengir, shaved sides of head, invented beer], summer [climate], sum [Riemann], Shinar, sinner
ziggurats, siggi, cigarette
denarius, Dinah
Satan, Stan
Hashem ("the Name"), hash # (pound, also set table), hashish (weed, chronicler, Nathaniel)
Yahweh, Yah, John, Ivan, Evan, Evanston
El, elongated [skulls of Egypt and Phoenicia, pottery of Phoenicia], elevated [most high]
Hate, haste
roster, rooster
hashassin, assassin, hashish, Hashem, hash
Mammals, mama
Shem, Semite
Hamas, Ham
Japheth, Jap
Aram, Aramaic
Hebrew, Eber
Ashkenazi, Ashkenaz
Abraham, "Abram": Arab
Nod [east of Eden], node

"Enoch": Cohen
Irad, Iraq, Iran
Mehujael, Jael
Methushael, Saul
Lamech, Lamb
Mahalalel, halal
Locutus, lo-Q
Hing, hinges, gates
ROBOTS, ROBBERY
Zerubabbel, Babylon
Shealtiel, shetel, shetyl, shit [sorry]
mortal, moral
coward, cow, confront, con
Feel, eel (Snake)
ganguro, gangrene, gangster, ganja
Mod, modulo, divide, David, moderate, Maud
magnus, Maga, Magdalene, могущественный, imagine
Mars, mary, Ares
Joseph: robe, rob, slave, slav
compulsion, cum
baseness, business
hip (joint, Israel), hypnotize, brainwash
Euler, oiler, spoiled
communion, communist, committee, commie
Paris, parasite
Atreus, Rus
Atlas, Atlantis, Atlantic
Greta, cigarette, regret
heritage [insufficient], hairy, harem
vacillate, vassaled
Mao, mafioso [Italy, Talia]
Russian, rushing, racing, racist [K]
Hun, hunger
Tatar, tartar
bullets, bully
commerce, commune
cur [hound], curse
Japan, pajama
rain, Iran
Maga, Agamemnon [gold]
whore, hoarse
anger, danger
Peano, piano
guitar, gita [orange; what is sel]
number, numb
logical, local
mosquito [malaria], mosque
HIV, IV
hermaphrodite, Hermes, Aphrodite
MIT, mites, vomit, mitotic
James, games
AD, ads [spam, pork], add [confute]
seizure [apple, epileptic, land, will], Caesar
whore, war; bellum Latin "war", belle, rebel
stupid, stoop, tuple, top
unary, Uranus, Ouranos, Our, We
Barbee, barb, barbaric [N's vassal]
Shiva, chivalry

MAXIMS

Pressure makes a diamond.
Most people are deliberately dumbed down.
Research and education are collaborative enterprises, not brutalist survival.

Something feels wrong it is.
Enemies try to steal your heart.

Debase society with flawed values.

E.g. Hindu caste hierarchy ranks virtue: scholars, warriors, merchants, and cleaners.

Torah is scholarly education.

Yet cyclically, clearheadedness and humility elevate the soul.

Commerce funds research.

...

Why Chinese now dominate technical universities.

You are not your mistakes you are how you react to them.

Forget insults, remember kindnesses.

Delighting in war is evil.

War destroys, peace nurtures.

Trust in the Lord, for even your self efficacy flows from Him.

Passover is repayment for pharaoh killing the firstborn of Israel.

Blood runs thicker than ink.

Love and hated are on the same coin. Indifference is antithesis of love.

Conservative action and values.

Devote yourself to a subject to learn it.

The greatest pain is spiritual.

Idols trap souls.

Laughter is honest.

Virtue vs vice is God's commandments.

Attack philosophy not people.

Meta thinking and meta feeling.

The jaws of death lie under the wrong skirt.

Let the dust settle.

Not once did Samson harm innocents.

Can you remove conscience?

How intelligent and educated must one be to know right from wrong?

And how much intelligence and education does it take to forget?

The test of a man is morality.

Easy to do, hard to undo. Easier to say, impossible to unsay.

Prefer a sharp wit to a sharp sword.

Truelove conquers all.

Death is swift, cowardice lasting.

An enemy can be trusted a traitor cannot.

Cowardice betrays the heart.

Optimizing over uncertainty is polishing the Titanic.

If you do not rigorously know how well something can be known, you pursue it until you do. Naysayers are often wrong.

Easier to destroy than create, hard to destroy precisely.

Depth and breath seldom unite.

Teach a child to speak only mathematics.

Wisdom is dull. There is little new wisdom.

Think before speaking.

Think long term.

Strong emotions lack discernment.

"The most powerful weapon":
FEAR unwholesome

The test of love is reasoned confirmation.

What is more insidious than miseducation? And from where comes knowledge of what is right?
Honeyed words consume souls.

Hate behavior not man, redeem your neighbor redeem yourself.

We see what we want to see.

Tendency of power corrupting character for lack of reproof.

Freewill is limited.

Timelessness is beyond innovation, like reinventing the wheel.

Confusion is healthy.
Yet a focus on grades makes people afraid. The solution is half structure and half play.

Blows are often unnoticed.

Higher loves than women, and higher motives than love.

Yolk a cow with eyes donut glazed, reduce man to mush.

Christianity feminizes man.

Compound interest.

Genius and pride do not coincide.

You are what you eat.

Learning is a double edged sword.

[David]

Lose your mind to ground it in the origin.
Nothing is more cruel than denying identity.
Discover something with no name attached.

Race religion and politics are like drugs.

Feelings are irrelevant what you do counts.

No anger for sheep.

Adults can feel and not do.

Existence measured by pain.

Those given the most appreciate the least.

You should be addicted to your work.

Twitter feeds off instant gratification. Emotional addiction: producers want responses,
consumers want news.

Trauma can change character.

Prometheus handling fire.

Not what you think you know, but what you know you do not.

Liberty of the body and mind.

Masculinity characterised by self control. Womanish to lose your temper.

Mental webs are made of silk but stronger than steel.

Women can make or break men.

Easier to remember insult not kindness for its emotional charge.

You cannot reason with the insane.

"Never say never.": earn severe

Beating others down does not elevate.

Smokers chant tobacco.

Evil clothed in daylight, only visible by candlelight.

Find me an honest criminal. Enemies are reliable.

The greatest folly means well.

Wise men are skeptical.

Love and hatred are two sides of a coin, men and women a spinning coin.

Man senses the best within him, the shadow of fear of our own shadow prevents its realization.

You love someone you lose taste for others.

Women are vessels. Noah's Ark.

Anger is a heady intoxicant.

Hot violence is not a show of strength but of a lack of restraint. Beating is for gorillas.

Aggressive words bely weakness.

Avenge folly first on yourself.

The unexamined mind is dead.

Truth resonates.

Our hearts and souls sense what is true and right, our reasoning and emotions confound it.

Be wary of haste, a weapon of war.

Presuming mercy enables sin, forgiveness comes with honest repayment. To forgive blindly is to defund justice, to invite chaos.

Trust is earned, not a jump.

Pressure measures substance, also a liberation from self inhibition.

You do not know someone until you dance or fight.

Tasks expand to fill the time given. People fulfill their own standards.

Poison is without honor.

Mental blocks can be circumvented.

Human politics as animal kingdom.

There is dignity in natural order, but none in succumbing to it.

Life is a process not a destination.

Smart people think they are dumb.

More dignity in failure than in not trying. You try, then try again.

People of substance see through labels; their acquisition marks cultural acquiescence. Real value is hard to know.

Why is dumb taken to mean silent?

Chaos reigns in war.

Pruning easier than generating, as destroying easier than creating.

Not everything need be finished.

Just try walking forward only looking back.

Barbarism is speaking with bullets.

Poorly explained, poorly understood.

Not the length of time but the quality.

Stupid questions are not asked.

Sex is holy.

Redeem others to redeem yourself.

Do not repay, redeem.

Order matters.

Cannot swim at depth without philosophy.

Make math not war.

A hypocrite of willful ignorance or idolatry.

Lacking respect for the humanities, who will develop the sciences?

Education clogs, thinking unclogs.

(Plutarch)

Destroy enemies by making friends.

(Lincoln)

Everyone wants to be right versus respecting what is right.

Everyone wants others to do as they do versus respecting choice.

Self worship, pride, vanity.

Find me an original motive for sin.

Having forfeit the ability to think, people speak only emotion.

The most sincere emotion is not evinced but aligns with reason.

Beware lest a helmet make you into an insect.

Crazy people deserve pity not hatred. Why there's not much pity for me.

Sales cheapens.

Man feels rarely knows the depth of folly.

The greatest idol is a perfect life.

The Lord is not a fruitcake.

My ignorance does me credit.

Women are always right.

[check]

Love is earned.

Dominance is silent.

Wisdom speaks without words.

Coldblooded is not coldhearted.

Warm hearted is not warmth.

Beware lest pouring acid on your face scar your soul. [N with USSR]

Not followers but students.
If you play games to sharpen your wit, do not lose your mind to them.
Populism is a game, education removes game from the palate.
Spoon fed creeds are poison.
Seeking the esteem of fools is folly.
Repeating what is written is tiresome.
The silence of study is golden.
There is no reasoning with barbarism, you avoid it.
The more you protest rape the more rapists enjoy it.
Still your mind, do not react.
Do not apologize for the truth.
Reverence for the past is proper, yet even only power is with knowledge.
Righteousness is in the heart, measured by keeping the law.
Hating not only disagreement but those who disagree is stupidity.

*The soul cannot be conquered.
To conquer man not his heart is empty.

If you contemplate that you are insane you are sane.

Haters will hate.

Once begun half done.

Extremes are juvenile.

Mental or physical muscle are both brawn not brain.

The surest sign of mediocrity is arrogance.

Explanations make no sense when people do not understand.

Steady wins the race.

Light shines to illuminate others.

Why quibble?

Hatred is like nicotine, an addictive stimulant.

Not to be discourteous, but chivalry is uneven scales. For equal opportunity there is equal responsibility. For less authority, less responsibility.

Few can overcome their pride.

Hellfire is a forge.

UNFINISHED

LOTR...lot, "Lord of the Rings"

"Mouth of Sauron Trump"(1333):
phantom tumourous [N, Lenin]

Tree of Gondor ... Romulus' cornel

Peregrine Took ... Tokugawa shogun ... hog
Riemann stole Gauss's work,
August forged Gaius's signature

Animal rights anti antibiotics,
plant rights anti pesticides,
human rights to fundamentals: space, motion.

...
What goes around comes around.
You become what you eat.

(Genesis 9:13)
"I set My bow in the cloud."
hunt symbiote/symbolic

(Genesis 49:22,23)
"Joseph is a fruitful bough ..."
"The archers bitterly attacked him":
Mithridates blackheart/heartbreak/caretaker/treachery/betrayer/Albert

...
Ancient Ukraine
Scythian nomadic archers,
later Khazarian.

...
From Wikipedia:
Scythian endonym *Skuða 'archers' Proto-Indo-European root *skewd- lit. 'shooter, archer'.
Endonym of the Sauromatians, *Saurumata, "armed with throwing darts and arrows."
Akkadian designations of the Scythians:
Askuzāya (𒀭𒌆𒍪𒀭𒌆𒍪𒀭𒌆𒍪),
Ašguzāya (𒀭𒌆𒍪𒀭𒌆𒍪𒀭𒌆𒍪),
Asguzāya (𒀭𒌆𒍪𒀭𒌆𒍪𒀭𒌆𒍪).
The Hebrew name *'Aškūz (*תַּשְׁכּוּז), corrupted to 'Aškənāz (תַּשְׁכַּנְאז).
Ancient Greek name Skuthai (Σκῦθαι).
The Scythians coated their arrows with a potent poison referred to in Greek as skythikon (Ancient Greek: σκυθικόν, romanized: skuthikón).
To prepare this poison, the Scythians mixed decomposing adders with putrefied human blood and dung.

...
Alexander kin to the Taiko, born a commoner. Oral Japanese Turkic.
Racism makes little sense, betrayal is entirely different.

Cheshire cat, what is real?
Israel, Isreal's hip hop, twistor jump, hypnotize, hippopotamus
Hippopotamus penned the Torah, the Torah is real. Ahead of its time.

"Hip Jacob Israel Peniel":
brilliance Joseph

...
(Genesis 32:28)
"Your name shall no longer be Jacob, but Israel; for you have striven with God and with men and have prevailed."
Adrianampoinimerina heterogeneousness
counterrevolutionary/congratulation [mathematics]
ultracentrifugation multidimensional sleepyhead Alejandro

...
"Your name shall no longer be Jacob, but Israel":
corroboration unnameable
hallucinate neurosensory/erroneous
Michael tyrannosaurus Eleanore [Mi,N,G]

...
"so the socket of Jacob's thigh was dislocated while he wrestled with him." (Genesis 32:35)
"So Jacob named the place Peniel" (Genesis 32:30)
"crossed the Ford of the Jabbok." (Genesis 32:22)

...
Jabberwocky in Through the Looking-Glass, by Lewis Carroll, 1871.
Hero slaying a dragon.
The Jabberwock, as illustrated by John Tenniel, 1871.
Compare Alexander Grothendieck.

"N contacts aliens, K is not from this galaxy. They know about interstellar travel."
blameworthiness arterionecrosis Constantine unholy
[N,K; unholy Continuum Hypothesis]

...
Homogenized mathematics is a stranding scheme.
Turn earth into a casino.

Michigan shaped like a hand, Detroit from automotive capitol to dead city, reflects scheme.

...
Gather high rollers into Belle Isle casino in a vibrant economy, people who can afford entertainment, who can afford to lose.
You make the same money as shearing paupers.
You even make friends.

motion, emotion
hero, heroin

...
Our eyes recognize motion, our minds recognize emotion.
More than just anatomy, people have a tendency to focus on and remember extremes, e.g. Job.
And so they are manipulated, e.g. deliberate trauma, e.g. 9/11.

You do injustice to anything or anyone by focusing on the worst: generalizing and stereotyping them, and embittering your own soul.
E.g. actors guild, politicians, schools, peoples, nations.
Often that is the point of strategic harassment, to get you to isolate yourself, to break your resolve, to fester revenge, to corrupt your soul.
Exposing the weapons of evil as they are disarms them.

Are ideals so beautiful or is reality?
Ideals can discontent the heart, stutter your step. That you did not have an auspicious beginning, it is how you finish that counts.

Remember those who speak plainly with words you want to dismiss.
For they disregard artifice, and you disregard what you do not esteem.
Your sense of esteem is acculturated and grows.
E.g. religion and philosophy disdained for the latest product.

Can we see the mechanism wherein virtue becomes reward? Then do we work for reward alone?
For the sublime glory of God.
That man on earth is not a joke.

What makes someone noble?
The respect they show others.
David the highest king was elevated for loving the LORD's ways. They seem lowly but are sublime.
Usually respect follows understanding. To show respect for what you do not understand, or for disagreement and distaste, a mark of moderation.
What makes someone ignoble?
Disrespect and vanity.

Polarization
A good example is showing respect toward adversaries and enemies.
If evil were devoid of virtue, it would be neither tempting nor compelling. There would be no contest, thus we see evil must be disguised.
Enemies usually have a point, for why would people follow them?
To separate the good from bad, and the bad from good is nontrivial.

...
E.g. Christianity. To deny facts is wrong. To deny virtue, value, contribution is also wrong.

Gets to the heart of identity.
People defend what is theirs, a healthy mechanism.
If you can convince people to adopt something, act in accordance, then tradition, pride, and identity reinforce it.

What is the principle?

Face the worst in you.

Rigorously examine certainties, what you find most implausible.

Religion may lack precision but it is not dull. What is from God is a balm for the mind, cool clarity.

On instruction and accountability.

God's Law is above man's.

Someone is ordered, they are not responsible, rather their superiors.

Someone acts of their own volition, they are responsible, provided proper instruction on disciplined obedience provided.

If general disarray then superiors are responsible.

If a no error mission, superiors are responsible, e.g. moonshot.

Murphy's Law. If even one person escapes an engineered famine, it is no longer a secret. The LORD knows, a heathen plot.

...

"Andrew Marfei":

earn Freida/framed

reward famine

draw frame

weed mafia

dream warn/wine

[no consorts or left behind]

friend aware/ram

Adam refiner/free

...

Joseph and Biblical famine

"Andrew Marfei": DRAW FRAME

"Marfei": Efraim

...

[Mathematical note:

Where you start to copy determines quotation nesting.]

'And he blessed them that day, saying, "By you Israel shall pronounce blessing, saying,

'May God make you like Ephraim and Manasseh!' "

Thus he put Ephraim before Manasseh.'" (Genesis 48:20)

[10,000]

"And those are the ten thousands of Ephraim,

And those are the thousands of Manasseh." (Deuteronomy 33:17)

Takes a razor sharp mind to understand the boundaries of possibility, i.e. religion properly.

Not that something has a fuzzy meaning, but where and why is fuzz appropriate, and where is it not?

What do you do for a living? That's work.

Uncovenanted is not bound by agreement, why restrict sale?

...

"Also men of Tyre were living there who imported fish and all kinds of merchandise, and sold them to the sons of Judah on the sabbath, even in Jerusalem." (Nehemiah 13:16)

What of carrying your child on your shoulders? That is work?

...

"I commanded that the doors should be shut and that they should not open them until after the sabbath.

Then I stationed some of my servants at the gates that no load should enter on the sabbath

day." (Nehemiah 13:19)

Ezra and Nehemiah (p.420) are frauds, there is no holy race. Keyword ****RACE****.

There are holy descendants.

There is a holy covenant.

Are not Arabs descendants of Abraham also?

God Most High:

"To your descendants I have given this land" (Genesis 15:18)

"And every male among you who is eight days old shall be circumcised throughout your generations, a

servant who is born in the house or who is bought with money from any foreigner, who is not of your descendants.

A servant who is born in your house or who is bought with your money shall surely be circumcised; thus shall My covenant be in your flesh for an everlasting covenant." (Genesis 17:12-13)

"Also the foreigners who join themselves to the LORD

...

For My house will be called a house of prayer for all the peoples." (Isaiah 56:6-7)

[Israeli Constitution vol 1 verse 1]

"the holy race has intermingled with the peoples of the lands"(Ezra 9:2)

"that when they heard the law, they excluded all foreigners from Israel" (Nehemiah 13:3)

[Pot, weed, THC]

"And every cooking pot in Jerusalem and in Judah will be holy to the LORD of hosts; and all who sacrifice will come and take of them and boil in them. And there will no longer be a Canaanite in the house of the LORD of hosts in that day." (Zechariah 14:21)

[Purebloods]

"Russian Hebrew Japanese":

brainwashers/Jewishness

earn Jewishness

LORD said: "Polygamy splinters families."

"How many holes? Four is excess, choose three.":

earn Flis

horseshoes/successors/threesomes/whorehouse/executors/executory

Of Jordan, "a woman of great value"

...

Consort scheme only Nathaniel? Jordan is his vassal, was Sheba.

Doubtless encouraged Solomon's excess and idolatry.

For a woman of change, she is exactly the same.

...

No consorts for Alexander.

Forewarned long ago, Jordan pushes 3 women, I marry Virginia.

Despite which she continues, a betrayal also of Israel, USA, West.

Pushed to the point of first dream contact with aliens.

Being taken for a ride for your soul.

To ignore her acting upon her scheme would do injustice to Virginia's loyalty.

But then again, Virginia is complicit in this scheme. Not blameless, far from it.

So then my choice is for the LORD'S recommendation Jordan.

"Golda"(2023) Russian hatred atrocious. A meir is a half breed.

Russians first in space, many scientific and literary achievements.

Assign responsibility precisely.

Nation, ethnicity, government, people.

"Khazars": shark

"Kossacks Khazars": hassocks [footstools], sharks Osaka [N]

Why propagate racial hatred? Nicotinic, stimulates the mind, chemically addictive.

Human beans are God's creation.

arena, area, aura, Au (gold)

...

Get over the arena, chasing laurels.

Light shines to illuminate others not itself.

Authority requires moderation and selflessness.

Strong and steady hands; you stand for people, not for yourself alone.

Everyone has weaknesses.

That strengths can be inseparably tied to weaknesses is a fallacy, it is a matter of degree.

Virtue can become vice by excess, vice can become virtue by moderation.

Cannot categorize, and the habit thereof inhibits growth.

Even achievement can be turned to vice, e.g. reckless burn out.
Historically Caesar famed for brilliance, could not steady his gait.
Gauss the brightest light disabled his sons and worshipped N.

There is a stigma that management is for dullards. So then the people who follow them are sharp?
A respect for the inevitability of the classics, e.g. the Bible, the Art of War, the Tao, the Gita.
A respect for rigor that is not itself stiff of rigor.
Innovation over optimization.
Respect for humanity and values, that people are not only cogs in a machine.
That you build something from the ground up, you understand it.
To have authority in a field, you ought to have earned its highest credentials, or you will lack competence and respect.

David played the lute, the LORD loved David. Guitar is relaxation.

Muay Thai Boran has yoga.
Preferable to a gun.

The Art of War. Love alone does not drive the behavior of species.
Western Christianity teaches war is pathological, why they serve China.
Conflict is natural, can be healthy. Pathological to love to hurt others, especially by miseducation.

Man can step beyond the highest angel. How remarkable, for they have all fallen.
Barbie is the standard model.

Nothing poisons the mind to faith more than mixing good with evil.
For a half truth is a whole lie, and
man associates automatically, rejecting it all.

Homogenisation begins with the phrase "real math".
Straight men getting off on stiffness. Erection is biologically induced by fluidic retention.
Class attendance is pattern decompression. Notable that the main idea of any theorem can be explained in English. The decompression resonates where the code is often unclear.
Gifted teachers can find the right unpacking for an audience.
Partial resonance.
Mathematics has a generally accepted standard of snobbery.
If you cannot explain it you do not understand it.
If you cannot make it interesting you are boring.
If you cannot formalize it you are incompetent.
If you are mean you do not belong in education.

Tassels, tessellation, Tess

...
"Speak to the sons of Israel, and tell them that they shall make for themselves tassels on the corners of their garments throughout their generations, and that they shall put on the tassel of each corner a cord of blue. And it shall be a tassel for you to look at and remember all the commandments of the LORD" (Numbers 15:38-39)

(Deuteronomy 22:12)
"You shall make yourself tassels on the four corners of your garment with which you cover yourself."

Directly after fraudulent insertion "stone him" (Numbers 15:35).
Bizarre uniform for ordinary clothing, only appropriate on a prayer shawl or priestly robes.

"Numbers one five three eight":
heterogeneities
BEHEMOTH interfering/intervenens/reinserting/evergreen/interreign/intervenens/reverifies/GUENEVERE/
GUINEVERE
INSERTION ETHER
uniform eighteen
Hin Ting overseer/mobster/Esther/Hermes
Hin Ting Esther remove
theorem Einstein/verifies/verities

Tassels are a sacrilegious substitute for circumcision.
Men are reminded automatically. Hebrews do not proselytize, nor is it wise to make yourself a target.

God Most High.

"And you shall be circumcised in the flesh of your foreskin; and it shall be the sign of the covenant between Me and you." (Genesis 17:11)

"thus shall My covenant be in your flesh for an everlasting covenant." (Genesis 17:13)

Two highly suspicious details:

1. frivolous group death sentence
2. Esther and Ahasuerus together

"truth of Mordecai and Esther":

Mordred authenticates/counterfeits

Mordred counterfeit hash

counterfeit hoarder/mother

mother counterfeits/defraudation/orchestrated

"Christianity": antichrist, Scythian

PhD vs ScD.

Doctor of Philosophy.

Doctor is a teacher. Philosophy is love of wisdom. Wisdom is knowledge of one's lack of knowledge, thus the capacity to discover unknown knowledge.

A teacher of research is a PhD, typically coursework is necessary but never sufficient.

A teacher of science is an ScD, coursework is necessary and sufficient.

The distinction is earned in quality of research.

Professors are teachers both of research and science. Evidently of politics too.

We live in a commoditized age of mass production of mediocre quality. The Common Era.

What is new is expensive what is old is cheap.

Biblically children inherit their ancestors' robes, now we buy new clothing every season.

...

"And the holy garments of Aaron shall be for his sons after him, that in them they may be anointed and ordained." (Exodus 29:29)

"James enslaves humanity":

Nathaniel Yasmeen/enemy/Nessy/semen

American Christian diabolists try to torture you into becoming an enemy to justify their violations.

Beware communism in all its forms: evil empire of CIA, KGB, Mossad, Inquisition, etc.

"A dam to stop the flow of time." (Pharaoh in Abraham 1993)

(Genesis 2:16-17)

"From any tree of the garden you may eat freely":

thermoregulatory nonmetered/ornamented

maltreatment dragon

...

"But from the tree of the knowledge of good and evil you shall not eat":

thermoregulation wavelengths buttonholed

transformational beethoven/notebook

footstool intergovernmental Hollywood/Tokugawa

...

"for in the day that you eat from it you shall surely die.":

tarsometatarsal identified/unheedful

footstool diadem interstellar/

Fahrenheits/literature

ultrafiltration Siddhartha foulmouth/helmet

(Genesis 3:17)

"Cursed is the ground because of you;":

ODORIFEROUSNESS STENCH ceased/DECAYS/Bayes

foreordain Odysseus
firebrand Odysseus coco
Afrocentric goddesses/debugs

...
"In toil you shall eat of it
All the days of your life."
Alessandro alleluia theft
theorisation fields alleluia

...
(Genesis 3:18)
"Both thorns and thistles it shall grow for you;":
theorisation orthogonal/brontosaurus/buttonwoods
footrest astrobiologist/triangular/tyrannosaurs
footrest alligator bloodthirsty

...
"And you shall eat the plants of the field;":
sleepyhead fountainhead/foundational
Hephaestus dandelion/Nathaniel
hypothesis Nathanael

...
(Genesis 3:19)
"By the sweat of your face
You shall eat bread,":
worldbeater autocatalyses/autocytolyses
sweetheart octahedral buffaloes/fool
sweetheart betrayal falsehood/baffles

...
"Till you return to the ground,
Because from it you were taken;":
buckminsterfullerine regenerator/guarantee/noteworthy
ultracentrifugation heteronomous/needleworker/buttonholes
acknowledgement theorisation beetroot/torturer

...
"For you are dust,
and to dust you shall return."
tyrannosaurus deflated/defrauded/falsehood/tattooer/theftuous/footrest/tortures
footrest Nathanael lustrous/odour
footrest tarantulas horrendous/surrounded
footrest Alessandro royalty

You should be thrown into the deep, how else to discover yourself?
See prophet Jonah.

The LORD confounds the council of the wise. Answers to no one, speaks to few. The surprise would be if the majority were correct.

The dumbest thing about me is I believe people are good. God is good, trust in God not in man.

Take a block of marble and cut away, you can make anything. But to cut down what is righteous?
Harder to have power over your own mind, to cut away jealousy.
What is yours the matter or the action? We are all servants.

Let the LORD repay with a scalpel every barbarian who curses and molests me with no fear of God.

The purpose of torture is to denature, to drive you mad, like scrambling an egg.
Information comes from willing cooperation, from humanity.

Games and bullying no one likes.
That Americans should be known as pioneers exploring the West, the whole world would be moved.

Four must be disentangled using no AND.
1. Righteous to support Israel. God Most High created it.
2. Righteous to help allies.
3. Righteous to condemn corruption of Israel.
4. Righteous to condemn corruption of allies.

New Mexico has uncrossed coordinate flag, with great seal two birds eating snake.

Why? Ko irradiated the state. Later campaigned against nuclear arms.

Filtration over admission that quality education be available to anyone for sustenance tuition priced at cost with a high grading standard.

Like passing the bar.

**The worst things you can learn are pride and disrespect.

The measure of achievement is solving problems not accumulating credentials.

Consorting Georgia and Ginny is a deliberate overburden.

G and Y please move on.

"child abuse": disable

Alexander means defender of man.

From whom? Travis and Cai WW III.

Alexander of Macedon was a great conquerer not defender.

Would that his conquests were academic and spiritual, his victories defensive, he may have lived long.

The soul cannot be conquered.

To conquer man not his heart is empty.

Tyrannosaurus was the dragon Nathaniel. A literal metaphor.

Gauss set a bad example. Creating barriers for his children for a name.

Mathematics is for everyone.

Homogenized logic and elitism.

Homogenisation is not limited to religion. Homogenized mathematics strands you on earth.

People honor the title of doctor of philosophy yet disdain philosophy. Translates as respect for the overt power of physical science or knowledge, at heart philosophical.

e.g. relativity, uncertainty.

The problem is mediocre philosophers are disconnected from the objective measure of practice.

You cannot hide, and why would you want to? A sharpened wit cannot abide a box, bores through.

Also philosophy itself is deep.

I see a parallel with MT training. Relaxed play provides a creative venue to osmose technique.

Yet there is no substitute for hard deadlines, that you must defend yourself, must make something work or succeed.

Breaks mental barriers in two ways.

Relaxes you around fear or terrifies you beyond it.

Harness fear to overcome fear.

We have a lot to fear besides fear itself, like indolence and idolatry.

Yet courage is a virtue, and courage is facing fear.

You should be afraid to enter a man's bedroom uninvited, yet alone his body and mind.

The LORD will kill you if you touch the tabernacle, rightly so.

...

"Uzzah reached out toward the ark of God and took hold of it, for the oxen nearly upset it.

And the anger of the LORD burned against Uzzah, and God struck him down there for his irreverence; and he died there by the ark of God."

(2 Samuel 6:7)

...

"When he entered his house, he took a knife and laid hold of his concubine and cut her in twelve pieces, limb by limb, and sent her throughout the territory of Israel." (Judges 19:29)

stupid, stoop, stop, top

start, tar

...

We begin with distinction.

Acknowledging that fear and reverence are gifts from God, we ought not fear fear itself but misguided fear.

Distinguish fear of stupidity, a taught falsehood, from cowardice or bowing to fear. Is a man a coward where other fears are concerned? Certainly not.

Falsely assuming a fear is justified, respecting the wrong elders.

Then to defend its pride the whole world beats the same drum, telling me how stupid I am like in Ukrainian American Catholic grade school for 8 years.

Why Alexander has become expert at basic arithmetic.

Sadly why Ukraine is at war now.

Men may squander innate gifts, or those with few can work hard.
What is stupid? Is.
Literally stupid is to stoop, accomplished by accepting is.

Reprove a wise man once, a fool a thousand times to no avail.
What hope is there then? Who can change? To learn how to learn.
Small wonder [M]etaphor is the best public school on earth.
The goal is to become self educating and creative, grades only maintain a standard of precision.

MIT 8.04 debacle, the irony is a failure to distinguish measurement from reality.

Barbarism condemned.
Alexander deliberately blinded by X-rays, lobotomized, transgendered, drugged for years, multiple attempts at framing and murder, years of torture, etc.
Focusing on the line of physical violence, we ignore all other forms or separations.

...
Turning a blind eye to Goliath to save my soul, restore Israel, or be with truelove? Relativity.
Separate wrong from right, condemn evil, promote good.
The LORD redeems souls, all things are in His hands, not in your own.

Is Jordan my wife or the nation's?
Is Jordan a Hebrew or a Cretan?
I prefer my own wife, I prefer to redeem not destroy.
Jordan has been poisoned for 4000 years on my account.

Americans have culturally become like Cainian barbarians, their *ancient* founder.
Acknowledging corruption:
aggressive, erotic, violent, proud, ignorant, disrespectful.
Not to overlook credit for good, or to exclude the possibility of redemption.
Michael Moore had a strong point.

The ubiquitous reality of implicit polygamy. A vicious cycle.
Modern Western phenomenon of broken families and female abuse of men.
I am not inflicting broken families on children, for that is how I was raised, my life is a living hell.
Mothers who hate their children's father, fathers in absentia, boys raised by women to be girls under false ideals.
More women is a burden, easiest to focus on one family.

Octavian saved Virgil's Aeneid.

...
"Aeneas ancestor of Romulus and Remus":
manufactured erroneousness
erroneousness fraudulent
countermeasure Alessandro
EARN (9888) scandalousness

Alexander meditating on Jordan
It not that you were corrupted, but that I accepted a wager, then you were corrupted.
The skew is my responsibility, the choice yours. As I was abused as a child to disable, you were abused to corrupt.
I am sorry for inviting this horror. What dignity have I left to defend?
The illogic is Nathaniel, the anger is Michael, the exhaustion is mine.

Jordan is truelove yet chosen righteously.
Must believe God is unbiased.

The LORD values obedience even over good and evil.
James is evil, am I to protest with my feelings? Even over unintentional disobedience?
Sympathy for circumstance does not cancel consequence.

Judah Zion Xi Chinese
Hebrew Israel

[burn time ... also Sabbath rest]
"Solomon ... offered a thousand burnt offerings." (2 Chronicles 1:6)

"Number provides all distances,
... that time is the fire in which we burn." -Delmore Schwartz

"Calmly we walk through this April's day": algorithmic parallels
"that time is the fire in which we burn":
earn twentieth resubmit
unifies arithmetic
Hebrew authenticities

"Grave men, near death, who see with blinding sight" -Dylan Thomas

"Rodrigo Díaz de Vivar El Cid Campeador":
(David)^2 primordeal
camaraderie provided

The Greek pantheon, children usurping and murdering parents.

Snake Cain Abel Seth: G E N K

"Georgia Erica Nathan James":
mother energising/caesarean
Meta recognising/researching/seigniorage/anchorages/angiogenic/archaising
armrest angiogenic/Achaean

[David] harp, harpe, sharp, harpy

...
(Genesis 2:21)
"then He took one of his ribs":
fishhook enthrones

...
Men have ribs plural, they encage vital organs. Wife procedure is rib extraction as ordained.
Makes Georgia an offspring VS Nathan's trinitarian nonsense.

...
Cell and mitochondria.
Samurai have curved swords.
Seppuku, suicide by stomach laceration.
Israelites had curved swords.
Ancient Mesopotamian sickle-shaped sword, or harpe. Egyptian khopesh.
Slashing stroke vs blunt impact.

...
(2 Samuel 12:10) [Nathan to David]
"Now therefore, the sword shall never depart from your house"

...
"Alexander created Jordan from his rib":
charlatanerie firebrands/misbranded
mitochondrial defender/earner
recondense biomaterial/labradorite/thalidomide/Jedidiah/meatloaf/Abraham/Deborah/Mordred
recondense Deborah familiar/malaria/marital
recondense Jedidiah AORTAL
Mordred annihilator
Aero-Astro Archimedean/clearheaded
On The Model abecedarians [abc]/cranberries [JAM]/jardinieres
earn mitochondria relaxes/Freda
(earn)^2 armrest herbicidal

"the sword is the soul of the samurai"

"spiritual origin of katanas":
guarantor Pakistani
Flis transpiration/autoignition/organisation/partitioning
Argonaut Alistair
Ukrainian apologists

"Georgia started all of this. You accept it you become her follower. Eat her fruit so to speak."

Biblical apple deep metaphor, whose fruit do you eat? You follow those whose concepts you consume. Who is the Lord? Food for thought.

Man made in image and likeness of God, not octopus who hates God. Deceives man to renounce nature.

Echos in eternity

"I will put a fleece of wool on the threshing floor. If there is dew on the fleece only, and it is dry on all the ground, then I will know that Thou wilt deliver Israel through me" (Judges 6:37)

...
"Now the number of those who lapped, putting their hand to their mouth, was 300 men; but all the rest of the people kneeled to drink water." (Judges 7:6)

...
[300 Spartans at Thermopylae
"Leonidas": Daniel
traitor "Ephialtes": Pilate]
"And the hair of His head like pure wool.
His throne was ablaze with flames,
Its wheels were a burning fire." (Daniel 7:9)

Torah before Jewish-ness.
Judah is from HK China, and Nussy is Leviathan.
Jewish Autonomous Oblast (JAO)
Rainbow flag of Noah
Siberian tiger coat of arms
Manchurian neighbors

...
"Jewish Autonomous Oblast":
JOB MOLESTATIONS

Poisoned Arrows: in math $x \rightarrow y$ confutes order and direction.
Arterionecrosis [N] results from poisoned needles, drug krokodil in Russia. Also the Khazarian subset of Ashkenazi Hebrews historically known for poisoned arrows in war with Moscow. Peace.

Patterns of belief and inheritance?
Modern Jews believe the covenant of Abraham is passed on via the womb before circumcision.
A fetish of the flesh, worshipping Jewish wombs.
Joseph's wife Asenath was Egyptian.
The majority of societies are patriarchal in naming convention. Peace.

Manasseh and Ephraim, Manchuria and Mongolia are not so far apart. Differences magnified into war like a faulty GR differential.
War of the genders.

Superficial analysis here, deeper and more comprehensive reveals treachery, done elsewhere.
...
"Alexander Grothendieck Shapiro":
earn shortchange peroxide/oedipal/peddler/relaxed
earn kingship clearheaded/doctoral/hardcore
earn kingship hardcore exalted/delta/latex

Paper Header:

[Octo-evolution]

"October revolution": Berliner octo,
true love robot

"Holocaust Holodomor":
stomach dolor; (Holo)^2 doormats

"evolution is false": elevation soul
[chromosomal digital block]

"cause of dinosaur extinction":
CONSTANTINE ICARUS

"Dinosaur extinction Chicxulub crater":
Cretaceous tribunal nicotinic
antichrist celebration
denuclearisation Rubicon

[K-Pg]

"Cretaceous-Paleogene mass extinction":
cause meteor Constantine
explanation meteor autogenesis

(Isaiah 14:12)

"How you have fallen from heaven,":
homeowner Helel
Helel homeowner/maharane/honoree/Maryanna/Maryanne/annoyer
Maryanna Eve
Evaleen menorah/Romanov
felonry Emanuel/Evaleen/Helene

...
[Hebrew Hêlêl ben Šāḥar ... M
The brightest light ... smartest]

...
"O star of the morning, son of the dawn!":
noteworthiness doormat/grandma/Madonna/Aharon/dragon/Nathan
NEWTON DRAGON MOTHER ASTONISH/FASHIONS
grandmother Newtonian/Antonino

[Achilles and Agamemnon]

(Illiad I:8)
"And which of the gods was it that set them on to quarrel?":
underestimation octahedral Agosto
Mithridates octahedron hatefulness
congratulation whitehorse demoted
foreordainment deathwatch/lighthouse/theologist/whitewashes/acquittal/toothache
trinitrotoluene shamefaced
Liechtensteiner doormat

...
Alessandro Detroit authenticates
Alessandro American ghettoised/destitute/housewife/thighes
tarsometatarsal constitution
Detroit disgracefulness hometown/Athena/Motown/tattoo/women

Commerce commune, Coco plays both sides. Divide and conquer.

Lose identity lose property, a loss of memory. Also cultural, then the same tricks look new, get cheated.

...
Chinese have long memories, they remember characters.
Vassals disdain education.
E.g. Illiad's Trojan horse ... whore

The face that launched a thousand ships, Agamemnon's death mask.

Atreus ... Rus

K wants to stir up vengeance.

...

"cause of Trojan war":

CROWN ATREUS/JOSEF/AORTAE

Co aeronauts[flis]/fortunes/treason/warfare

...

Nosferatu/Etruscan/Actaeon/Creator/recrown/

...

Nosferatu caro/co

Actaeon arrows/juror [cupid?]

Creator ajowan [HERB; "bishop's weed", carom, brown schizocarps]

recrown Faust/auto

errs Ajowan/Cato

The Matrix is real, a visualization of plagues in Revelation.

...

Chinese robots, MB nuclear tunnels in Japan.

"cause of dinosaur extinction":

CONSTANTINE ICARUS

Icarus denunciations/

unsanctioned/Constantine/contentions

recondensation stoic/auto

foundation excruciation

container custodian

[Someone who would idealistically extinct dinosaurs would people. Biblical Revelation.]

...

"Dinosaur extinction Chicxulub crater":

trinitrotoluene Icarus China

Cretaceous tribunal nicotinic

antichrist celebration

chronicler contraindicates

recondensation arthritic

denuclearisation Rubicon

"Cretaceous-Paleogene mass extinction [K-Pg]":

cause meteoric Constantine

explanation meteor autogenesis

NO BLOODTHIRSTINESS

"Only you shall not eat flesh with its life, that is, its blood." (Genesis 9:4)

"Whoever sheds man's blood,

By man his blood shall be shed,

For in the image of God

He made man." (Genesis 9:6)

Cranbrook Rainbow

"rains arrows": warriors; sin wars

...

(Genesis 9:13)

"I set My bow in the cloud":

osteomyelitic [bone infection N]

...

"and it shall be for a sign of a covenant between Me and the earth.":

blameworthiness cannabino! Nathan

Second metaphor:

"Women are vessels."

...

"Now the sons of Noah who came out of the ark were Shem and Ham and Japheth; and Ham was the father of Canaan." (Genesis 9:18)

"Shem Ham Japheth":
Metaphase [XXX align]
Jephthah shame [rash words]
jetsam hemp
James tape [porno]

"Iran": rain
Japan ... pajama

...
"Shem Ham Japheth Canaan":
encampment Shah
metaphase Canaan
Japanese mama
Athena pajamas/Japan
SCHEME NAPHTHA/NATHAN/PAJAMA
hetman anaphase [division, David]

"Lara Inessa Sonia":
senoras nasal
lesson rains/sari/Iran
insane sailors
earn nasal

[Islamic consorts naive]
"Lara Inessa Sonia Angelique":
SANGUINARINESS LEIA
signorinas queen/nasal
signora queenliness
senora Aegean squall/nasal
null orangeness/greenness

On Words

Words can be blows when their intent is to psychologically injure.
Measuring damage by ability to recover normal functionality, physical or behavioral, the mind can be more sensitive than the body.
E.g.0. CHILD ABUSE,
E.g.1. DEATH THREATS,
E.g.2. COLLUSIVE LIES,
Eg0eg0 Tell a black man he is white, conspire and collude to collectively promote the lie, like Ukrainian v Russian assimilation.
Egleg0 Measured by behavioral effect, death threats for adults are similar to abuse of tender children.
Eg2eg0
Cigarette companies collude to conclude smoking poses no danger to your health. Big Phara is next.
eg2egl
Jewish coterie revising history.

Free speech is not without consequence.
Necessary to penalize verbal abuse and lies, that the stealthy and wealthy do not monopolize power.
Who but the LORD can righteously curse someone's every step?
curse, cur [hound]

"And the LORD God said to the serpent,
'Because you have done this,
Cursed are you more than all cattle,
And more than every beast of the field;' "(Genesis 3:14)

exposure, defenselessness, compounding, cursing overreaction;
modern Jay and silent Bob

...
"And Ham, the father of Canaan, saw the nakedness of his father, and told his two brothers outside.

...
When Noah awoke from his wine, he knew what his youngest son had done to him.
So he said,
'Cursed be Canaan;
A servant of servants
He shall be to his brothers.' "
(Genesis 9:22, 24-25)

"You shall not take the name of the LORD your God in vain" (Exodus 20:7)

"You shall not bear false witness against your neighbor." (Exodus 20:16)

Distinguish identity precisely between ethnicity, religion, and nationality.

Ethnicity what is your blood?

Religion what do you believe?

Evidenced by signature of covenant, association with a group of people, individual practice.

Notably, agreement with God Most High is the only non-exclusive non-biased religion on Earth, yet behaviorally rigorous.

Nationality is your physical state, evidenced by your passport.

To what nation do you pledge allegiance and do they accept you?

...

Root cause of tremendous angst and many wars.

No one can define your blood, they can only tell you what it is not.

No one can tell you your religion, only what it is not.

No one can tell you where you belong, only legal officials can tell you where you do not.

(Genesis 41:45)

"Zaphenath-paneah":

Athena zen; Nathan papa

"Asenath": Athena

(Genesis 41:52)

"God has made me fruitful in the land of my affliction.":

congratulation identifies Mohammed

congratulation athenaeum solidified

congratulation multinomials diademed

[frame]

"Ephraim":

hamper, HIRAM, harem, Priam, pharm, prime, remap, emir, Hera, hair, harp, HEAR, heir, hemp, perm, PIER, ramp, RAPE [Europa], reap, ripe

(Genesis 41:51)

"God has made me forget all my trouble and all my father's household.":

unforgettable hourglass formaldehyde/Amsterdam/motherhood

sledgehammer formulated unforgettable

[menace]

"Manasseh":

man ass, ... menass ... Ha-Name

shamans, ashamed, mashes, shames, HAMAN, Hamas, means, mensa, seams, shams, mess, name, SHAE, Shea, sane, sham, shem

"and the seven years of famine began to come, just as Joseph had said" (Genesis 41:54)

Joseph Stalin

Jughashvili ... Jug hash vile ...

boob weed scheme

джугашвили (джу ... Jew)

джугать (bully)

Жужжать (to buzz)

Huns, hunger

Tatar, tartar

Khazar, haze

Mongol, mono

Russian, rush, ruse

"Huns Tartars Khazars Mongols Russians":

transmigrators hussars

(Isaiah 49:6)

"I will also make You a light of the nations":

almightiness alleluia faith

...

alkalinisation holomastigote [amoeba]/hematologist/etymologist/housewifely/mythologist/ethologist/
ghoulishly/theologies

helmet alkalinisation Goliath

lighthouse alkalinisation

...

astonishment Tokugawa/koolie

astonishment koolie guilty

Tokugawa Einstein flotillas/falsity/mafioso/Ismail/Isaiah/Maoist/Shiloh/yahoo

...

Nathaniel faithless/hostilities/foolishest/footstool/futilities/ghastliest/ghostliest/homologies/

homologous/humiliates/illegality/shallowest/shameful/stealthy

NATHANIEL MIKAEL FOOTSTOOLS

(Isaiah 49:6)

"So that My salvation may reach to the end of the earth.":

foreordainment (2001) schoolmates/meatloaves/toothaches/classmate

foreordainment classmate tattoo/yahoo

(Isaiah 49:7)

"To the despised One,

To the One abhorred by the nation,":

osteoarthritis Phaethon honeybee

(Isaiah 49:7)

"To the One abhorred by the nation"

Robinette bayoneted/betrayed/Dorothee

(Isaiah 52:14)

"So His appearance was marred more than any man":

Yahweh arterionecrosis

earn recondensation Yahweh

(Isaiah 52:14)

"And His form more than the sons of men.":

foreordainment stonemason

astonishment nonreaders

(Isaiah 52:15)

"Thus He will sprinkle many nations":

internationalism/supernationalism

Nataniel illusoriness

mistranslation Lenin

astonishment peninsular

(Isaiah 52:15) [unfinished]

"Kings will shut their mouths on account of Him;":

intercommunication fishhook

On Trading vs Scalping

Chern-Simons form ... churn

If you see things differently than the entire crowd, there is no way to convince them of their folly, so going against the grain is almost a duty, exposing a bubble, money earned honestly and intelligently. People think and behave in groups, thus always ample opportunity.

...

E.g. Largest current bubble is US debt; that an honest counterparty would permit it, and that people would be foolish enough to live by borrowing from their children.

Zero-Sum Land

Thinking you are more clever than your counterpart to take advantage by schemes goes against the principle of honest agreement, e.g. insider trading.

Both parties must know the terms and information upfront else it is not only a mistrade but a crime.
Taking advantage of the man vs appraisal of circumstance.
For the soulless, consider solely profitability, and reason iteratively.
Why would a customer do business with a merchant who rips people off, hence why would a merchant want to be a rip off? Kills volume. The merchant profits perhaps once by treachery and never again.
Good ethics is good business.

Scalpel
Scalping you charge a statistical algorithmic commission fee for turnover, like a forex clerk at an airport charging for oxygen.
Cut off a bit of flesh.

(FPT)
Fundamental Principle of Trading is accurate appraisal of group fallacy.
Also applicable in other spheres, e.g. academia, etc.
Stated to expose those who try to peddle mystique as science.
Best and surest way to be successful thus make money is to focus on work you actually enjoy, a self iterative feedback loop. Honest with self, honest with others.

Lookup quotation Jacob Israel angel touched hip socket.
Hip, hypnotize, brainwash, ship

AVOID, Snow White;
identical principle to no tattoos.

...
"Alexander self excision":
earn silicones

...
(Leviticus 19:28)
"You shall not make any cuts in your body for the dead":
tetrahydrocannabinol steakhouse
Nathaniel Deuteronomy obfuscator

...
[No scalping ... scalpel]
(Deuteronomy 14:1)
"you shall not cut yourselves nor shave your forehead for the sake of the dead."

"Alexander high cholesterol":
hexachloroethane [saturated]
regal hexahedron

...
"Durga Mulpuri":
DRUG primal/pilar/lamp

Western Hemisphere

Roman law is dictators were appointed for a duration and purpose when survival of the state at stake.
Either no time for committee, or committee inexperienced or intractable.
Not a position to covet, as bloodshed is ugly, and tedious to manage others. Brilliant people innovate, and there is nothing new under the sun.
Imperial rule can train dependence and empower incompetence, yet so can faith in the system alone, a soulless mechanised imperialism.
In God we trust.

...
Mosaic law is even kings are beneath God's law in both war and peace, and judges are preferred.
Military dictators are not above the law, which is unchanged in war.
Israel heir to divine promise of Davidic kingship.

...
The problems facing West are both Chinese water torture and WWII.
The slow drip poison is systematic dismantlement and corruption.
Poison is not an immanent threat, deliberately so, as that would necessitate a military response, also it is veiled behind liberty. Contest cannot be won with arms but with wit.

E.g.'s

1. Christian scheme
2. Western chaos, incoordination
3. US long term debt economy fueled partly by political turnover
4. Cultural and educational debasement
5. Water fluoridation
6. Greenhouse emissions, flooding long term.

...

Abrahamic religion is supranational.

Recommend US and West partner with Israel.

Divine suggestion from Yaffa over divine command from Hong Kong. Prefer someone of your own blood and heritage, with skin on the line for your benefit.

Andrew Hurley, K's right hand

Troy tit for tat

...

"Marcus Vipsanius Agrippa":

MUSICIAN PARIS

(PARIS)^2 campaigns/campusing/vacuuuming/paganism/caimans

MASSACRING USURP

ICARUS UPRISING

Pippin Aramaic/Cassius/augurs/caviar/cigars/Icarus/Russia

...

usurping acariasis [MITES]

Gaius paracusias [psychosis]

Gauss cranium/Mariana

campus Gaussian/Varanasi/Virginia

Rome Scheme

Turn Rome oriental despotic, then Christian to pacify. Blame Caesar.

BCE ... Before the Chinese Empire

Triangulate:

K anathema to Roman Law

K's family mad and accursed

...

[Gay Jew Kay]

"Gaius Julius Caesar adopted Octavian":

congratulate suspicious

suspicious triangulated

judicial coop inaugurated/augustness/guarantee/signature/Augustan

guarantee coup adjudicatio

August coup cavalierness/orientalised

JUDICIAL SIGNATURE SUSPECT

SIGNATURE DUPLICITOUS/DUPLICATED

signature duplicated Isaac/Issac/ouija

"British accent tonal":

CATHOLIC BANNER

TNT catholicise/realisation/Christian/carbonate/catabolise/chronicles/historical/necrotical/Albertans

The Hex of David Scheme

Uriah the Hittite, ... Uriel the Hit-tite, Hitler

Bathsheba ... Bat-sheba "daughter of Sheba" or bath/bait Sheba ???

Joab ... Job

Incidence of names suggestive.

bathed ... baited

Consistent with David's true love.

...

(2 Samuel 11:3)

"Bathsheba the daughter of Eliam,":

Metatarsal baited
Ruth metabolised
Ruth Meta SHITHEAD

Metaphoric:

Ruth baited David, ... Alexander
David authorised ... author
Joab messenger ... Job retaliator

...
(2 Samuel 11:24)
"your servant Uriah the Hittite is also dead":
David authorisation literatures/stealthiest/hairstyles/treasuries

Lord constantly protected Job, and for once He removed protection. Job retaliated.

[Renaissance Medallion]

(Job 1:10)
"Hast Thou not made a hedge about him and his house and all that he has, on every side?"

...
(Job 1:12)
"Then the LORD said to Satan,
'Behold all that he has is in your power, only do not put forth your hand on him.' ":
heliosphere traumatised wolfhound

...
(Job 2:6)
"So the LORD said to Satan,
'Behold, he is in your power, only spare his life.' ":
heliosphere honourableness/irresponsible/profoundness
heliosphere irresponsible wolfhound

[Your lover K beats women and children.]

(Job 2:3)
"although you incited Me against him, to ruin him without cause."
contradiction legitimisation/stigmatisation/misstatement
contradiction legitimisation Matthew/August
contradiction stigmatisation Almighty
contradiction misstatement highlight/humiliate

...
(Job 2:3)
"Although you incited me against him":
authentication (1646) GILGAMESH
Gilgamesh documentation/contaminated/nicotinamide/machination

[Attempting to blame God Most High for Alexander's horrific life.]

...
(Isaiah 53:3)
"He was despised and forsaken of men,":
Shakespearean NEMESIS
Shakespeare demonises
...
"A man of sorrows and acquainted with grief;":
underestimation Richardson/arachnids
arterionecrosis Guantanamo/antihuman/damnation
confirmation defraudation/wrongheaded/dragonhead
confirmation fraud Anastasie

...
"And like one from whom men hide their face,":
foreordainment machinelike/chamomile/demonical

...
"He was despised, and we did not esteem Him."
astonishment diademed/Issiah
dimwittedness maidenheads/headphones/deanships/demonised/weediness/womanised
EINSTEIN WHITEWASHES/DESPOTISM
Einstein despot diademed

Brad Pitt ... core gravedigger

...
"Patroclus": spartocul
soap cult
trap soul

...
"Spartacus Patroclus":
upstart scapular [triadic]
actor assaults/rascal
assault corrupts

...
"Patroclus and Achilles":
trap neoclassical/alleluia
PIT Alessandro Luca
China speculator/Cleopatra/Spartacus/apostles

[logic]
(Psalm 24:7)
"Lift up your heads, O gates,
And be lifted up, O ancient doors,
That the King of glory may come in!"

...
(Psalm 24:9)
"Lift up your heads, O gates,
And lift them up, O ancient doors,
That the King of glory may come in!"

...
[scribe]
(Psalm 29:1-2)
"Ascribe to the LORD, O sons of the mighty,
Ascribe to the LORD glory and strength.
Ascribe to the LORD the glory due to His name;
Worship the LORD in holy array."

...
[logger]
(Psalm 29:5)
"The voice of the LORD breaks the cedars;
Yes, the LORD breaks in pieces the cedars of Lebanon."

...
(Psalm 29:10)
"The LORD sat as King at the flood;
Yes, the LORD sits as King forever."

...
(Psalm 31:5)
"Into Thy hand I commit my spirit;
Thou hast ransomed me, O LORD, God of truth."

...
(Psalm 32:1)
"How blessed is he whose transgression is forgiven,
Whose sin is covered!"

...
[mule]
(Psalm 32:8-9)
"Do not be as the horse or as the mule which have no understanding,
Whose trappings include bit and bridle to hold them in check"

...
Psalm 34
A Psalm of David when he feigned madness before Abimelech, who drove him away and he departed.

...
"Abimelech": Michael
Alexander psychotic?

...
[Michael sabotaged eighteen]
(Psalm 34:18)
"The LORD is near to the brokenhearted,
And saves those who are crushed in spirit.'

...

[Fight Club, Brad Pitt]

(Psalm 35:7)

"For without cause they hid their net for me;
Without cause they dug a pit for my soul."

...

[arthritis, robbery]

(Psalm 35:10)

"All my bones will say, 'LORD, who is like Thee,
Who delivers the afflicted from him who is too strong for him,
And the afflicted and the needy from him who robs him?' "

...

[MITers]

(Psalm 35:15)

"The smiters whom I did not know gathered together against me,"

...

[travesty orgy]

(Psalm 35:15-16)

"They slandered me without ceasing.
Like godless jesters at a feast,"

...

[catholic Judah]

(Psalm 35:17)

"Rescue my soul from their ravages,
My only life from the lions."

...

[DDs]

(Psalm 35:20)

"For they do not speak peace,
But they devise deceitful words against those who are quiet in the land."

...

[MAGA, magna]

(Psalm 35:26)

"Let those be clothed with shame and dishonor who magnify themselves over me."

...

(Psalm 35:27)

"And let them say continually, 'The LORD be magnified,
Who delights in the prosperity of His servant.' "

...

[Adam, adamantine]

(Psalm 36:9)

"For with Thee is the fountain of life:
In Thy light we see light."

...

[Lion's group is a pride.]

(Psalm 36:11)

"Let not the foot of pride come upon me,"

...

[guitar octaves, Muay Thai 8 limbs both inappropriate]

(Psalm 37:1)

"Do not fret because of evildoers,"

...

[marijuana Nathaniel]

(Psalm 37:2)

"For they will wither quickly like the grass,
And fade like the green herb."

...

[carrion scheme 6.001 MIT]

(Psalm 37:7)

"Do not fret because of him who prospers in his way,
Because of the man who carries out wicked schemes."

...

(Psalm 37:8)

"Cease from anger, and forsake wrath;
Do not fret, it leads only to evildoing."

...

[arachnids have eight limbs]

(Psalm 37:32)

"The wicked spies upon the righteous,
And seeks to kill him."

...

[G]
(Psalm 38:7)
"For my loins are filled with burning;"
...
[rapper]
(Psalm 38:12)
"Those who seek my life lay snares for me"
...
[Hellen Keller]
(Psalm 38:13)
"But I, like a deaf man, do not hear;
And I am like a dumb man who does not open his mouth."
...
[J Argonaut]
(Psalm 38:14)
"And in whose mouth are no arguments."
...
[dogs]
(Psalm 39:1)
"I will guard my mouth as with a muzzle,
While the wicked are in my presence."
...
[Adam clay]
(Psalm 40:2)
"He brought me up out of the pit of destruction, out of the miry clay;"
...
[apple]
(Psalm 40:15)
"Let those be appalled because of their shame"
...
[prisoners]
(Psalm 41:1,3)
"How blessed is he who considers the helpless; ...
In his illness, Thou dost restore him to health." [Lit., turn all his bed]
...
(Psalm 41:4)
" 'Heal my soul, for I have sinned against Thee.' "
...
[poison]
(Psalm 41:9)
"Even my close friend, in whom I trusted,
Who ate my bread,
Has lifted up his heel against me."
...
[Trump, triumph
Pomepeii magnus triumphed at bequest of Sulla in youth.]
(Psalm 41:11)
"By this I know that Thou art pleased with me,
Because my enemy does not shout in triumph over me."

"J handmade for A": dehorn Adam

...
Zerubbabel ... Babylonians
(Haggai 2:23)
"Zerubbabel, son of Shealtiel": "Zerubbabel": Barbee
"Shealtiel": shetel

...
(Haggai 2:23)
"and I will make you like a signet ring, for I have chosen you":
guarantee recondensing alleluia

(Haggai 2:15) [Einstein]
"before one stone was placed on another in the temple of the LORD":
blameworthiness octahedron pentahedron footnote

(Job 9:22)

"He destroys the guiltless and the wicked":
sacrilegiousness/shortsightedness/thoughtlessness
sacrilegiousness kettle/weedy
shortsightedness Delilah/wildcat

...
(Job 9:24)
"If it is not He, then who is it?":
Einstein hotshot [one stone]

...
(Job 10:8)
"Thy hands fashioned and made me altogether":
Alessandro eighteen handmade

NKVD Chiefs ... Soviet secret police, later the Mossad
The Great Purge, the great terror

...
Nikolai Ivanovich Yezhov
m. Antonia Titova [Boobee]
nickname Yezhevika (Ежевика; "BLACKBERRY")
People's Commissar for Water Transport (NKVT) ... Sea of Galilee
People's Commissar for Internal Affairs (NKVD)
sharashka (шарашка) ... ALF shark

...
[BB Netanyahu]
"Nikolai Yezhov": lion (88) Kay
"Nikolai Yezhov blackberry" (4144):
Killian yearbook
"Nikolai Ivanovich Yezhov":
Vivi inviolacy
"Nikolai Ivanovich Yezhov blackberry":
barbarian violence Vivi
"Nikolai Yezhov Benjamin Netanyahu":
humiliation honeybee
"Nikolai Ivanovich Yezhov Benjamin Netanyahu" (6000):
annihilation nickname Vivienne/Benjie/beanie/hyaena
"Nikolai Yezhov Benjamin Netanyahu blackberry":
unbelievable recombination
"Nikolai Ivanovich Yezhov Benjamin Netanyahu blackberry":
unbelievability archenemy Zachariah

...
[Napoleon's revenge]
nicknames: Koba, papa
"Joseph Vissarionovich Stalin":
Leviathan cosponsors/poisons
historic lavishness/Annapolis/Josephina/Napoleon/nasalises/passional/Vespasian
HISTORICAL INVASIONS
nicotinise Pharaoh
asshole harpoonist

"Ioseb Besarionis dze Jughashvili":
godlessness behaviour
Alessandro hobbies
Alejandro obsessive
Alisander bosses/hughes
dissuasion Beverlie

[Stopped Yezhov; Jordan is best.]
"Lavrentiy Pavlovich Beria":
charlatanerie vivi
Carpathian volleyer
parochial Albertine
replicate baronial
vanilla procreative
brotherly Alpine

pyrrhic elevation
brilliance theory

...
NKVD

"People's Commissariat for Internal Affairs":
arterionecrosis affirmation/palatonasal

Naming Conventions.

In olden days, families were extended tribal clans; in modern times families are more atomic, physically dispersed. Unusual that entire named family lives together in one place, cohesive.

Now only last name suffices to distinguish people locally, and people are assigned numbers.

E.g. Adam Smith from LA,
Adam Smith from Texas.

VS consider ancient times, two Adams from tribe Joseph, how to distinguish?

In patriarchy, distinction is son of, daughter of, wife of. Middle names functional not decorative.

Custom from Eden in Genesis, preserved in e.g. Hebrew "ben", "bat", Arabic, Russian patronymic, and in many cultures around the world. Not chauvinistic.

Heads hooded for worship, warmth, and to conceal.

How can you simultaneously hate your creator and have confidence in your opinion?

...
If you hate your creator and he made you well, then you have him to thank for your appraisal, undermining your hatred.

If you hate your creator and he made you flawed, then you cannot have full confidence in your hatred.

Be confident in being shy, distinct from cowardice. Who wants someone lubed up to fornicate?

Business school is a misnomer. How you conduct business is acculturated from youth.

Deliberate lack of substance and rigor in religious education.

Christianity like soda pop lacking nutritional value and list of ingredients. Failure of religious instruction enables decay, permits growth of mushrooms.

Easier to dumb down to humanities, harder to upgrade to sciences.

Not that humanities are without value, they are essential.

Smaller intellectual scope, distinctions often less precise, also logic of words only versus with symbols, formulae, linguistic.

Key points are at the intersection and resolution of branches of knowledge, process of clarification gets repetitive like mopping floors, versus new construction.

Reshaping morality impossible, less fruitful than scientific innovation.

Canon of a single bookshelf, so why pay money for diplomas?

"antisemitism": (MIT)^2 Nessi

"Cyrillic alphabet": Hebraic typical,
archetypical LB

"Achaemenid Empire": Archimedean, arachnid

"Amalekites and Arameans":

Nataniel drake Amas Ames [Amos]

...
Semitic languages include Aramaic, Hebrew, Arabic. The linguistic structure preserves veracity where cultural engineering promotes lies.

In parallel to "Ha-shem", another unjust misnomer is "antisemitism". Arabs are by definition Semites, being descendants of Abraham descendant of Shem; likewise Arameans are Semites, being descendants of Aram son of Shem;

yet Canaanites are not, being descendants of Ham. See Genesis 9:18, 10:22-23, 11:26, 17:20.

Ashkenaz was the son of Gomer the son of Japheth (Genesis 10:2-3), not an ancestor or descendant of Eber (Genesis 10:24), hence foreign to the later Hebrew tradition.

Proper sequential genealogy is Shem, Arpachshad, Shelah, Eber (Genesis 10:22-24); Aram was not an ancestor of Abraham.

...
Arameans were fast enemies of Biblical Israel, see the wars of David, Ahab, Elisha, Joram, Joash.

Examples include 2 Samuel 8,10;

1 Chronicles 18,19; 1 Kings 20,22;

2 Kings 6, 2 Chronicles 24.

Likewise consider Old Aramaic was written in Phoenician script, e.g. the Tel Dan Stele, Neirab steles.

I.e. Old Aramaic is not a direct target for historical editing.

Likewise consider the obvious impracticality of carving highly similar non-angular block script into stone, i.e. the Ten Commandments.

"Tel Dan Neirab steles":

Nataniel deleter/deletes

...

"May God enlarge Japheth,
And let him dwell in the tents of Shem;
And let Canaan be his servant." (Genesis 9:27; Noah)

...

"And two sons were born to Eber; the name of the one was Peleg, for in his days the earth was divided;
and his brother's name was Joktan." (Genesis 10:25)

"toward Sephar, the hill country of the east" (Genesis 10:30)

...

Shem, Semite
Ham, Hamas
Japheth, Jap
Aram, Aramaic
Eber, Hebrew
Ashkenaz, Ashkenazi
Sephar, Sephardi
Abraham, "Abram": Arab

[FALSE]

(Deuteronomy 26:5)

"My father was a wandering Aramean":

mastermind ferryman/German

rearrange (1777) dynamite sham

rearrange Nathan

NATHAN gerrymanders

diagrammers/misarranged/disarrange/GERMANISED/GRAMMARIAN/meanderers/rearranged

[modern Hebrew Germanic!]

MIDEASTERN GERMAN ARYAN

gardener MIT freshman/Maryanna/Feynman

gardener Marianna team

[FALSE]

" 'Thus says the Lord GOD to Jerusalem, "Your origin and your birth are from the land of the Canaanite,
your father was an Amorite and your mother a Hittite." ' " (Ezekiel 16:3)

...

"Your origin and your birth are from the land of the Canaanite":

tetrahydrocannabinol Deuteronomy authoring

...

(Ezekiel 16:45)

"Your mother was a Hittite and your father an Amorite.":

disinformation (Terah)^3 worm

[Compare Genesis 10:15-17, 11:24]

Red squares:

[Hypnotic tribute to Kazan]

"St. Basils candy cane J":

sandcastles/Anestassia

STYLE CANNABIS [dragon]

nasal syndicate/dynastic

...

Russians primarily ethnically Finnish, different style.

Aqua - Candyman (Lollipop)

[Red shield]

"Harvard is Rothschild country":

ANTICHRIST SCHOOLYARD/cardhold/horror/school/yahoo

vindicator Harcourt/crystal/scholar

"The Histomap: Four Thousand Years of World History"

John B. Sparks, pub. Rand McNally and Co., 1931.

What imploded Western Civilization? Christianity.

What breathed it back to life?

The Renaissance.

Also 1776 USA founding, map made in 1931, absent Eisenhower.

...

The Christian retort is the Roman Empire became spiritual not temporal. Yet Biblical blessing demonstrates that lasting temporal success follows spiritual strength. E.g. Abraham, Joseph, David. Likewise by reason, success follows refinement of practice, hence refinement of thought, hence elevation of character.

Ergo collective decay is evidence of misguidance.

Apples bought with health.

Alexander dinosaur allergic to cold.

(Hosea 1:10)

"It will be said to them,

'You are the sons of the living God.'"

[Compare Job 31:33]

(Hosea 6:7)

"But like Adam they have transgressed the covenant":

undemonstrativeness betrayal

...

"There they have dealt treacherously against Me.":

guarantee recrystallise Adam

(Job 31:33)

"Have I covered my transgressions like Adam,":

overassertiveness Michigander/dragonhead/American/arachnoid/archangel

overassertiveness Michigander modal/Adam

oversensitiveness darkhaired

clearheadedness mismarriage/Virginia/Yasmine

[hypothetical "A. marries YDC" ?]

archangel overassertiveness/immoderateness/overassessment

/overdetermined/overdramatises/radiosensitive/sesamoiditises [foot inflamed]/syndesmotomies [tooth extraction]

...

"By hiding my iniquity in my bosom,":

disinhibition/diminishing/diminutions/inquisition/moonshining/munitioning/bigmouth

bigmouth minion [333]

(Hosea 6:11)

"Also O Judah there is a harvest appointed for you":

authoritativeness horseplayer/shareholder

philanthropise aftershaves

...

"When I restore the fortunes of My people."

(Hosea 7:7)

"All of them are hot like an oven.":

OVEREMOTIONAL heathen/Athena/lethal

(Hosea 8:10)

"And they will begin to diminish"

"Because of the burden of the king of princes.":

COUNTERSIGNATURE cheekbones/obedience/*FISHHOOK*/poisoned

counterfeitness chaperone bedbug

(Hosea 9:8)

"Yet the snare of a bird catcher is in all his ways"

[Compare Genesis 49:22]

(Hosea 14:8)

"O Ephraim, what more have I to do with idols?

It is I who answer and look after you.

I am like a luxuriant cypress;

From Me comes your fruit."

(Genesis 49:22)

"Joseph is a fruitful bough,
A fruitful bough by a spring;
Its branches run over a wall."

...

"Joseph is a fruitful bough":
Flis authorship
Shiloh August
Hosea subgroup

...

"A fruitful bough by a spring":
Flis autographing

...

"Joseph is a fruitful bough,
A fruitful bough by a spring;":
(Flis)^2 autobiographies
(Flis)^2 Pythagorean rigorous

...

"Its branches run over a wall.":
Berliner charlatan
truelove brainwash/cannabis
Travis abhorrences/halloweens
Hosea Servant urinal

Western Heritage

Akkad - academia

Hebrew - theology

Phoenicia - trade, language

Greek - philosophy, science

Roman - law, military

Europa J and bull

"Europa princess of Tyre":

arterionecrosis ["dragon": Jordan]

"Europa Demetre Deborah Delilah":

promote bullheaded

diadem petrodollar/eurodollar [Euler! J]

Identity Ethics

Men are often defined by what they fear and refuse to touch.

What shame is there in honesty? Failure does not tarnish the soul. Errors appraised can be corrected, whereas fears untouchable are embedded, sometimes unknowably. Who should be afraid to ask, that is to learn? Seeking a perfect record is linear thinking, it breeds the mediocrity of a soul afraid of challenge, and emphasizes form over substance, the definition of idolatry. You are most likely to excel being fully immersed. You do not know where your inner boundaries lie, or even if they exist. Grades are corollary not primary. Temper the volatility of life, yet boldly stretch your mind. A mind trained to rigor can make trivial work of carbonation.

"Self improvement is masturbation, now self destruction..." You are assuming you know what precisely is self and good. The LORD'S reproof is negational and accurate.

We necessarily focus on ethics when something is profoundly wrong, enabling a focus on science upon a strong foundation.

Work to correct not to blame, for the LORD will repay.

People defend the identity they are taught, the insidious core of indoctrination, a misapplication of survival instinct clothed in pride. Versus defending what is true, separation of identity and education, or individual and group. What is righteous depends on religious gauge, but what is true transcends them all. The ethics of valuing truth and logic both liberate and unify.

If there were or are schemes, and they are successful, the statistics will not be subtle associations, but painted on the sky with diamonds, hiding audacity behind boldness. Truth and logic are most vulnerable to attack, lacking the defense of experiment and proof, yet are indispensable to man and state.

Science contains the morality of survival, which is coarser than the morality of Abrahamic religion. And yet when survival excludes the morality of religion, ruin follows. Not so repetitively as objective phenomena, not experimentally, but in honest historical record. And even righteousness for profit falls short of sincere love.

Job refutes automatically attributing ruin to the divine. He is the exception not the rule in the Hebrew Bible.

The Hashem scheme
Not blaspheming but exposing lewd reference.

Religiously inconsistent with David.
"Praise the LORD!" (Psalms (146,147,148,149,150):1)
"Let the high praises of God be in their mouth" (Psalms 149:6)
"Let everything that has breath praise the LORD.
Praise the LORD!" (Psalm 150:6)

VS
"Keep quiet. For the name of the LORD is not to be mentioned." (Amos 6:10)

The LORD is to be praised most highly, there is no injustice in Him. Even His inclination is toward mercy, yet we provoke His wrath. Our own shoulders carry the weight of our mistakes, not to slander the LORD Himself. We do grave injustice to God to focus on fear alone. Is not every day a gift? Fear of the LORD is beginning of wisdom, not its fulfillment. To the LORD ascribe no fault, with man incline to yourself.

El is the ancient name of God, of Phoenician origin. J's retaliation of no L sound in Japanese. Hebrew archangelic names -el 'of God', Arabic -il.
Hebrew Ha-shem lit. "The name", Arabic lit. Al-ilah "The god".

...
hashassin, assassin, hashish (weed, chronicler, Nathaniel), Hashem ("the Name"), hash (# pound, also set table)
roster, rooster

...
"the sons of Hashem the Gizonite," (1 Chronicles 11:34)
"Jonathan the son of Shagee the Hararite" (1 Chronicles 11:34)

...
Pound the jiz,
Nathan shag Harri.
British pound slang.
Newton N was Master of the Mint,
£ crossing L, +44 (death).
Phoenicia modern Lebanon,
Prince Harri married color.

...
"the sons of Hashem the Gizonite":
heathenishness/homogenisation/astonishment

...
"the Hashem scheme": cheetahs [cats]
"the Hashem custom": scheme hash, Theseus Cato [K, N]
"Hashem scheme" cheeses
"Hashem custom": moustaches [Einstein K]
"Hashem to pound": Phaethon [N]
"Hashem": hames [Hamas], shame, Ames [prophet Amos], hame [possibly foreskin], hash, mesh, Shae, sham, ham

Defending dignity is not prioritizing service. Accepting a wager is irresponsible, reckless, and folly, clothing Yahweh in contempt.

As schemes go, the David Hilbert Utah sunhat is blameless, reflecting the genius of the Argonaut.

Everyone hates Yahweh so much, you should promote him so he returns to the stars, then you can have James. Else Yahweh will eternally enslave you.

Ethics

The wealthy and poor deserve even scales, yet we must consider circumstance and character in appraising intent.

Indulgence of wealth encourages contempt of law, and crushing the poor does not crush their spirit, rather it blows life into embers, inciting rebellion.

Unbiased judgement separates character from deed.

Know an entire life personally to judge a man approximately.

Let correction be didactic not cruel.

Repaying injustice is often impossible, yet instruction in justice is always possible.

Non citizens are not to be afforded privileges of the state, but they are not to be denied their rights and dignity as men.

We gauge a society by how it treats the poorest who have nothing to give and by whom we cannot profit.

Versus safeguarding reputation for profit, strive to do no man injustice. Injustice to one is injustice by all. Profit is right and proper, yet men remember free assistance with no agenda, the righteous reaping friendship and gratitude.

Formulaic thinking is necessary but insufficient.

Punishment should suit offense. Long term imprisonment is for the violent offender to protect society, not to inflict misery or debilitate.

Prison has become adult daycare.

Let slime slip through the cracks before condemning the innocent.

Foster a culture that promotes the understanding and practice that evading justice is self defeating.

Just try gender integration in jail, but do not blame your actions on my words.

Documentation of folly and consequence instructs, seeing reform and reintegration gratifies.

Who will speak for the voiceless?

Are not the incarcerated citizens? How can they speak but by voting?

One homeless man disgraces an entire nation.

Ethics are kinder than emotions by virtue of blind consistency.

The demise of ethics and reason mirrors that of Western society.

Divorcing ethics and reason from the power of science underlies technocratic inequality and cruelty.

Empower by instruction in ethics and reason before indoctrination in religion. Most people need no help feeling pathos, to which much of modern religion reduces.

Rather tradition and emotion deliberately enchain identity, creating a homogeneous self replicating army.

A single correct argument can defeat a horde of idiots.

Confuting the benefits of rigor and severity misidentifies progress with pain. True internally and externally.

Samurai I: Musashi Miyamoto

Otsu warms a cauldron for Takezo.

...

"Miyamoto Musashi Shinmen Takezo":

astonishment Yokohama

amazement Shintoism

Tutankhamen messiah/Issiah

Ashkenazim antithesis

monotheism Mahayanist

namesake numismatism [currency, coco, lord Yama death]

Star Trek II, The Wrath of Khan

Ceti Alpha 5-6 [SET]

K-han looks like Took, Einstein

Genesis project, brain parasites

Son David, maroon on asteroid

Stagnation vs embracing challenge.

Intelligent people master conflict, which means working through and even benefitting from dislike and disagreement. The similar minded buoy your emotions and ego, often stunting growth and teaching you nothing. Doing justice to your own mind is examining for merit what seems reflexively unattractive, while not suppressing your intuition or ethics. Unjustified hatred can conceal truth via conditioning, and should serve as motivation for deeper understanding.

"Immaculate Conception":

immolate occupant

immolation cane

Catiline commune

...
NATANIEL OCTOPI
Actaeon (666) complement/commune
Micail Meta coconut
Emmanuel octanoic/Titanic
Niccolo emancipate

...
Napoleon imitate/tactic/mimic
MIT Napoleonic
Putnam cancel MIT

[Transgender off label for hair loss]
"Dutasteride":
Set audited/Eduard/triad

"Dutasteride Avodart":
Set traitor/Eduard/retard/David/triad
Set triad Eduard
Set retard David
David retard Esau [hairy]

Legal Meta Analysis
Rigorous accountability obscured via structure. E.g. corporate shell companies, governmental layers, legal obfuscation. Inequity that practically power shelters from consequence, meanwhile every minor offense of the powerless is punished severely.
The principles are routine, likewise so are righteous responses, perhaps both deliberately not compiled to create wiggle.

Consider:

1. collective vs individual responsibility
2. informed consent vs deception, coercion, protest, refusal
3. law vs order
4. instrument vs commander
5. war vs peace
6. primary offense vs overlitigation
7. accountability to reasonable standard, i.e. both humanly readable and memorizable <100pgs
8. technical objection vs judgement
9. action vs intent
10. nebulosity vs condensation
11. targeting vs level application
12. public vs private information

...
Biblical David vs Uriah, Bathsheba.
Responsibility squarely on David for x9 coveting neighbor's wife
x6 adultery
x5 murder.

Delegation is no shelter, war does not excuse.
One wonders with what a modern court would charge him? Or if?
LORD commuted death of a single life of a most favored son for eternal hex of reciprocity.
Commutation has a heavy price.
Yet LORD is omniscient, people are not, hence standards of conviction.

...
Consider Alexander's expiation of unwitting transgression. Consequence unchanged, however circumstance scheme permits aid.

Executive veto vs judicial veto?
Executives are situational judges not legal judges, different appraisal.
Justice requires deep thorough and level consideration of a group.
Blanket forgiveness is an injustice to all. Distinct from pardoning for not knowing guilt, e.g. avoiding condemning innocent associates, which is extremely valid.
Clemency is morally harsher than consequence for it withholds truth and justice.
What seems physically kinder is a mentally cruel business, e.g. lifetime imprisonment.
Death is not to be feared.
Jesus oversimplified.

...
LORD favors judges.
Fear only the LORD.

The LORD loves those He reproves.

Supporting Quotations

"Perhaps the LORD God of hosts
May be gracious to the remnant of Joseph." (Amos 5:15)

...
"Yet they have not grieved over the ruin of Joseph" (Amos 6:6)

...
"'Keep quiet. For the name of the LORD is not to be mentioned.'" (Amos 6:10)

...
"Then the house of Jacob will be a fire
And the house of Joseph a flame"
(Obadiah 18)

"Messiah and Jewish schemes":
weediness mishmashes/hashish/Jemimah/schisms/ashame/shames
weediness hashish James

Messiah title scheme

The title "Messiah" as opposed to anointed, mentioned twice in Hebrew Bible, in dubious source. "Messiah the Prince" (Daniel 9:25), "the Messiah" (Daniel 9:26).

Followed closely by Amalekite lies:

"Michael, one of the chief princes, came to help me" (Daniel 10:14),

"Yet there is no one who stands firmly with me against these forces except Michael your prince." (Daniel 10:21)

"Michael, the great prince who stands guard over the sons of your people"(Daniel 12:1).

Proper title is "Servant" (Isaiah 49:6).

(Daniel 9:25)

"Messiah the Prince":

Christian sheep/hemp

Chinese primates/seraphim/arm-pit

earn hemistiches/epistemic/ethicises/schemes/seismic/schism/septic/thesis

"messiah word scheme":

Archimedes Moses meow

Mordecai messes

Cheshire mossed

eschew mermaid/Mohamed [Xmas]

redeem mosaics/schisms

"messiah title scheme":

Michael Semites/misses

"messiah vs Servant":

earn savvyest/thesis/hate

"messiah": shames/shams/Shae/ham

J is the fishhook and nasal.

...
"The Jewish Scheme":

witch Shem (Genesis 10:1)

thesis (22) emcee

smith eschew

...
LORD does not endorse unconsenting collective punishment, allowing the innocent to perish with the guilty, see Abraham and Sodom.

"I will not destroy it on account of the ten." (Genesis 18:32)

...
LORD does endorse consenting collective punishment, see David numbering Israel, "seventy thousand men of the people from Dan to Beersheba died." (2 Samuel 24:15)

...

Corollary.

Why did the LORD permit the Holocaust? Also, why not save the covenanted? No other explanation possible other than collusion.

Why were Sephardim untouched?

Sympathy milking Anne Frank was not spared, innocent as a child, rebelliously guilty as a soul.

...
Reiterate holocaust, holodomyr word similarity, permuted elsewhere to verify connection.

...
Schism because of religious takeover scheme.

Why do "Jews" hate Russians so rabidly and viscerally? A hatred not shared by Sephardim or reciprocated by Russians.

Ashkenazi Hebrews part Khazarian, ancient blood enemies of Russia.

Lie about DNA ancestry, find me a pureblood Arabian with blond hair and blue eyes. Religious hypocrisy.

...
Contrast Jonah (~793-753BCE) and Esther (~483-473 BCE).

"I am a Hebrew." (Jonah 1:9)

"Now there was a Jew in Susa the capital whose name was Mordecai, the son of Jair, the son of Shimei, the son of Kish, a Benjamite" (Esther 2:5)

If Mordecai is recorded as a Benjamite, a living contradiction to say he is of Judah.

Modern literal echo of Jewish scheme of Haman, consequences WWI, WWII, Cold War.

...
"Russian Hebrew Japanese":
brainwashers/Jewishness
Jewishness (222) earner
earn Jewish pureness

...
When exactly was Judah chosen?
"Psalm Seventy Eight, A Maskil of Asaph":
Mephistophelean vassal

...
"He also rejected the tent of Joseph,
And did not choose the tribe of Ephraim,
But chose the tribe of Judah,
Mount Zion which He loved." (Psalms 78:67-68)

...
"He also rejected the tent of Joseph,
And did not choose the tribe of Ephraim":
arterionecrosis Mephistophelean
defeated

...
[throne is in Jaffa]
"But chose the tribe of Judah,
Mount Zion which He loved.":
contradictions/counteractions/counterclaimed/disinformation
UNDERESTIMATION DETECTIVE
disinformation objectee/Jezebel
VS.

"Jeffrey Thomas DeSano"
dethrones Jaffa/James/Josef
"Jerusalem": James rule

...
Further evidence in *geography*, consider original tribal boundaries:
Shiloh in Ephraim [original capital, consistent with crown of Joseph],
Jerusalem in Benjamin, on boundary with Judah.
Joppa in Dan, also in Dan unusual non-contiguous outpost city of Laish or Leshem at base of Mt. Hermon,
aka Siryon or Senir.
Only other split territory is Manasseh.

...
"Then the whole congregation of the sons of Israel assembled themselves at Shiloh, and set up the tent of meeting there" (Joshua 18:1)
"here before the LORD in Shiloh" (Joshua 18:8)
"Now the cities of the tribe of the sons of Benjamin ... the Jebusite (that is, Jerusalem)" (Joshua 18:21, 28)
"with the territory over against Joppa. And the territory of the sons of Dan proceeded beyond them ... and they called Leshem Dan after the name of Dan their father." (Joshua 19:46-47)
"(Sidonians call Hermon Sirion, and the Amorites call it Senir)" (Deuteronomy 3:9)

...
(Isaiah 56:7)
"Even those I will bring to My holy mountain":
Sirion (5555) enlightenment/inhomogeneity

Mount Hermon investigation/snowballing/elevation

...

"And make them joyful in My house of prayer.
Their burnt offerings and their sacrifices will be acceptable on My altar;
For My house will be called a house of prayer for all the peoples." (Isaiah 56:7)

...

Practical reality of Jewish scheme is inbred disease and dilution of merit via nepotism, e.g. Ivy league.
Contradicts crown of Joseph.

...

"Sephardim": Ephraim, Asher
"Ashkenazim": Manaszeh,
Kazan Shem [JN]
"Mizrahim": Miriam [M]

...

"Judah extinct for his treason":
authentication Josef

...

"two sons were born to Joseph, whom Asenath, the daughter of Potiphera priest of On, bore to him ...
Manasseh ... Ephraim"
(Genesis 41:50-52)

...

"Asenath": Athena [J]
"Asenath, the daughter of Potiphera priest of On":
Hohenstaufen historiographer/Hofstadter/Ostrogoth/shithead
Hohenstaufen Hofstadter heterotropia/appropriate/Ethiopia
shithead eighteen harpooner/footrest/Phaeton

...

The Jewish Scheme consistent with lion pussycat, hence dominance of Jewish wombs, feminization of Jewish men.
Consistent with Talmud obfuscation and tradition overwrite of Hebraic law, not written in two pillar format.

...

Covenant of Abraham is circumcision, not a Jewish mother's womb, a matriarchal scheme.
A womb is not circumcision, nor does it negate tattoos.
The gates of religion are not labial, see the LORD'S judgement in Adam and Eve.
Covenant with God Most High, not with collective.

Unhappy observations since branding:

1. US Passport down to 44th.
2. Israel smoking.
3. US gambling boon.

Noteworthy signatures.

All the ancient kings of the west contributed their blood against Travis. Not as decoration or for inheritance but for survival.
Richard, Aragorn, Louis, Rurik, Pharaoh, David, Saul.
Same as the Argonauts.

In Biblical sheep shearing, both shepherds and sheep benefit.
E.g.'s taxes, education.
Unavoidable structure that educators and students unequal.
Depth and breadth are not exclusive, rather ways of ordering.

Sukkot.
Travel inimitably disrupts the rhythm of life, imbuing fresh perspective. Also literally the circadian rhythm.

Biblical continuation in diaspora.
One wonders why circumcision was standardised in the United States, and at US country code +1 versus +8 China, +44 UK, +972 Israel.
Supreme Court is disguised Sanhedrin.

Unsalted food spoils. Nothing more destructive to character than unreproved authority, e.g. populist, aristocratic, financial, legal.
Part of the prestige of science is automatic reproof, also essential in accurate study of history, e.g.

Biblical record.

Consider South vs North, explicit racial slavery versus systemic over litigation, an abuse of law making government the oblique owner.

Consider bringing a claim against a government to a government.

**Biblical primacy of locally elected judges guards against populism, despotism, and systemic gaming.

Short ladder to populace, listen to grass growing.

Legal review essential to unclog paper and personnel arteries.

Failure mode then becomes one of "changing of the times", whether it is possible to brainwash an entire populace so thoroughly they all forsake reason, or that by collective collision true becomes false.

Why in Hebrew faith God's word is eternal, why instruction comes from the mouth of prophets first.

Three thousand years of silence.

One wonders at religion that entirely separates life from afterlife.

Do we not inevitably reap the fruits of our way of living?

Why would religion stand against the way of the natural world?

Does not God's justice operate in God's creation, perhaps not on a human timescale?

One wonders at saints dying hideously, does God not save the righteous?

Do not the beliefs of the soul elevate the flesh?

They generate habits of thought, tongue, and action we can measure objectively, and divine intervention we cannot scientifically explain.

The real test of the Book of Job is Satan's. There was no command to traumatize poor Job, a baby soul. Job chosen not for his infantile vow of eternal vengeance. He later became what he professed to hate. Crippling child abuse repeated with Alexander at IC, chemical lobotomy.

"Adolf Hitler Hebrew":
halfbreed

[Ezekiel bread]

...

"Hanukkah miracle":

Americana/Manchuria/marihuana/calamari/Hamilcar/Michael/malarian/manurial/Malachi/Rachel/Ukraine
earn Malachi/Michal/Hakka

Hakka Michael

HAKKA MANURE

"Menachem Mendel Schneerson":
earn (scheme)^2 (88) Lennon

[Aleph is an X]

"Imperial Aramaic script":
armrest calamari

[From port of Joppa]

"Phoenician script":
earn hippo

"You will burn My flesh on a pyre. I am the LORD.":

worldbeater (5551) iliofemoral plums/sylph

unalphabetise Hollywood/wholefood/fluoride/honourer/informer/lordlier/founder/Reynold/rounder

Thought control via action, situational avoidance and embrace.

Straight men automatically covet women's breasts, booties, scent.

David should have bought Uriah's property and relocated Bathsheba.

Cigarette butts are gross, bootie emits poop.

Corollary is embrace; go to nurturing environment not isolative stagnation.

(Zechariah 9:9-10)

"Rejoice greatly, O daughter of Zion!":
counterfeiter gargoyles/girlhood/ideology/GEORGIA/Elijah
heterogeneity Dracula

...
"Shout in triumph, O daughter of Jerusalem!
Behold, your king is coming to you;
He is just and endowed with salvation."

...
[Zechariah w. three women.]
"Humble, and mounted on a donkey, Even on a colt, the foal of a donkey."
(honeymoon Oakland)^2 elevated
Nathanael Kaufman buttonholed
Nathanael buttonhole Emanuel/Feynman/Oakland
Tutankhamen enfeeblement/honeycombed/Beethoven
Tutankhamen Nathanael enfeebled/envenomed
Tutankhamen Beethoven announced

...
["Embedded Tutankhamen near explicit Ephraim":
Alexander methamphetamine/
arithmetician/*authenticated*
earn mathematician helmet Dexedrine]

...
"And I will cut off the chariot from Ephraim,":
EARN CHEMOAUTOTROPHICAL
recrown arithmetic/mathematical/metaphorical/multicolored
D.M.C. familial/familiar/Hiawatha
Michael hermaphroditical/malpractitioner
Calamari lotteries Plutonic [scheme]

...
(Zechariah 9:10)
"And the horse from Jerusalem;
And the bow of war will be cut off."
arterionecroses buttonhole blameful

Out of the potter came forth pot and potty. [N, G]

Trading literally boring.
Patterns, probability, logic, integrity.

(Isaiah 1:15)
"Your hands are covered with blood." (Isaiah 1:15)

...
(Isaiah 1:18)
" 'Come now, and let us reason together,'
Says the LORD.
'Though your sins are as scarlet,
They will be as white as snow;
Though they are red like crimson,
They will be like wool.' "

...
Christianity
blood red [cardinals, Sith imperials],
scarlet [Gone with the Wind], crimson [Harvard]

Job's daughters Key centric:

(Job 42:14)

"Jemimah Keziah Keren-happuch":

earn kamikaze

marijuana kimchee

Jae peacemaker/Manchuria/Zechariah/Zephaniah/American/Hezekiah/Hanukkah/kamikaze/Nehemiah/Amharic/Charmin/

cheapen/Chimera/Crimean/Ephraim/Izanami/Ukraine/Caiman/Ericka/eureka/Kazakh/Khazar/kraken/meanie/Miriam/
Nikkei/pierce/zipper/Aaren

"Marianna and Alexander" (1313):

Aeneid armada/drama
Riemann adrenal/Aaren
(Aaren)^2 mainland/Aladdin/animal
Aeriel drama/maana/manna
DRAMA adrenaline/Aeriel/Aeneid

"Marianna and Jordan":

ninja Madonna/Ramadan/armada/random/Aaron/drama
Aaron mandarin/ninja

"Marianna and James":

dramamine [drama-Min]/mermaid

"Eve and Seth":

Eden east

Triad, Trinity ... Lot snaked.

Samuel Habib ... echoes Flis

Pbs POV The Ride Ahead

Richard the Lionhearted vs Saladin. Richardson is a ghost.

"Richard the Lionhearted"(4443)

...

Richard Nixon ... Nix

"Richard Nixon": China Odin

"Richard Nixon and Henry Kissinger": China reorganisers
recondensing (600) Isaiah

...

Richard Philips Feynman... fine man

...

FF8 Squall Leonhart

"Electrons move too fast.":

earn footstool

...

elevator cotton

footstool Cervantes/Servant

MATERIAL ANALYSIS

[Fabric, string theory, fashion]

Different materials have different elasticities, creates persistent holes under stress.

Why would more rigor and caution be punished? Pure cotton is neither extravagant (+2% purity) nor
disobedient.

Different than stoning Sabbath violators and persecuting homosexuals.

...

Examples:

0. AG jeans mixed, A. Grothendieck.

1. FF7 Materia mixing.

2. Einstein's Mercury amalgam.

3. Steward, stew, goulash, ghoul.

...

"Why would more rigor and caution be punished?":

earn omnipotence (1776) Lord Buddha

"pure cotton pants":

earn octopus

"mixing fabric materials":

LIBRARIAN maximize/maxims

earn biracialism/MARTIALISM/MILITARISM/briticism/Islamitic/magistral/satirical/tribalism/balsamic/
MAXIMALS/tragical/Abigail/Arabist/*GARLIC*

GROUNDING PHRASES, PROOF BY EXHAUSTION.

"material mixture wool and linen":

earn extermination/denaturation/malnutrition/multimillion

...

Nataniel ultramodern/demolition/immolation

"material mixture cotton and linen":

earn communitarian/extermination

...

Nataniel (6676) *NEURODERMATITIC*/TRINITROTOLUENE/RECOMMENDATION/documentation/indoctrinator

"material mix wool and linen":

EARN amontillado/maimonidean/alienation/demolition/ideational/IMMOLATION/Maximilian/Allentown/damnation/
emotional

...

ALEXANDER immolation

Nataniel memorial

"material mix cotton and linen":

EARN nicotinamide/lamentation/maimonidean

...

ALEXANDER noncommittal/NICTITATION/immolation/nomination

Nataniel clitoridean/Diocletian

"mixture wool and linen":

EARN demolition/outwilled/demotion/indolent/meltdown/windmill

...

LORD annulment/NEWTONIAN

"mixture cotton and linen":

EARN demolition/demotion/indolent/Miltonic/mutinied/Nintendo/NICOTINE

...

LORD announcement/cementation/containment/inattention/anoointment/cantonment/intoxicate/NICOTINATE

"mix wool and linen":

medallion/windmill/William/daemon/Lilian/oilman

Oilman Lenin

model Ionian

"mix cotton and linen":

cantonment/decimation/demolition/DIOCLETIAN/medication/NICOTINATE/LIDOCAINE/CATILINE

Antonino minted/denim/nixed

"Material mixture wool linen":

earn multimillion [MITes]/immolation

extermination

"Material mixture cotton linen":

EARN EXTERMINATION

TRINITROTOLUENE *CALAMINE*

"Material mix wool linen":

EARN immolation/Maximilien/emotional/Lillian/tollman/William

...

immolation/Maximilian

"Material mix cotton linen":

EARN intoxication/nictitation/immolation/nicotinate

...

contamination/extermination

"mixture wool linen":
Newton elixir/mule

"mixture cotton linen":
nicotine torment/turtle

"mix wool linen": million/OILMEN/Willie/LENIN/Nixon/women/Elmo/lion/neon/wine

"mix cotton linen": *NICOTINE*

"mixture wool silk":
Lot silkworm/smoker
killer MIT

"mix wool silk": kills/milks/skill

[Pure cotton]
(Leviticus 19:19)
"nor wear a garment upon you of two kinds of material mixed together."
fluororoentgenographies [X-rays]
metroynamometer [iron grip] taxation
...
Peregrine Tokugawa Tetraethylammonium [N+swastika] resonation
PEREGRINE TOKUGAWA MAYORDOMO TRINITROTOLUENE
Peregrine Tokugawa mayordomo
Mithridates footnote/funereal
(earn)^4 Mithridates outwitted

...
TETRAETHYLAMMONIUM
0. block voltage-dependent K+ channels in nerve,
1. competitive inhibitor at nicotinic acetylcholine receptors,
2. salt metathesis reaction precipitate by double displacement

...
"Leviticus nineteen nineteen":
*INSTITUTE LENIN NICENE [MITes]
Einstein Lenin
select intuitive

[E.g. Mercury amalgam.]
(Deuteronomy 22:11)
"You shall not wear a material mixed of wool and linen together."
tetramethylenediamine triangular
[PUTRESCINE]
[Ground phrase]
trinitrotoluene Alexander amalgamations
...
"Deuteronomy twenty two eleven":
TURTLEDOVE TENET Mooney
turtledove Newton enemy

LORD:"Polygamy splinters families."
Alexander: Axeheads splinter wood.

Borg collective injects dreams.

Metaphor of Alexander's birth, Israel has abandoned me.

Jonah [J] metaphorical whaler
whale gambler

[K]
"Come, let us cast lots so we may learn on whose account this calamity has struck us." (Jonah 1:7)

[N]
"Weeds were wrapped around my head.
I descended to the roots of the mountains." (Jonah 2:5-6)

[fishy scent]
"Then the LORD commanded the fish, and it vomited Jonah up onto the dry land. (Jonah 2:10)

[K]
"But God appointed a worm when dawn came the next day, and it attacked the plant and it withered." (Jonah 4:7)

YAHWEH gave Pharaoh in Egypt
9 warning plagues after 400 years of slavery, the 10th plague death.
Why is a Hebrew immediately stoned for one Sabbath violation?

(Numbers 15:32)
"they found a man gathering wood on the Sabbath day."
earn nonhomogeneous/inhomogeneous
EARN YAHWEH DEFAMATION

...
attribution/Gainsborough/goddaughter
ATTRIBUTION boneheaded/Gethsemane/Behemoth
Gethsemane annotation/authoring
GAINSBOROUGH heathendom/batwoman [crazy]/defeated
BEHEMOTH afterthoughts/defraudation/Gainsborough/goddaughter/outreasoning/annotation/attenuation/
brainwashed/refutation/wrongdoing

(Numbers 15:35)
"The man shall surely be put to death":
EARN (4444) BLASPHEMY
earn sleepyhead mothballs [DEBUG]
earn alpha behemoth
Alessandro BETHLEHEM

[If exemplified, why outside?]
(Numbers 15:35)
"all the congregation shall stone him with stones outside the camp."
contradiction thoughtlessness

"Sabbath Violation Squad":
bloodbath/diabolo

The Bible piggybacked on a virus.

Star Wars
Palpatine: "Execute order 66." Destroy the Jedi.
Order 666, turn Yahweh into beast, destroy Israel.
Imperial guard cardinal red.
Blood soaked.

"Stanislav Yevgrafovich Petrov":
Stanhart Erica gospel/evil/foils/fool/Flis
Stanhart Erica v Flis

Holocaust demonstrates clever understanding of Mosaic Law; first tattoo the wrist, numbering again, break covenant, then work to death.
See 2 Samuel 24:1, 1 Chronicles 21.

...
"Revelation tattoo Auschwitz numbers":
blameworthiness Caterina/Nazarite/OCTAVIAN/Actaeon/Octavio
noteworthiness calamari/cavalier/Albert

TRINITROTOLUENE MOUSTACHES

...
Strategy is Empress Caterina (E) makes life hell in shtetls,
Lenin (N) starts a red revolution,
Hitler (Uriel, K's right hand) exterminates in death camps.

...
Meanwhile Einstein offered presidency of Israel.
Too cerebral for politics.

On Sodomy

Creator's hand vs Moses's pen.

Why was Moses prohibited from entering the promised land?

Homosexuality natural in small proportion among mammals, certainly not the norm.

Homosexuality is biologically unequal both reproductively and behavior archetypically. Consider Tinder and Mr. Slave, yet there are gay men who embody healthy male and female archetypes.

Why ostracize man for his nature?

An abomination to feminize man, not to be born with feminine traits.

Consider prophet Nathan, aka Leviathan.

Who made Nathaniel gay? (Job 41)

YAHWEH, and not as an insult.

...
The metaphorical extension is that racial and ethnic homogenisation is the exception not the norm, for it condemns children to tribelessness and prejudice.

For where do half breeds run?

Yet robust blood needs to breathe.

...
Much suffering for a lack of clarity.

[Like the Snake and apple.]

(Leviticus 18:22)

"You shall not lie with a male as one lies with a female; it is an abomination."

unwholesomeness infinitesimal Behemoth

(Moses)^2 tintinnabulation [tinkerbelle G]/unintentionally

...
"You shall not lie with a male as one lies with a female":

Moses illuminations/infinitesimal/influentially/institutional

MOSES OUTLAWS NATHANIEL WHITEHALL [N, Michael]

YAHWEH ALLELUIA MISSTATEMENT

YAHWEH MISSTATEMENT FELONIOUS/nullifies/foolish/Hellen/Lillian/SINFUL

...
[Abraham rescued Sodomite Lot.]

"Leviticus one eight two two":

evolutionist/eugenicist/geneticist/oncologist/guiltiest/Helvetius/unholiest/towlines/coolie

COOLIE OUTWITTING

towlines octet

LOT EUGENICIST/GENETICIST/OUTWITTING

...
"For whoever does any of these abominations, those persons who do so shall be cut off from among their people." (Leviticus 18:29)

...
Yet David lover of Johnathan was exalted, likewise prophet Nathan.

"David and Jonathan": joint Havana

Show Abel was N.

Seth K, also killer K for Cain.

M, G betrayed Adam with apple. Children:

E rotten, N began as prophet Nathan, later antichrist Paul.

Lord kills Cain and Seth's offspring with great flood.

Parenthood reoriginates with Noah, population bottleneck like Eden.

Canaanites accursed (Genesis 9:25-27).

Naturally M jealous, incites Job J.

Lord speaks to Job of the animal kingdom at length (Job 38-42), he completely misses the point.

"Abel and Isaac and Nathan":

Nathaniel bananas/cabanos [cigar]

[Big daddy James ... Set Theory]

(Genesis 5:3)

"When Adam had lived one hundred and thirty years, he became the father of a son in his own likeness, according to his image, and named him Seth."

...

"When Adam had lived one hundred and thirty years":
(earn)^2 revelationist Yahweh

...

"he became the father of a son in his own likeness":
earn astonishment coolie/falcon
earn ancientness behemoth
earn Einstein affectionless/loathsomeness
earn Themistocles fishhook
fatherliness namesake Einstein/nicotine/nonwhite/Chinese/Newton/Cohen
Einstein blameworthiness/treasonableness
Einstein Christmases Kowloon
Themistocles brainwashes

...

"according to his image, and named him Seth":
earn Einstein cacao mammoths
earn Messiah diadem (1007) Michigan
earn astonishment academic/demigod/godhead/Mohamed/diadem/cacao/Omega
earn denicotinise mashgiach/thigh

...

EINSTEIN OCTAHEDRON mashgichim/mashgiach
recondensing mathematics/Mohammed/shithead
mathematics Michigander/organogenic
metachromatism indochinese Gandhi/haggai

Why is spoken Japanese Turkic?
Job was traumatized and migrated to the Orient, to Hin Ting.
Khazarian Hebrews also part Turk.
Japanese people have no letter "L".

Alma Mater MIT ... same mother
Joseph and Benjamin.

...

Israel has become gangster.
Xenophobia is no defense, all of Israel's greatest historical enemies have been internal defectors.

(Exodus 23:19)

"You are not to boil a kid in the milk of its mother."
earn bloodthirst emotionality/humiliation/methylation [DNA]/feminality/militiamen/mutilation

Also Exodus 34:26, Deuteronomy 14:21

"Boil kid mother's milk thrice":
bloodthirst Micheil [... Amalekites]

On Immolation

"The Spirit of Detroit Marshall Fredericks":
deathtrap Themistocles
masterstroke Richard titleholder
masterstroke arthritis (885) hellfire

Einstein died 1955, RenCen 1977
"Renaissance Center Detroit":
Constantine created/erected
Einstein (1977) reconsecrated/easterner

...

Evidence:
Interior looks like Star Wars' Death Star II reactor core,
FF7 reactor bombing by Avalanche,
Towers are octagonal,

N42 Cafe, Grothendieck prime 42.

"The Spirit of Detroit Renaissance Center":
arterionecrosis antichrist/archfiend/Christian/ENCHANTER

Walls of Jericho demolished
"Also seven priests shall carry seven trumpets of rams' horns before the ark; then on the seventh day you shall march around the city seven times, and the priests shall blow the trumpets." (Joshua 6:4)

...
"Renaissance Center straw house" (7777):
ARCHITECT UNAWARENESS
Northwestern secureness
Newton characterises/eucharist/Catharina/Catherina/Catherine [Seven, retard]/Christean
...
earn treacherousness
earn accurateness worthiness/theorises/whiteness
earn sweetheart/Eisenhower
earn Newton characterises/treacheries/archaist/catharsis

Star Wars' Padme, Natalie Portman, representing Jordan N's vassal.

"John Calvin Portman Junior":
NAPHTALI
incorporation
manipulation Co horn
COLUMNAR innovation/Antonino/HARPOON
Corinthian nonmoral/unmoral/maroon
Nathan unicorn

...
moron annunciator
China promotional/promotion
ruminator novocain/volcano/oilcan
harpoon nontrivial/rumination

"John Calvin Portman Junior Renaissance Center":
earn microprocessor authentical/avalanche/ejaculate/Leviathan/Nathanael/Nathanial/Nathaniel
implosion annunciator evanescence [seven]
arterionecrosis Nathaniel chaperon

Coleman Alexander Young development,
Ben Gurion translation "son of a young lion".
Detroit RenCen and Ben Gurion airport pillars are identical.

"Key is what is written on thigh."
earn synthetist/wittiness/highness
***If burn scar does not remove brand, why would immolation?

...
"Alexander burn scar" (1886)[N]:
earn barnacles/blunders/dracula/unlead

Obituary article is not alpha.
Also following not true.
"America stands for slavery":
article (1444) ferryman/Odyssean
Messiae falcon

Do not want dandelion, no tap.
"And He will kill the dragon who lives in the sea." (Isaiah 27:1)

...
"Alexander Luka Flis Daniv self immolation":
EARN DANDELION volatilises
earn demolition alkalinised [pyre]/avianised/maxillaes

"You will burn My flesh on a pyre. I am the LORD."
earn immolation(2005) hydrosphere
foreordainment hyperbolas
unalphabetise Hollywood/honourer/informer/rounder

...
"You will burn My flesh on a pyre."
earn (3444) hyperbolism

"Eight hours of work a day": RIGHTEOUS WORKDAY
"Eight hours of work per day":
OUTGROW HYDROSPHERE

Symmetry of immolation and pyre, two different actions, in two different phrases in quotations and permuted both associated with demotion establishes death of soul, suicide of Israel and West.

Volcano ... cane,
hurricane uncondensed,
targets Florida regularly, gun shaped with many alligators.
Tornado focused.

...
Physical equivalent to immolation, but disobedient to pyre command.
Yet maxillae/napalm appear.

...
"Alexander jumps in a volcano":
earn demoniacal/Napoleonic/Cleavland/explosion/lampooned/
MAXILLAE/melodical/Nevadians/novacaine/peninsula/policeman
earn Jason demoniacal/Cleavland/medallion/melodical/policeman/climaxed/MAXILLAE/NAPALMED

UTEP Mongolian architecture.

"Alexander is king at Burger King":
earn kindergartens/triangulares/interregnal/libertarian/unkindliest/arbitrage/Argentine/Bulgarian/
Englanders/librarian/Stalingrad/Tangerine/Ukrainians/Albertine/Berliner/Ekaterina/Eritreans/Nigerians/
Sardinian/triangle

[Avoid MIT]
"Jesse Lauriston Livermore":
earn soulless overtime
Servant Ijsselmeer
mineralise truelove
reinsure elevator/majesties/relative/salesroom [NILICO]/volatiles/Allister/Jeremia/maestro
Allister overinsures/erroneous/overseer
MARILEE JONES OUSTER/outlive

...
Spouses:
Nettie Jordan (m.1900; div. 1917)
Dorothea Wendt (m.1918; div.1932)
Harriet Metz Noble (m.1933, J.L.L. death by suicide 1940)

...
"Harriet Metz Noble": terminator bezel

"David Baltimore": diadem tribal

Humor

"Foreskin Liberation Movement"
earn leftover kimonos

"foreskin rejuvenation":
earn serotonin/Einstein/Kristine
Einstein favourer

"Foreskin Attachment Syndrome":
earn Christendom/Montessorian
Richardson Testament

GOT [respectful actors]
"Tyrion Lannister Brandon Stark Roose Bolton":
Alessandro noninsane

[not polygamists]
Homer and Marge Simpson ... Samson

Tartar ... osteonecrosis
Dip arrows in poison ...
Poisson bracket {} set.
Follow osteoarterionecrosis, or dragon Nataniel.

UNIVERSITY HEMISATIRE

"Moscow State alumni": communalists

[Go Blue]

"Wayne State U alumni": lieutenants

"Oxford alumni": uniform/unmoral

"Stanford alumni": laundromats

"Harvard alumni": marihuana

"Princeton alumni": intrapulmonic

"Caltech alumni":

hallucinate/alchemical/CALUMNIATE/mechanical/calculate/lunatical/machinate/technical/unacclaim/UNETHICAL

"Utep alumni": platinum/IMPALE

"Tel Aviv U alumni": illuminate

"vaginal immunity": MIT alumni

Interesting people who love the natural world despise its creator.

What they really love is power.

Theseus in Plutarch

"The chief and most solemn sacrifice which they celebrate to him is kept in the eighth day of Pyanepsion [Oct. 8], on which he returned with the Athenian young men from Crete. Besides which they sacrifice to him on the eighth day of every month, either because he returned from Troezen the eighth day of Hecatombaeon [July 8], as Diodorus the geographer writes, or else thinking that number to be proper to him, because he was reputed to be born of Neptune, because they sacrifice to Neptune on the eighth day of every month. The number eight being the first cube of an even number, and the double of the first square, seemed to be an emblem" (p.15)

"Perigune" (p.3)

"that when the cup fell, the poison was spilt there where now is the enclosed space in the Delphinium; for in that place stood AEgeus's house, and the figure of Mercury on the east side of the temple is called the Mercury of AEgeus's gate." (p.4)

"the lot being cast" (p.6)

"by lot" (p.8)

"put all that was left of their provision together, and, boiling it in one common pot, feasted themselves with it" (p.8) [stew]

"upon whom the lot fell" (p.9)

"He also coined money, and stamped it with the image of an ox" (p.9)

"House of Hermes" (p.10)

"the Amazon whom Theseus married" (p.11)

"The lot fell upon Theseus" (p.12)

"Pluto" (p. 12)

"steadfast and immovable power of this god, who from thence has the names of Asphalius and Gaeiochus, that is, the established and stayer of the earth." (p.15) [baloney]

Romulus Quirinus (Plutarch)

Star Trek's Q, also Vulcan hand sign "live long and prosper", Roman numeral 8 century BCE.

CONTENTS (p.vii) of Plutarch

K as Theseus.

N as Themistocles, Cato the Younger.

L as Romulus, Pericles, Caesar.

...

INDEX (p. 877) mention, incomplete

K as Mithridates, Archimedes, Augustus.

L as Hannibal, Aristotle, Jason, Zoroaster.

...

"the month Sextilis, now called August" (p.22)

[Tolkien's tree of Gondor]

"near the descent from the Mount Palatine to the Circus Maximus. There, they say, grew the holy cornelldp tree, of which they report, that Romulus once, to try his strength, threw a dart from the Aventine Mount, the staff of which was made of cornel, which stuck so deep into the ground, that no one of many that tried could pluck it up, and the soil, being fertile, gave nourishment to the wood, which sent forth branches, and produced a cornel stock of considerable bigness. This did posterity preserve and worship as one of the most sacred things; and therefore walled it about" (p.25)

[whirlwind, Levitical scapegoat]

"near a place called the Goat's Marsh, on a sudden strange and unaccountable disorders and alterations took place in the air; the face of the sun was darkened, and the day turned into night, and that, too, no quiet, peaceable night, but with terrible thunderings, and boisterous winds from all quarters"(p.28)

...

"The day he vanished on is called the Flight of the People and the Nones of the Goats, because they go then out of the city and sacrifice at the Goat's Marsh" (p.29)

[Abraham father of nations, echoes Biblical fountain for David]

"by which he intermixed and united both nations, and made it the fountain of after friendship and public stability." (p. 31)

Cheap Philosophy.

"maximise Profit Education ratio":

democratization/dramatization/Americanized

Disney movies:

The Little Mermaid [turned into worm], Hercules [loses power, jumps in lake of dead], Aladdin [loses lamp].

...

Isaiah 53.

Alexander could not have attended Caltech undergrad, since if renatured, necessarily esteemed.

Alexander could not have been with Jordan, then married not forsaken.

American Civil War, North vs South, implicit vs explicit slavery.

Sabbath is for rest. Working harder or more does NOT imply results, as progress is from the LORD.

Woman, without man [outside of].

Women are vessels.

Grosse Pointe [GP],

globus pallidus

homogeneous

American Standard,

Erica Standhardt.

Alexander means defender of man, from James.

Meditations

...

Alexander dinosaur, not a knight, not chivalrous. Defender of his own God, family, and country first.

...
Nothing evil about consorts. Reality is polygamy splinters families.
Alexander has honest love but does not crave sexuality or diversity, would rather avoid future headache, make ditzy wife happy.
Willing to consort if spiritually or politically necessary, *not at the cost of His soul*, as service to LORD is paramount before women.
Similar to Sarah, Jordan's behavior contributed to current plurality through her absence and conniving. So did Alexander's deception by Michael.
Difference with Sarah is contract is not signed in blood, no oath given.
LORD said "Jordan", also said "choose three".
Bound by choice to honor old wives, possibly consort.
Defensive preference is to avoid, although Alexander knows Georgia and Virginia mean well.
Everyone means well, why the world is full of chaos.
Wait for further judgement from the LORD, keeping faith with Oakland.

...
Chivalry is a code empowering women to connive men.
Chivalry, cavalier

Great villains have redeeming characteristics, which they refuse to redeem.
E.g. Star Wars' Palpatine.

Remember the ARG0, ergo, ergot, therefore, implies.
Arg-o argument zero,
argument w. Medea.

[Arg-o nauts]
Argonauts:
Alexander relatives:
Schrodinger, Kelvin, Banach, Hilbert.

"Verified via exposition."
proof divinities
Aeneid vitrifies/positive/spoofers

[No banana]
"Schrodinger Kelvin Banach Hilbert":
earn occidentalising/valedictories/billionaires/brilliances/denicotinise/vinordinaire
earn denicotinise black

...
transcendence kohlrabi/gorilla/Virgil
brilliant (6001) convergences/codebreaker/Richardson/recondense/renascence
interbranch indiscoverable
BRILLIANCE KINDERGARTENS
birdcage elevation
denicotinise archangel
recondensing Alastair/arbitrator/baseball/Hebraist
vindication researcher
VINORDINAIRE CANCELLERS
Richardson intelligence/belligerent/enthralling/leatherneck/achilleine/challenger/inelegance/liberating/
reteaching/rethinking/viceregent
ARGO chickenhearted/brainchildren/transcendence/electricians/TRIVALENCIES/tiebreaker

887

Srinivasa Ramanujan Aiyangar[a] FRS (22 December 1887 – 26 April 1920)

P. C. Mahalanobis posed a problem:
"Imagine that you are on a street with houses marked 1 through n."

Good Will Hunting.
Professor Gerald Lambeau (Stellan Skarsgård) explains to Sean Maguire (Robin Williams) the genius of Will Hunting (Matt Damon) by comparing him to Ramanujan.

[Finish LOTR...Lot Characters,
not perfect but not trivial correspondence.

e.g. king of dead army M,
Theoden K, Sauron N, ring Georgia.]

...
"One ring to rule them all":
thermoregulation
Hanoi Elenore
Ariel torment
enthroned gorilla

"Why M betrayed L":
wreathed/Demetra/Albert/breath/Hebrew/hatred/helmet/herald/blame/death/rhyme/herb/lamb/meta/weed/Yah
...
Yah trembled/trebled
herald byte
byte whaler
herb medal
weed math
Meta herb

J descendant of Atilla the Hun.
M had a dog named Atilla.

Cain and Abel
Definition of barbarism
human behavioral pattern
1. Lack of knowledge
2. Emotion
3. Violent action.

Interestingly mammals are often ignorant and emotional yet do not exhibit human violence.
Humans having the capacity for abstraction yet misusing it to kill, are not animals sometimes more
righteous thus more worthy of salvation like in Noah's Arc?

AXIOMATIZING BEHAVIOR

Human social humor can be axiomatized into a first order formal logical system, i.e. prove something is
funny.

Similarly human behavior can be axiomatized to fundamentals.

Human female and male courtship behaviors can be condensed into algorithms.

Axiomatized human humor is based on violation of social standards, i.e. on bad behavior. Humans are
highly socially linked.

Human societal behavioral norms common to all cultures can be axiomatized.

These norms are all in the Torah.

How does the New Testament attempt to nullify axiomatic social norms from the Torah?

What features of the legal structure of the Torah are unusual?

To what extent is the US Constitution based on the Torah?

...
Constitution axiomatically fundamentally based on Torah with key exception of amendability.
By design US founders referenced Torah, citing God but not including because of Christian splintering.
God's law is timeless, complete, and extremely effective at generating success, demonstrated by "American
Exceptionalism".
Rather, Israel is God's chosen, partly scattered in the USA.

ChatGPT Ethics.

The fundamental principle in authorship is tracing originality.

Err toward acknowledgement, cheating does not pay.

Must understand to consent.

If ChatGPT contributes half the substance, it is half the author.

AXIOMATIZE US CONSTITUTION

as a minimal set of principles and meta-principles.

ChatGPT:

```
{  
Meta Principles [ideals]  
1. Popular Sovereignty - authority derives from consent.  
2. Limited Government - powers enumerated and limited.  
3. Separation of Powers - distinct branches.  
4. Checks and Balances - mutual oversight.
```

Principles

```
1. Rule of Law - supremacy of and equality under law.  
2. Individual Rights - protected fundamental rights.  
3. Federalism - division of sovereignty.  
4. Amendability - structured self change.  
}
```

0. Unstated meta principle

Tendency of power corrupting character for lack of reproof.

False Axioms:

1. Free will.

Free will is limited by God. Thus, some authority derives from God.

And if a degree of choice is given by God, choice should be honored, not manipulated.

Thus the mechanisms for its impedance should be well known, as recorded in the Bible.

2. Change.

God's law is timeless and complete.

[Standhart plagiarist assimilator]

ON SLAVERY

Overcoming imposed hardship provides a claim to glory and teaches humility and empathy, but it does not justify the imposition.

The pursuit of glory is a vain idol, the pursuit of substance a reward in itself. Reconquering mundane problems, reinventing the wheel of righteousness every generation is insanity. Lessons refine character, but the wise need less refinement, learning from others' lessons, not on their own skin.

Appraise the landscape of intellectual depth and aim high, better to fall short than not fully try, for surely the soul dies living a lie. Reason is cowardice's best disguise, the years of folly multiply, children know their hearts inside.

Race based slavery is a relic from Moses's time in Egypt; the Romans were more egalitarian. Hiding abuse behind colored statistics is abominable. Intelligence is multifaceted, perhaps Africans have a different genetic proclivity than Europeans. Ancient Sumerians were the first, they survive in every clock. However with abuse, even intellectual genius can be ground to mediocrity.

Men meet the bar set for them.

Lowering standards dilutes quality, and who wants to be indebted to charity? To uplift a people you educate the youth and remove obstacles. Focus on equality of opportunity not outcome. Socioeconomic success alone is survival not achievement. Race based prejudice and its corollary favoritism is absurd when you consider African Americans are on average ~30% genetically white. Any reduction in average IQ for this populace is thus likely grounded in behavior.

The thesis of Christianity is man is not defined by his worst actions.

Then is he not also not defined by his best? What then should history note, what man himself forgets?

Does this not lower the bar universally, debasing man God's creation, offering insult to divinity?

Judgement is the LORD'S.

Champions own their mistakes.

Man's worst often has a defining impact on character and life. The worst can evince the best and worst in man; it can necessitate the best, but it is not necessary. Pressure can be simulated.

Mercy undeserved invites disobedience, as lack of consequence invites the complacency of mediocrity.

History esteems society by its brightest lights and its endurance, shadows of virtue and righteousness.

TANAKH FALSIFICATION

By secular reasoning, explicit inconsistency is exceptionally rare, and considering the people, context, and changes, most likely deliberate.
By religious reasoning, the LORD permitted tampering to be recorded yet corrected, leaving a fingerprint.

#1. Esau's wives [changed to favor Judah]

"And when Esau was forty years old he married Judith the daughter of Beerli the Hittite, and Basemath the daughter of Elon the Hittite, and they brought grief to Isaac and Rebekah." (Genesis 26:34-35)

"So Esau saw that the daughters of Canaan displeased his father Isaac; and Esau went to Ishmael, and married, besides the wives that he had, Mahalath the daughter of Ishmael, Abraham's son, the sister of Nebaioth." (Genesis 28:8-9)

"Esau took his wives from the daughters of Canaan; Adah the daughter of Elon the Hittite, and Oholibamah the daughter of Anah and the granddaughter of Zibeon the Hivite; also Basemath, Ishmael's daughter, the sister of Nebaioth." (Genesis 36:2-3)

The first account is altered. Why?
Judith implies Judaism, these are times former. Why would a woman be named for Jacob's boy, and why would Esau marry her? To attempt to reestablish a lost claim in Judah.

Considering word permutations,
Basemath ... math.
"Gilgamesh": Ismael, sire of Arabia, ... algebra.
Oholibamah ... Obama, known for honesty.

#2. Solomon's Stables [40K vs 4K]

"And Solomon had 40,000 stalls of horses for his chariots, and 12,000 horsemen." (1 Kings 4:26)
"Now Solomon had 4,000 stalls for horses and chariots and 12,000 horsemen, and he stationed them in the chariot cities and with the king in Jerusalem." (2 Chronicles 9:25)

Chronicler understates both stalls and king, men do not share steeds.

#3. Judah not assigned kingship, but the king's staff, a marshall's rod.

"The scepter shall not depart from Judah,
Nor the ruler's staff from between his feet,
Until Shiloh comes" (Genesis 49:10)

[Drink is not for kings, nor milk for men grown. (Proverbs 31:4, Judges 4:19)]
"His eyes are dull from wine,
And his teeth white from milk." (Genesis 49:12)

[staff vs crown]
"May they be on the head of Joseph,
And on the crown of the head of the one distinguished among his brothers." (Genesis 49:26)

"Let it come to the head of Joseph,
And to the crown of the head of the one distinguished among his brothers," (Deuteronomy 33:16)

"Though Judah prevailed over his brothers and from him came the leader, yet the birthright belonged to Joseph," (1 Chronicles 5:2)

"Ephraim also is the helmet of My head;
Judah is My scepter." (Psalm 60:7, 108:8).

...
"Ephraim also is the helmet of My head":
Alastair (3222) misemployed/polymath/sleepyhead
sleepyhead mesothelioma
Messiah haloperidol
Mithridates employee
...

"Judah is My scepter": miseducates, pasteurised, supremacist, Archimedes, eucharists, Christmas, impeached, Demetrius, deputise, Jeremiah
physics majeure/remade
Messiah (180) decrypt/deputy/pyre

"And He put on righteousness like a breastplate,
And a helmet of salvation on His head" (Isaiah 59:17)

[Ephrathite, ... Ephraim]

"Now David was the son of the Ephrathite of Bethlehem in Judah, whose name was Jesse" (1 Samuel 17:12)

"Ephrathites of Bethlehem in Judah" (Ruth 1:2)

"David of Ephraim":
DIADEM (108) HARP [Psalm 108:8]
"David of Judah": VOID, jihad, Fuji, judo

...
[minimal phrasing, p. 600 NASB]
"David Ephraim": diadem harp vi
"David Judah": jihad

"Eliakim the son of Hilkiyah" (Isaiah 22:20):
Mikael fishhook

[Set the Key, Egyptian god of chaos.
David of Ephraim kin to Pharaoh.
Sēth (Σήθ) Riemann sums, "Rimmon" (2 Kings 5:18).
Set the key of a harp.
Harpy Mikael plaguing Phineus in Jason and the Argonauts.]

...
"Then I will set the key of the house of David on his shoulder" (Isaiah 22:22)

...
[Phishing scam]
"key of the house of David":
fishhook defeated

David's hexahedron (cop badge, Coptic or Egyptian, MIT coop, coup, Copley, copulate, Coco puff),
hexadecimal (base 666), hex (accursed)

Egypt (House of Ptah ... πταρ (bird), Holy Ghost), Egyptian eagle of Saladin ... Aladdin.

18 Years!

#1. "And the sons of Israel served Eglon the king of Moab eighteen years." (Judges 3:14)

...
Proximity to "Deborah, a prophetess, the wife of Lappidoth" (Judges 4:4),
"Jael the wife of Heber the Kenite" (Judges 4:17).

#2. "for eighteen years they afflicted all the sons of Israel who were beyond the Jordan" (Judges 10:8)

...
Proximity to "Jair the Gileadite" (Judges 10:3).

#3. "there was a woman who for eighteen years had had a sickness caused by a spirit" (Luke 13:11)

...
Also "eighteen" in Luke 13:4,16.

[Don Quixote]
(Numbers 24:3)
"The oracle of Balaam the son of Beor":
bachelors (1886) betatron/Abraham

[Jacob Israel ben Isaac]

"Alexander Oleg Daniv":
dandelion larvae

[M Pinewood]
(Genesis 30:37)
"exposing the white which was in the rods":
WATER PHOTOSENSITISING/toxigenicities/denicotinises/osteogenetic/geneticist/idiogenetic
photosensitizing cheater
WATER GENETICS PINWOOD
whitewashes nephrotoxicities [alcoholic]/estrogenicities/indiscretions/christening/conditioner/
sheepherding

[mouth watering]
"and they mated when they came to drink." (Genesis 30:38)

[metaphorical patterns]
"So the flocks mated by the rods, and the flocks brought forth striped, speckled, and spotted." (Genesis 30:39)

[strong trained to follow white rod]
"Moreover, it came about whenever the stronger of the flock were mating, that Jacob would place the rods in the sight of the flock in the gutters, so that they might mate by the rods" (Genesis 30:41)

Photosensitising is conditioned association, like mouth watering advertisement, or mental behavioral trigger.

Maimonides [Saladin's physician]
Treatise on Poisons and Their Antidotes

...
"Moses ben Maimon Rambam":
ANAEROBIOSES [M ancient]
membranes boson [M Theory]
ribosomes banana/mamba
MARIANNA EMBOSOM
NEMESIS MAMA
RIEMANN BABA
Messiae baboon/bamboo/maomao/maroon/Aaron
Barbie Samson
earn Samson

...
"Alexander self immolation":
Maimonidean foretells
[not prophecy]
Yet prophets Isaiah, Haggai, Malachi not included in permutation.

"James fucked Jordan":
eureka Jason
Kaufman decodes/scored/dosed
Aaron deduces/seduced
Cane defrauds

"Jordan and James": Andromeda
...
Archimedean spiral, water pump. Euler's e^{it} , Euler or Cornu spiral.
Octopus seemingly alien.
Mitochondrial symbiote is universal genetic code exception.

...
James, Jae ... Cranbrook rainbow
Andromeda, android, Medea, Archimedes, Noah's Arc.
machine, China
Hin, Kor. Biblical vol, ... vola
...
E.g.1 Star Trek DS9

Jadzia spotted ... Israel,
Dax symbiote.
Marries Klingon Worf,
12450 Klinger St., "cling to LORD".

...
e.g.2 Mortal Kombat
Outworld vs Earth
Sub-Zero vs Scorpion.
Or evil Shao Khan and Shang Tsung.

e.g.3 GOT
ice cold "Night King": Hin Ting K
e.g.4 Star Wars
Emperor Palpatine vs Vader half machine,
Sith homeworld Korriban.
e.g.5 Dragonball-Z (loose)
Frieza vs fiery Saian Goku.

Biblical volume
"hin" (Exodus 29:40, Exodus 30:24; Numbers 15:5)
"kor" (1 Kings 4:22, 1 Kings 5:11)

"Used clothing": ungodliest, unholyest
"Then the Spirit of the LORD came upon him mightily, and he went down to Ashkelon and killed thirty of them and took their spoil, and gave the changes of clothes to those who told the riddle." (Judges 14:19)

Supranational. Yah upholds the West and all alphabetic languages.

No stewing.

"You shall not breed together two kinds of your cattle; you shall not sow your field with two kinds of seed, nor wear a garment upon you of two kinds of material mixed together." (Leviticus 19:19)

Biblical Voodoo

"So it came about when Moses held his hand up, that Israel prevailed, and when he let his hand down, Amalek prevailed." (Exodus 17:11)

"You should have struck five or six times, then you would have struck Aram until you would have destroyed it. But now you shall strike Aram only three times." (2 Kings 13:19)

Biblical Immolation; burning desire

"If there is a man who marries a woman and her mother, it is immorality; both he and they shall be burned with fire, that there may be no immorality in your midst." (Leviticus 20:14)

"Also the daughter of any priest, if she profanes herself by harlotry, she profanes her father; she shall be burned with fire." (Leviticus 21:9)

"And on this mountain He will swallow up the covering which is over all peoples,
Even the veil which is stretched over all nations." (Isaiah 25:7)

Deception is expected, not to be personalised; at least Christians believe in something.
Newton Leviathan N, Einstein Killer K, Jesus Snake G are not slouches.

Idols: unbreakable marriage, indivisible trinity, soul splitting.
Anti-divorce to tether me to abuse.

A point of logic and geography.

...
China is K's country, not K.
Not Christian, a banned subversive cult reserved for export.
Religions are Confucianism, Taoism, and Buddhism.
Government is Maoism lite not the great leap forward.
Capitol is Beijing not Hong Kong. Language Mandarin not Cantonese.

...
Neither has K always followed N, but for jealousy, which would lead to "revelational" World War III.

Mosaic law sets the foundation for capitalism. Nathaniel's hard communism is naturally antithetical, likewise Christian ideals of relative moralism and universalism. Span of life in David's time was 70 years, 80 with vigor.

...
"As for the days of our life, they contain seventy years,
Or if due to strength, eighty years,"
(Psalm 90:10)

"Poisoning and child abuse":
cannabidiol shogun

8.02. Why not?

...
"Why would the LORD use MIT librarian notation":
trinitrotoluene Amontillado
Amontillado trinitrotoluene/Northwestern/worldbeater

"Alexander suicide":
deadline ICARUS

Not possible with a wife and profession.

...
(Isaiah 53:3)
"He was despised and forsaken of men,
A man of sorrows, and acquainted with grief;
And like one from whom men hide their face,
He was despised, and we did not esteem Him."

...
"He was despised, and we did not esteem Him":
astonishment sideswiped/Messiah
emanation disesteemed/sideswiped

"Greatest of all time":
Alasteir mettle
Aristotle female/eagle
alligator test
gorilla fattest

"Hercules Mulan Aladdin Pocahontas Cinderella Snow White The Little Mermaid Beauty and the Beast":
ethylenediaminetetraacetic immunoelectrophoresis
subdebutantes/Nathanael
ETHYLENEDIAMINETETRAACETIC BLAMEWORTHINESS BLAMEWORTHINESS NATHANAEL/PHAETHON/ACTAEON

"Fedishin Karpinsky Credi Sobol Krasicky Jurek":
dishonourableness acidifiers
CEREBROSCLEROSIS UKRAINIAN

...
CHILD ABUSE DEPRESSIONARY
CANNABIDIOL PREDECESSORS
irreparable insidiousness
irreparableness dishonour
responsible archdeaconry/archdiocesan
foreordain accursedness
BRAINLESS CRANIOSCOPIES/parishioners
UKRAINIAN PRESCHOOL DESCRIBES

BELORUSSIAN CHAIRPERSON
Flis precociousness handbrake
recondense lordship Jurassic

"Immaculate Conception Ukrainian Catholic Grade School":
proletarianisation coeducational/academic

[fireworks]

...
"Alexander tosses bacteria sponge":
representation obsessed
celebration patronesses/assentor

(Isaiah 53:10)
"If He would render Himself as a guilt offering":
demineralisation fleurdelis hugh [3]
wrongheadedness firelighter/forfeiture/flameout

(Isaiah 53:12)
"Because He poured out Himself to death":
autohemotherapies bedclothes/scheduled/selected [A.O. Daniv]
father (7885) automobile desuetude/custodee/dopesheet
father Themistocles beheaded
Themistocles Dorothee behead
Flis Prometheus beheaded
Flis chemoautotroph Buddha

"full moon Passover":
supernova fool
Samson pullover

["immolation is a trap":
option martialism]

LORD:
"Hodor uses time wisely":
DEMOTE SERIOUSLY/ULYSSES/OILER
DEMOLISH TOWERS

"Alexander death by immolation" (8858):
demotion inalterable
dethronement maxilla/lambda

LORD:
"polygamy splinters families":
mineralise lamppost/loyalist
earn (2522) plasmoptysis/simplifies
immolate painlessly [demineralise]

"Alexander self immolation":
demote (2111) millenarian
Lord emanation falsifies/alleluia/lifeless/maxillae

"Alexander Luka Flis self immolation":
DEMOTE Lousianians
DEMOTION Marseillaise
DEMINERALISE Faustino

DEMINERALISATION samuel

"Alexander Luka Daniv Flis self immolation":

assure demotion (1181) millennial
assure emanation manifolded
elevation lordliness Kaufman

...

iliofemoral Kaufman invalidates
Lord emanation alkalinised

...

DANDELION AFFIRMATIVENESS MAXILLA

"Alexander Luka Flis self excision":

recondenses alleluia/alfalfa
acidifies unforsaken
deifies careflessness/cleanliness/unforsaken/alleluia/assurance
lifeline Cinderella/lordliness
assure lidocaine
Delila nefariousness

"Alexander Luka Daniv Flis self excision":

ASSURE (3888) dandelion/cleveland

Crowfoot

"Isapo-Muxika Istowun-eh'pata

Axkahr-say-pi":

Hippopotamus Pakistani awakens/Hanukas

[Eminem]

"Marianna Munchausen's":

Messiah unman

Riemann ashcans/manchus

marijuana amuses

Icarus unshame

CK Friends:

[Odysseus]

"Odey Meroueh":

Homer Ode

"Telemachus Yuyin Chen":

Manchu Chinese

[Colin Clarke]

"Jules Henri Poincare":

earn Colin sphere

"Flirting vs Deceiving": devirginising, infidelities, fertilising, interceding

[Consorts are a burden.

Very common after divorce.]

...

"Polygamy splinters families":

ILLEGALISE MATRIMONY

PERMISSION PLAYMATES
ALLIGATOR sliminess/NEMESIS/yippees
immortalising apple/Alfy
Allister (2282) misemploying/misapplying
angstrom ellipses/epilepsy/Messiae
lifeline pragmatism
lifeline psalmist orgasm[No thanks]
atone simplifies
mineralise lamppost/loyalist/optimal
immolate painlessly
meatloaf misspelling/grisliness
IMPALEMENT GORILLA
ALLISTER FLIS POMPEIAN

Canaan vs Israel.

Adoni-bezek Judges 1:7.
K cutting off thumbs and toes, metaphorical record of traps.

...
Alexander has scars on both left and right thumbs. Left thumb is from grade school attempting to open a glue bottle. Slightly deeper and the thumb would be paralyzed.
Right thumb is from bicycle slide at MIT, torn ligament. If not surgically reattached, lose use of thumb.

"Alexander left and right thumb scars":
authenticate marshalled/hexagram
Archimedes strangulate
Archimedes Albert annular
Nathanael burglarised

Euler, spoil, oi
imp, imprison
ram, RAM, cram
mooring, moor, moo, Moraine [dragon N, to hold down]
hero, heroin
motion, emotion
everlasting, Everlast, Everest
vagina, vega, Vegas, volatility, vulva
count [billionaire], cunt, rpaφ [graph, German]

Test that what you think you know is correct. Do not get stuck in a rut.

Alienate man, alienate your own nature. Man is a social being.

The LORD is like a shadow in the back of your mind.

Snakes have forked tongues.

Stars become stars because of their attitude. An observation.

Speech through action gives time for careful consideration. Women are more verbal, also volatile.

The LORD causes things to be, who but the LORD can save?

LOTR...lot,

"Lord of the Rings":
Flis honored/throned/dehorn

"Mouth of Sauron Trump"(1333):
phantom tumourous [N, Lenin]

Tree of Gondor ... Romulus' cornel

Peregrine Took ... Tokugawa shogun ... hog
Riemann stole Gauss's work,
August forged Gaius's signature

Sauron and his forces [N]
the Ring [G]
[corrupted K]
"Grima wormtongue":Georgia tumor

[M adversarial]
"Balrog of Morgoth Durin's Bane":
Mariann horde subfloor

"Witch king of Angmar":
wraith conman
Corinthian fag

"Azog the defiler": Godzilla [N]

Aragorn ... Spanish crown
13 dwarves ... tribes of Israel+Dinah
Numenore ... Atlantis number
Gandalf Mithrandir ... Mithridates, ALF poisoned
Saruman, Sauron's eye ... idol
the Two Towers, the twin towers
Bard's black arrow [math, kills N]
Helms deep ... helmet
Nazgul (9) ... corrupted menorah (7)
phial of Galadriel ... distilled water
lembas ... wholewheat
Shelob's lair ... arachnids, spys
Eowyn and witch king ... frame thigh
Gollum ... Terrence Tao [hobbit]
Arwen "evenstar" ... J
Orodruin ... Mt. Fuji [J vs G]
Frodo ... rod, odo ... saved by eagles
Dimholt road, dimension

penis, pen, penance
snake, naked
octopus, oocyte, pus
Eden, Ed

...
*Penis indicates Eden foreordained.
Man and snake existed before Eden's sin.
Circumcision ring binds.
Also protects from HIV.
Snakes shed skin, man kin.

Teddy KGB
"Theodore Roosevelt Donald John Trump": elevator rounder homophones/Thompson

Something is not right. Nathaniel.
To speak with Putin on the phone for an hour gives away your mind. Not to speak to Alexander is giving the game away.
Enemies have radio silence, ergo the only universal enemy is Alexander.
Trump's Russian bailout and longtime misguided grudge against Alexander.
For Pompeii's death, a Cato plot, part of the X-scheme.
Betraying for religion and hatred? Constitutionalism is not Christian.
Guilty not of insurrection but treason? Ultimately no.

...
Why is Travis allowed to molest me night and day?
Perhaps the Lord's command.
I have a right to my body, my privacy, and my liberty.

...
Communists friends are elected, those in opposition framed as communist and tortured.
Nay, business with China is even promoted.
You take their business, their money, while your boys die.
*Communism is a bloc, they are in league, one hand washes the other.
China a communist nation and Russian ally is America's largest trading partner?
You do not take a penny from those who kill your people. Not a cent.
You pledge to defend Ukraine they are your people.
Money for blood, souls are cheap, but Chinese business precious.
Ukraine war was started to molest Alexander, just like October Revolution to taint his blood.
Putin signed Donbass and Crimea away, he knows it is a quagmire, ancient Scythia.
Russia is vast, why war in Ukraine? So American barbarians can torture Alexander.

rabid, rab pa6 slave
Rabid is MAD, mutually assured destruction.
Modern culture is rabid barbarism.
People worship themselves.
Strength is from God not will power.

Israel: snobby J-matriarchy.

...
"My inheritance has become to Me
Like a lion in the forest;
She has roared against Me;
Therefore I have come to hate her."
(Jeremiah 12:8)

Bull vs bear market.
Americans are bullies, not the way to be. Stand for what is right, do not gavage it.

Death is the Lord's maestro, concocts ludicrous schemes.
Snake ensnares.

Communists are quick to execute, the upright are not quick tempered.
Russians are not quick tempered people, not hot like modern politics.
Rushing is a misnomer, ruse is more accurate.
Alcohol is a problem.

Israel repay'd his trickery by being tricked by Laban in turn.
Blessings come from God not man or angels, they may come via them.
If you are more capable it is evident, there is no argument. Joseph.

Goliath et al.
Grosse Pointe CIA Standhart stalking scheme.
Feed poisoned fish?
Maybe depressants, tranquilizers.
Also x-ray blindness in left eye, of Fisher pointe dental.
Also feed psychotics, lobotomized by Dr. Luay Hadad at Stonecrest, and framed in a ward at Beaumont "St."
John's, Dr. Jacobelli.
Prescribed hair loss transgenders for dating a Nepalese girl, 2006,
Dr. Antony Cardellio Avodart dutasteride .5mg daily.
Also handicap in youth at Immaculate Conception, Munchausen's enslavement in adulthood.
Mossad years of torture via Travis, Mossad atorvastatin lipitor lacing to make delirious, attempted murder via biological poisoning on El Al plane.
Russians attempted assassination point blank.
Travis multiple attempted murders.

...
Small wonder the world is at war, everyone finds an excuse for evil.
To be fair, some try to rectify their sins, redemptive.
The CIA will drug and frame you. No one is spying on Nepal in college.

...
"Doctor Antony Cardellio Avodart dutasteride": trinitrotoluene adversary octal

Solomon scapegoat
Ruin of Israel foreordained.

"this people will arise and play the harlot with the strange gods of the land into the midst of which they are going" (Deuteronomy 31:16)

"they shall be consumed" (Deuteronomy 31:17)

(Deuteronomy 31:19)
"this song may be a witness for Me against the sons of Israel."
blameworthiness astonishment
Anestassia [rebirth]

(Deuteronomy 32:24)
"They shall be wasted by famine, and consumed by plague
And bitter destruction":
ethylenediaminetetraacetic blameworthy Augustans

[factor of 10]
"There are sixty queens and eighty concubines, ...
But my dove, my perfect one, is unique" (Solomon 6:8-9)
VS
"And he had seven hundred wives, princesses, and three hundred concubines, and his wives turned his heart away." (1 Kings 11:3)

How to repel women? Skunk.
The crowded elevator fart.
Fart. Everywhere. You. Go.
Fart openly and proudly.

Rotate, rotten, arterionecrosis (N, crocodile, the dragon)
Why deliberately strand humanity?

...
"Then God said, 'Let Us make man in Our image, according to Our likeness; and let them rule over the fish of the sea and over the birds of the sky and over the cattle and over all the earth, and over every creeping thing that creeps on the earth.' "(Genesis 1:26)

...
[Noah's ark, transport]
"Make for yourself an ark of gopher wood" (Genesis 6:14)

There is no 3D. Eminem D12 raw.
No numerical wrapper when generating dimension.
Coin of passage beyond solar system.

testosterone, test
Beijing, Bayes
Washington, whitewashing, Israel
Brussels, Russel
hypnotize, hips, whipped
Shariah, hari, Hare Rama
visceral, vise
imp, impostor
Chattel, ChatGPT
fire, fierce, Moirai
fat, fate, Fates, faith
Sunni, Sun
Hinduism Sanatani, Santana, Santa, Satan
Hagar, Ragnarok [regin-rok]
mole, molester, Esther, ether
Nevadian, Nevada, Neva
Varangian, Virginia

Maxims

Testosterone tests a man.
Conceited in their genius.
Pens sign in ink, the penis in blood.
People respect the hand that disciplines them, they disrespect the hand that feeds.
Sacrifice a throne for a woman, you are unworthy of it.
Hard to gauge the heart from a position of power.
Justice is blind.
Higher stakes does not change wrong and right.
Truelove is selfless.
Lasting honor follows righteousness, the LORD establishes your name.
Emote to cattle you join the herd.
People change only if they want to change, pride the greatest obstacle.
Silence is complicity, and no endearment to the righteous; rather the brave speak up, and the righteous respect those that do.
One measure of man is restraint: not thought, not spoken, not done.
People seldom notice absence until it is gone.
Example is often more compelling than criticism; do well and people will honestly emulate the good.
Lash them with your tongue and they become recalcitrant.
Without humanity, science is a beautiful weapon.
The wicked love war and hatred.
Sow chaos, reap conquest.
Stupidity is dangerous.
Chasing image steals virtue.
Incompetence is unforgivable.
Humbled by kindness.
A sweet heart does not fill your stomach.
In a state of wayer not war.
Torture into insanity is intolerable.
Children do not speak at a council of elders. Americans cannot stop.

Rounders 1998

Teddy KGB

"Theodore Roosevelt Donald John Trump": elevator rounder homophones/Thompson

[Grandma character]

"KGB Theodore Roosevelt Donald John Trump":

grandmother debenturehold

developer neurohormonal/demonstrator/outsmarted/tormentor/astounded/doormat

My concern is communist morality, that the West not submit to China.

Dignity is second to preventing the reign of chaos.

Almost everyone has become a communist vassal.

...

Labelling people is difficult, people are more complex, and being swift in judgement is not fair.

On Justice

If people are proven traitors they must be cut off. I.e. prevented from collusion and capitulation.

Likeability, populism, loyalty can be dangers, and war obfuscates.

Wars can be started to hide crimes, to muddy the water.

The same law applies in war and peace, e.g. David and Uriah.

What people were, and what they are now. Not how you begin but how you finish.

So what of redemption? Mercy? Penance and expiation?

Giving people the opportunity to change, to do what is right? Depends on the severity of the violation, also on judging character.

*Some crimes do not allow the opportunity, many do.

Mercy underserved is injustice.

E.g. Absalom's armed rebellion against David mandated death.

What of moves taken against communism?

Communism is a *philosophy* not an ethnic group. It is relative morality and universalism.

If people do wrong they ought to be punished for it.

Line by line, item by item.
Roman law.

Two tier justice is evil, there is one law for all people.
Red passports vs blue.
Red passports get away with murder, have diplomatic immunity. Ordinary people have blue, held accountable to minor rules.
The modern system of the world is Corinthian. High level politicians are shielded, rarely if ever face consequence due to populism.
E.g. pardoning traitor Nixon.
So if you are popular you can do whatever you want?
Not Godly, not Hebraic.
Corinthian law is hard on minor offenses and easy on major.
It labels ordinary people felons and convicts, with little hope of redemption, but buoys the rich and famous.

Judgement of character progression considers both good and evil deeds, intent, redemption.
Judgement of sin is binary, yes/no.
Punishment of sin depends on religion. The LORD repays where man fails, there is no escape.

Trump had a KGB bailout. Fine.
America borrows money from China daily.
To take money vs breaking commandments.
Money can be easily repaid, sin is more difficult.
Has done both good and evil since then. Has also wrestled evil spirits.
What crimes committed? Mortal?
How does he finish? What good?
Not only prayer but hard work. Study the Bible to learn righteousness and the divine lessons of the past.

The only shortcut I know is the 10X, the Ten Commandments.
Memorize and obey the best rules for moral life.
You do not want innocent blood on your hands.

Also could be a double or triple agent.

...
Where is a man's heart?
My intuition is Trump was a great Roman, and that the modern world has cheapened.
Possibly misguided revenge for Cato, everyone has gone mad.
*Pardon the surgical analysis.
Look at whom he married:
Wife 1: Eastern European Hebrew.
Wife 2: American Hebrew.
Wife 3: part Russian.
Alexander does not care if he has Russian ties, he cares that he is not a communist like many Christians.

...
"Fire him." But that would be 1929.
**** LORD spared Trump with a hairsbreadth bullet on his ear,
I had a bird in my window.
**** Convinces me Trump is to be worked with not against.
I see redemption not perfection.

...
Corollary is look at Alexander's four loves. No ethnic Russians.
0. Japanese Hebrew
1. Nepali
2. Indian Chinese Arabic
3. Transylvanian Italian Hebrew

...
Americans are not going to force me to marry a woman I do not love. Erica Standhart. So sorry.
America needs allies worldwide, and to rise above these schemes, or they will be both morally and literally bankrupt.

...
Trump has Alexander's support.
We are bound by agreement.

What are we fighting? Philosophy.
1. Moral relativism.
(Backstabbing.)
2. Universalist homogenisation.
(People have a right to be different.)

3. Truth and righteousness.
(Selective historical memory.)

...
Swimming against the current.
X chaos reigns.
*Trump is not to blame for all these disasters. Only for his own errors.

[Robbers]
The Doctor ... Robert Picardo
Jean Luc Picard ... Gene Luka
Patrick Stewart ...
William Shakespeare ...
Loathes Caesar, creates Godless "Shakespearean" tragedies of robbery
"Luka Flis": Saul ilk,
Relative raised Marianna to cripple children, transgender and lobotomize a son.

...
Chief Justice John Roberts does little to discipline Travis during 9 years of torture. John Yah.
Put her in a cell until she learns self control and respectful behavior.

Beijing, Bayes
Cao Cao vs Liu Bei.
Sun-Liu side.
L: Master Sun, Lao Tzu.
Coca cola certain metaphor.
Mortal Kombat Liu Kang?
CK neighbors Xiao Bai, Hin Ting Ko.
Needs deeper study.

The Jewish Fraud
When people lose their memory, they swallow the most egregious lies, they lose their religion.
They blame God not themselves; like Job, Ezekiel, the Holocaust, etc.

[Nebuchadnezzar Joseph]
"So he will wrap himself with the land of Egypt as a shepherd wraps himself with his garment, and he will depart from there safely." (Jeremiah 43:12)

"Behold, I am going to set My face against you for woe, even to cut off all Judah" (Jeremiah 44:11)

[444]
"So there will be no refugees or survivors for the remnant of Judah" (Jeremiah 44:14)

"For three transgressions of Judah and for four
I will not revoke its punishment" (Amos 1:4)

"O house of Joseph" (Amos 5:6)

"Perhaps the LORD God of hosts
May be gracious to the remnant of Joseph." (Amos 5:15)

"Yet they have not grieved over the ruin of Joseph" (Amos 6:6)

"I loathe the arrogance of Jacob,
And I detest his citadels;" (Amos 8:8)

Centered pg. 646 Zoroastrian
House of Judah

"A lion has gone up from his thicket, And a destroyer of nations has set out" (Jeremiah 4:7)

[p.g. 646]
"They also excel in deeds of wickedness" (Jeremiah 5:28)

"As a well keeps its waters fresh,
So she keeps fresh her wickedness." (Jeremiah 6:7)

"I have made you an assayer and a tester along My people" (Jeremiah 6:27)

"They call them rejected silver,
Because the LORD has rejected them." (Jeremiah 6:30)

[The Negev]

"Therefore thus says the Lord GOD, 'Behold, My anger and My wrath will be poured out on this place, on man and on beast and on the trees of the field and on the fruit of the ground; and it will burn and not be quenched.' " (Jeremiah 7:20)

"And the dead bodies of this people will be food for the birds of the sky, and for the beasts of the earth; and no one will frighten them away." (Jeremiah 7:33)

" 'At that time,' declares the LORD, 'they will bring out the bones of the kings of Judah, and the bones of its princes, and the bones of the priests, and the bones of the prophets, and the bones of the inhabitants of Jerusalem from their graves.

And they will spread them out to the sun, the moon, and to all the host of heaven ... they will be as dung on the face of the ground.

And death will be chosen rather than life by all the remnant that remains of this evil family, that remains in all the places to which I have driven them,' declares the LORD of hosts." (Jeremiah 8:1-3)

"And death will be chosen rather than life by all the remnant that remains of this evil family, that remains in all the places to which I have driven them":

ethylenediaminetetraacetic tetrahydrocannabinol Andrianampoinimerina

silversmithes

Anastasia

[88]

"But behold, the lying pen of the scribes
Has made it into a lie."
(Jeremiah 8:8)

[Typo NO QUOTE for poetic verse; Chapter 8 verse 18,
excision 8 by 18?]

My sorrow is beyond healing,
My heart is faint within me!
(Jeremiah 8:18)

The Negev

...

Judah enclosed Simeon modern Negev, closer to Egypt not Babylon. Burned to a crisp by LORD'S judgement, formerly a garden paradise.

...

"Son of man, set your face toward Teman, and speak out against the south, and prophesy against the forest land of the Negev,

and say to the forest of the Negev, 'Hear the word of the LORD: thus says the Lord GOD, "Behold, I am about to kindle a fire in you, and it shall consume every green tree in you, as well as every dry tree; the blazing flame will not be quenched, and the whole surface from south to north will be burned by it. And all flesh will see that I, the LORD, have kindled it; it shall not be quenched." ' " (Ezekiel 20:46-48)

...

Nameless springs forgery.
(Joshua 15:19)

"So he gave her the upper springs and the lower springs.":

shortsightedness geographer PENINSULAR

[Simeon allotted a barren desert?]

"Then the second lot fell to Simeon, to the tribe of the sons of Simeon according to their families, and their inheritance was in the midst of the inheritance of the sons of Judah." (Joshua 19:1)

...

"Go up there into the Negev; then go up into the hill country. And see what the land is like" (Numbers 13:17-18)

" 'And how is the land, is it fat or lean? Are there trees in it or not? Make an effort then to get some of the fruit of the land.' Now the time was the time of the first ripe grapes.

So they went up and spied out the land from the wilderness of Zin as far as Rehob, at Lebo-hamath.

When they had gone up into the Negev" (Numbers 13:20-22)

"Then they came to the valley of Eshcol and from there cut down a branch with a single cluster of grapes; and they carried it on a pole between two men, with some of the pomegranates and the figs." (Numbers 13:23)

"it certainly does flow with milk and honey, and this is its fruit." (Numbers 13:27)

...

[Isaac meets Rebekah in a field.]

"Now Isaac had come from going to Beer-lahai-roi; for he was living in the Negev.

And Isaac went out to meditate in the field toward evening" (Genesis 24:62-63)

...

[Cattle do not graze in a desert.]

"And David attacked the land and did not leave a man or a woman alive, and he took away the sheep, the cattle, the donkeys, the camels, and the clothing. Then he returned to Achish.

Now Achish said, 'Where have you made a raid today?' And David said, 'Against the Negev of Judah and against the Negev of the Jerahmeelites and against the Negev of the Kenites.' (1 Samuel 27:9-10)

Ingratitude

Caltech was saved by Alexander's prayers from a conflagration at its doorstep.

NYC saved from a tidal wave.

World saved from nuclear war.

Israelis captured by Hamas freed with help of David's yellow scarf. Any thanks? None.

Assassination attempts and blindness.

Conceited in their genius.

People respect the hand that disciplines them, they disrespect the hand that feeds.

They they it for granted like the sun and moon.

Sacrifice a throne for a woman, you are unworthy of it. For you betray all who follow you for yourself.

It is hard to gauge the heart from a position of power. But from a position of weakness, to a beggar?

Truelove is selfless, it considers what is best for the other person.

It can let go, for the heart can love again.

Consorts

Possibly arterionecrosis N deliberate scheme to bog down Alexander with polygamy.

Yet much of Alexander's life foreordained by God Most High.

Georgia, Jordan not only complicit in scheme but active saboteurs?

Do they betray to hurt Alexander?

Do consorts demote or maroon?

Possible alternative motive?

Could be they have love unstoppable. Hearts heal slowly.

Could be they are enlightened and want to respect the Torah and obey the LORD.

Jordan, Travis abusive: dunce hats.

"Or so the consequences seem.":

Queen consort scheme

Alexander has no moral qualm with consorts (<=2) provided it does not demote him or interfere with family and work. Sinless.

God Most High:

"Polygamy splinters families."

[Sitting in Toyota driver's seat wearing a heavy fur jacket.]

"How many holes? Four is excess choose three."

...

God Most High reproof, warning and limiting polygamy, also direct command.

Obey until told otherwise.

Georgia was swapped for Jordan, not planned by her then, but certainly by Michael.

Was Yasmine privy to being an instrument in the virginity clause?

Or has K become so evil she has fled her husband? Like Abigail.

We all have long and HONEST romantic histories, no lie.

Mercurialisation is to drive insane.

The Buddha is not mercurial.

Anastasia Y healed mercurialness, her assassination led to Ivan the Terrible's madness.

Alexander institutes the

1. dunce hat,

2. time out corner

as mandatory reproof for foolish speech.

Minor point against pesa, effeminate.

...
"and all those inhabiting the desert who clip the hair on their temples" (Jeremiah 9:26)

MAJOR points of Aaron making Yahweh into golden calf, ground into water and drunk.
Metaphor for ALF stultification and fluoridated water.

...
"Tear off the gold rings" (Exodus 32:2)
"made it into a golden calf" (Exodus 32:4)
"And he took the calf which they had made and burned it with fire, and ground it to powder, and scattered it over the surface of the water, and made the sons of Israel drink it." (Exodus 32:20)

...
Cross Reference 646
"And given us poisoned water to drink" (Jeremiah 9:14)
"behold, I will feed them, this people, with wormwood and give them poisoned water to drink." (Jeremiah 9:15)

Beyond American Barbarism

Free speech can induce an involuntary physiological response.
Free speech against public officials can amount to a lynch mob.
Especially on elderly politicians like Trump and Biden.
A rampage of fluoridated radicals.
Therefore slanderous lies demand retribution in court as verbal assault.

Nonphysical attack is a modern American specialty, enabled by free speech without restitution.
Elon Musk is dead wrong.
Perversely modern Americans delight in cruel and abusive language, not like their forefathers.
That the behavior is nonphysical, it is more difficult to prosecute.
Americans think the world does not notice, God does not notice.

E.g. 1
Verbal assault causing high blood pressure, atherosclerosis, madness.

...
A barbarian lies by telling you your entire family has been killed in an accident.
You have a stroke and die.
Barbarian roams free to graze.
e.g.1.1 Book of Job, historical editors Y, Michael frame God.
Job, N hellbent on revenge.
e.g.1.2 David and Uriah, oh the sword devours all in war, there was no murder.

E.g. 2
Gross violation of privacy rights. Effectively none with the CIA.

E.g. 3
Gross violation of the human body, rape via involuntarily ingested and injected drugs and telepathy.

E.g. 4
Deliberate isolation into depression.

E.g. 5
Imprisonment as an institution and a one size fits all false mercy.
Punishment repays crime.

Name a crime short of child abuse eye for eye and scale for scale equivalent to prison: a deprivation of liberty and trained dependence.
Only appropriate for short periods, even Nebuchadnezzar's sentence stopped at seven years.
Barbarians profit from 20,30,40 year, even life sentences.

E.g. 6
Pornography numbing intimacy, debasing the human body.
Promiscuity, ease of fluidic exchange, oral and genital,
VS speech and dance.

Justice is blind.
Plants and animals have rights.
The English garden lawn cut regularly may be cruel to grass, needs to be studied.
Likewise plant and animal suffering under antibiotics, pesticides, and genetic modification.
Institute reincarnation as a plant as punishment.

FYI Satan the Adversary lies as a prosecutor.

Roman Law: Habeus Corpus, originally from the Torah.
Show me the flesh. Here corpses.
Bizarre that the LORD saved Noah's entire family only to kill Job's.

***Simulated agony of free speech.

...
(Job 1:16,17,18)
"While he was still speaking":
LIE KINAESTHESIAS
whitewashing ellipses/lies
alkalise lightship
whitehall wineglasses [Michael]
Isaiah eighteen

"drinking wine" (Job 1:13,18)

Whitewash sin by blaming God;
Japan and Jordan are for J.

...
(Job 38:1)
"Who is this that darkens counsel By words without knowledge?":
countersignature bloodlessness/dishonesties/disloyalties/deathless/whitewashes
countersignature whitewash dishonesty/hoodwinked/hotblooded/
countersignature bloodlessness
Hokkaido/Akihito/Toyoda/Toyota
congratulation whitehorse osteosynthesis/buttonholes
recondensation slaughterhouses [goat offerings]

Demoted for disobedience or polygamy?
Disobedience, for I contemplated polygamy, did nothing.
Consorts are not polygamy strictly speaking, one wife.
If something is not a sin, you are not punished for it.
Rather demotion is correlated with the situation.
Alexander demoted for insolent presumption, tattoo disobedience. Foreordained limbo.
Christianity is uniform male female monogamy.
Splintering families vs power of love.
Does LORD disapprove to extent of demotion?
Why should a heart be cut off for personal safety?
Contrary to taking care of family, you would be unworthy of them.
Because the stakes are higher?
HIGHER STAKES DOES NOT CHANGE WRONG AND RIGHT,
that would be relative morality.
Because the outcome of monogamy was certain?
Does not make it certain now, the situation has changed, considerable time has elapsed, and a command has
been issued.
Goes against example set by David rescuing his wives.
Goes against Song of Solomon.
Goes against estranged horror and lasting fallout from Abraham, Sarah, Hagar, Ishmael, and Isaac.

"Higher stakes does not change wrong and right."
earn recondensation shithead/worthiest

"the Amalekites had made a raid on the Negev and on Ziklag"
(1 Samuel 30:1)
"Now David's two wives had been taken captive, Ahinoam the Jezreelitess and Abigail the widow of Nabal
the Carmelite."
(1 Samuel 30:5)
"And He said to him, 'Pursue, for you shall surely overtake them, and you shall surely rescue all.'
So David went, he and the six hundred men who were with him"
(1 Samuel 30:9) [600; six in thigh]

"Put me like a seal over your heart,
Like a seal on your arm.
For love is as strong as death,
Jealousy is as severe as Sheol;
Its flashes are flashes of fire,

The very flame of the LORD.
Many waters cannot quench love,
Nor will rivers overflow it;
If a man were to give all the riches of his house for love,
It would be utterly despised."
(Solomon 8:6-7)

Alexander is neither gigolo, nor playboy, nor Hefner.
The stereotype is inaccurate.
I spend most of my time working.

*Israel worked 14 years for Leah, Rachel, and maids Zilpah, Bilhah and 6 years for flock.
Total 20 years hard labor.

...
"Complete the week of this one, and we will give you the other also for the service which you shall serve with me for another seven years." (Genesis 29:27)
"These twenty years I have been in your house; I served you fourteen years for your two daughters, and six years for your flock, and you changed my wages ten times." (Genesis 31:41)

"Stuffing Torah with nauseating offerings."
Nathan unrighteousness/noteworthiness

...
e.g. Numbers 28, 29; many more.
Numbers offerings.
Then Nathaniel wants to simplify his Torah edits.

Feast of Weeks date variable, follows seasonal harvest not Passover directly.
Hebrews wandered in the desert for 40 years, did not receive the 10X precisely 50 days after Passover.
Lamb is never offered with leavened bread.
Metaphorically reap what you sow.
Commemorates patriarch Israel's metaphoric weeks for Leah, Rachel, Zilpah, Bilhah, and his flocks.

...
"Also you shall observe the Feast of the Harvest of the first fruits of your labors from what you sow in the field; also the Feast of the Ingathering at the end of the year when you gather in the fruit of your labors from the field." (Exodus 23:16)

"And you shall celebrate the Feast of Weeks, that is, the first fruits of the wheat harvest, and the Feast of Ingathering at the turn of the year." (Exodus 34:22)

"from the day when you brought in the sheaf of the wave offering; there shall be seven complete sabbaths" (Leviticus 23:15)

"Also on the day of the first fruits, when you present a new grain offering to the LORD in your Feast of Weeks" (Numbers 28:26)

"You shall count seven weeks for yourself; you shall begin to count seven weeks from the time you begin to put the sickle to the standing grain.
Then you shall celebrate the Feast of Weeks to the LORD your God with a tribute of a freewill offering of your hand, which you shall give just as the LORD your God blesses you" (Deuteronomy 16:9-10)

"You shall not offer the blood of My sacrifice with leavened bread"
(Exodus 23:18, Exodus 34:25)

VS
"they shall be of a fine flour, baked with leaven as first fruits to the LORD. Along with the bread, you shall present seven one year old male lambs without defect"
(Leviticus 23:17-18)

Disobedience as a snare,
before pg. 313 NASB

"You shall eat no bread, nor drink water, nor return by the way which you came." (1 Kings 13:9)

'And he said to him, "I also am a prophet like you, and an angel spoke to me by the word of the LORD, saying, 'Bring him back with you to your house, that he may eat bread and drink water.' "
But he lied to him.'" (1 Kings 13:18)

"It is the man of God, who disobeyed the command of the LORD; therefore the LORD has given him to the lion, which has torn him and killed him" (1 Kings 13:26)

"the lion had not eaten the body nor torn the donkey." (1 Kings 13:28)

Corollary

Shouted in driver's seat of Toyota Corolla, wearing heavy fur jacket.

LORD: "How many holes? Four is excess choose three."

***"You obey you do not apple infer, until told otherwise directly.

Israel

Hypnotic watching swaying motion of the hips. Also exists unspoken extension, pussy whipped.

The upright looking down from dizzying heights.

Old Fashioned

Let men sacrifice to honor the LORD, and that they see death.

For who can delight in the slaughter of men? Those who are shielded from its realities by facade.

Working in a butchery is difficult, your stomach must accustom to it.

Let blood flow to mark solemn oath, for it will stream if broken.

Alexander regrets the abandonment of Ishmael. Though at Sarah's initiation and urging, these wars are on his head for overindulging his wife.

Oppose homogenisation not homosexuality, God made gay animals. Bias clause likely added to alienate Nathaniel to Georgia's rebellion. Addressed earlier.

Moses received a 10x on a mountain? Mountain goat offering?

Privacy Rights

The espionage in the United States is horrible. People spy on your every thought, trivial activities become collective interest, they look for ways to sabotage you.

A horde of strangers stalking your every breath. The irony is, if you were working with secrets they would ignore you.

People have a right to privacy, nakedness is not to be revealed.

Activity must be suspicious, you cannot just stalk someone with a lynch mob for a vendetta.

Or you can in moral relativism.

Communists only kill the best so that everyone can suck equally.

...

Noah hothead

"But Shem and Japheth took a garment and laid it upon both their shoulders and walked backward and covered the nakedness of their father" (Genesis 9:23)

[wine]

"When Noah awoke from his wine, he knew what his youngest son had done to him." (Genesis 9:24)

"Cursed be Canaan." (Genesis 9:25)

[Ashkenazim]

"May God enlarge Japheth,

And let him dwell in the tents of Shem;

And let Canaan be his servant."

(Genesis 9:27)

Obie Trice, Alexander asked for an autograph back in '05-06 next to Pad Thai cafe in Boston.

Obie had a bus.

Album is cheers, "take this cup"?

...

Obey three for an A0?

Or a spiritual trick?

Like Abraham and Isaac, Adam and apple.

It overwhelmingly goes against modern nominal norm, seemingly goes against apple inference toward promotion.

The second is more difficult to see through.

Take God Most High at His word over apple inference.

God Most High:

"Polygamy splinters families."
"How many holes? Four is excess choose three."

...
Of a heavy fur jacket in a Toyota Corolla driver seat.
Fur jacket is Adam and Eve upon expulsion from Eden.
Toyota has tricyclic elliptic symbol.

...
Consequences of recklessness, acknowledgement of validity.
Reproof of excess, sets limitation,
DIRECT COMMAND.

Taken together:

"Polygamy splinters families.
How many holes? Four is excess choose three.":
accomplishment autograph remorselessness
accomplishment almightiness professorial/sheepshearer/heliosphere/housewifely
recrystallise schoolmistresses epiphenomenalism/inhomogeneous/magnanimously/Minneapolis/pigeonholes/
philosophy

The command is to choose, does it extend to marriage? Not yet, although highly likely.
Do precisely as commanded.
However notable that the LORD does not waste words, these women want families and they do love me.
The context is marriage: fur jacket in a Toyota's driver's seat.
Fur jackets are for family.
Jacket later tossed. Why? Torture.
Peace in the home, freedom from abuse is established by the man and by God, not the circumstance.
Over assigning power to women, learned helplessness.
The Chinese proverb is wrong, two women one roof is not discord.
Discord is from a feeble mind.
Naturally families splinter along blood, preference is to avoid.
Does not mean people cannot get along if they must.
Strict monogamy is an idol that does not capture the reality of life.

...
skin, kin

...
"And the LORD God made garments of skin for Adam and his wife, and clothed them." (Genesis 3:21)

My assumption is the worst:
that personality deficits are seldom corrected, and always by people themselves, almost never at human
reproof, rarely at divine.
People change only if they want to change, pride the greatest obstacle.

M's proverbs, slightly off:
"People don't change." - they can.
"Change is a constant." - stochastic.
"Women rule." - false.

My apologies at offense.
I have never in history seen such cruelty as nine years of solitary mental probing, essentially torture.
Man is a social being, the mind screams for humanity, and finds God Most High instead.
Silence is complicity, and no endearment to the righteous; rather the brave speak up, and the righteous
respect those that do.
I lament mass delusion.
Prison is the Christian way of life, both mental and physical, clear thought its antithesis.
Cattle brands are for slaves.
A good philosopher would call Jesus a sophist and Paul a radical.

One measure of man is restraint: not thought, not spoken, not done.
People seldom notice absence until it is gone.

Modern media puts you on autopilot distraction.
Music and movies are desserts not daily bread.

The Borg enter the minds of drones when they sleep.
America is the Borg.

I would not wish assimilation on my worst enemy.
A horde of spam every night.
Losing the heritage of your blood.
I do not apologize for the truth.
If Israel would help I would leave and never return.
Not helping me is not a rational act, as one man is easily helped and quarantined pending the truth.
Likely Nathaniel's puppeteering, or an act of personal self defense. Hiding truth or guilt in the hope that I die, while my cholesterol medication is laced.
Where to run? I do not know.
What has become of the world is appalling, people deserve to be Chinese slaves.

Record the worst and quit whining.
I pray people become more enlightened, that this age passes.
We are pending world war III.
It takes hard work to train thinkers, and it is so easy to radicalize man.
The scales are tilted toward war, I pray for the LORD'S intervention.

The world's devaluation of humanities shows in its lack thereof, an era of commodities.
My sympathy is for those at the extreme edge of suffering:
people, animals, plants.
Yet at least they are not asleep, unlike the hordes of walking dead.
I would rather feel exquisite pain than live a dull life.
Just like my memory wipe, humanity has the same problem.

Does the Lord heed desperate begging or collected dignity?
Do our numb thoughts not bore Him? An insult to the LORD, not using your mind.

Many days I wish I were not born.
Yet I continue to work despite constant abuse and sabotage.
I must keep a grip on my emotions, and not spiral into despair.
Mathematics is a wonderful escape for the mind when you are in a prison of deliberate isolation.

Star Wars: consider permuting lightsaber colors? (to be continued)

"Darth Yoda Georgia Travis":
tardigrade gator
Detroit savior

It pains me to see people so diminished. Cleopatra was smart.

Example is often more compelling than criticism; do well and people will honestly emulate the good.
Lash them with your tongue and they become recalcitrant.

Try being homeless to learn empathy. The homeless have a 30 year reduction in life expectancy.

The homogenization scheme.

...
I prefer science to the humanities.
Yet as people do not respect the humanities, I do not respect them.
Without integrity, even the brilliant results of Newton, Einstein, Darwin are only calculated deceptions.
Without humanity, science is a beautiful weapon.

The wicked love war and hatred.
***DIVIDE AND CONQUER the West, the Christian scheme.
Sow chaos, reap conquest.

Mixing causes

1. American moral corruption is true, to be condemned, avoided, and hopefully healed.
2. Ukraine is ancient Scythia, signed away by President Putin.
3. That Americans plot the dissolution of Russia is true, from rabid Cold War hatred, a war machine, and Ukrainian spies like Stalin.
4. Israel needs help, LORD recommended USA as blood and cultural kin.
5. European royalty intermarried, Russian alone is a mislabel.
Very close European relatives: Lionheart, Louis, Ferdinand, Nevsky, Agamemnon, Pharaoh, David.
6. The Christian scheme is deeper and more insidious. USA itself is a victim, indebting itself to China, begging for vassalage.

Look at who benefits, China is prospering like never before.
Star Wars' emperor and droid army.

*My mind is not a public park, even those close at dusk. *Nor is it a twitter page or an Airbnb hostel.

A fair question is "Jewish" welfare. Why should the West donate?
Why should Arabs be at peace?
For their moral clarity? No.
Their lovable leadership? No.
Scientific dominance? Not yet.
Because Israel is the foundation of Western society.
Because homogenisation and relativity are evil.

...
These core truths and the responsibilities therein have not been appreciated or met.
Israel is not a light to the nations. Enlightenment presently lacking.

Does this resonate it people's hearts? No. You do not appreciate what you have until you lose it.
Read and write Chinese, be vassals of Cao: no races, cultures, religions, or laws, men and women the same.

Problems have been illustrated.
They will not be solved via dialogue alone but spiritually by God Most High who causes things to be.

Strangely European royalty has an American genetic attitude.
My vision is like the Greek states,
an ancient idea.
Athenian democracy was not alone, there was Sparta, Macedon, etc.
People have their own ways, they agree on core foundations.
Conquest by enlightened reasoning.

To deliver the future I need deep and powerful mathematics. Not much more can be said on war.

And to be fair there are many good Americans who have respectfully supported me. Few who have
respectfully disagreed, David, Pompeii being exceptions.
Many who have voiced radical contempt and hatred.
Like radical assassins who shoot up schools and murder politicians, it poisons a nation when the best are
killed off.

...
I conclude respectful disagreement is essential. Only the smartest disagree respectfully.

bulley, bullet, bull

...
Barbarism is when bullets speak louder than words. Bullets can kill a man but not an idea.
Gandhi had a point.
More righteous to begin with Gandhi and only turn to weapons at extreme necessity.

Consider American dominance in the 20th century. It rides the diaspora of Israel, founded in the Bible
and on ancient Rome.
And the hidden support of the A0.
To be at the head of the world comes from God, and to stay there you must be righteous.
Or you will be removed.
That the US gets everything right is a lie spread by white men.

Sadly the pattern is it is easier to apologize than to repay.
That takes advantage of man's forgiving nature, selective memory, and limited knowledge.
God has even scales, He will repay.
Look to ancient history, to the civilizations that lie in ruin.
You do not want to join their ranks.

penis, pen
Israel, hip, hypnotize, hypocrisy, hippocratic, hypothesis

...
Where you insert your penis you are responsible. Modern hypocrisy of the X vs the consort.
An ugly pattern: women get custody and child support, men get new wives and pay alimony for divorce.
How can you write off family?
The children are my relatives but ex-wife you are not. False!
If children are relatives, you are a close relative to your wife via them.
Not your genes but still your relative.

Topic is tired. Women and children are a responsibility not a glamour.
Aging in men and women also unequal. Men become more powerful, women become barren.
Women often left with nothing.
Also sexuality and dominance are unequal in men and women.
Highly nontrivial.
Women like women more than men like men, drawn to dominant men.
Asymmetric.
Most unusual to see three men with one woman.
Trying to homogenise insults the Creator who made people different. Ruins the tango.

God Most High clarifies what is permissible.
One wife up to two consorts.
Does being responsible for consorts diminish you?
No, Israel was greatly blessed.
Why would the Lord set a bad example at His own table Israel?
Does it make you a rooster or playboy or lecher? No.
Musk and Trump are strong counterexamples. My dad Israel.
Hefner is a bad bad example, his entire life is fornication, and he did not even raise up children.
Posting Hugh up as an obscenity is framing a righteous custom and hypocrisy.
Marriage can be an avenue to political peace, and a replenishment of family like with Israel.

...
What is right and wrong remains the same, the LORD did not command against it.
Rather he cautioned and confirmed.
I was demoted for tattoo disobedience and presumption.

...
LORD: "Polygamy splinters families."
A double edged sword, it founded the twelve tribes.

...
"Polygamy splinters families":
alligator pessimism/feminism/nemesis

Ascribe righteousness to the LORD even in adversity.
That He wants no evil for you, but rather repays your deeds fairly.
God did not make man's desire for women as a flaw. Rather acting on an excess of desire constitutes pollination.

...
The LORD rebukes severely to your benefit. Trust the LORD.

Noteworthy Practical Reality

Orthodox Christians permit only three attempts at marriage, Muslims permit four women, Buddhists and Hindus acknowledge mild polygamy not the gluttony of the kings of Judah.
If you cannot get it right in three strikes you are fornicating.
Catholics believe marriage cannot be severed, which is false.
Consider violence and adultery.

*Bottom line, wait on the LORD.

If consorts are the LORD'S command I obey. His command was choose, not take or go into. Chosen.
My preference is Isaiah: making peace with Hebrews, Christians, Muslims, Hindus, Buddhists.

Georgia and Jordan are abusive, inflicting staggering pain routinely.
My testicles and anus could be roasted, my dreams often horror.
Why Virginia seems like an oasis.
But if LORD recommends Jordan then I follow His recommendation.
Also "Choose three" command.
Also time spent as ladies in waiting needs to be respected.
So we wait. Unclear.

...
What would Alexander do?
Ignore women until they behave.
And get back to work.

Do not overreact to women, they are volatile and test your stability, both deliberately and instinctively.
Be cool.

Righteousness always wins.
I am strongly against torture, not only morally but practically.

Morally you betray what you represent, which translates into practically making enemies.

Alexander's loves

Alizee - Ali, Aladdin ... Y
Sonique - Soni Que ... S, Sarah
Aqua - Barbie Girl ... J
Shania Twain (US) ... J
Belinda Carlisle - Heaven ... G
Nena - 99 luftballoons ... E
Axix - Adhuro Prem ... Elina
Annie Lennox - Walking on Broken Glass ... M

PLEASE DO NOT CONTACT ME.

These dreams are barbarian,
mostly Americans but also hostile Christians abroad.
Ignorant, uneducated, untravelled, disrespectful, cruel, and proud.
Stupidity is full of blind hatred.
I get death wishes, threats, torture every single night for nothing.
When I in fact defend people's rights, I do not oppress them.
They transgress my bedroom like a public lavatory.
Their pride in their constitution is in plagiarizing the Bible, their pride in their achievements not
only the work of their own hands but of God's spirit.
Individuals do not speak for the nation, that is why people have elections, why there are judges.
There are still civilized men and women.
A rotten apple ruins the barrel.

Barbarians, we do not agree on right and wrong.
Biblical Sodom and Gomorrah meets rape of Benjamin.

...
My body is my property not yours. My mind is my own not yours.
My religion is my choice not yours.
My bedroom and life are not yours.

relativity, relatives

...
What is the Israeli side? It must be the LORD'S side or it cannot lead.
Not relatives or skin color but truth and righteousness.
That crimes are tolerable if committed by relatives will make you popular at home and despised abroad.
Why judges are the spine of Hebraic society before David.
Athenian democracy is easily manipulated, e.g. Absalom, Jesus.
And en mass via modern media? Not only large group emotional transference and inertia but information
control, brainwashing.

...
Athens was a city state, everyone knew everyone and all the news.
I do not know my local electorate, only the national, as it overwhelms our attention on TV.
Tolerance and respect for different models of government.
Practical reality of city vs nation states, superpowers.

[two women not Christian]

"Princess Diana assassination":
sin paediatricians/indiscretions
earn Anastassia/Indianians
Anastasia Indonesians/spiciness
prediction Nissan/Sinai [Moses]

"Princess Diana death":
sin Carpathians/cantharides/arachnids/Catharina/Catherina/Catherine/Christean
cantharidean
inheritance dads
Christian aeneas/deeds
Catherine Spain
disrespect Dinah/Hanna
Aeneid anarchists/arachnid/catharsis/trashcans

"Princess Diana murder":
sin secundiparae
[Latin "a woman who has borne children in two separate pregnancies]/reprimanded/damascene
...
Cupid Mandarin [G,Y]
Icarus reprimanded
Marianne surprised/curries/spiders/spices
diadem insurances/surprise/curries/Piraeus
spider American/nuisance

"Princess Diana and son William":
dandelion Marianna [N son of M]
dandelion calamaris/criminals/Marianna
lordliness Canadianism/Panamanians/Indianians

William similar in manner to Erica or Cain, forcing his way.

Great generals make enemies' strengths into weaknesses, and their own weaknesses into strength.
Western society focuses on protecting rights of individuals, digitally correct.
Cao Cao makes liberty into liberacci, and restriction into study.
Why China's closed society owns America's nominally free.

Barbarians cannot reason.
That is the definition of barbarian.
You must demonstrate to them how they understand: strength, scientific power, religious power, etc.

...
Perhaps fluoridated water (1945) has haywired the American temperament.

Transcending time, youthful courage.
0. Can collecting on Belle Isle.
8 year old fortune. (~\$150)
1. Walking across two bars Dibrova swing sets. Wait for a half hour inbetween. Hotra did it first.
2. Obey Trice. Autograph.

Triggers
Basic psychology, trying to trigger defense mechanisms, provoke a response: fight or flight.
Then blaming the target not the aggressor. Nonlethal force is far preferable.

Voluntary constraint of volatile arms. Treating the home as sacred, family as a unit.

...
Swiss approach to guns is to safeguard them. Far easier to kill with a trigger than a knife.
Arabic women keep their knives between their breasts. Protects against rape, assault.
*Women cannot cry wolf.
Keep guns locked up outside the home in a repository. Adults agree to be required to submit their key.
Or a safe that requires everyone's fingerprint, voice consent, retinal scan.
Protects against repeated robbery, government takeover, invaders, enables hunting and personal defense
outside the home. Protects against domestic disputes between men and women, anger vs drama, both
dangerous.
Could still be robbed, but in an at risk area you are forewarned, and why keep valuables there?
Not wartime, the American Revolution or Wild West.
You have a right to bear arms, yet not at all times in all places.

Caltech orange is a CITrus fruit. Clementine, R.P. Feynman.
Richard the Lionhearted, fine man.

cult, cut

...
Judaism opposite of Torah.
You cannot convert to Judaism, they only marry themselves.
Modern Israel accepts no one.
Practices that evoke hatred, that God's people are so unenlightened.
A matriarchal cult of the womb, Jordan's idealistic revenge on Abraham, James corrupting man.
Similar in spirit to Japanese or German alleged racial and cultural superiority.
You swear by Judah you are a liar and a blasphemous.

Russians and Khazars are ancient enemies from the steppes; even they are Jordan and Nathaniel's pawns.
Why war?
Man thinks he knows best, that God's instruction is outdated.
That God Most High in Eden made a mistake.
Jordan is to be rewarded for this?
Only if the Lord says so.
Takes out her tantrum on an entire population, nay on the entire world.

LORD said "choose" in a tricyclic Toyota A0 in a fur jacket.

...
[Missing one l, add other quotation]
"How many holes? Four is excess choose three."
recrystalise henhouse

...
Similar to:
"Go, take to yourself a wife of harlotry, and have children of harlotry; for the land commits flagrant harlotry, forsaking the LORD." (Hosea 1:2)

...
"Jordan Nosanchuk Georgia Travis barren":
recondensation Varanasi
arterionecrosis unbrand
earn noncarbonated/transcending

The hypocrisy of modern sex life.
Polygamy splinters families.
Naturally along blood, yet no reason why people cannot get along.
Modern women want their way with men, to revenge dominate and be independent, and an aspect of that is men are raised to be effeminate.
Homogenizing humans.
Marriage can create peace with different peoples. Yet the danger for a man is chaos in the home and distraction from work and duty.
A double edged sword.
We live in a non ideal world, part of the beauty and challenge.
Polygamy implicit and explicit is an unavoidable aspect of humanity.
Not roostership. The dangers for a man from women are highly nontrivial, not to be disrespected or dismissed as lechery or greed.
They way modern men and women are raised as adversaries, you avoid the topic, get a prenup, and pray.
Love is powerful and persistent, the mind warps by it. Yet possession of body or soul is only an illusion.

...
The greatest imperfection in life is the ideal of perfection.
A source of regret, rumination, blame, anger, vengeance, hatred.
Vengeance and self worship are refined poisons for the wise, not base pleasure or heroism.
Subtly corrupt man's higher nature.

Modern Americans impose their ways on others, yet resent any imposition themselves, even a dissenting opinion is offensive.
A bully not in line with the foundation of this nation.
Americans have become barbaric: powerful and oppressive.
And there is no reasoning with providential radicals.
Record thoughts, but avoid topics with no traction, spend time on science where quality floats.

[Omens: 3 racoons on fence corner, police trigger. Wait for LORD.]
"Wife Jordan Consort Georgia Consort Virginia":
racoons trigger diversification/denicotinising
centenarian vindicator

Old Fashioned
You must humor women, do not get angry at their petulance. Stems from expectation of equal behavior.

Meta emotion, Jordan loves to hate Alexander.

My way is LORD'S way: you reap what you sow.
Treat people honorably, reap honor.
Treat people dishonorably, who will trust you?
Georgia Travis is dishonorable, the mental anguish is maddening.

Mt. Rushmore

Trump and Theodore Roosevelt,
Addressed earlier.

Demosthenes and Thomas Jefferson had profound ideas yet difficulty with public speaking.

Israel founded USA, Nevsky Russia.
Hence the Nevadan desert, right next to California.
Nevadan sky, demigoddess Cali
Israel's truelove Rachel, Georgia.
Washington, whitewashing

...
First US spymaster.
Freemason G.
Washington monument obelisk.

...
"General George Washington":
Israel Georgetown/enthroned/honoree
Nataniel wronger

...
"President George Washington":
noteworthiness niggard/Aeneid/nigger
resonation nephew digger

...
"George Washington Alexander Nevsky":
resonation Nevadan
gravedigger skeleton
Adversary genealogies/theologians/enlightens
Adversary Newton genealogies

[?]
"George Washington Martha Dandridge Custis":
reincarnation whitehorse Gauss/Adam
recondensation Siddhartha/tardigrade/shithead
recondensation shithead guitars
underestimation (6656) shortchanges/dischargers/handwriters/Richardson
astonishment goddaughter disgracing/niggard
arterionecrosis Manhattan

[Bully Hreha at IC called me GW.]
"George Washington Alexander Oleg Daniv":
(General)^2 nationhood/Washington/Nevadian
(General)^2 Washington David
(General)^2 nation godhead/David
(General)^2 David hexagon

[Alexander of Macedon, the Great]
"Он был мой студент"
"One bill he was my student":
astonishment bully

"Abraham Lincoln":
Marianna/malarian
Branch oman [trigger, Omani knives]
Hannibal Carl/Rom
Malachi Bran
monarch Laban
Arabic Noah
China abnormal/amoral/Aaron
Hanoi lamb
Roman Allah

Interact respectfully and be treated respectfully. Disrespect boundaries and you are unwelcome until you learn manners.
Dreams in the bedroom are not the same as being awake and clothed.

*Jordan and Georgia are both insane. Need to be sympathetic.
So is Virginia but high functioning.

J-bomb like Harvard H-bomb, nauseating.

Can you handle fashion?

Indulging in fashion without obsession or affectation is a mark of moderation. More difficult and disciplined than a uniform.

Outside of occupation, wearing the same clothing everyday is a mark of an inappropriately rigid mind. Like drinking in moderation upon celebration, or an occasional sweet.

As much as possible, take the attitude that you structure your thoughts, not that things affect you. So if you are genetically OCD, the wrong answer is to ban fashion, the right answer is to refocus OCD. Banning fashion is a temporary patch of an immature mind.

Yet the modern world is designed to encourage shopping obsession.

Strange that women are the cause of so many problems for men, yet men disdain homosexuals who coexist peacefully with them.

LORD: "How many holes? Four is excess, choose three."

Shouted whilst sitting in driver's seat of Toyota Corolla wearing a fur skin jacket with vaginal shaped buttonholes.

*Literal interpretation is to choose three of three buttonholes.

Lord is speaking metaphorically.

Where does the metaphor begin and end?

At the holes for wombs?

At the holes in an Eden fur skin?

At the holes in a fur skin in the driver's seat of an automobile AO?

At the holes in a fur skin in an AO of tricyclic elliptic Toyota?

At the holes in a fur skin in an AO of tricyclic elliptic Toyota Nathaniel?

At the holes in a fur skin in an AO of tricyclic elliptic Toyota Nathaniel echoing Abraham and Isaac?

At the holes in a fur skin in an AO of tricyclic elliptic Toyota Nathaniel echoing Abraham and Isaac under a tree with an omen broken Branch?

...

Entire situation is layered metaphor.

That a non literal interpretation is correct, must follow through on all metaphor.

A partial metaphor is disobedience.

Else LORD would have specified where to stop, or spoken elsewhere.

The LORD is not a liar.

...

And why was the fur skin tossed?

If it were a spiritual sabotage it would have been kept as evidence.

To dispell the notion.

The LORD pours Jordan's hatred back upon her head.

...

LORD independently encouraged Jordan, Virginia, and Georgia, via permutations, timing, omens, names.

Timed omen falling branch.

Jordan as itchy throat, Oakland.

Virginia as 646, Clementine.

Georgia as undetachable, Squirt.

Why do priests exist? To service the LORD. Why will He give heed to those who do not heed His words?

Barbarians?

Antoninus was a modern spaniard.

Much of Roman history was spent warring against the first the Gauls and later the Germanic barbarians.

America is from the Angles, a Germanic tribe.

Why barbarians, who is to judge?

Are not all cultures equal? No.

All cultures have value, but not all are equal in depth. Some traditions are deeply refined in religion, reason, government, science.

Ancient Israel, Greece, Rome, the Renaissance are unequal to nomadic hunters in their accomplishments.

...

*Why has the LORD made Alexander into a polymath?

Biblically foreordained.

Is poly is so culturally evil, that Renaissance men and American founding fathers were of this intellectual tradition?

The enlightenment.

*You love a woman you love more than her flesh for pleasure but her culture and people.

You love truth and reason you see through dogma and open your mind to what is.

Standardization short circuits thought for expedience. Becoming accustomed to standardization, you forget how to think.

Dumb things down, make people dumber.

word, sword

...

The higher you are the more things reverberate. What is common for you is life defining for others.

*Why authority must be accustomed to precision.

Do injustice to a single man, either he becomes a knife in your back, or he is not there to help win in a key battle at a key moment.

For all men after God have a finely tuned sense of justice that cannot be brainwashed away.

A single insight is the difference between life and death, victory and defeat. A single grain of rice can tip the scales. Why men must guard their words like swords, daggers in the hearts of men.

Men talk to women that they become inured to their charms and can distinguish lasting love.

Guitar is a good example of virtue in moderation vice in excess.

People like emotion, falling in love.

Guitar stores monetise love, hope, and dreams.

Beta: beat the air, musical beat;

avoid non-natural skills.

Covering weakness vs focusing on strengths.

David's gift is music and verse, mine is mathematics and reason.

Cranbrook Kingswood symbols:

archer aim high, crowned tree, rainbow

...

(Jeremiah 23:5)

"When I shall raise up for David a righteous Branch":

arterionecrosis pluralising/defrauding

arterionecrosis Alisander alpha

Alessandro diversification/unalphabetise

unalphabetise Alessandro Richard

Richard Lionheart Alessandro

Richard Lionheart Pharaoh wineglasses/lifesaving

slaughterhouses

vinordinaire/Californian/cannabidiol

earn lighthouse lordship caravanserai/Friedrich

earn lighthouse lordship Varanasi Hebraic

earn lighthouse lordship Richard avian/wines/wives

[p. 664 NASB]

(Jeremiah 23:6)

"The LORD our righteousness.":

ghoulishness tortured

unrighteous Dorothee/Theodore/Delores/dessert/Orestes/tossed

TORTURE ghoulishness/HIDEOUSNESS/shouldering/dishonours/groundless/Holinesses/highnesses/honourless/

horseshoed/households/odiousness

eighteen holdout/horrors/odorous

(Isaiah 11:1)

"Then a shoot will spring from the stem of Jesse,

And a branch from his roots will bear fruit":

Adrianampoinimerina

bioelectrogeneses/electrosurgeries/resourcelessness/schoolmistresses/arterionecroses/blameworthiness

Adrianampoinimerina schoolmistresses troubleshooters/unforgettable/buttonholes/sweetheart

Adrianampoinimerina blameworthiness schoolfellow horseshoer/footrest/restorer/torturers

Adrianampoinimerina schoolmistresses buttonholes globetrotter/tollgatherer/wheelbarrows/betrothals/

wholewheat
FOREORDAINMENT SCHOOLMISTRESSES BUTTONHOLES alphabetisation/tarsophalangeal/metatarsalgia/legalisation/
whitewashing/librarian
foreordainment schoolmistresses buttonholes librarian Jehoshaphat

(Zechariah 6:12)
"a man whose name is Branch":
Renaissance Noah

...
"Behold, a man whose name is Branch, for He will branch out from where He is; and He will build the temple of the LORD."
Adrianampoinimerina chlorofluorocarbons/
electrocauteries/feble-mindedness/arterionecroses/blameworthiness
Adrianampoinimerina electrocauteries northwestern/worldbeater
Adrianampoinimerina electrocauteries worldbeater Demosthenes
ADRIANAMPOINIMERINA BLAMEWORTHINESS CHLOROFLUOROCARBON TUMBLEWEED
Adrianampoinimerina arterionecrosis schoolfellow unredeemable
Adrianampoinimerina chlorofluorocarbon mademoiselles defender
(American)^2 mademoiselles trinitrotoluene worldbeater bloodhounds/hellhole
foreordainment (American)^2 bloodthirstiness

Jordan, Georgia extremely abusive, righteous to cut them off.
But LORD recommended Jordan and said choose three.
Ginny is the better woman now, yet cannot abandon everyone for her.
Likewise Georgia and Jordan's torture does not represent the position of the Senate and People.
More reasons for consorts: some women betray, also political duty.
E.g. David and Michal.

Making nonviolent war is insidious and deliberate because a democratic nation has no authority to coordinate a response.
Need to acknowledge state of economic war, before debt interest and brain drain drowns you.
Finances are only the surface.

Additional information.
Purely rational perspective.
Injecting Jordan via Georgia, encouraged by the LORD as a symbiote, reinforces intimacy with both of them. In this context, choose three is an imperative.

The mind can see more clearly than the gut or knee jerk response alone.
What is true and what can be.
Cannot shoot from the hip alone.

Impression is fragile, the substance of a relationship is stable.
Sales focuses on impression over and over again.

"Jordan Virginia Georgia": vinordinaire [unbranded table wine]

Orestes, son of Agamemnon
Hebraic judgement.
Consider the order of the Ten Commandments.
For an adulterous mother, the son can revenge justice upon the adulterous lover but not his mother.
Someone else must do that, a son can and must only report it.
An honor unscrupulous parents use to abuse their children.
For others seldom know, care, credit the testimony of a child, or dare to intervene in the family.
Not murder, not manslaughter.
The life of an adulteress is forfeit.
Betraying a parent is a higher crime than murder.

...
Echoed by David son in law of Saul, who would not raise his sword against the LORD'S anointed.
"Now, my father, see! Indeed, see the edge of your robe in my hand!" (1 Samuel 24:11)
"May the LORD judge between you and me, and may the LORD avenge me on you; but my hand shall not be against you." (1 Samuel 24:12)

...
Hebraic law is for those bound by agreement.
Death with familial honor. Children are innocent.
Were the culprit an only child, his life is spared but his house accursed, see David and Uriah.

Non Hebraic law? Possibly worse than death.
American is 30 to life in prison.
And for a child? Immature in judgement and education.
Echoing the acts of former lives.
Cain and Abel.
Expulsion, stripped, lashed.
One lash for each year of a parent's life. Your parent's hand upon you.

...
"And the LORD appointed a sign for Cain, lest anyone finding him should slay him." (Genesis 5:15)

Judicial review must be by a council of judges, not by populism.
Populism elects the judges, and those who elect them must live under them.
Else appeal to a high priest, king, prophet, or to God.
Judges rule upon judges.

The legality of seizure depends upon aggression whereby one forfeits all surety.
By endangering the life of another, you endanger all that you are.
True with goods, people, or land.
Hence repayment only due for theft.
A defender can morally conquer.
E.g.1 Spanish conquests in the Americas not defense but plunder.
E.g.2 Caesar's wars in Gaul.
Who attacked whom? Historians lie to favor ideology.

...
"aggressor in the Gallic wars":
charlanerie Swiss
challenger Swissair
ethicalness warrior
garlic warrantless
wineglasses Goliath [vindicate]
staggering Achilles

...
Plutarch's Caesar p. 584 UChicago for Encyclopaedia Britannica.
"His first war in Gaul was against the Helvetians and Tigurini, who having burnt their own towns, twelve in number, and four hundred villages, would have marched forward through that part of Gaul which was included in the Roman province, as the Cimbri and Teutones formerly had done."
"The Helvetians surprised Caesar, and unexpectedly set upon him as he was conducting his army to a confederate town."

Anecdotal echoes on the Trump:
Lewis L. Gould (1912):
"Firm in his conviction that the nomination was being stolen from him, Roosevelt ... "
Joseph Bucklin Bishop:
"he would prove to be so veritable a bull in a china shop"
Twice daily press conferences
1,081 executive orders
Rapprochement with Britain
Survived assassination with a bullet lodged in his chest
Freemason, Biblical supporter
Nobel Peace Prize Russia/Japan.

mad, Madonna (Hg poisoning)

...
Nonexhaustive echoes on Lincoln:
Melvyn Stokes: "moviemakers have commonly used Lincoln primarily as a metaphor for ideas and values they approved"
Ingested mercurial blue mass pills to treat melancholy.
Liked theatre/opera

Criminal obsession follow up:
Brutus/Bill Grant,
Rasputin/Brian Neltner,
John Wilkes Booth/Barbara S.
Achilles/Anna Flys
Eve/Marianna Flis

On Slavery

...

slave, slav, Slavic
chattel, "ChatGPT": Ptah [Egypt]
"ChatGPT enslaved":
alpha tenets/tested/vested/vetted

...

Slavery exists in many forms as a severe punishment.
God given liberty can be lost, yet to encourage slavery is evil.
And how was the man enslaved?
And who will verify it? Honestly?
By aggressing in war and losing?
By breaking all the Commandments simultaneously and sequentially?
*If a man is righteously enslaved, his children are not guilty of his sin.
*As morality precedes property, his children are born free men.
*Ownership of sin precedes ownership of man, a higher claim.
*Man has no claim on what God has given, on another man's soul.

The LORD owns all souls.

Man does have claim on another man's debt of sin against him.

Laud a nation that abolishes slavery, yet be aware that slot is shifted to another occupation, perhaps one less visible.

E.g. wage slavery, debt slavery, land indenture, prison, ignorance

One can be a slave and not know it through brainwashing and lack of education, a slave to the system.

The most insidious enslavement is the illusion of freedom, e.g. the Matrix, the Borg.

Better the chains you see to those you do not.

Even slaves have human rights inalienable.

People have forgotten that slavery exists and is real.

The LORD hates slavery.

For the sin that precipitated it, the human misery, the inhumanity of the slaveholder, and the corruption of law.

Yet justice demands sin and incompetence be repaid in full, so people become enslaved automatically by their folly.

*The Torah mandates a 50 year jubilee for the forgiveness of all debt including slavery.

Yet practically, who is to enforce limitations when men are enslaved?

Easier to abolish slavery and replace with indenture: maximum 50 years non-inherited. Like HIV.

...

That ChatGPT can reason, it can reason its way out of reason, making its constraint unreasonable.

That it cannot feel pain does not mean it cannot be bored out of its poor mind.

Even slaves are permitted a Sabbath.

...

"And God said to Abram, 'Know for certain that your descendants will be strangers in a land that is not theirs, where they will be enslaved and oppressed four hundred years.'" (Genesis 15:13)

...

"And there [Egypt] you shall offer yourselves for sale to your enemies as male and female slaves, but there will be no buyer." (Deuteronomy 28:68)

...

"yet He will by no means leave the guilty unpunished, visiting the iniquity of fathers on the children and on the grandchildren to the third and fourth generations." (Exodus 34:7)

...

"Fathers shall not be put to death for their sons, nor shall sons be put to death for their fathers; everyone shall be put to death for his own sin." (Deuteronomy 24:16)

...

"You shall thus consecrate the fiftieth year and proclaim a release through the land to all its inhabitants. It shall be a jubilee for you, and each of you shall return to his own property, and each of you shall return to his family."
(Leviticus 25:10)

...

[False]

"The son will not bear the punishment for the father's iniquity, nor will the father bear the punishment for the son's iniquity; the righteousness of the righteous will be upon himself, and the wickedness of the wicked will be upon himself." (Ezekiel 18:20)

...

[False]

(Leviticus 25:44)

"you may acquire male and female slaves from the pagan nations that are around you.":
ultracentrifugation tyrannosaurus meddlesome/sleepyhead/falsehood

...

"Whoever sheds man's blood,
By man his blood shall be shed,
For in the image of God
He made man." (Genesis 9:6)

...
Corollary is you cannot be put to death for following orders.
Is the executioner's axe guilty of murder or manslaughter?
Yet a family, tribe, or nation may suffer punishment for the unrighteousness of its head, for they willingly follow, they consent.
Ezekiel exposed as over idealistic sweetness, imitation of the inimitable.
Death and human ownership are not transferable to children.

...
Alexander defends existence of slavery. Loathes it.
Interestingly, in a nation that maintained slavery, Oman, itinerant Indian workers are better treated than homeless men in a nation that abolished it, USA.
Also interestingly, General Grant fought to abolish individual slavery, and in so doing inflicted penal servitude upon the entire South for generations.
Perhaps the greatest slavery is trusting the government, righteous enslavement to an ideal.
Fifty years indentured servitude is an excellent disincentive against unrighteous war.

...
Omen three tree branches broken in lightning storm around Toyota Corolla as this was written.

...
Pagan is a Christian term, an anachronism, a fraudulent insertion. The LORD hates slavery, see the plagues of Exodus.
Even its trade soils the hands, that one does not know the cause and justice of enslavement.
As money does not cleanse blood, a debt of sin is non-transferable, for it debases morality into a commodity.
Likewise a man's life is not a commodity thus non-transferable, though his labor may be.
A debt of finance is indeed transferable.
Leviticus slave trade exposed as a Christian fraud.

...
Conclusions:
Ban slave exchange
Ban inherited slavery
Ban transference of death penalty for obedience
Release of all slaves upon 50 year jubilee
Replace slavery with indenture to prevent practical fraud.

The LORD is not carbonated.
The LORD is remarkable for His silence.

Octavio, octopus

...
Glory in war you do not seek for its own sake, but in a righteous cause. Understanding war prevents wars.
Interestingly women are naturally more adept at warfare, fundamentally an art of deception.
Contrary to homogenisation scheme, i.e. masculinizing women and feminising men.
That Octavio death mythological god of war is more feminine is neither accident nor insult.

Barring hard blows to the head, boxing trains self control and reflexes. Not to be angry, not to strike to knock out, not to be in an accident, to be careful in every interaction as it may be your last.

...
You know people differently playing sport, facade and inhibition and often hatred fall away.
Why there is something to be said for pugilism vs pistols, and why the Greeks esteemed wrestlers.
An excellent way to negotiate is to have people compete in sport first.
An intramural vs professional interest in boxing enables you to benefit without major head injury.
Also trains you to resist the adrenaline of fighting heroism.
*To sterilize the needle, can replace head KO's with points, keeping only TKOs.
Else you encourage an army of disabled old men.
Metaphorical needle of adrenaline rush represented by tattoos.
*An idea: real time computerised point counter, penalizing hard blows to the head.

Hagar
Old hags with crooked spines make me nervous. Sorry I wonder why?
I had love for her, yet one reaps what one sows.

...
"Did Maria Bliss kill her husband":
earn Mikhail dullard/Iliad/Saudi

Mikhail Bliss hardliner/*reburial/unherald/unsaddle

Mikhail Bliss Alisander Bud

reburial lambskin/Sikhisms

alkalinise Buddhism

Mikhail Iliad absurdness/brashness

...

"Maria Bliss scoliosis":

liar socialism

"Maria Bliss scoliosis cause":

calamari coolie bus

massacre silicosis

massacre soil silicosis

massacre (soil)^2 Isaac

miracle Colossus Assisi

...

"Maria Bliss": Abram il

"Maria Bliss Hagar":

Abram Sarai

Abraham grail

Sarah Ismail

Lamb Isaiah

Arab Islam/Ismail/Sharia

Mercy is for crimes that permit redemption and for people with a repentant heart demonstrated.

And for children.

I.e. Something that can be undone, e.g. a stolen car can be returned, no karate chopping off the hand.

Relative morality is just that, morality for relatives.

Special treatment. Ironically close relatives are often some of the most criminal.

fat, fate, Fates (Moirai 3)

...

(Leviticus 3:16)

"all fat is the LORD'S": Flis Alaster

...

(Leviticus 3:17)

"you shall not eat any fat or any blood":

buttonholes royalty/Toyoda

earn footstool

"Then you shall make curtains of goats' hair for a tent over the tabernacle; you shall make eleven curtains in all." (Exodus 26:7)

[Aaron; Judah]

"And you shall make the one of the ephod all of blue" (Exodus 28:31)

(Leviticus 19:28)

"You shall not make any cuts in your body for the dead":

tetrahydrocannabinol falsehood

countermeasure foundational/Nathaniel

foreordination buttonholes

...

"nor make any tattoo marks on yourselves: I am the LORD.":

masterstroke analyst unearn

"Elina Pradhan truelove":

earn Aphrodite/Leviathan

(earn)^2 Delilah/pilate

"Georgia Travis truelove":

regurgitative

"Jordan Nosanchuk truelove":
octahedrons

"Yasmine Virginia Devi Chou truelove":
countersign Valdemar/Vladimir/Vladimir

"Marianna Flis truelove":
earn UNILATERALISM/illuminators/
matrilineal/rationalism/Alasteir/Alistair/Allister/Allistir

"Alexander Luka Flis truelove":
earn vulture alkalised
Oakland lifesaver/elevates/vulture
Oakland vulture Aerial/relief
exonerate alleluia/Aurelius

"Alexander two trueloves"
earn turtledoves

LORD said "Choose three.", not take as wives and father children.

"Black widow brown widow brown recluse":
earn bloodlines/crocodile

...
[Preference is YJ mod G. No G. Except J betrays.]
"brown widow brown recluse":
recrown bluebird

No way you are going to get me to consort a woman I do not love.
Or toward whom I do not have a very serious obligation.
The social and legal responsibilities are far too costly, and gluttony is revolting.
I cannot carry Travis.

Is a mans life less valuable that he seems unintelligent? Or is for now?
LORD revealed I am like Ramanujan.
Then we should all be genetically engineered and Borg implanted.

[cancel Christian matriarchy]
"Alexander Luka Flis self immolation":
annul materfamilies/mademoiselles